

[YEAR 3 EVALUATION]

[Deliverable 6.5]

Carina Girvan

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Deliverable 6.5 presents an evaluation of the third year of the ER4STEM project, industrial evaluation and whole project evaluation. The primary aim of this deliverable is to provide an evaluation of the year 3 activities implemented in the third year of the project, specifically the workshops and competition. To achieve the primary aim, this deliverable presents the evaluation of 72 workshops implemented in five European countries by project partners and one competition in the third year of the project. The secondary aim is to provide an overall evaluation of the three years of the project, against the research aims, objectives and specific questions outlined in the DoW.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

To meet the primary objective, deliverable 6.5 presents an evaluation of the workshops and conference reported in D2.3, D3.3 and D4.3. Data were collected through the evaluation kit (D6.2) and a modified version during the competition. Information presented in D2.3, D3.3, D4.3 and D6.4 are referred to as appropriate, so as not to replicate information. The industry evaluation informs WP1. To meet the secondary aim, this report draws on D6.3, D6.4, D5.3 and D1.4. Finally, this deliverable informs D1.4 and the final project report.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

Following a brief introduction to the report, the Year 3 evaluation of the ECER conference and the workshops run in Year 3 are presented. The discussion considers the findings in relation to the year 1 and year 2 recommendations for the Framework and Activity Plans. The appendixes contain the detailed analyses which are referred to at various stages of this report. The report then moves on to the industry evaluation of the 3 years of the ER4STEM project. The industrial evaluation of the ER4STEM project (section 4) provides an industry perspective on the outcomes of ER4STEM. This involves reflection on the original recommendations of the industry partner Certicon; how these have been implemented and are reflected in the evidence from the research data. Following the industrial evaluation, the whole project evaluation is presented, which examines the outcomes from the 3 years of the project in relation to the research aims, objectives and questions posed at the start of the ER4STEM project. Finally, unresolved issues, future areas for research, as well as technical and pedagogic development in the field are identified based on the outcomes of ER4STEM.

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2 INTRODUCTION

This report presents the evaluation of the third year of the ER4STEM project. It examines the outcomes of workshops and conference completed in year three of the project and considers these in relation to the recommendations which emerged at the end of the second year of the project (D6.4). This is followed by an evaluation of the project from the industry partner Certicon. Finally, the evaluation of the project in relation to the objectives and research questions derived from the objectives is presented.

The evaluation and analysis of the first year of the project (D6.3) informed the development of workshops (WP2) and activity plans (WP4) implemented in project year 2 and the development of the framework (WP1) and repository (WP5) through a series of recommendations. The first year evaluation also provided an opportunity to pilot the evaluation kit and consider amendments. At the end of the second year of the project, the evaluation and analysis focused on the implementation of these recommendations by analysing data collected during the conference (D3.3) and workshops (D2.3, D4.3) using the final evaluation kit (D6.2) and the revised activity plan template (D4.2). Evaluation and analysis of the second year of the project (D6.4) demonstrated that ER4STEM activities were maturing by implementing the recommendations. While there were further recommendations for activities in year 3, these were focused on refinement of existing practices, rather than the introduction of anything substantial. Importantly the evaluation and analysis of the second year of the project reinforced the importance of the recommendations made at the end of year one. These research informed recommendations have then been used to significantly inform the development of the final ER4STEM Framework (D1.4).

In Section 3, this report presents the Year 3 Evaluation, examining evidence from workshops and the ECER conference implemented in Year 3. Two case studies from each partner’s workshops, plus two case studies from the conference are presented in the Appendixes. The evidence points towards increased integration of the pedagogic recommendations from previous years. While the evidence overall, supports the findings of years 1 and 2, it also reveals unexpected findings which are important for the future directions of educational robotics activities to promote STEM subjects and careers.

Beyond providing research informed guidance for partners and teachers, through a series of recommendations and informing the design of activity plans and the ER4STEM Framework; the other stated objective of the evaluation is to provide a systematic evidence base for the evaluation of the entire ER4STEM concept. To achieve this, having presented the evaluation of the third year of ER4STEM workshops and competitions, this report goes on to present an evaluation of the three

years of the project from the perspective of industry (section 4), followed by an evaluation of the ER4STEM project in relation to the project objectives and emerging research questions (section 5).

From the three years of the ER4STEM project, we can see that the interventions have had a positive impact on young people from a wide variety of backgrounds. The research methods employed in this study are novel within educational robotics, providing a window into what happens during educational robotics activities and not just the outcomes. As a result the ER4STEM partners have been able to refine their approaches, communicate their approaches to a wide range of potential stakeholders and develop a framework for the future development of educational robotics activities in STEM.

Overall, this report demonstrates how ER4STEM activities have developed and matured through the lifetime of the project. It shows how the objectives of ER4STEM have been met and identifies areas for future research and development which emerged from the research but are out of the project scope.

3 YEAR 3 EVALUATION

The evaluation of the third year of the ER4STEM project is based on data collected and analysed from workshops and competitions implemented in the same year. Data collection followed the approach established in the previous year (D6.4) and detailed in the Evaluation Tool Kit (D6.2). The only adjustments to data collection from year 2 to year 3 were following the recommendations of the second year evaluation:

- 1) **Evaluation:** Draw-a-scientists gender to be reversed (language dependent) – female form first for all partners.
- 2) **Evaluation:** Remove inspiration question from research questions.

The data analysis followed a similar approach to that of the second year, focusing on the recommendations which had emerged from the evaluation of year 2 (D6.4) and undertaking a series of in-depth case studies which are reported in section 8 (Appendixes). Other reports which have informed the evaluation of the third year include D2.3, D3.3 and D4.3 which provide an overview of the workshops, conference and activity plans.

Following a reminder of the recommendations from the year 2 evaluation, this section outlines the evaluation context and data collection. The findings from the analysis of the year 3 ECER competition and conference are then presented before exploring the outcomes of the analysis of the workshops. This section ends with a discussion of the outcomes of the third year of the ER4STEM project.

3.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR YEAR 3

This section presents the recommendations for the ER4STEM project which emerged from the evaluation of the second year of the project (D6.4). It is worth noting that the primary aim of these recommendations was to further refine existing practices which had developed in year 2 following the recommendations at the end of year 1, rather than introducing radical changes. Some of these are targeted at the design of the activity plan template which acts as a prompt for educational robotics workshop designers. Thus, it is not expected that every activity plan will include all of these elements, rather they would emerge across the activity plans included in the ER4STEM curriculum (WP2, D2.4).

- 1) **Teamwork:** Activity plans should include specific tasks to explicitly introduce and engage students to/with relevant aspects of teamwork (e.g. involving everyone in the completion of a task, how to effectively communicate ideas).
- 2) **Team roles:** Where teams are expected to distribute roles amongst the team, it is important that all children get the opportunity to take each role, that roles are specific, required and not repeated. More than one child may take a role (e.g. programmer) at any time.
- 3) **Teamwork, exclusion and disengagement:** Where students are seen to be excluded from activities, students need to be reminded about how to work in a team and be supported to develop collaborative/cooperative working practices. Where a student has also disengaged it is also important to reignite the spark of interest in robotics. This will take time and is more practical in workshops with multiple tutors.
- 4) **Teamwork and exclusion:** Students who are excluded need to be provided with opportunities to demonstrate to their team or the wider class their ability and potential to contribute to the team. This may be more effective than the teacher telling the team to work together.

- 5) **Teamwork and gender stereotypes:** Activities to raise awareness of implicit and explicit gender biases in relation to STEM should be part of the wider ER4STEM curriculum.
- 6) **Teamwork, identity and ownership:** When teams are first formed, provide ways for them to develop a sense of team identity (e.g. creating a team name) and ownership (e.g. allowing them to customise a pre-built robot).
- 7) **Supporting between-team interactions:** Provide shared spaces for students from different groups to meet and encourage the sharing of ideas/supporting others (e.g. a shared resources/testing table)
- 8) **Competition and community:** Foster and develop a sense of community and peer support in otherwise competitive environments.
- 9) **Creativity:** Continue to develop multiple ways for students to incorporate a creative element within robotics workshops.
- 10) **Critical Thinking:** Develop ways to introduce students to ‘ways to think’ when they encounter problems.
- 11) **Developing resilience:** The ER4STEM framework, activity plan templates and repository should draw attention to the need to develop resilience and provide recommendations for non-specialists
- 12) **21st Century skills:** Should be gradually developed across the ER4STEM curriculum.
- 13) **Evidence of learning:** Develop ways to evidence learning as part of activity plans.
- 14) **Evidence of learning with SLurries:** Identify achievable routes for teachers/students to evidence learning in the virtual world.
- 15) **Differentiation:** Develop approaches to the differentiation of activities for learners.
- 16) **ECER Competition:** Provide at least two, easily accessible practice spaces and encourage the use of free testing time.
- 17) **Evaluation:** Draw-a-scientists gender to be reversed (language dependent) – female form first for all partners.
- 18) **Evaluation:** Remove inspiration question from research questions.

3.2 ECER CONFERENCE AND BOTBALL COMPETITION

3.2.1 Context and Data Collection

As reported in D3.3, there were 130 students at ECER 2018 who participated in the Botball competition in Malta. These students came from four countries, with the majority of students travelling to Malta from Austria, but also Bulgaria and Poland. In each of the three years of the ER4STEM project, ECER has had a majority male and majority Austrian participation.

There were 13 student presentations at the ECER conference. 1 was from a student from Poland, another from Malta and the rest were given by Austrian students. Only two of the presentations related to a real-life problem, with most focusing on technical issues they had encountered or developments that they had made. Three presentations were given in tandem with the Robotics in Education conference which is a conference for adults (academics and practitioners) which is run at the same time, providing an opportunity for the best ECER papers to be presented to adults.

Four teams participated in the focused data collection which involved questionnaires, interviews and video recordings. Two of the teams were from Austria (with a mix of previous experience at ECER),

one from Malta who were new to ECER and one from Bulgaria who had participated in ECER 2017. The teams were encouraged to take Go-Pro cameras with them and record what they were doing throughout the competition. In this way the power/control over data collection is given to the students but is also reliant on them.

A modified version of the evaluation kit for workshops was used throughout ECER. In addition to questionnaires to 72 students, four teams agreed to be video and audio recorded throughout ECER and participate in three small-group interviews - at the start, mid-way through and at the end. These interviews aimed to provide students with an opportunity to express and discuss their views about ECER but also to encourage them to reflect on their past experience, what they were doing and what they planned to do in the future. This replaced the need for a separate reflection activity.

One of the teams involved in the evaluation had members who first participated in ECER in 2016 and were in the focus group for both the year 1 and year 2 evaluations (reported in D6.4). The original four-girl team lost and gained members in each of the subsequent ECERs, becoming 'Nothing to C Here' (NTCH) in Year 3. In ECER 2017 the team was comprised of three of the original girls and one boy. In 2018 one of the girls had left and six more boys had joined, all who were new-comers to ECER and Botball. As teamwork has been an important topic for the evaluation, and this team presents an example of more experienced (female) and less experienced (male) team members, an in-depth case study of the team in action throughout the robotics competition was undertaken. This is reported in full in Appendix A.

Another interesting aspect of the ECER competition from the perspective of the ER4STEM objectives, which has not previously been explored in depth is the Alliance round. The Alliance round at ECER was a competition round for all teams that didn't reach the finals of Botball or PRIA Open, scoring less than the top four teams. In theory, the alliances were optional, but at ECER it was expected that all teams participate. The aims of the alliance round were twofold. Firstly, the competition organisers aimed to promote communication between teams that ordinarily would not encounter each other. In order to achieve this, teams were paired to form heterogeneous alliances - mixing up countries, competition type (Botball and PRIA Open) and mixing up teams that dropped out early with those who almost reached the finals. The second aim was to provide non-finalist teams with a purpose for the final two days of the competition, whilst the four finalist teams continued in the double elimination tournament. Three of the four focus-group teams participated in the Alliance round. As the Alliance round presents a novel approach to collaboration within ER4STEM, the experiences of these three teams is analysed and reported in Appendix B.

3.2.2 Findings

This section of the deliverable presents the key findings of the reports presented in Appendix A and B, and discusses them in relation to the relevant recommendations from Year 2 and the broader objectives of ER4STEM. It additionally presents other findings which are based on observations, interviews, questionnaires and analysis of the papers presented. Some of these findings will be referred to in the whole project evaluation in section 5.

3.2.2.1 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: FOSTER AND DEVELOP A SENSE OF COMMUNITY AND PEER SUPPORT IN OTHERWISE COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENTS

ECER is clearly a competitive environment with teams competing against each other in various rounds with the aim of winning a trophy. Traditionally less competitive activities, such as the conference presentations, also have a competitive edge, with a team of judges and scores awarded. Two activities in ECER have the potential to foster and develop a sense of community and peer support. The first is the Alliance round and the second is the writing of postcards to other teams.

3.2.2.1.1 ALLIANCE ROUND

All teams who do not make the final are expected to participate in the Alliance round. Alliances are formed between two teams which are different from each other in some way. Pairs are decided by the competition organisers and are largely informed by skill level (based on scores thus far achieved) which should foster peer support. Pairs are also decided on based on where students come from, mixing countries to foster a sense of community.

Prior to the Alliance round it was observed that the Bulgarian team VG did not spend time with any other teams and would spend a lot of the competition time working on their robot in their room (the event was held at a hotel where these students stayed) rather than the pit area with all other teams. Their teacher also encouraged the older three students to leave the younger two students to work on their own so that they developed their technical skills, and this was particularly noticeable during the Alliance round. However, it is noted in the report on the Alliance round that when the Alliance round began, team VG made a change in their physical location, leaving their allocated table to relocate to their alliance partner's table, as is shown in Figure 1. VG used this as a base for the remainder of the round, sharing the space with their alliance partner and bringing their Bulgarian flag from their own table to their Alliance team table.

Figure 1 VG working at their alliance partner's table

This was a dramatic change in behaviour for VG and certainly suggests that the Alliance round fostered a greater sense of being part of the ECER/Botball community for this team. However, language was a barrier. Although VG and the alliance partners would communicate in the medium of

English when talking between the two teams, they would both quickly revert back to communicating in their native languages when talking within their original teams rather than within the alliance partnership. This was likely because it was easier for them to use their first language, as the VG team members admitted to the researcher that they weren't confident in their English. However, this meant that the two teams were unable to understand each other unless they were specifically directing communication at the other. This would have limited their collaboration, but overall we can consider that the change in behaviour, in terms of interaction with the wider ECER community was a positive outcome of the Alliance round, given that there would be a high cognitive load, speaking in a second language whilst identifying, deconstructing and solving problems.

A particular incident captured on video by the students shown that when this Alliance team went to the practice table they positioned their robots on the same side of the table as each other. As a result the two sub-teams had to communicate with each other in English as they recognised problems and in these moments there are clear instances of 'norming' behaviour through knowledge exchange. However, once the team realised that their robots did not have to be on the same side of the table, their need to collaborate diminished as did their tendency to communicate with each other.

Appendix B goes into more detail on how other Alliance teams functioned and not all were observed to physically work together. This was important not only in terms of developing a sense of community but also for peer support. Of particular note here is Child 4 from NTCH. NTCH remained in their same working areas during the Alliance round. However, Child 4 (m), who was working most closely with their alliance partners, physically left NTCH and spent the majority of his time at their alliance partner's table. The two teams physically came together as a whole less often than the other two alliance teams whose engagement is discussed in Appendix B. Child 4 acted as a "door" (as described by the students in the interviews) between the two teams as he was able to speak Polish (the language of the alliance partner) and the other team had weak English language skills. While he had primarily been involved in documentation earlier in the conference (as reported in Appendix A) and had little to do with the robots, the Alliance round gave him an opportunity to be actively involved with the robots and he is seen to position himself with the alliance partners at the competition table. While Child 3 asserts that she was trying to provide peer support to the Polish half of the alliance, it required Child 4 for the alliance to be successful:

- Interviewer: Ok so, talking about that, with you working with the alliances, with your language barrier. So how did you guys find that?*
- Child 1: We had a door*
- Child 2: We had a door*
- Child 1: Child 4*
- Interviewer: Very useful, yeah, so that was quite lucky wasn't it*
- Child 4: Yeah it was quite lucky*
- Interviewer: Yeah? I mean if they hadn't had you they might have found it a bit harder?*
- Child 3: Yes. Because I was trying to explain to them and it was really difficult to explain, I was like showing and they still didn't know what I was talking about"*

During the Alliance round all focus-group teams referred to helping their alliance team in some way during the interviews, something that was also observed over the last two days of the competition. However, the above extract highlights the difficulty of a language barrier within an alliance partnership. According to the competition organisers, the Polish team being paired with NTCH and

Child 4 was a case of 'luck' and had not been planned based on his skill. As discussed in the NTCH report, Child 4 was given a new role because of the language barrier to communication in the alliance partnership, which he explained to the researcher: *"I'm now like overseeing the Polish kids now... I give them tips so they can improve the robot"*. Overall, NTCH appeared to have good communication with their alliance partner, but it was implied that this would not have been the case had Child 4 not been there.

Overall, it was observed that those teams who communicated more with their alliance partners and had a closer physical interaction with them gained the most from the Alliance round in terms of fostering and developing a sense of community and peer support in an otherwise competitive environment. This is something that should be actively fostered if this round is to be valued. For example, by requiring Alliance teams to compete on the same side of the game table and rearranging the pit area to bring teams physically together.

3.2.2.1.2 POSTCARDS

The writing of postcards to other teams was a small activity introduced this year to encourage a sense of community. The postcards were sent to the judges who read them out on the last day of the competition during the awards ceremony. Whilst the implementation worked well the impact was limited by teams sending multiple postcards to other teams at the same school as them. Whilst this shows a sense of camaraderie with peers, it is also exclusionary with some teams receiving fewer postcards. Limiting who can send postcards to whom may address this small issue in future years.

3.2.2.2 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: PROVIDE AT LEAST TWO EASILY ACCESSIBLE PRACTICE SPACES

It is clear from the in-depth case study of NTCH that this team used the practice spaces that were made available to them throughout the competition. However, it was only the Robot sub-teams that were involved that used this space. The Documentation sub-team were never observed at any of the test tables and from Figure 2 it can be seen that they never left their allocated team table.

Figure 2 Location of NTCH workspaces throughout the course of the competition

Throughout the competition, teams were observed using the test table in the pit area (main room) and the competition tables when they were available for testing. In general there were no comments about the lack of testing tables and students were observed watching other teams as they waited at the testing areas, as observed in Year 1. While one team of Maltese boys had created their own testing area (with the course marked out on a sheet), they had difficulties when transferring between this and the competition tables because of the different surfaces. This was a technique used by some teams in Year 2 because of the lack of test areas, however the creation of the Maltese team of their own testing space was not for this reason, but due to their lack of confidence in the wider shared space.

Overall, we can see that this revision of the ECER setup (which was also used in Year 1) has had a positive impact on the ECER competition, although the lack of testing tables continued to be mentioned, this is only by one respondent. It is worth noting that there were fewer students in 2018 (~130) than the previous year (~200). With larger numbers of students and teams participating, it will be important to maintain a good ratio of testing space to teams in the future, as per ECER 2016.

3.2.2.3 ER4STEM OBJECTIVE 2: ER4STEM WILL OFFER EDUCATIONAL METHODS FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS TO ENGAGE ALL YOUNG LEARNERS

Within Objective 2 of the ER4STEM project, a number of research questions were identified (D6.1) which are relevant to the competition. Relevant findings are presented here and discussed as part of the whole project evaluation in section 5. A point that should be noted: the girls referred to are all voluntarily participating in a robotics competition, in male-dominated teams.

3.2.2.3.1 DO THE APPROACHES/ACTIVITIES APPEAL TO GIRLS?

While in the minority, throughout ECER 2018 girls were observed to engage with the activities as much as boys. The report on NTCH in Appendix A details how the two girls (in a team of nine) took leadership roles and were actively engaged with working on the robots throughout the competition. Child 2 (f), the team leader, was also observed to review the documentation sub-team's work (Figure 3 Child 2 reviews other team member's work). An important factor in this was their experience, having participated in ECER 2016 and 2017. While Child 4 (m) had attended the previous year, his work focused around documentation and he delivered the onsite presentation.

Figure 3 Child 2 reviews other team member's work

An opportunistic and informal conversation with one of the female ECER participants from Austria who had participated in the competition for several years, along with observations of the ECER conference presentations provide an interesting angle on the question of whether the activities appeal to girls. This student had just presented her paper to students at ECER and adults from the Robotics in Education conference who came to three selected student presentations. Having given her paper, she took questions from the audience, facilitated by one of the adult ECER organisers (m). Her paper was on the importance of using robotics to solve real-world problems, advocating that working on innovative ideas to protect the earth's environment should be one of the major tasks of robotics competitions. Her team had modified PRIAs underwater robot "Shark" to motivate young people to think about water pollution.

The ECER organiser took the opportunity to ask her if she thought that activities like that would appeal to girls and encourage more girls to participate in robotics activities and competitions. Her

answer was to state that there was no reason why this type of activity would not appeal equally to boys and girls. Following this, the researcher (f) spoke to the student in the main pit area. The original intention was to congratulate her on answering a tricky question well. In the conversation that followed the student expressed her frustration about being asked that type of question. The “how could we get more girls interested?”, “would X appeal more to girls?” type questions, she felt, were addressed to her because she was a girl. She stated that because she was already interested in robotics, how would she know what would appeal to someone (a girl or a boy) who was not interested in robotics. She also disliked the assumption that girls would not be interested in activities that boys were interested in, as that was not representative of her experience. In her experience she saw boys who were not interested in activities that other boys were. Essentially she felt that the notion of activities that particularly appeal to one gender or another was a false and unhelpful dichotomy which failed to move the issue of engaging ALL young people in robotics.

3.2.2.3.2 DO GIRLS ENGAGE WITH CHALLENGES OR LET BOYS ‘TAKE OVER’?

The experience of NTCH shows that girls did engage with challenges and they participated in collaborative work. In this case, with one of them being the team leader. The previous experience of Child 2 (f), 3 (f) and 4 (m) influenced how the 2018 team functioned, as their collective knowledge was brought forward and applied to the new team. Although Child 3 stated in an interview that everyone had an opportunity to question ideas, observations throughout the week demonstrated that this rarely happened, particularly by the less experienced members – although this could have occurred in unobservable forms such as pre-competition. While it was not explicitly stated by the team, it is implied that the new team members respected the knowledge of those who had experience of the competition and that this respect played a part in the leadership of the team. Gender did not appear to be the influencing factor, experience was.

Rather than letting boys take over, as mentioned girls were in a leadership position throughout the competition, but this leadership did not go unchallenged. While Child 2 (f) was the assigned team leader and so coordinated other members’ work, Child 1 (m) was observed taking control at various points. Both Child 2 and Child 1 attempted to control how the team performed by managing how the other team members worked.

Child 2 acted as a coordinator, through **delegation** of tasks to different team members, which was observed at multiple points over the course of the week. Child 2’s **coordination** meant that she oversaw the team members’ work and ensured that it was completed to a desirable standard and on time. As Child 1(m) stated: *“So our team leader, our team leader is Child 2. She was also responsible for organising when do er when some deadlines are due for documentation. She also decide er she also was responsible for getting everyone to work.”* Although, analysis of the video data showed that she mostly spent her time working on one of the robots with Child 7 (m), this does not account for the preparation time that students had to work together ahead of the competition which was not captured.

While Child 2 was mostly observed working on her robot, Child 1 (m) who worked on the other robot with Child 3 (f) was involved in **multiple tasks** throughout the week, working on robot 1 and delivering the onsite presentation. This allowed him to have control over multiple tasks, both through his own work and through directing others working on the same tasks. Child 2 was rarely seen to be directly instructing team members, while Child 1 was regularly observed to be very physical in his directing, for example by pointing and telling others what to do. Although the control

discussed here could be interpreted as a way of gaining or asserting power, there were no indications of that the boy intended to take control from the girl or that the girl wanted to let him take over.

By taking a leadership role, Child 2 (f) accepted a level of responsibility for the team. For example, when the team did not function as well as planned, Child 2 placed the **blame** on herself.

“Child 2: I think to coordinate a team, so I have to make sure that everyone has something to do, and that there is a person for everything and that all. Yeah but, some are bored, so I’ve failed.”

Child 1: Yeah but that’s kind of not your fault because there’s just not more to do.”

She clearly states that it is her personal mistake and not a fault of the team as a whole. Child 1 (m) disagrees with this blame and reassures Child 2 that she should not take this responsibility.

When the team competes with their robots, it is in the competition rules that only two team members may be located at the competition table. In every round of the competition, Child 1 and Child 2 represent the team at the table (Figure 4), again taking responsibility – in this situation ensuring that the robots are correctly set up.

Figure 4 Child 1 and Child 2 represent the team at the competition table

Finally, it is observed that during the interviews and researcher drop-ins both Child 1 and Child 2 were comfortable **speaking on behalf of the team**.

3.2.2.3.3 DO GIRLS PARTICIPATE IN COLLABORATIVE WORK?

Within their sub-teams, both girls were observed to work well with their male partner on the robots. Child 1 (m) and Child 3 (f)'s primary role was to work on robot 1 throughout the duration of the week, the only time they didn't work together was being on Wednesday morning whilst Child 1 delivered the onsite presentation. The pair spent almost all their time together and had a close working dynamic that included both working on all aspects of the robots – strategic, programming and mechanical. The pair communicated lots, including directing each other, discussing ideas or actively observing the other. Furthermore, they were often seen co-constructing the robot, as shown in Figure

5. Although Child 3 had a respectable amount of experience of the competition and Child 1 had natural leadership qualities, as described above, the pair were never observed to come into any conflict in their working dynamics, instead adjusting their leadership qualities to work effectively together.

Figure 5. Child 1 and Child 3 co-construct Robot 1

Although they had essentially the same objectives as Child 1 and 3, just working on a different robot, Child 2 (f) and Child 7 (m) had a very different working style as a pair. Whereas Child 1 and 3 very much shared the role, working on most things together and taking turns, Child 2 and 7 instead divided the work between them. Child 7 mostly worked on the programming, whereas Child 2's work focused on the physical robot. Furthermore, the two were often observed working separately, even sometimes physically distanced. This is an interesting comparison as both working groups seemed to have positive outcomes and work well, regardless of their very different working styles.

3.2.2.4 ER4STEM OBJECTIVE 3: ER4STEM WILL STUDY REAL-WORLD SOCIETAL PROBLEMS AS PERCEIVED BY EACH CHILD AND RELATE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES TO EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES AND REQUIRED INNOVATIONS

Rather than take each research question in turn, this sub-section explores this objective by looking at the papers written and presented at the ECER conference and Robotics in Education conference over the past three years. The papers and presentations by students was a task for which points were available as part of the wider ECER competition. There was no requirement for them to involve real-world societal problems or to be on the theme of that year's robotics competition. See Appendix C for full details of the papers.

Each year, at least one paper has explored a real-world societal problem as perceived by the students and related these challenges to existing technologies and required innovations. The topic for the ECER competition is often an inspiration. For example, in 2017 the theme was farming, with hay bales that had to be moved, corn seeds that had to be gathered and water that had to be collected (all represented by different coloured and shaped foam objects). That year, four of the 18 papers

identified a real-world societal problem related to agriculture and suggested ways that robots could be used to address the problems.

In 2018, the two papers (out of 13) which focused on real-world societal problems were not inspired by the topic and instead related to water pollution and the aging population. Both suggested how robots could be used to tackle problems and the one on water pollution suggested making specific challenges in future ECER conferences to motivate young people to think about water pollution and start to develop innovative solutions using robots.

These papers demonstrate that the students could identify and define problems that influence their lives at a societal level. While they did not evidence that they were able to solve these challenges, they typically involved 'grand challenges', which would take many years and large teams to solve. What they did demonstrate was an awareness of the issues and they were empowered to present their ideas to each other, and in some cases to adults attending the Robotics in Education conference (research scientists and teachers) as 'proper' scientists.

The students' presentations followed the style of presentations given at a scientific conference, with students delivering a short talk about their paper followed by the opportunity for the audience to ask questions. The talk followed a scientific structure – outlining their methods, findings and explaining the wider implications of their area of research. Questions to the presenters were in some cases asked by adults attending the Robotics in Education conference, by the competition organisers and by students in the audience. The latter allowed students who were not presenting to also actively engage with the process of a scientific presentation.

3.2.3 Conclusion

Overall, during ECER 2018 we found evidence of young people actively participating in all aspects of the conference and there are positive answers to the main research questions. However, the context of the findings needs careful consideration. All students involved in ECER had chosen to participate and therefore we could assume that the girls would enjoy and participate in the activities and that all students are already inclined towards STEM subjects and careers. Additionally, the findings from the Alliances report (Appendix B) highlight that while there is an intention to foster community spirit through collaboration, it is almost by chance whether this occurs or not. To increase the value of activities such as these and their efficacy in achieving their aims, the nature of the task and the structure of the working environment needs to be redesigned to not only facilitate but to require cooperation between teams, which is likely to result in increased communication through problem identification, deconstruction and solving, and in turn facilitate the development of collaboration skills and a sense of community.

3.3 WORKSHOPS

3.3.1 Context, Data Collection and Analysis

In total 1676 students participated in 72 educational robotics workshops in year 3 (as reported in D2.3), with 853 male and 823 female students spread across all partners. The children were between

the ages of 6 and 18. PRIA and TU Wien implemented 22 workshops with 515 students in Austria and Italy (1 educational robotics workshop in Italy), ESI CEE implemented 15 workshops with 396 students in Bulgaria, University of Athens implemented 9 workshops with 145 students in Greece, AcrossLimits implemented 13 workshops with 269 students in Malta and Cardiff University implemented 13 educational robotics workshops with 351 students in the UK.

A visual representation of the distribution of educational robotics workshops and the respective number of students per project partner can be seen in Figure 6. It also shows that most partners had a similar number of male and female participants. Female participants were 49% of the total number of students and male participants were 51% of the total number of students. With a few exceptions, there were no significant deviations between the shares of female and male students based on variables such as implementing partner, robotics kit and programming languages, which makes the research rather balanced in terms of gender in the majority of its aspects, as reported in D2.3.

Figure 6 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per project partner

Of these students, 1572 (93.8%) participated in the research and completed at least one of the pre or post questionnaires. This shows that the vast majority of children who participated in the workshops had parental informed consent to also take part in the research.

As outlined in the pre-kit (D6.2) in detail, a mixed-method approach to data collection was identified as most suitable for this project. A semi-structured approach to qualitative data collection was provided structure for rigour and flexibility to account for individual research contexts. Data collection began before the workshop with a Draw-A-Scientist (at work) Task and throughout the workshop either written observations were recorded or video data collected of the whole class and/or a focus group. Mid-way through the workshop, students were asked to complete a reflective task and a final reflective task was incorporated into the post-workshop questionnaire. Following the recommendations of the Year 1 and Year 2 evaluations, some workshops integrated the reflective activity into evidence of learning activities. At the end of each session the tutors were asked to

complete a reflective form. After the final workshop session, a focus group (typically the same focus group in the observations) was invited to take part in a short semi-structured interview. At the end of the workshop artefacts of learning that were created by the students were recorded, this included images of robots that were created, copies of code and worksheets.

Quantitative data was collected through pre- and post-workshop questionnaires, to rapidly survey the opinions of students. The primary purpose of this data was to provide an overview of the background of participants and the outcomes of the workshops from the perspective of the participants. Both quantitative and qualitative data collection approaches have acknowledged limitations but by using a mixed-method approach many of these can be countered.

Table 1 presents an overview of the data collected across the 72 workshops and 1572 students who had informed consent to participate in the research.

Table 1 Overview of data collected

	Number of workshops	Number of participants
Pre-questionnaire		1505
Post-questionnaire		1378
Draw-a-Scientist		1251
Observations	65	
Interviews		171
Artefacts of Learning	72	
Student Reflections	61	Varies (individual and group)
Tutor Reflections		164

Of the 1572 students who participated in the research, 1504 (96%) completed the pre-workshop questionnaire and 1378 (88%) completed the post-workshop questionnaire, which is a slight increase on the previous year. This data is used to gain evidence on students' experience, attitudes and assumptions. To complement this, 1251 (80%) completed the Draw-a-Scientist task. In year 3, it was increasingly common for students to attend more than workshop, either in the current year or previous years and they were not asked to repeat the Draw-a-Scientist task.

65 of the 72 workshops (90%) were observed using a variety of tools including written observation schedules and video. This was a notable increase on the previous year, due to non-academic partners gaining experience and familiarity with the processes involved. To understand the workshop from the perspective of the teacher or tutor, reflections were collected from most of the workshop tutors with some workshops collecting reflections from more than one tutor. A sample of students who attended workshops took part in a small-group interview after the workshop. This sample represents just under 11% of all participants in year 3. Additionally, 85% of workshops provided personal or team-based reflections on the experiences – this was a notable increase on the previous year and may be linked to the expectation of opportunities for critical thinking and reflection in year 3. The interviews and reflections, supplement the post-workshop questionnaires, observations and artefacts of the learning process, to provide detailed insight into the learner experience during the workshops. Overall, the data collection was comparable to Year 2.

Analysis of data collected during the workshops was completed in three phases. The first involved in-depth case study analysis, focusing on the recommendations from the evaluation of years 1 and 2 and the ER4STEM objectives. In total two workshops from each partner were analysed, each workshop counting as 1 case study, allowing the researchers to be sensitive to relevant contextual factors. Data analysis was distributed between the three academic project partners, TU Wein, UoA and CU, with Cardiff University leading and over-seeing the data analysis. These case studies are presented in Appendixes D and E (workshops by UoA), F and G (workshops by Across Limits), H and I (workshops by TU Wein), J and K (workshops by PRIA), L and M (workshops by ESI), N (3 workshops by CU reported as a single multiple-case study looking at evidence of learning) and O (3 different workshops which the same group of students participated in with CU, which focuses on collaboration). The second involved the quantitative analysis of the pre and post workshop questionnaires, at the level of each partner (Appendix P). The final phase of analysis was at the project level. A cross-case analysis of the

case studies was undertaken in relation to the recommendations for Year 3 and the ER4STEM objectives, drawing on the partner-level analysis of the questionnaires to support or refute generalisations and provide relevant contextual information.

3.3.2 Findings

This section presents the results of the final analysis phase, discussing them in terms of the recommendations for Year 3, followed by the ER4STEM objectives. It also draws upon the reports on the workshops and activity plans presented in D2.3 and D4.3. It should be noted that some of the recommendations are modified or collapsed for the purpose of reporting.

3.3.2.1 YEAR 2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the evaluation of workshops in Year 1, 10 recommendations for the framework, activity plans, workshops and repository emerged (D6.3). These were implemented in workshops in Year 2 and the evaluation of these workshops resulted in a further set of recommendations to refine the workshops in the final project year. In Year 3 the educational robotics workshops curriculum was mostly connected to six of the recommendations, namely teamwork and collaboration, mixed gender teams; communication; creativity; critical thinking and evidence of learning as those six skills were among the most frequently targeted by the ER4STEM partners' Year 3 activity plans. Figure 7 illustrates the implementation of the 10 recommendations in the workshops of the third year as reported in D2.3. It should be noted that not all workshops were expected to address all of the recommendations.

Figure 7 Share of all Year 3 workshops that cover the Y2 recommendations in terms of 21st century skills

While only 7% of workshops were reported as including differentiation (26% partially) is the lowest implementation of all of the recommendations, it is notable to see examples of differentiation in the workshops analysed in depth in Appendixes J, K, L and N. In the Mathbot workshop (Appendix L), for example, there is differentiation by outcome – extension activities are given to those students who complete the earlier tasks.

What we don't see across ER4STEM activities is differentiation by task. So students who are more or less able are not given different tasks. In fact, where known, students of different ability levels are usually grouped together in the same team, e.g. Insects' Battle workshop (Appendix E). The mixing of abilities aligns with the ethos of ER4STEM and therefore differentiation by outcome is the most appropriate approach.

3.3.2.2 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: ACTIVITY PLANS SHOULD INCLUDE SPECIFIC TASKS TO EXPLICITLY INTRODUCE AND ENGAGE STUDENTS WITH RELEVANT ASPECTS OF TEAMWORK

While objectives in activity plans often stated the importance of children learning to share ideas, about communicating and other relevant aspects of teamwork, from the case studies selected there was little evidence of specific activities to introduce students to these skills.

For example, while the activity plan 'Engaging with robots in a fun way' from AcrossLimits included the social and action related objective "*students collaborate, share ideas with each other and learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being in teams/groups*", there were no specific activities to support this. As a result, we see in the case study presented in Appendix F of this workshop implemented with 11-12 year old students, a team of two students who do not collaborate throughout the two day workshop. Instead the boy takes the lead, the girl engages when the teacher provides encouragement, but otherwise the two students work independently. A particularly good example of this is found in the reported Episode 3 of this report during which the students had to make Dash turn when a sound is heard. When a problem came up 520315 (f) asked again for the tutor to come close. When tutor gave her feedback, 520315 (f) changed the program by herself and after programming for approximately 5 minutes she decided to test it. She didn't include her teammate in the decision making about their program but she asked him to make the sound for Dash in order to check if their program was correct. 520315 (f) continued to make changes for the next 12 minutes and 520314 (m) seemed to get bored. When a part of the program was decided, 520315 (f) gave the tablet to the boy and wrote down her answer on their worksheet. While the intended design of the workshop was for students to alternate roles (programming and writing), they were expected to work together to solve the problems, however, in this case we saw that one child was always disengaged. We return to discuss this case in more detail and the tutor's actions in section 3.3.2.4 below.

The conclusions of this case study highlight that the students' negative attitudes towards collaboration in the pre-questionnaire may have been part of the reason for the difficulties encountered by this team. This emphasises the need for specific tasks to introduce students to relevant aspects of team work, particularly as teachers do not typically ask students about such things before requiring them to work in teams.

Another consequence of not including specific tasks to explicitly teach skills can be seen in the case of Cardiff University's workshops with SLurtles (Appendix O), where students had to communicate with their partner predominantly through the virtual world. While the children, aged 11-12 years old, could use the text chat for basic communication, they struggled to express more complex ideas about

the design of their houses in this medium and preferred to meet their partner face-to-face to discuss ideas. While the students in this case were able to verbally communicate their ideas face-to-face, it was the technology which created a significant barrier. Computer mediated communication (CMC) is well known to be a difficult medium for communication for adults and so these skills need to be developed. In this case, it may have been better to provide it as an option during the short workshop sessions (typically less than 50 minutes), but to initially provide face-to-face planning time.

While text-based communication was problematic for students, in the same case study there were frequent reminders from the teacher about how to work as a team. As mentioned, students were provided with designated face-to-face planning time and the value of this was explained by the teacher who had a clear expected outcome by the end, for example, to have a list of tasks for each person to complete that session. The teacher monitored this by asking each student to write the tasks that they would complete during that session on a small personal whiteboard, which was then placed above their computer (Figure 8). This task, whilst not mentioned in the activity plan is a good example of how to incrementally introduce students to relevant skills and ways of working for effective teamwork to occur.

Figure 8 List of objects for student to create in the virtual world

3.3.2.3 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: WHERE TEAMS ARE EXPECTED TO DISTRIBUTE ROLES AMONGST THE TEAM, ALL CHILDREN SHOULD HAVE THE

OPPORTUNITY TO TAKE EACH ROLE, AND THAT ROLES SHOULD BE SPECIFIC, REQUIRED AND NOT REPEATED.

In Year 2, it was observed that while some workshops included the rotation of roles between students, to provide everyone with an opportunity to programme (for instance), some of the roles were unclear, appeared unnecessary and repeated, meaning that more than one student was doing the same task. This was seen in the Mathbot workshop by ESI. In Year 3 ESI used the same workshop activity plan and we see again that there are multiple roles which do not include programming (the main task) and there is still overlap between roles (one person who makes sure the rules are followed and one person who makes sure everything is correct and reads the task). One implementation of this workshop is reported in Appendix L in which **power and control** are identified as major categories in the interactions between the focus group, which comprises two girls and two boys. While this is interpreted as linked to gender, there are some incidents which appear to be linked to the lack of specific and necessary roles. While the boys are generally observed to take over the activity, one of the girls actively tries to take control at different points by taking ownership of tools that were required for the task.

In theory, the movement of tools should have corresponded with which individual was assuming which role, and as stated in the activity plan, this should have changed after each task. However, team members would often be seen to take over each other's roles, through individuals physically taking away the tool that another team member was using. This is shown in Figure 9 where Child 4 (f) reaches to take the keyboard away from Child 2 (m) whilst he is distracted by Child 3 (f) talking to him.

Figure 9. Child 4 (f) moves keyboard away from Child 2 (m)

Another example is shown in Figure 10, where both Child 2 (m) and 3 (f) both trying to hold the robot, whilst Child 2 also presses buttons on the keyboard at the same time as Child 4 (f).

Figure 10. Team members try to contribute to and take over other member's roles

The majority of the interactions observed in the focus group (15 out of 17 interactions), where one group member takes a tool off another member happened between the genders, rather than for example, one of the girls taking the robot off the other girl. However, there were also some instances where this intervention would occur within the gender, for example when the boys are both trying to do that same role at the keyboard while the girls both hold the cable. While it could be interpreted as a gendered interaction, involving gender stereotypes that boys would be 'in charge', it may also be due to the lack of meaningful roles for all partners.

This case highlights a particular issue for teachers wishing to engage young learners in robotics activities. That is, working with limited resources. In the case where a class set of robots only allows for one robot between four children and there are only two distinct roles, the orchestration of an equitable collaboration is clearly difficult. So while all children should have the opportunity to take a role that is specific, required and not repeated, they may also need clear guidance and specific tasks (relating to the previous recommendation). For instance, introducing the children to how to effectively collaborate in such circumstances, as what happens in this case is not dissimilar to that in Malta, reported in Appendix F in the previous section. Another point to consider and concept to introduce to students, is that while someone might have a specific role within a team, it does not necessarily mean that they are the only person who can or should do that role and that they may effectively collaborate with others to complete their individual task.

Returning to the case in Appendix F from AcrossLimits, discussed in the previous section, even though the students were expected to exchange roles during the activities, as mentioned, 520315 (f), who was fully engaged in programming, worked separately from her teammate. Throughout the workshop she would ask questions and discuss solutions with the tutor rather than 520314 (m), but also, when she had taken her feedback, she acted by herself, not sharing her thoughts and decisions with the other student. This continued until the program was completed and she noted it on the worksheet. 520315 (f) took responsibility for both tasks, coding and writing down the code, which were supposed

to be split between the team members and rotated for each puzzle. Only when 520315 (f) left the tablet did 520314 (m) take over, trying to complete the code, without having discussed with his teammate what she had been already done. In this case, although there were two roles, for these two students there was no collaboration and at best there was cooperation, but only on rare occasions following the intervention of a tutor (illustrated in the next section).

3.3.2.4 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: DEVELOP STRATEGIES TO RE-ENGAGE EXCLUDED OR DISENGAGED STUDENTS

As previously mentioned, Appendix F presents a case study in which one of a pair of students (one female, one male) was always observed to be excluded from the activities of their partner. While the case study presents this as one gender taking control, it is not clear that this is a gendered interaction and could feasibly occur within a single-gender team. What is interesting though, from the point of view of the recommendation to develop strategies to re-engage excluded and disengaged students, is that the analysis includes episodes during which tutors use different approaches to engage both students in the activities.

In the first episode, the boy seemed to be interested in the subject of the workshop, raising his hand willingly to answer tutor's questions while the girl was seen sitting behind, listening carefully. As mentioned in the case study, it is possible that their different initial reactions are linked to their differences regarding their attitudes towards STEM subjects and their previous experience with programming. More precisely, the girl mentioned in the pre-questionnaire that she didn't like science and math and she didn't have any previous experience with programming, unlike her teammate. However, it may also be linked to their own personality, gender stereotypes or the student's own preferences around working with other people. Whilst the girl stated in the pre-questionnaire that she didn't like to work by herself, the boy stated that he did. In response to the question about working in teams their answers were reversed.

When a tutor gave tablets to the students, the boy took the tablet and started exploring while the girl hesitated (seen behind the bot in Figure 11). However, when the tutor explained to the class that the robot was controlled through the tablet, she came closer (Figure 12).

Figure 11: While the boy was engaged, the girl was more hesitant.

Figure 12: The girl became more interested, as she realises the relation of the tablet to the robot.

A tutor, who was near the team, then further facilitated the inclusion of the girl, pushing her closer to the tablet so she could see. This way the team moved closer together so both members could participate.

Figure 13: The tutor is encouraging the girl to participate.

After the tutor's intervention, 520315 (f) appeared to be more willing to participate. Even if 520314 (m) continued to hold the tablet on his side, she would move closer and started touching the tablet's screen, exploring the software (Figure 5).

Figure 14 After the tutor's encouragement, the girl participates more

In episode 2 the students worked on a puzzle. While the boy was programming, the girl decided to come closer to the tablet again. This time he gave her the tablet and explained to her what they had to do. She began to program and after approximately 2 minutes the boy lost interest and started playing with his cell-phone. When later the girl had a question, she called the tutor for help, rather than the boy. When the tutor gave some directions and the girl seemed to understand, the tutor asked her to explain to her teammate what they had to do and when the tutor left the students were

engaged in an active discussion for about 5 minutes. Then, as the girl continued programming both students were observed discussing their ideas.

Figure 15: The girl isolates herself again, as the boy works on the programme by himself.

At points when the boy was programming the robot and the girl appeared disengaged, the tutor intervened in some way and the girl became more actively engaged. However, without this intervention she would isolate herself from the activity (Figure 15). Similarly, when the girl was programming the robot, the boy appeared completely disengaged and did not reengage until control of the tablet was given to him by the girl. In this case, while the girl appeared initially reticent to get involved, she was quickly motivated by the activity, but in spite of her claim in the pre-questionnaire she tended to work on her own.

The most significant intervention by a tutor occurred when the boy stopped working on a puzzle and the girl made a suggestion to him. He left the tablet to her and she began to program. After a while she raised her hand, possibly having faced a problem or having a question. The boy checked her program and tried to explain something to her but she kept asking tutor's advice. When the tutor came close to the team both members were encouraged to explain to him the problem. The tutor listened to the girl and then the boy took the tablet and showed the tutor what he proposed. The tutor asked the boy questions about his proposal and included the girl in the discussion. The students then discussed their ideas in the presence of the tutor, who listened to both sides. While the students were not fighting they appeared uncomfortable with each other. When the tutor left, the girl tested the program which proved to have the desired result and the boy wrote the solution on the program sheet.

Once again the girl turned to the tutor for help instead of taking seriously the boy's proposal. However, this time the tutor didn't seem to give guidance but acted as a facilitator of their communication. Being a mediator between the two helped them express themselves better and in a more open way. This kind of role for the tutor encouraged more effective/efficient communication, promoting this way of working to promote better understanding between the members of the team.

Following this the atmosphere became more collaborative as, right after, the boy took over noting their code and the girl waited for him to finish in order to go on in the next puzzle together.

The strategies observed in the case include:

- Physically moving students
- Answering a student's question and asking them to explain the answer to their teammate
- Mediating interactions between students

What is clear from this case study is that tutors/teachers need multiple strategies to encourage children to work together throughout workshops. While this pair struggled to work together, not all teams did. Providing different ways of collaborating through engaging in different workshops as part of the ER4STEM curriculum may provide opportunities for learners to develop their team-working skills through different types of experiences and find ones that work well for them. This links to the recommendation made in 3.3.2.11 below.

3.3.2.5 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: DEVELOP ACTIVITIES TO RAISE AWARENESS OF IMPLICIT AND EXPLICIT GENDER BIASES IN RELATION TO STEM

Across the Year 3 activity plans, there were no specific instances of activities to raise awareness of the implicit and explicit gender biases that people hold in relation to STEM. However, the ESI introductory activities were centred on the Draw-A-Scientist Task which was part of the evaluation and this provided a point for discussion of children's existing assumptions about scientists and associated stereotypes. In this way the evaluation (from which the need for such activities was identified) became a part of the solution.

3.3.2.6 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: WHEN TEAMS ARE FIRST FORMED, PROVIDE WAYS FOR THEM TO DEVELOP A SENSE OF TEAM IDENTITY AND OWNERSHIP

In Year 2, workshops implemented by UoA identified the value of providing teams with an opportunity to develop a sense of team identity and ownership of their artefacts (robots or other constructions). In Year 3, structured activities by AL that involved collaboration such as asking questions, listening to one another and reflecting on questions about the collaboration (through the evaluation), provided a way to foster team cohesion and with that, potentially foster a sense of team identity. Workshops run by CU involved students creating artefacts with SLurtles in a 40x40meter space in the virtual world. Having a designated space with a group name which others could visit and allowing learners to choose what they created in this space, helped to foster a sense of ownership over what was created.

3.3.2.7 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: PROVIDE SHARED SPACES FOR STUDENTS FROM DIFFERENT GROUPS TO MEET AND ENCOURAGE THE SHARING OF IDEAS/SUPPORTING OTHERS

There were various opportunities provided to students to share what they had done, across the workshops implemented in Year 3. In the Robotics in Virtual Worlds workshops by Cardiff University, students were often observed visiting other people's spaces in the virtual world. They would use their avatar to navigate to another section of the class island. Linked to this, as students worked in

physically-distributed pairs (see Appendix O), they were typically sat next to friends and would visit their friend's space on the island, or simply look at their friend's computer screen. This facilitated the sharing of ideas between teams and opportunities to support other teams.

In the robot elevator workshop by TU Wein (reported in Appendix I and J), at the end of some activities groups would present their solution to the real-life problem they had been given. The problem was to find a solution to lifting a weight using the robot and could be solved in a number of ways. When they presented their solution the groups had to explain the advantages and disadvantages of their solution and after all the presentations had been given, the class was asked to come to a consensus on the best solution.

These two examples illustrate two very different approaches to the concept of shared space. The first is that by freely (unconstrained by the teacher, and even encouraged by the teacher), physically moving through a shared space (whether virtual or not) students gain opportunities to meet others, share ideas and support each other. Also, in the case of a physically distributed collaboration, students are able to gain supports and share ideas with those around them, thus generating a collaborative, whole class learning environment.

While the first is a very free-form, self-organising version of a shared space which facilitates collaboration, the second is teacher-driven. In this case there is a designated time for all children to share their solutions and they discuss together which will be chosen as the preferred solution. The shared space in this case is the whole room. We see similar teacher-driven sharing of ideas in other workshops and in the Alliance round of the ECER competition. This is unlike the free-form collaboration that was observed in the Greek workshop in Year 2 which provided a shared space for students to collect materials from. Both structured and free-form opportunities to share ideas are valuable and are orchestrated in different ways.

A very different application of 'shared space' can be seen in the Education Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills workshop by ESI, in which teams competed against each other in a sorting task involving robotic arms to sort recycling, described in more detail in section 3.3.2.11 below and Appendix M. The game took place in a new game area that was shared between the teams, meaning that no one team had ownership over the environment or tools other than their robot. A photo taken whilst the students played the game is shown in Figure 16, which illustrates this shared space and the interest that the students are taking in the game.

Figure 16. Students playing the collaborative game

While this is a shared space created by the teacher it is not controlled by the teacher. Each team has one member who is controlling the robot and the other team members can support, observing the actions of other teams to get ideas. It should be noted that this activity could be collaborative or competitive, with teams either working together to complete the task or against each other to see who could complete their recycling first.

3.3.2.8 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: CONTINUE TO DEVELOP MULTIPLE WAYS FOR STUDENTS TO INCORPORATE A CREATIVE ELEMENT WITHIN ROBOTICS WORKSHOPS.

Across the workshops implemented in Year 3, new creative elements were introduced to the robotics workshops. These included students writing stories about their robot's adventures (Figure 17), designing a prototype robot using craft materials (Figure 18).

Figure 17 Artefact of storytelling activity with Thymio robot

Figure 18 Glasses and robot made during the Design Thinking workshop

Further examples are available in the report on the activity plans (D4.3). Overall, we can see that most workshops incorporate a creative element. Those that don't tend to focus on students investigating mathematical concepts, although there are some which are primarily focused on mathematics which also include a creative element.

3.3.2.9 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: DEVELOP WAYS TO INTRODUCE STUDENTS TO 'WAYS TO THINK' WHEN THEY ENCOUNTER PROBLEMS.

In University of Athens' workshop 432 'Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine', spatial orientation and spatial visualisation were used to support students' expression of what they understood. The communication of students' ideas through this kind of representation helped them adopt the right referring context in order to describe robots' movements. Critical incidents are described in Appendix D, with one example of students using multiple representation systems presented here:

In order to draw the desirable shape, students had to imagine which move would result in which line of the net that the robot would draw. To do this, it was necessary to translate the mental dynamic imagery about the robot's movements into the corresponding schematic representation that would be drawn on the paper. This led students to constantly move from one representation to another to check if the result of each movement resulted in the desirable shape.

An example of the above is the work of group 3, which adopts an enhanced strategy. While the girls discuss the robot's movements to create the shape they want, at first they use gestures to represent the movements of the vehicle so that they can come to a conclusion about the commands they are going to use and their sequence. However, this proves not to be enough. So they decide to create and use another, more concrete representation of their work. They draw the desired net on the paper (Figure 19) and for each line of that net, they represent kinaesthetically the robot's movement and for each of these movements they make a decision about the command they are going to use:

Students on video, numbers relate to movements illustrated in Figure 19:

S2: So, at first we have to do this line (1)...

S1: And then this one (2).

S2: Yes, so the small vehicle goes forward (1) and then the two bigger vehicles go forward (2)...

S1: Yes and then we have to go like this (3)... so the small vehicle goes forward again.

Figure 19 Movements 1, 2 and 3 corresponding to line segments each move draws

In the above episode, students facilitate their thinking using additional representations moving from one representational system to another. The schematic representation they designed on the paper guides them regarding the "steps" of the robot. Their representation helps them to control step-by-step the result of each movement. Each command corresponds to a line and each line has a specific direction. The direction of each line corresponds to the entity which they orient to each time. This continuous transition from the graphical representation to the visualization of the robot movements and then to the creation of the program, helps them adjust their orientation with respect to a different entity for each movement. This way students progressively build a mental representation, a dynamic image of the way in which the robot moves, thus developing their spatial orientation and visualisation skills.

While many of the activity plans do not include a specific section on ‘ways to think’ when encountering problems, we do see in the activity plans and analyses of the workshops that tutors were responsive to students who encountered difficulties and introduced them to new ways of thinking. There are essentially two approaches that are used: 1) provide students with a method to follow just-in-case, or 2) provide methods just-in-time. The latter can be more helpful but often requires much more time from the tutor on a one-to-small-group basis and is less efficient than introducing a way of working to the whole class, however the latter may easily be forgotten ‘in the moment’ of encountering the problem. Therefore, most teachers are likely to use a combination of the two, but where adult or another more knowledgeable person is unavailable (particularly common as most teachers teach classes on their own), other supports such as worksheets to scaffold may be valuable.

3.3.2.10 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: THE ER4STEM FRAMEWORK, ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATES AND REPOSITORY SHOULD DRAW ATTENTION TO THE NEED TO DEVELOP RESILIENCE AND PROVIDE RECOMMENDATIONS FOR NON-SPECIALISTS

Within the activity plan template there is an activity block called “Handling failure” which is integrated in the repository to support non-specialists. The aim is to highlight the importance of encountering problems that are not easily solved by students, to experience failure, uncertainty and develop resilience. D.4.2 illustrates some of the activities that were designed for each workshop that use this block. In different workshops we see students introduced to different way to think when they encounter problems from the perspective of resilience.

For example, in the PRIA workshop ‘Design Thinking’, students were introduced to the concept of prototyping and aimed to develop resilience when encountering errors, through the activity “Clapping Game – Errors Happen”. This was a clapping game which was made more complicated over time to attain more mistakes and the game rules were also changed over time. The aim of the activity was to give the students the feeling that making mistakes is not bad, but rather something which happens and to promote a freer idea development process. Then to support students as they began to develop prototypes, the concept was explained to them with an emphasis on the notion that “there is no bad idea”:

PRIA_170928_Tutor_Reflection

What was the most successful part of today’s session? Why?

Tutor 1: ‘Students had the most fun when turning their ideas into actual design prototypes and building them’.

Tutor 2: ‘Building the prototype robots with the constraints the students had to deal with from the cards they had drawn’.

Tutor 3: ‘What I feel was the greatest success of today is that they actually followed the one, most important rule we gave them at the beginning of the workshop: “There are no bad ideas – if you think that somebody should do something in a different way, don’t say, ‘That’s a really stupid way to do it’, but say, ‘Alright, that looks pretty good but it could be even better by adding this...’” There was a task where they had to present their ideas to their

neighbour. During this part, nobody was rude, and everyone appreciated the others' work. That was the biggest success to me'.

3.3.2.11 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: 21ST CENTURY SKILLS SHOULD BE GRADUALLY DEVELOPED ACROSS THE ER4STEM CURRICULUM.

In the ESI workshops, we see several students returning in the second and/or third year of the ER4STEM project to engage in a second or third workshop. This provides opportunities to develop 21st Century skills with returning students. However, one of the difficulties is that these workshops also contained students who had previously not participated in ER4STEM workshops. These workshops provided multiple opportunities for students to learn 21st Century skills in one activity and then get an opportunity to apply and develop them in another activity with another group of students.

For example, in the Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills workshop (reported in Appendix M) was held over two sessions, four days apart, lasting two hours per sessions and four hours in total. Students worked in groups of three to five members, and each group had their own robot and computer. Seven participants had completed the ER4STEM workshop 'Visualising Mathematics with the Mathbot' a year previously, of which six of these participants had also completed the ER4STEM workshop 'Educational Robotics for Creativity' two years previously. Alongside this recurring participation, the group also participated in robotics workshops run by ESICEE as part of their school curriculum for the year, outside of ER4STEM. Furthermore, ten participants had programming lessons writing in the programming languages JavaScript or C++, four participants had attended extracurricular robotics clubs and six participants had used robots at home. Overall, the group were of high ability and were familiar with the style of work and teamwork involved in the workshop, were familiar with the tutors running the workshop and were only unfamiliar with the type of robot being used.

The workshop involved an innovative approach to collaboration at the end of the workshop in the form of a game. Previously, students had been working in groups of 3-4 participants, but during this final game individuals from each team took it in turns to play collaboratively alongside members from the other teams, whilst the other participants watched and supported. Analysis of data from the workshop demonstrates that it was effective in teaching the students the importance of working in a team.

The game was based on the simulation of a waste separation station, with students using the robots to separate textile (felt balls), bio waste (coffee capsules) and plastic (bottle caps). The game is explained in the activity plan as such:

"The setting of the game consists of 2-4 tables merged together with a sufficient amount of chairs around them so that 2-4 teams could work on them. Every team has their own computer and robotic arm (in case of PCs that can't be easily moved, USB extension cables will be needed). Arms are placed on the same game board. The game board could be one of the sheets they previously worked on but should now be divided into three segments, similarly to as shown on the diagram below.

This way Arm 3 will be responsible for collecting textile (in our case felt balls), Arm 2 will collect bio waste (in our case it is represented by the coffee capsules) and Arm 1 will collect plastic (bottle caps). Elements are collected from all over the field and placed in respectively marked rectangle.

All elements are scattered in the middle of the field in a way that will prevent every arm being able to collect all objects of the material it is responsible for collecting, without relying on somebody else helping them out by pushing or dropping an element they need within their range.

The teams have 7 minutes for actual waste collection and 3 minutes to discuss or come up with a strategy before the game and to put the arm in a starting position of their choice. After the game, a collaborative reflection lead by the tutors takes place.

Score is formed by how many items are overall collected by all teams.”

During the whole workshop, the students had been working collaboratively together in teams to learn about, by designing the final game to include each team to work together in one giant team, a form of meta-collaboration takes place. The students worked both within their team (with one student taking the lead and the others supporting) and also within the whole class (using the robots collaboratively to achieve the most points they can).

During the interview, the participants explained that the final game had taught them a lot about the importance of teamwork and collaborating with others. Upon being asked what they would remember from the entire workshop, students mentioned the collaborative game:

“21001 (m): The activities with the arm and the main game with the recycling because you gave us problems that were difficult to solve by yourself and everything had to be happening in a team.

...

23032 (m): I learned from this activity with the arm that it is better to play in a team with someone, to help each other, it is better than to work alone and that it will be hard to make something similar alone. With friends you are able to do much more.

21012 (m): I also liked the last game because I understood that it is better to work in team than to work alone because in a certain moment, for example in this game with the

waste, our team had to collect bottle caps and when we collected all nearby bottle caps, we needed help to collect the bottle caps that were not within our reach and thus I realized how important it is to have a team.”

As this is the third workshop by ESI, which build upon the previous experiences of students, it provides an opportunity to extend and develop students' 21st Century Skills. This is one of the benefits of an integrated generic curriculum (deliverable 2.4), which allows teachers to flexibly adapt activities to the needs of learners. While some students may be very comfortable working in teams, others may require additional supports and so approaches from other activity plans can be applied to more technically advanced workshops.

3.3.2.12 YEAR 3 RECOMMENDATION: DEVELOP WAYS TO EVIDENCE LEARNING AS PART OF ACTIVITY PLANS.

Across the workshops reported in the activity plans and analysed in the appendixes, we see a marked increase in the awareness of the consortium of the importance of evidencing learning and the difficulties that are encountered. In the workshops run by Cardiff University, students created an online workbook called a Sway to document the work that they had done. As is standard practice in the UK, the class teacher provided the class with specific learning objectives for each lesson. In the Sways the students had to demonstrate how they had met these objectives. However, as discussed in Appendix N, there were problems with the completion of these online books. Students were expected to write about how they had met each objective and include relevant screenshots as evidence. Despite this being a standard expectation in the school, students either did not complete the task or simply parroted back the learning objective with “I have...”, followed by the learning objective.

However, the more specific a learning objective, the more likely it was to have some form of evidence. Where students had to show they had completed a task, they often only gave partial evidence. For example, if students had to programme the SLurtle to build a square, they often included a screenshot of the square but not the code. Therefore, the teacher has no way of knowing how the students had created this square, for example, not knowing whether the student had included a loop in their programme. As loops were not included in the objective it is perhaps understandable why a student might not include the code, but equally the teacher would not know if the student had simply run a ‘When touched, move 1 meter, turn right 90’ script 4 times to create the square.

Another problem was that the students often viewed recording what they had done as a distraction or a chore - something that had to be done but that took them away from what they wanted to do. We saw similar evidence of this in one of the workshops reported last year from Malta. This activity also required the teacher to remind students to complete their Sways and provide them with dedicated time to do this. When this did not happen, we see (in Appendix N) that there is a rapid loss of engagement with this activity.

There are of course direct and indirect methods of evidencing learning. Direct methods rely on artefacts of learning, such as the Sways or a worksheet, but as part of the research project there were three opportunities to evidence learning: 1) interviews, 2) post-questionnaire and 3) observations. Typically, a class teacher would also use observations when assessing their students' learning. However, increasingly this evidence has to be recorded in some way.

One of the difficulties with evidencing learning in robotics activities is identified in the analysis of Evidence of Learning in Appendix L. That is, while there was some effective evidence of learning for the groups as a whole, there was no evidence of what individuals learnt. However, taking a communal constructivist approach, it is the knowledge of the group that is most important. This resonates with the ethos of ER4STEM, that each member of the team brings their own knowledge and skill set to bear on a robotics problem. This is the power of robotics in education, as it requires students to engage with 21st Century skills and an opportunity to develop an understanding that in industry (and most work environments) individuals need to be able to work effectively in a team to effectively solve a problem. However, with the emphasis on individual assessment across education systems, teachers and parents might reasonably find the evidencing of learning at a team rather than individual level problematic. This is an important tension to consider if educational robotics activities are to become common place – the expectations of those in education because of the demands of individualised assessment regimes (decided by government or international bodies i.e. PISA) and the needs of industry.

3.3.2.13 ER4STEM OBJECTIVE 1: ER4STEM WILL APPROACH AND ENGAGE CHILDREN BY OFFERING MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS INTO CREATIVE STEM (STEAM) VIA ROBOTICS

Year 3 of the ER4STEM project has seen yet more ways to engage young people in creative STEM via robotics. Across the activity plans we see students engaging in real-world problems, (e.g. Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills), introduced to Design Thinking, given challenges that they may or may not be able to complete but given the skills to attempt these and the environment in which failure is unproblematic and viewed as an opportunity to learn and develop.

We also see students using robots to explore things which are of personal interest to them but not specified in activity plans. For instance, in Appendix M, it was found that during their exploration of the robotic arm, while students did not clearly define and identify problems, they did relate the use of the robot to their own lives, making it personally meaningful and undertaking playful exploration. Furthermore, they considered the wider implications for use of the robot, for issues that perhaps didn't affect them personally, but that they identified as societal problems. The activity plan sets out for each group to take part in a collaborative game, which was based on a simulation of a waste separation station. In the tutor reflection, the tutor stated that *"The collaborative game was a huge success and could be further improved on in order to teach other real life principles."*

Whilst the students did not directly refer to the game and its real-life scenario, students did commonly refer to real-life applications of robots in the interview and in their mid-point reflections. For example, Group 6 stated in their mid-point reflection that they had learnt *"that every robot serves different purpose and while some robots have wheels and serve the purpose of moving, in the two-dimensional space, there are other robots, like this arm or even drones"*. Group 2 stated that *"We saw a new robot that was different than the other robots we have worked with. We also seen other applications of robotics."* Two themes can be noted here: that the robot arm was different to the other robots the students had worked with, and that robots have applications in real life. Group 1 further expanded on these concepts:

"We worked with a robot that is, how should we say... more realistic, more down to earth. The other robots look like toys or cars, but this one simulates a human arm and is a smaller"

copy of a robot that is used in engineering about a lot of things. So we saw something that looked like robotics more than the Finch robot, for example.”

The students found that they could connect to the realism of this robot and its applications, which made it personally meaningful. This personal connection was observed in the video and photo data through playful exploration, in which groups would use the robot to pick up their own belongings, such as a phone (Figure 20), lipbalm (Figure 21), to squeeze their nose (Figure 22) or to attempt to write something with a pen (Figure 23).

Figure 20. Robot holding a phone

Figure 21. Robot holding lipbalm

Figure 22. Robot squeezing a student's nose

Figure 23. Robot holding a pencil

Regarding making the robot hold a pen – which was observed in multiple groups - Group 4 reflected that they were most proud of *“When we picked up a pen with the robotic arm and tried to write something. It wasn't successful but it is something we'd remember.”* The interviewees even explored how they could be successful in using the robot to write with a pen by making it even more *“realistic”* by having more grippers. In this example, the students identify a problem by themselves and find a hypothetical but realistic creative solution:

“23033 (m): We can add more fingers to the arm and move these fingers.

Interviewer: So, you would like more functional arm with more degrees of freedom? (C2) What will be the advantage if the robotic arm is like a real human arm, with more fingers?

23033: For example, the arm can take a pen and write with it. To try writing a letter or word and it will be interesting because you should consider very

precisely how many seconds it should write when you program it, for example, for a “w”.

Finally, participants mentioned in four different sources (mid-point reflections and the interview) that they could relate and apply what they had learnt in the workshop to other subjects. This largely included mathematics, through their new knowledge of 3D coordinates. However, participants in the interview expanded that they thought their knowledge of the robot could be applied to many of their other school subjects.

“23038 (m): Well, in mathematics and information technology it could help us. If we can learn also how the robot is built, it can help for the subjects of technology and entrepreneurship.

...

23032 (m): Yes, for the engineering, according my opinion, it is very useful because we know the purposes of the robot’s components and also, this is based on the human arm, in the case with the robotic arm. Or the human body, in relation to other robots, and thus we could learn about the human system before we have biology classes.

21012 (m): According to me, for this workshop we needed knowledge in mathematics to know the coordinates, how to deal with such type of systems; we needed knowledge in Human and Nature to know the place and functions of the parts of the human body, we needed knowledge on information technology for the programming. And this workshop developed our knowledge in these sciences.”

This example demonstrates just one occurrence of students demonstrating a natural curiosity when it comes to interacting with robots and this is one of the reasons why robots are a powerful vehicle to engage young people with STEM ideas through creative STEAM activities. They connect them to their personal interests and share their ideas through tangible objects while exploring, testing and extending their understanding of STEM concepts.

3.3.2.14 ER4STEM OBJECTIVE 2: ER4STEM WILL OFFER EDUCATIONAL METHODS FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS TO ENGAGE ALL YOUNG LEARNERS

The notion of ‘all’ young learners is a very broad one. In ER4STEM activities reported in Year 3, we see workshops have been successfully engaged with by boys and girls (almost an equal split), with an age range of 6-18. Some have physical disabilities, while others have a range of hidden additional educational needs. ER4STEM participants come from a diverse cultural, socioeconomic and religious background, including some students who are non-native speakers of the local language. So from this perspective we can say that ER4STEM activities have reached all young learners with high levels of engagement across the board. This is discussed in more detail in Section 5.

3.3.2.14.1 DO THE ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM EDUCATION AND CAREERS?

Overall, the Year 3 workshops did encourage interest in STEM education, although understandably, which subjects depended on the focus of the workshop.

It was noted in Year 2 that children from Greece and Bulgaria are significantly more likely to already be interested in STEM subjects than children from the UK & Ireland, Malta and Austria. However, in Year 3, while Bulgarian students are still the most likely to be interested in studying maths and science in the future, those from Malta were likely to already be interested in studying maths and science (highest percentage across partners). Again, students from Austria and the UK were least likely to be interested in STEM subjects before the workshops (see Table 2).

Table 2 Percentage of participants per partner for the questions “would you like to study maths or science when you are older?” The percentage is calculated per the total number of participants of each partner.

	Would you like to study maths when you are older?		Would you like to study science when you are older?	
	no	yes	no	yes
AL	20%	56%	26%	54%
CU	69%	31%	61%	38%
ESICEE	21%	66%	32%	48%
PRIA	68%	23%	63%	25%
TU Wien	45%	13%	36%	25%
UoA	60%	37%	50%	49%

Comparing these responses to questions about students’ attitudes towards science and mathematics, (reported in Appendix P), we see that students who attended PRIA’s workshops were least likely to agree or strongly agree with the statement “I like science” (48%), followed by TU Wein and CU (54%) and UoA (57%). There is then a significant jump to ESI (75%) and AL (79%) who were most likely to already like science. The unexpected result here is for UoA, as those students went on to state that they were less to study science when they were older. This suggests that while these students like science they were not interested in studying it in the future.

For mathematics, the responses to the Likert statement ‘I like maths’ compare less favourably. Students attending workshops run by Cardiff University were least likely to (strongly) agree with the statement (43%) and then there is a significant jump from this to TU Wein (64%) and PRIA (72%), who were the least likely groups to say they would like to study maths when they are older. This suggests that while, on average, students in Austria like maths lessons those involved in the workshops were less likely to be interested in studying maths when they were older. Similarly, for students who participated in workshops at UoA (77%). AL (75%) and ESI (81%) were the partners with the highest percentage of students who liked maths.

Knowing that students in Austria and the UK, followed by Greece, were least likely to be interested in STEM subjects, it would be reasonable to assume that these are the groups most likely to be positively affected by the ER4STEM workshops. To explore this, we look at a subset of the post-workshop questionnaire questions in Table 3. For the purpose of this report and due to the sample sizes, we consider anything with over 5% change as note-worthy.

Table 3 Percentage of students per partner for yes/no statements "I like maths/science" in post-questionnaire. N reported in brackets.

Partner	I like maths		I like science	
	No	Yes	No	Yes
AL	13% (33)	69% (182)	10% (27)	69% (181)
CU	43% (88)	50% (101)	39% (79)	54% (109)
ESI	13% (45)	80% (278)	14% (48)	79% (276)
PRIA	11% (26)	74% (174)	18% (43)	65% (153)
TU Wein	34% (71)	61% (127)	22% (46)	72% (151)
UoA	17% (21)	81% (98)	22% (27)	75% (91)

Following the workshop we see an increase in the percentage of students who liked maths who attended the CU workshops (50%, up from 43%), while there is no notable difference for students at TU Wein workshops (61% down from 64%), PRIA (74% up from 72%), ESI (80%, down from 81%) and UoA (81% up from 77%). The only notable drop was at AL (69% from 75%). The increase for students at CU workshops may be because all of these workshops were closely linked to mathematics. It is also notable as this group were most likely to (strongly) disagree with the statement 'I like maths', in the pre-questionnaire.

For science, again AL has a drop (from 79% to 69%), CU shows no change at 54% for both, while there was no significant difference for ESI (from 75% to 79%). However, following the workshops at PRIA we see an increase in the percentage of students who liked science (65% up from 48%), similarly for TU Wein (72% up from 54%) and UoA (75% up from 57%). These significant positive changes are most likely associated with the fact that the majority of these workshops were focused on science topics or made direct reference to scientists.

To explore whether the activities encouraged interest in STEM careers, we analysed responses to the pre and post-questionnaires which asked students to write what career they wanted to pursue after school. Responses with frequency of one were not coded. Some responses included more than one career, for instance "Singer and Dancer". This was coded as **Singer** and **Dancer**. The profession with the highest frequency was **Engineer** with 157 references. **Sports** the second with 131 references and **Teacher** third with 119. Similarly, the profession with the highest frequency in the post-questionnaire was **Engineer** with 167 references. The results show that there is no significant increase in the number of female or male students who were interested in STEM careers after the workshops. This is true at both the project-level and partner level.

3.3.2.14.2 DO THE APPROACHES/ACTIVITIES APPEAL TO GIRLS?

Overall, from the post-workshop questionnaire, we see that the Year 3 workshops appealed to girls. They found the problems interesting, not too difficult and fun. They enjoyed working with robots, but not as much as the boys. Interestingly, they tended to enjoy teamwork more than the boys did.

It is worth noting that in the younger age group (6-10 years) there are over 100 more girls that participate in ER4STEM workshops than boys. A ratio of almost 7:5 in favour of girls. In the middle age range there is an insignificant difference of 19 more boys than girls. But in the eldest age group (14-18) there are considerably more boys than girls. 60 more boys, with a ratio of over 5:2 in favour of boys (see Table 4). This may be explained by the fact that, at this age, many female students have opted not to take STEM subjects. Workshops in Austria and Greece with this age group took place in schools which specialised in STEM subjects. For instance, the Insect Battle workshop analysed in

Appendix E took place in a vocational technical school in Athens and the eleven students that took part were all male. This emphasises the importance of engaging young people, but particularly girls, in educational robotics activities from an early age and ensuring that there are opportunities to continue to engage throughout their school experience to inspire and maintain interest in STEM subjects.

Table 4 Number of participants per gender, age group and partner in the pre-questionnaire.

Partner	(6,10]		(10,14]		(14,18]		Total
	M	F	M	F	M	F	
AL	24	130	39	50	0	0	243
CU	0	0	141	149	0	0	290
ESICEE	132	144	47	17	0	0	340
PRIA	58	48	50	57	43	7	263
TU Wien	61	66	11	9	30	22	199
UoA	12	10	42	29	22	6	121
Total	287	398	330	311	95	35	1456

While the robotics workshops were deliberately implemented during the school day and were designed to be fully inclusive of the students in the classroom (not an elite group as often occurs with out-of-school robotics clubs), ER4STEM robotics workshops have typically been implemented as one-off-activities over one or two days where the normal timetable is suspended. These workshops typically get the highest star ratings, possibly because they are not a part of the normal school day with tutors who are not their regular teachers. Therefore, they have a ‘wow’ factor which can be highly motivational. By comparison, the workshops run by Cardiff University gained the lowest overall average star rating (Table 5). It is difficult to draw any firm conclusions from this as there are a number of factors which mark these workshops out from many of those run by other partners. CU workshops involved the trailing of a new and developing technology (virtual robotics) and so there were technical issues throughout. These were also the only workshops that were fully integrated into the school day, taking place in 50-minute computing lessons twice a week for a whole school term. Of the 13 workshops reported by Cardiff University, only one was run over three weeks (1 lesson per week). While there were some technical difficulties, this workshop was done at a faster pace and there was an atmosphere of interest, curiosity and a positive reaction to a novel technology. This novelty or ‘wow’ factor may be the reason why the students who took part on the activities for three weeks were significantly more positive about the workshop than those who had sustained engagement. Stars are also a very subjective measure with some students answering the question about why they gave the workshop that rating, by explaining that they personally did not put much effort into the workshop and therefore demonstrating that they had misunderstood the question. All of this raises unanswered and unanswerable questions (in the context of this project) about the integration of robotics activities in a standard curriculum and standard school timetable. If the loss of the ‘wow’ factor is so notable, should robotics activities only be used as one-off events so as to capitalise on the motivational aspects of robotics.

Table 5 Workshop overview

Partner	Number of Participants	Number of workshops	Average number of participants	Average Stars Rating
TU Wien	232	11	21	4.39

ESICEE	396	15	26	4.88
PRIA	183	11	17	4.36
UoA	145	9	16	4.47
AL	269	13	21	4.57
CU	351	13	27	3.51

Overall, students report that they have enjoyed the robotics activities. The majority of students in Year 3 gave the workshops 4 or 5 stars (Table 5) and this is a similar trend to previous years. While there was little variation between genders, there was some variation between age groups, with older students more likely to give a lower rating to the workshop (Table 6). This trend is particularly well illustrated in the data from PRIA's workshops and is reflected in students' responses to the question of whether the problems that they had to solve were interesting (discussed below).

Table 6 Average number of stars by age group, as reported in Appendix P.

Partner	Age Group	Average Rating
AL	(6,10]	4.78
	(10,14]	4.14
CU	(10,14]	3.53
	(6,10]	4.87
	(10,14]	4.90
PRIA	(6,10]	4.78
	(10,14]	4.13
	(14,18]	3.95
TU Wien	(6,10]	4.73
	(10,14]	3.87
	(14,18]	3.94
UoA	(6,10]	4.70
	(10,14]	4.42
	(14,18]	4.42

There were no significant differences between genders in the ratings, as per the previous 2 years. However, there were again noticeable differences between age groups. Although all age groups were, on average, positive about the workshops, as shown in Table 6 **Error! Reference source not found.**, the younger ER4STEM age group of 6-10 tended to give a higher rating for the workshops.

Unexpectedly, when asked if they would like to do more activities like the workshop (yes/no question), 57% of students at CU workshops and 55% of students at UoA workshops said yes, higher than any other partners. Equally unexpected was that only 16% of students at ESI workshops answered yes to this question. Whilst the students at ESI rated the workshop higher than those at CU, they were significantly less likely to want to take part in a similar workshop. It is unclear the reason for this. It may be because the ESI workshops involved a series of discrete activities and involved learning specific things, whereas the students that participated in the CU workshops commented that they were free to create what they wanted and that it was up to them to find out things for themselves and so learnt about things that were relevant for what they wanted to do. While this resonated with Papert's idea that engaging in the construction of *personally meaningful* artefacts is particularly powerful for learning, it is also notable that students comment that they do not usually

get this type of opportunity in school. Overall, it is not possible within the scope of the evaluation to determine why there is such a difference but a number of factors can be explored.

Table 7 Post-Questionnaire: frequency per partner and gender of the Likert question: The problems we had to solve were interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Gender	1	2	3	4	5	Total
AL	Male	0	1	7	15	41	64
	Female	2	1	12	47	127	189
CU	Male	7	3	27	25	32	94
	Female	8	5	27	44	19	103
ESICEE	Male	1	0	2	29	154	186
	Female	1	1	4	12	139	157
PRIA	Male	5	1	14	40	74	134
	Female	1	1	4	18	64	88
TU Wien	Male	1	2	9	34	64	110
	Female	1	8	4	30	53	96
UoA	Male	1	3	12	19	37	72
	Female	1	2	5	12	28	48
Total		29	28	127	325	832	1341

To explore whether there was any significant variation with different components of the workshops, by comparison to the overall star rating, students were asked questions about the problems they had to try to solve, working with robots and working within a team. Overall, while activities were perceived to be challenging, they were also described as fun. This aligns with Papert’s notion of ‘hard fun’ which can be intellectually stimulating and intrinsically motivating, something which robotics activities appear to facilitate well. As reported in Appendix P, students agreed or strongly agreed that the problems they encountered were interesting. TU Wien and CU had the highest percentages of female students who (strongly) disagreed with the statement “the problems we had to solve were interesting” (9% and 13% respectively). Interestingly girls at CU workshops were more likely than boys to (strongly) agree with this statement (although they had a lower average) and this is a trend that is representative of the Year 3 data (Table 7). There is also a pattern of declining interest in the problems from youngest to eldest students. This is illustrated in the data from PRIA shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner and age group of the Likert question: The problems we had to solve were interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree

Partner	Age Group	Median	Average
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Partner	Age Group	Median	Average
AL	(6,10]	5	4.66
	(10,14]	5	4.34
CU	(10,14]	4	3.69
ESICEE	(6,10]	5	4.83
	(10,14]	5	4.77
PRIA	(6,10]	5	4.83
	(10,14]	5	4.38
	(14,18]	4	3.89
TU Wien	(6,10]	5	4.64
	(10,14]	4	3.75
	(14,18]	4	3.92
UoA	(6,10]	5	4.25
	(10,14]	5	4.33
	(14,18]	4	4.13

While it might appear from Table 9 that an older female student is less likely to find the problems interesting, the number of female students in the older age range is too small to draw any strong conclusions.

Table 9 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner, gender and age group of the Likert question: The problems we had to solve were interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	Male	(6,10]	3	4.00	5.0	4.41	5.0	5
	Female		2	5.00	5.0	4.70	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.00	5.0	4.50	5.0	5
	Female		1	4.00	4.0	4.24	5.0	5
CU	Male	(10,14]	1	3.00	4.0	3.80	5.0	5
	Female		1	3.00	4.0	3.59	4.0	5
ESICEE	Male	(6,10]	3	5.00	5.0	4.82	5.0	5

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
	Female		1	5.00	5.0	4.84	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	4	5.00	5.0	4.80	5.0	5
	Female		4	4.00	5.0	4.64	5.0	5
PRIA	Male	(6,10]	1	5.00	5.0	4.76	5.0	5
	Female		4	5.00	5.0	4.91	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	1	4.00	4.0	4.22	5.0	5
	Female		2	4.00	5.0	4.54	5.0	5
	Male	(14,18]	1	3.25	4.0	3.92	5.0	5
	Female		1	3.50	4.0	3.71	4.5	5
TU Wien	Male	(6,10]	3	4.50	5.0	4.71	5.0	5
	Female		2	4.00	5.0	4.58	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.00	4.0	4.11	5.0	5
	Female		2	2.00	4.0	3.29	4.0	5
	Male	(14,18]	1	3.50	4.0	4.00	5.0	5
	Female		1	4.00	4.0	3.90	5.0	5
UoA	Male	(6,10]	1	3.00	4.0	3.75	5.0	5
	Female		3	4.00	5.0	4.58	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.00	5.0	4.29	5.0	5
	Female		1	4.00	5.0	4.38	5.0	5
	Male	(14,18]	3	3.75	4.5	4.25	5.0	5
	Female		2	3.00	4.0	3.71	4.5	5

When asked whether the problems they had to solve were difficult, students tended to answer neither agree nor disagree. This suggests that there was an appropriate level of challenge. Students from UoA and CU were more likely to say the problems were difficult (37% or neutral (45% and 41% respectively). Interestingly, drilling into the data at age and gender, we see that younger children and girls were more likely to (strongly) disagree across partners. The exception to this is UoA 14-18 age group, who were the only group when split by gender to have a median of more than 3 (boys median = 4, girls median = 5 *note there were only 7 girls in this age group). The responses to whether the problems were fun, show a similar trend (though with slightly lower averages) to when students were asked if the problems were interesting.

The overwhelming majority of students found working with robots interesting. When asked if working with robots was interesting, girls in the middle and older age groups at TU Wien and the eldest age group at UoA had lower averages than the boys in the same age range (see Table 10). All other groups had a similar average between boys and girls, except for the youngest age group at UoA, where girls had a higher average than boys.

Table 10 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner, gender and age group of the Likert question: Working with robots was interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	Male	(6,10]	3	5.0	5	4.68	5.0	5
	Female	(6,10]	2	5.0	5	4.85	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.0	5	4.56	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	2	4.0	5	4.65	5.0	5
CU	Male	(10,14]	1	3.0	4	3.77	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	1	3.0	4	3.77	5.0	5
ESICEE	Male	(6,10]	3	5.0	5	4.86	5.0	5
	Female	(6,10]	1	5.0	5	4.87	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	4	5.0	5	4.87	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	4	5.0	5	4.79	5.0	5
PRIA	Male	(6,10]	3	5.0	5	4.84	5.0	5
	Female	(6,10]	3	5.0	5	4.87	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	3	4.0	5	4.59	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	3	4.0	5	4.64	5.0	5
	Male	(14,18]	3	4.0	5	4.66	5.0	5
	Female	(14,18]	4	4.5	5	4.71	5.0	5
TU Wien	Male	(6,10]	2	5.0	5	4.74	5.0	5
	Female	(6,10]	1	4.0	5	4.65	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.0	4	4.11	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	2	3.5	4	3.86	4.5	5
	Male	(14,18]	1	4.0	4	4.10	5.0	5

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
	Female	(14,18]	1	2.0	4	3.71	5.0	5
UoA	Male	(6,10]	1	5.0	5	4.50	5.0	5
	Female	(6,10]	4	5.0	5	4.83	5.0	5
	Male	(10,14]	2	4.0	5	4.49	5.0	5
	Female	(10,14]	1	4.0	5	4.41	5.0	5
	Male	(14,18]	3	4.0	4	4.38	5.0	5
	Female	(14,18]	4	4.0	4	4.14	4.0	5

Asked if working with robots was difficult, on average students' answers were in-line with their answers to whether the problems were difficult, tending around neither agree/disagree and mostly disagreeing. As the problems were linked with the robots (whether making and/or programming the robot) this result could be expected.

When it came to teamwork, girls were more likely to (strongly) agree that teamwork was interesting, across all partners, but particularly at AcrossLimits, Cardiff University and University of Athens (see Table 11). When split by age, at both AL and UoA the older age groups were less likely to agree that teamwork was interesting with averages going from 4.2 to 3.8 at AL and 4.4 to 3.7 at UoA (Cardiff University only worked with one age group in Year 3). When split by age and gender we notice the biggest gender splits occur amongst the younger age groups at AL and UoA (highlighted in Table 12).

Table 11 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner and gender of the Likert question: Working in a team was interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Gender	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	Male	1	3	4	3.72	5	5
	Female	1	4	5	4.22	5	5
CU	Male	1	3	3	3.38	5	5
	Female	1	3	4	3.69	5	5
ESICEE	Male	1	4	5	4.53	5	5
	Female	1	4	5	4.60	5	5
PRIA	Male	1	4	5	4.43	5	5
	Female	1	4	5	4.55	5	5
TU Wien	Male	1	3	4	4.08	5	5
	Female	1	4	5	4.26	5	5

Partner	Gender	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
UoA	Male	1	3	4	3.97	5	5
	Female	1	4	5	4.43	5	5

Table 12 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner, gender and age group of the Likert question: Working in a team was interesting. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	Male	(6,10]	1	3.00	4.0	3.78	5	5
AL	Female	(6,10]	1	4.00	5.0	4.30	5	5
AL	Male	(10,14]	1	3.00	4.0	3.56	5	5
AL	Female	(10,14]	2	3.00	4.0	3.98	5	5
CU	Male	(10,14]	1	3.00	3.5	3.40	5	5
CU	Female	(10,14]	1	3.00	4.0	3.69	5	5
ESICEE	Male	(6,10]	1	4.00	5.0	4.56	5	5
ESICEE	Female	(6,10]	1	5.00	5.0	4.61	5	5
ESICEE	Male	(10,14]	3	4.00	5.0	4.50	5	5
ESICEE	Female	(10,14]	3	4.00	4.5	4.43	5	5
PRIA	Male	(6,10]	1	5.00	5.0	4.47	5	5
PRIA	Female	(6,10]	1	4.00	5.0	4.37	5	5
PRIA	Male	(10,14]	2	4.00	5.0	4.41	5	5
PRIA	Female	(10,14]	3	5.00	5.0	4.72	5	5
PRIA	Male	(14,18]	2	4.00	5.0	4.42	5	5
PRIA	Female	(14,18]	3	4.00	4.0	4.29	5	5
TUWien	Male	(6,10]	1	3.00	5.0	4.09	5	5
TUWien	Female	(6,10]	1	4.00	5.0	4.29	5	5
TUWien	Male	(10,14]	1	4.00	4.0	3.67	4	5
TUWien	Female	(10,14]	2	3.00	4.0	3.86	5	5

Partner	Gender	Age Group	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
TUWien	Male	(14,18]	1	3.25	4.0	4.03	5	5
TUWien	Female	(14,18]	3	4.00	5.0	4.38	5	5
UoA	Male	(6,10]	1	3.00	5.0	4.00	5	5
UoA	Female	(6,10]	4	4.00	5.0	4.58	5	5
UoA	Male	(10,14]	1	4.00	4.0	4.08	5	5
UoA	Female	(10,14]	3	4.00	5.0	4.57	5	5
UoA	Male	(14,18]	1	3.00	4.0	3.75	5	5
UoA	Female	(14,18]	1	3.50	4.0	3.57	4	5

Across partners, students disagreed (on average) that working in a team was difficult. But interestingly girls were more likely to disagree with this statement than boys and this was the case across all age groups (see Appendix P). When asked if it was fun, students at CU were less positive but most students agreed or strongly agreed that teamwork was fun. Again, we see a gender split with girls more likely to agree that teamwork was fun (Table 13).

Table 13 Post-Questionnaire: Descriptive statistics per partner and gender of the Likert question: Working in a team was fun. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Gender	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	Male	1	3.00	4	4.00	5	5
AL	Female	1	4.00	5	4.33	5	5
CU	Male	1	2.00	3	3.36	5	5
CU	Female	1	3.00	4	3.66	5	5
ESICEE	Male	1	4.00	5	4.52	5	5
ESICEE	Female	1	5.00	5	4.72	5	5
PRIA	Male	2	4.00	5	4.57	5	5
PRIA	Female	1	4.00	5	4.51	5	5
TUWien	Male	1	3.75	5	4.06	5	5
TUWien	Female	1	4.00	5	4.35	5	5
UoA	Male	1	4.00	4	4.21	5	5
UoA	Female	1	4.00	5	4.33	5	5

Students' previous experiences and attitudes are also likely to influence the post-questionnaire results. One example to illustrate this comes from the pre-questionnaire Likert statement 'I like using computers' (Table 14). Interestingly the average for CU is noticeably lower than other partners and reflects the same pattern as seen in the answers to the above questions, particularly students' interest in robotics, the problems encountered and the overall workshop rating. As the CU workshops all took place during computing lessons, it raises a question as to whether these student's interest in the subject was the reason for the workshop rating and had the workshop occurred outside of the normal timetable and been taught by someone who was not the lead ICT/Computing teaching, whether they would have gained a different workshop rating.

Table 14 Descriptive statistics per partner of answers to the statement 'I like using computers'. One means strongly disagree and five strongly agree.

Partner	Min	1 Q	Median	Average	3 Q	Max
AL	1	4	5	4.56	5	5
CU	1	3	4	3.98	5	5
ESICEE	1	4	5	4.60	5	5
PRIA	1	4	5	4.36	5	5
TUWien	1	4	5	4.28	5	5
UoA	1	4	5	4.44	5	5

3.3.2.14.3 DO GIRLS ENGAGE WITH CHALLENGES OR LET BOYS 'TAKE OVER'?

Although we saw a case where the girl in a pair initially let the boy in the pair take over (section 3.3.2.4 and Appendix F), this was a rare event across the workshop case studies. What was more common was boys taking control, rather than for the girls letting them take the lead. For instance, in the ESI workshop analysed in Appendix L and referred to in section 3.3.2.3, the theme of 'Power and Control' emerged from the data, where the boys maintained a sense of power and control over their team's activities through objects and physical movements.

The tutor running the session stated in her observational notes that the boys appeared to take more of a lead on the activities, but were conscientious of including the girls:

"The girls were participating less than the boys, I feel, but the boys were very generous in terms of rotating and giving turns. What I observed as a pattern with them was that the boys were doing the new tasks, sort of 'researching' them first, and when they managed to do the tasks, they were giving turn to the girls, telling them what to do and all. The girls were very confused, when for the last task, I told them to reverse turns and to begin with the tasks first. They didn't really know what to do, so they asked the boys for validation of their ideas."

This observation implies that because the tutor intervened in the leadership the boys were taking quite late on in the workshop, this power dynamic had been ingrained to some extent into the working relationship of the group, meaning the girls were somewhat "confused" as to how they should lead a task. Evidence of this potential presumed authority of the boys over the girls was

observed in Child 3's behaviour – at one point she is seen approaching the keyboard, ready to contribute, but then realises that Child 1 (m) is approaching the keyboard at the same time and suddenly steps back.

It should be noted that the group made no specific mention of gender in their interview or in their questionnaires. In fact, Child 3 (f) stated in her post-workshop questionnaire that she had enjoyed working in a team, and this opinion was also shared by other group members in their interview:

“Interviewer: OK, I have a last question. If we have a workshop again next year, would you work together?”

C2: Yes, why not.

C3: Yes.

C1: Yes, definitely. According to me they are pleasant schoolmates, I can't say anything bad about anyone of them. They are just wonderful people and... Everybody listens to the others and nobody underestimates the others and their ideas and that's why working with them is very pleasant.”

However, the notion that allowing boys to take the lead may be ingrained as the same group, who participated in a workshop the previous year, noted the role gender played in their team in this excerpt from their interview in Year 2:

“C2: Yes, but it was just hard to take turns, everybody steps in whenever they feel like it and at the end we get mad and start shouting at each other.

C4: That happens most often with the boys.

C2: (indistinguishable), it's not just our fault.

...

C3: Well, I really liked us working together, it was unexpected that us of all people (stressed “us”, as them as a group of people couldn't usually get along) could do it.

...

C3: I learned that they work harder than we do. When we were programming they argued who would sit in front of the computer at first and we (C3&C4) just watched.

Interviewer: And next time if you're working together again, will you let them program a little bit more? [To C1 & C2]

C1 & C2: Yes.”

In this interview extract, the girls claim that the boys both behaved differently in the team to them and took a more active role in the tasks. This is also observable in the previous year's video footage, with the boys engaging more than the girls did. The boys agree that in the future they will ensure they share the ability to participate in the workshop with the girls, however according to the tutor observation from the second workshop, this did not necessarily happen. Whilst the tutor observed that the boys would lead the activities more overall, analysis of the video data has revealed that the

girls, in particular Child 4 (f), would use other methods of control to gain power within the group. In particular, this involved taking objects from one of the boys and physical positioning (e.g. Figure 24), as reported in Appendix L.

Figure 24. Child 4 takes ownership of instruction sheet but doesn't use it

What we see in this example and others, is that while boys do take over, it is often not because the girls have let them. Across workshops we see examples of girls taking and/or taking-back control. It may be that these instances are linked to limited resources or meaningful roles.

It is also notable in the CU workshops that occurred in the virtual world, where resources are effectively unlimited, that in some pairs there was an imbalance in the amount or type of work done by each member of the pair (see Appendix O), however there was no clear gender dimension and students' explanations were equally associated with letting the other person do what they wanted as they were with the a view that the other person knew more than they did.

3.3.2.14.4 DID THEY PARTICIPATE IN COLLABORATIVE WORK?

As shown above, although there were limitations in the collaborations, all students participated in teamwork in all workshops. Girls particularly enjoyed working as part of a team and it would appear that this was a particularly valuable aspect of the experience for them.

3.3.3 Conclusions

The evaluation of Year 3 of the ER4STEM project shows that the recommendations from Year 1 and Year 2 have been applied with successful outcomes. ER4STEM workshops include multiple entry points into creative STEM through workshops which children find interesting and enjoyable. Workshops which target a specific domain are more likely to result in an increase in students' interest in that subject area. Although there is a significant increase in positive attitude towards STEM subjects, participants did not report any significant change in career towards or away from STEM careers. It is likely that as many of the students who participated in Year 3 are in the older age

categories and therefore have already made considerable choices about their careers, they are unlikely to change their career aspirations following a short intervention.

Differentiation by outcome and mixed ability teams fit with the ethos of ER4STEM. Girls appear to particularly enjoy the teamwork element of workshops and rarely simply 'let boys take over'. Where boys do assert a level of control over the activities, the girls find ways to try to take back control. However, this points to an implicit assumption on the part of boys that they know what to do (and possibly that the girls do not). It also points to a tendency for boys to act and girls to stop and think before acting. Thus, boys are 'seen' to take over. It raises questions about the rhetoric around girls' engagement in STEM, which suggests that they are not interested or that they lose interest – suggesting that there is some deficit in girls. Girls were equally likely to participate in workshops as boys and were equally likely to enjoy the activities. Very few of the activities were gendered, designed to particularly appeal to girls. Instead they were aimed at all learners.

Various sections of this evaluation have emphasised the importance of the teacher/tutor monitoring and facilitating the development of effective collaborations. It is perhaps effective collaboration and teamwork which need to be addressed for both girls and boys to have the opportunity to equally participate in workshops. However, to facilitate this requires a teacher with the necessary experience and knowledge. This highlights the importance of teacher professional development not just in the design of workshops (and this is, of course, a central component in the success of any workshop) but also in ways of facilitating effective teamwork.

It is clear that problem solving activities in a classroom environment, particularly when students are working on problems they have identified themselves, requires responsive teaching of just-in-time knowledge and skills. This requires a lot of energy, knowledge and expertise on the part of the teacher and balancing this with the use of whole-class teaching is an important consideration. Again, this is an area for professional development and will require substantial time and effort for effective outcomes to be achieved.

Finally, tensions between national and international assessment regimes which focus on what the individual can do and the needs of industry which focus on team-based outcomes need to be addressed if the outcomes of ER4STEM are to be sustained. While the individual within the team needs to demonstrate that they can effectively contribute to the work of the team (in terms of both knowledge and skills), there is little/no assessment of this in most forms of summative assessment undertaken by school students in Europe.

4 INDUSTRY EVALUATION

This section provides an industry evaluation of the ER4STEM project across the three years. It gives an overview of the surveys and studies with focus on skills which are required by industry, summarises the results and provides a resulting set of the required industry skills. The evaluation focuses on how these skills were implemented within ER4STEM.

4.1 INDUSTRY SURVEYS AND STUDIES

This section presents resumes of a few articles and surveys. At the end, some issues about the gathered materials are mentioned and conclusions are provided.

Griffin, Gaw and Care (2012) prepared an analysis of the skills needed for the 21st century regardless of the field. They divided the skills into four categories as follows:

- Ways of Thinking
- Creativity and innovation
- Critical thinking, problem solving and decision making
- Learning to learn and metacognition
- Ways of Working
- Communication
- Collaboration (teamwork)
- Tools for Working
- Information literacy
- ICT literacy
- Living in the World
- Citizenship – local and global
- Life and career
- Personal and social responsibility – including cultural awareness and competence

Although those skills are not focused on a particular field, they are generally relevant for industry.

Another study focused on the gaps between industry expectations and the abilities of graduates (Radermacher and Gursimran, 2013) in which knowledge deficiency was defined as “any skill ability, or knowledge of concept which a recently graduated student lacks based on the expectations of industry or academia.” The authors then performed a survey among industry managers and discovered the most common knowledge deficiencies among graduates:

- Written communication
- Oral communication
- Project management
- Software tools
- Testing
- Teamwork
- Problem solving and critical thinking
- Programming

The authors hope that “by raising awareness of these areas, it is possible for educators to become aware of areas where students most frequently fail to meet expectations and to make curriculum changes or other adjustments to address these problems.”

The Institution of Engineering and Technology focused on skills demand in industry and skill gaps among recruits across the UK in 2015. They focused on trends in recruiting and mainly the industry expectations and the skill gaps. Results are shown in the graphs below (Figure 25 and Figure 26). Across all candidates the main perceived skill gaps were thought to be business acumen, practical experience, leadership and management skills.

Figure 25 Skill gaps of graduates and postgraduates identified in The Institution of Engineering and Technology (2015) report

Skills gaps in recruits – school leavers/apprentices

Figure 26 Skill gaps at school leavers/apprentices identified in The Institution of Engineering and Technology (2015) report

The graphs and the survey might be summarised as follows:

- More than half of employers claim that a typical new recruit does not meet their reasonable expectation.
- Common expectations primarily focused on the prevalence of soft and work ready skills as opposed to technical requirements.
- There is a common feeling that there is a disconnect between university courses and industry demands, leaving significant gaps in graduate capability.

The objectives of Harun et al.'s (2017) study was to evaluate employers views placed on the importance of employability skills and attributes that engineering and technology graduates should possess. The results showed that employers require people who can easily work with their colleagues, but are also able to work independently, people who are highly dedicated and committed to perform their jobs and understand the importance of quality of work.

The results are as follows in the order of importance:

- Teamwork
- Dedication And Commitment
- Quality Of Work
- Professional Ethics
- Ability To Work Under Pressure
- Able To Work Independently
- Analytical Skills / Critical Thinking
- Problem Solving Skills
- Oral Communication Skills
- Adaptability
- Innovative And Creative Thinking
- Technical Competencies
- Management Skills
- Computer Skills
- Written Communication Skills
- Interpersonal Skills
- Quantitative Skills

Finally, Prinsley and Baranyai (2015) dealt with the same topic as the previous one and aimed to understand:

- The skills and attributes that employers need from STEM graduates today and into the future
- Whether employers are able to recruit workers with the STEM skills they require and if not why not.
- The extent to which employers are engaged and satisfied with education providers to train work-ready STEM students to meet their requirements.

For our purposes, mainly the results of the first aim are important. The results shows roughly the same as the other studies, that the technical skills are not the most important. Here, the most required skills by the employers are active learning, critical thinking, problem solving and interpersonal skills.

Figure 27 The skills that employers need from STEM graduates (Prinsley & Baranyai, 2015)

4.1.1 Issues

The accumulated materials provide some ideas as what skills to look for in the ER4STEM activities. However, there are some issues to be taken into account. Some of the surveys were outdated or focused only on a fraction of region of interest (EU vs UK). Other issue is that some surveys used different terminology or aggregated skills whereas others did not. Moreover, some articles were only focused on a specific part of industry (e.g. computer science).

And another issue is that the results are quite different and the list of mentioned skills is very wide. This suggests that choosing the necessary skill sets is indeed domain-specific and subjective to some extent. Anyway, the results shows that even in STEM the most important skills are soft skills.

4.1.2 Industry skill set

The materials introduced in the previous section in combination with experience in computer science industry led to the skill set led to the identification of the industry skillsets for consideration in ER4STEM (Figure 28). The skills were divided into three categories (red, yellow, green), the red one is considered the most important and hence is evaluated in the following sections. The yellow one is less important and the green one is the least important.

Figure 28 Industry skillset for consideration in ER4STEM by level of importance (red = most important)

As was mentioned before, choosing the right skill set is highly individual and subjective. Another issue that makes finding the skill set more difficult is the fact that employer does not generally look for a homogenous army of equally equipped workers. He rather builds a team with clearly defined roles, seeking workers that will fill the gaps serving as proverbial building blocks. For example, a team needs a leader and a worker with creative thinking, who would produce an ample supply of new and innovative ideas. However, this does not mean that every employee should possess leadership and creativity.

4.2 ER4STEM GOALS AND VALUES

From the beginning, ER4STEM project aimed to turn curious young children into young adults passionate about science and technology with a hands-on use case: robotics.

The domain of robotics was chosen because it represents a multidisciplinary and highly innovative field encompassing physics, maths, informatics and even industrial design as well as social sciences.

ER4STEM project's activities mainly consisted of workshops and conferences, which we focus on in the evaluation. The important part was that the project's target group was all young learners and all the activities had to address all learners, not just female or male.

4.2.1 Year 1

During the first year, initial activities, like programming and robotics workshops and a conference were held. Then in the evaluation, throughout the data there was clear evidence that students constructed a robot or for example programmed the robot using the visual language Scratch, but it was unclear what they learned from this process and what they learnt beyond this.

Due to this fact, it was clear that each activity needed to be better specified and it had to be obvious what should students learn from the activity, what were the goals, what skills were targeted and how they were reached.

4.2.2 Changes in year 2 and year 3

Based on the experience from year 1 and research on required industry skills, the ER4STEM project partners agreed on using 21st century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills. As the

result, ten ER4STEM values were identified, which covered some of the 21st century soft skills, i.e. teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity and critical thinking.

By making this an explicit recommendation from the 1st year of the ER4STEM project, an explicit promotion of these skills and an emphasis on them were added to all the activities in year 2.

Those directions were further developed in year 3. In year 3 the educational robotics workshops curriculum was mostly connected again to teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity, critical thinking and moreover to evidence of learning.

4.2.3 Targeted skills

Within the framework, a general understanding of 21st century skills and what they stand for was crucial. To be able to correctly focus on chosen skills, implement the correct activities in workshops and conferences and finally, correctly evaluate the results, definition and meaning of the chosen skills was required.

In addition to the chosen 21st century skills, i.e. teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity and critical thinking, we also add definition of problem solving, as it is in our industry skill set.

Definitions taken from D1.3 and D1.4 are provided in the following sections.

4.2.3.1 TEAMWORK (COLLABORATION)

Students must be able to work effectively and respectfully with others. More specifically to:

- contribute constructively to project teams
- be helpful and make necessary compromises to accomplish a common goal
- assume shared responsibility and value the individual contributions when working in a team
- use collaborative technologies to connect and work with others globally.

4.2.3.2 COMMUNICATION

Students must be able to communicate with others effectively. This includes the ability to:

- articulate thoughts and ideas effectively using oral, written or nonverbal communication skills
- communicate complex ideas clearly and effectively
- publish or present content that customizes the message and medium for their intended audience
- utilize multiple media and technologies in order to communicate and know how to judge their effectiveness
- communicate effectively in diverse environments

4.2.3.3 CRITICAL THINKING

Critical thinking is the ability to think clearly and rationally about what to do or what to believe. It includes the ability to engage in reflective and independent thinking. More specifically, students need to be able to:

- use various types of reasoning depending on the situation
- analyse and evaluate major alternative points of views
- synthesize and make connections between information and arguments
- interpret information and draw conclusions based on the best analysis
- reflect critically on learning experiences and processes

4.2.3.4 CREATIVITY

By creativity skill we mean the ability to think creatively, which includes:

- constructing and generating new and useful ideas
- using a variety of techniques to create these ideas
- coming up with innovative, unique or imaginative solutions to problems
- implementing the creative ideas in tangible artefacts

4.2.3.5 PROBLEM SOLVING

Problem solving requires two distinct types of mental skill, analytical and creative. This includes ability:

- to solve different kind of problems in both conventional and innovative ways
- to devise effective solutions to real-world problems
- to identify and ask significant questions that clarify various points of views and lead to better solutions

4.3 EVALUATION

In the evaluation we mainly focus on how teaching and developing the required skills was implemented in ER4STEM workshops and how successful it was. Additionally, we examine if the workshops addressed all children, boys and girls, whether they liked the activities and if the workshops encouraged their interest in STEM education and future careers. In the following sections, we describe how teaching the chosen soft skills was implemented and what are the results.

4.3.1 Workshops and Conferences

Most ER4STEM activities were workshops, where the students were creating robots, programming them etc. It was clear from the evaluations that students loved the fact that they got to work with “real” robots (and computers) and the moment where they got to try out the practical implementation of their code and when the robots actually started to move was one of the most exciting moments for both the students and the implementation teams. The students enjoyed the workshops, they liked working with friends and learning about robots, science and maths.

This is actually the most important outcome of the project, that the activities were interesting for children and that they enjoyed them. Regardless of whatever results, children will remember the fun and the experience and it can influence their future interest in STEM education and future career.

Not only a good curriculum, but also teachers deserve credit for this success. Even students themselves referred to the positive presence of them. Without good teachers, well prepared curriculum is useless, even though there is for example explicitly written that the children should work in groups and should discuss the process. A teacher usually needs to be active and lead the children to discussion and communication.

Another great result is that the participants in the workshops were well balanced in terms of gender and with a few exceptions, there were no significant deviations between the shares of female and male students. This is really important, because gender equality and diverse teams at workplace are a huge topics at the industry companies these days.

On the other side, there were also some problems. The first expected problem was language. For those, who have native language other than English, it was sometimes difficult to properly understand written materials. The problem usually appeared at young children. Anyway, English is the most common language at industry companies around the world no matter the country where they are located, so we don't consider the English materials as a problem. Conversely, we consider the English materials a good practice to train children in English.

The other issue was, that when children were asked what they learned, they usually answered they learned programming, constructing robots etc. Only a few children answered they also learned soft skills even though there was a focus on them. From the previous evaluations, it is obvious that most children learned them, but they were not aware of it or they didn't consider the soft skills worth mentioning. It would be good to explicitly explain them that these skills are important too and it is good to learn and practice them.

Every year the ECER conference was also held. It consisted of tournaments, workshops, talks by researchers and students, awards ceremony, etc. This diversity in activities nicely addressed both beginners without any previous knowledge in robotics and also experienced children who are already interested in STEM. This is also important, because we need to address these both groups of children.

4.3.2 Teamwork and communication

Teaching children teamwork and communication is quite straightforward. Here are examples, what was implemented in ER4STEM activities:

- Split up into groups
- Take different roles within groups with its own area of responsibility
- Exchange roles in a group
- Talk about the task
- Solve practical problems as a team
- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips
- Communicate with other teammates
- Take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision
- Formulate and express ideas

The instructions are simple and were easily implemented at most of the workshops, but at the same time they were good examples of required teacher's activity. Here is really important to explain children how to work and talk with others.

Typical example of workshop, where these activities were used, was creating and programming a robot. While working in teams, students built a robot following generic guidelines. They had to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct a body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. At the end of the workshop, they got a questionnaire and as a team, they needed to think about what they had done that day and agreed their answers to the questions.

4.3.2.1 YEAR 1

In all workshops, students worked in teams, usually consisted of 3-4 members. In the most cases they had a good collaboration in their team, though there were some incidents that they faced some collaboration problems. Some group showed that the boys did not meaningfully collaborate with the girls, but within the pair of girls and pair of boys there was collaboration. In other workshop there were groups, where students were not listened to, feeling that they did most of the work. Here was really important teacher's activity, even for a dysfunctional team at the beginning of the one day workshop, after the teachers' involvement and subsequent work children had a positive impression of group work. Unfortunately, in other workshop, while the problems appeared to be resolved on day one with teacher intervention, on day two was evidence of it occurring again, with the girls either being excluded or excluding themselves from the activity. Another issue was, when the teacher advised children "Work as a team". This instruction was not definitely correct as children usually didn't understand what it means.

Anyway, from the interviews and open questions of post questionnaires, it is clear that most students found the collaboration very useful to their work and mentioned it as an important factor to their successful completion of the activity and moreover, all students reported that they believed that they were good at working in a team. As expected, while most students had stated that they liked working in teams and learned best with other people, the students had mixed-gender views about the difficulty of working in team. Some students also reported that they worked on their own and felt that others did not listen to them. On the other side, they also reported they were encouraged by their team and helped to programme the robot. This raised important questions about these children's concepts of teamwork.

From the perspective of learning about teamwork, it is clear from responses to the questionnaire that some students recognised they learned the importance of skills such as sharing. However it is unclear from the objective whether students were expected to 'do' team work or learn about it.

Because a teamwork and communication were key features of ER4STEM activities and the results wasn't completely satisfying, further development of different approaches for the orchestration of teamwork was included in the recommendations from year 1.

4.3.2.2 YEAR 2

According to the recommendations from year 1, new approaches for the orchestration of teamwork was added and tested. One example is that children worked in stable groups as usual but they also tried to work in non-stable groups, which changed from day to day. As expected, working in stable

pairs appeared to be the most successful and the least successful was the non-stable pairs. In two cases there were students who started working on their own to create their avatars then had to form pairs working at one computer, sharing an avatar, due to technical problems. There was no sense of a team or team identity and more frequently some children chose to exclude themselves from the activity by sitting back and, at most, simply observed the other.

Across case studies both cooperation and collaboration within groups came along to complete a goal, as well as turn taking. This was again dependent on the orchestration of teamwork by the teacher and the specific activities but there were multiple cases where teams worked this out for themselves. In various contexts students shared ideas, asked questions and provided help and encouragement between teams.

It was obvious the number of students per group and the number of roles was also important. When students worked in pairs sharing a tablet to write the code and have a worksheet to complete, student often share these roles and turn-take. However, teams of three rather than two tend to have more difficulties with at least one student disengaged as they had no specific task to get involved in. This also allowed a student who was initially less interested not exclude themselves and blame the activity.

Another example of effective role distribution were workshops where the students were encouraged by the teacher to rotate roles as they start each new task. This ensured that each student, particularly in larger groups, had an opportunity to engage in all aspects of the workshop and with this rotation was increased collaboration within the teams.

While there were many positive examples of collaboration within teams, there were also cases across case studies where students were excluded from activities by others as in year 1. This was seen across mixed and single gender teams. While in mixed-gender teams the exclusion of others appeared to be gender based, there was no consistency within or between countries – girls excluded boys and boys excluded girls.

Unlike exclusion, isolation or disengaging, disagreement within teams was a positive aspect of collaboration. Disagreements also demonstrated the complexity of the activities that the students engaged in during educational robotics activities, where there were often more than one correct or appropriate decisions to make about the development of the robot to complete a given task. Students engaged in higher order thinking and expression of that thinking through argumentation, critical discussion, analysis and synthesis of problems and solutions, testing 'known' facts, the construction of knowledge and the application of new knowledge to the construction of their robots and code.

It is obvious, that many ways of learning teamwork were already successfully implemented in year 2. However, because of some mentioned problem, there were still some recommendations on how to improve activities in year 3:

- Activity plans should include specific tasks to explicitly introduce and engage students to/with relevant aspects of teamwork (e.g. involving everyone in the completion of a task, how to effectively communicate ideas).
- Where teams are expected to distribute roles amongst the team, it is important that all children get the opportunity to take each role, that roles are specific, required and not repeated. More than one child may take a role (e.g. programmer) at any time.

- Where students are seen to be excluded from activities, students need to be reminded about how to work in a team and be supported to develop collaborative/cooperative working practices. Where a student has also disengaged it is also important to reignite the spark of interest in robotics. This will take time and is more practical in workshops with multiple teachers.
- Students who are excluded need to be provided with opportunities to demonstrate to their team or the wider class their ability and potential to contribute to the team. This may be more effective than the teacher telling the team to work together.

4.3.2.3 YEAR 3

According to the recommendations from year 2, another activities of learning and practicing teamwork was added and tested.

One of the workshops involved an innovative approach to collaboration at the end of the workshop in the form of a game. Previously, students had been working in groups of 3-4 participants, but during this final game individuals from each team took it in turns to play collaboratively alongside members from the other teams, whilst the other participants watched and supported. Analysis of data from the workshop demonstrated that it was effective in teaching the students the importance of working in a team.

Whilst during another whole workshop, the students worked collaboratively together in teams to learn about and explore with the robot, by designing the final game to include each team to work together in one giant team, a form of meta-collaboration takes place. The students work both within their team and also within the whole class. During the interview, the participants explained that the final game had taught them a lot about the importance of teamwork and collaborating with others.

In year 3, there were less problems in teamwork, especially in mixed-gender teams. Girls appeared to particularly enjoy the teamwork element of workshops and rarely simply 'let boys take over'. Where boys do assert a level of control over the activities, the girls find ways to try to take back control. It pointed to a tendency for boys to act and girls to stop and think before acting. Girls were equally likely to participate in workshops as boys and were equally likely to enjoy the activities.

This progress was mainly due to the fact, that teacher successfully followed the recommendations from year 2 and actively got involved.

Many approaches how to learn and practice teamwork were successfully implemented and tested in workshop, but still there were a lot of workshops, where the content and teacher's work and attitude should be improved.

While objectives in activity plans often stated the importance of children learning to share ideas, about communicating and other relevant aspects of teamwork, from the case studies selected there was little evidence of specific activities to introduce students to these skills.

Overall, enough activities to support learning and practicing teamwork and communication were implemented. But also various sections of this evaluation had emphasised the importance of the teacher monitoring and facilitating the development of effective collaborations. However, to facilitate this requires a teacher with the necessary experience and knowledge. This highlights the importance

of teacher professional development not just in the design of workshops but also in ways of facilitating effective teamwork.

4.3.3 Creativity

Unlike teaching teamwork, teaching creativity and creativity thinking is quite complicated. A typical approach is more about giving a space to children than literally teaching them. These activities were typically implemented in ER4STEM workshops:

- Experimentation
- Space to ask questions
- Discuss ideas
- Construct and generate innovative ideas

But again, these activities are more up to teachers than up to well written curriculum.

4.3.3.1 YEAR 1

In year 1, creativity was spotted mostly during the constructing part, which also was the part that students referred to as the more creative or challenging. Additionally it is clear from the interviews that the students were able to think of different applications of robots.

The workshops were typically for beginners, where the main goals were to teach basics (e.g. of programming) and thus there were limited opportunities for students to develop and express their creativity.

However creativity was targeted skill so there was a recommendation from year 1 to continue to develop multiple ways for students to incorporate a creative element within robotics workshops.

4.3.3.2 YEAR 2

Across the workshop cases studies from year 2, students engaged in various forms of creative expression, from thinking of different ways robots could be used in everyday life, to providing different craft materials for the construction of a robot.

In some workshops, students also found for themselves ways to add a creative art element to their robotic creations or customised their pre-built robots. Younger students also named their robots and spoke to them.

Another example of creativity was a creation of avatars in the virtual world. Students worked on a shared computer and created a shared avatar. They agreed on a name for their avatar and customise its appearance.

In other workshops the creative element was introduced through storytelling. Here the robot was programmed to tell a story or a story was written to match the actions of the robot. This appeared to be a popular approach with young children and required them to engage in complex abstract and creative thinking. It also had the potential to develop their argumentation skills.

Although there were these creative elements, it should be noted that many activity plans still relied on closed activities which provided limited opportunity for both creativity and critical thinking around possible solutions.

Thus again, the recommendation from year 2 was to continue to develop multiple ways for students to incorporate a creative element within robotics workshops.

4.3.3.3 YEAR 3

Across the workshops implemented in year 3, new creative elements were introduced to the robotics workshops. These included for example students writing stories about their robot's adventures or designing a prototype robot using craft materials.

Overall after some the changes in year 2 and year 3, children had enough opportunities to develop and express their creativity in ER4STEM workshops.

4.3.4 Critical thinking

Critical thinking involves a range of skills. To learn and develop these skills, following activities were implemented across the workshops:

- Analyse and evaluate information
- Identify problems
- Decision-making
- Discuss possible solutions
- Make assumptions
- Choose the best solution

4.3.4.1 YEAR 1

In workshops students were observing and discussing as part of the concrete process, which makes educational robotics well suited to developing critical thinking.

Reflection is a key part of critical thinking and provides us with one route to understand the abstract parts of critical thinking, specifically decision making. But not only does it allow us insight into the mind of the learner, it also allows the learner to engage in critical thinking through critical reflection, stepping-back and considering why they took the actions that they did. Although reflection is a key component of developing 21st Century skills, it is typically not taught in schools. So it is perhaps unsurprising that while there were tools within the pre-kit to encourage reflection, the evidence showed that the reflections were typically at a surface level.

From year 1 the recommendation was to highlight the importance of teaching and developing critical thinking through reflection by including prompts within the objectives, social orchestration, student productions, sequence of activities and evaluation, provide examples of critical thinking activities using reflective tools and integrate reflection in student productions.

4.3.4.2 YEAR 2

The activity plans from year 2 demonstrated a range of ways to engage students in critical thinking activities. Across the case studies students shared and discussed ideas, they often moved from a 'guess and test' approach to predicting what will happen, identified problems in their constructions and codes, and made informed decisions about next steps.

Another example of students engaging in critical thinking about problem solving was in workshops, where students had to develop multiple solutions to a problem, or where the parameters of the problem were changed.

In year 2, there was an evidence of the critical thinking in activities, but still there was an opportunity to improve them. So again, a recommendation from year 2 was introduced, to develop ways to introduce students to 'ways to think' when they encounter problems.

4.3.4.3 YEAR 3

Despite of the recommendation from year 2, many of the activity plans tended not to include a specific section on 'ways to think' when encountering problems. However teacher were responsive to students who encountered difficulties and introduced them to new ways of thinking.

Although there were not so much activities directly focused on critical thinking, thanks to the teachers, students had opportunities to develop their critical thinking. Anyway, more specific activities to develop critical thinking would be good to add to workshops.

4.3.5 Problem solving

Even though the problem solving wasn't chosen as a 21st century skill and thus there wasn't focus on it in workshops, problem solving was naturally part of the workshops and multiple activities developing problem solving were found:

- Identifying and solving problems
- Examine the options
- Decision-making
- Test possible solutions
- Choose the best solution

In general, children correctly understood the tasks they got and were able to identify and solve the problems, examine possible solution, find the best one and successfully implement it.

Although problem solving was an issue for some children before the workshop, by the end most children who responded agreed that they would like to try solve more challenges, additionally when asked what they had learned about themselves from the workshop, some students mentioned that they had realised they were good at solving problems.

However the data provides no insight into the problem of solving process or whether students learned anything about problem solving.

Overall the workshops provided multiple activities, where children developed problem solving even though problem solving was not one of the targeted 21st century skills.

4.3.6 Summary

From the industry point of view, the most important thing is that children liked the workshops and enjoyed it, no matter the results from interviews or post-questionnaires, children will remember the experience and there is a probability it will encourage their future interest in STEM education and/or career.

However, from the interviews or post-questionnaires it seems that the ER4STEM activities did encourage interest in STEM education, although understandably it depends on the focus of the workshop. Whether they also encourage interest in STEM careers, it is unclear.

The other success is that the participants in the workshops were well balanced in terms of gender, because the diversity of working teams is a big topic in industry these days.

Finally, there is a clear evidence that ER4STEM activities helped to develop targeted soft skills. With the focus on 21st Century skills recommended in year 1 of the project, students had more explicit opportunities to learn and develop those soft skills across workshops in year 2 and year 3. Only one issue emerged and that is how ER4STEM activities expand among more children in future and how to address children, who are not interested in STEM at all right now, to be able to fill the huge amount of vacancies at companies in STEM fields in future. However, this was beyond the scope of the ER4STEM project.

5 WHOLE PROJECT EVALUATION

The final objective of the evaluation is to provide a systematic evidence base for the evaluation of the entire ER4STEM concept. The evidence base comes from a cross-case analysis of the case studies from years 1-3 (D6.3, D6.4, section 3 of this deliverable and related appendixes), undertaken to identify how the objectives of ER4STEM have been met, exploring the case studies and reflecting on the development of ER4STEM over the three years. This is supplemented by the comparative analysis of questionnaire data across the three years of the project (Appendix P & Q) and deliverables from WP1, WP2, WP3 WP4 and WP5. Due to the range of research contexts but also the scale of the ER4STEM project, this approach allows us to make generalised claims whilst remaining sensitive to the specific local contexts in which the workshops and conferences were undertaken.

The following evaluation of the ER4STEM project is structured in relation to the project objectives and derived research questions, which are presented in Section 5.1 as a reminder. As the results of each year's evaluation are already available, the findings are not repeated here but referred to as relevant.

Overall, this evaluation demonstrates how ER4STEM activities have developed and matured through the lifetime of the project. It shows how the objectives of ER4STEM have been met and concludes by identifying areas for future research and development which emerged from the research but are out of the project scope.

5.1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the objectives of ER4STEM, the baseline research questions identified in D6.1 provided the basis for the design of the evaluation pre-kit and the finalised evaluation kit (D6.2) which was implemented in years 2 and 3 of the project. These are outlined here and supplemented by the measures of success, etc, which were recorded throughout the project in various deliverables particularly from WP2 and WP4. This provides the structure for the evaluation of the ER4STEM concept which follows.

Objective 1: ER4STEM will approach and engage children by offering multiple entry points into creative STEM (STEAM) via robotics.

Research questions:

- Are there multiple entry points facilitated through ER4STEM?
- Do the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests?
- Do children share their ideas with/through these tangible artefacts?
- Do they learn basic scientific concepts?

Additionally:

- What complementary approaches were used in ER4STEM?
- Was existing content adapted?
- Were all four areas of STEM, plus A for Arts, addressed?

Objective 2: ER4STEM will offer educational methods for educational robotics to engage all young learners

- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM education?

- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM careers?
- Do the approaches/activities appeal to girls?
- Do girls engage with challenges or let boys ‘take over’?
- Are girls interested in the STEM topics?
- Are popular gender stereotypes held? Are they changed?
- Did they participate in collaborative work?

Additionally:

- How did ER4STEM encourage young people to consider STEM subjects and careers?
- Were the approaches used in a large amount of workshops in schools across 5 European countries?
- Was equal access to STEM education and careers fostered?
- What innovative approaches to collaborative work were trialled in workshops and conferences?

Objective 3: ER4STEM will study real-world societal problems as perceived by each child and relate societal challenges to existing technologies and required innovations

- Did children identify and define problems that influence their lives?
- Were they equipped with the necessary skills to solve these?
- Do they have an opportunity to present their ideas and artefacts to each other as ‘proper’ scientists?
- Do they develop ‘soft-skills’?
- Do they learn intrarelational (how well they know themselves) and interpersonal skills?

Additionally:

- How were conferences designed to allow young people to present their ideas and artefacts to each other as proper scientists?
- How have perspectives of STEM fields been disseminated?

Objective 4: ER4STEM sets out to create a continuous STEM schedule by leveraging on already existing European approaches of innovative science education methods and measures based on robotics within one open operational and conceptual framework

- Comparison of 10 current EU strategies to encourage STEM education against the needs of STEM professionals in industry.
- Evaluation of the repository

Objective 5: To evaluate the success of ER4STEM, we proposed the following measures:

- Number of children who participated in conferences and workshops
- Number of presenters at conferences and number of public announcements about the conferences
- Participants’ satisfaction with the conferences and workshops
- Number of children in the different age groups that reported increased interest in STEM, number of girls reported increased interest in STEM.
- Number of children pursuing STEM in tertiary education when applicable
- Number of models built, number of requirements created, number of technologies matched, number of innovations achieved.

- Number of additional countries, municipalities, educational organisations involved/engaged/participated in conferences and workshops, this measuring the further outreach of ER4STEM
- Number of peer reviewed articles related to the project published in scientific magazines or at scientific conferences
- Number of educators and researchers that reported increased interest in using the methods developed in the project
- Number of entries in each category of the repository

5.2 OBJECTIVE 1: ER4STEM WILL APPROACH AND ENGAGE CHILDREN BY OFFERING MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS INTO CREATIVE STEM (STEAM) VIA ROBOTICS.

Within this objective, concepts from Constructionist pedagogic theory (such as the design, creation and programming of tangible and personally meaningful artefacts as a powerful way to engage young learners) were implemented in a wide range of robotics activities, to provide multiple entry points into STE(A)M. The idea of ‘multiple entry points’ emphasises that there is not a one-size-fits-all model for the design of robotics activities that engage learners with STEM topics. The emphasis within ER4STEM is that robotics activities must capture the imagination of young people and while activities such as robotics competitions can achieve this, not all people are interested in being competitive. For this reason, ER4STEM workshops and conferences identified complementary approaches.

For instance, the ECER conference has various components through which individuals within teams can engage with robotics in a way which is of interest and has meaning to them. While the main focus of the event is the BotBall competition, before and during the event students work on various non-competitive elements, including:

- technical documents recording their work;
- research;
- writing and presenting papers.

Reviewing the ECER conference presentations across the three years of ER4STEM (appendix C), we see a number of technical and non-technical papers which students present to each other and adults. These non-competitive elements engage learners with STEM concepts and robotics through alternative routes. So a child who has less interest in coding (for instance) can make a valuable contribution to the team and have an opportunity to be inspired by and learn from others.

However, while these activities are designed to be non-competitive, they are scored and the score contributes to the overall team score. So there remains a competitive element, with field notes in year 3 showing that students tailored their presentations to the scoring system. This is not necessarily a negative point. In fact, by scoring these so-called non-competitive activities, it gives value to them from the perspective of the wider team and therefore value to the team member(s) involved in those activities.

Other than the ECER conference, a competitive element is unusual in ER4STEM workshops, as noted in Year 2 (D6.4). That year, for the first time in Greece, three workshops included a competition. In all three workshops the winner was the team whose robot completed the task faster than the others.

This was observed to foster collaboration within teams, was highly motivational and led to high levels of engagement, including teams extending activities beyond the minimal requirements to complete the task.

While competition or a sense of competition can have many potential benefits, we see in the Greek data the potential for competitions to be a negative experience for some, potentially discouraging students from participating in robotics activities and thus removing the potential of robotics to ignite and change attitudes to STEM for these students. We see that the competitive element in this case prevented between-group collaboration and support, and encouraged rivalry and hostility between teams.

In Greece, we observe that students who were older (14-16) and had previous experience of robotics found competitive elements highly positive. However younger students, specifically those in primary school who had no previous experience of robotics had a much less positive experience. Specifically, those whose first experience of robotics was a competition which they lost, had a negative attitude towards robotics and STEM in a follow-up activity, even though it contained no competition. A key factor in this may have been the decision of the teacher in this workshop to announce not only who had won but also who had lost, resulting in public shaming.

From these results, it was recommended that workshop should provide non-competitive opportunities for learners to engage with robotics before introducing competitive ones. The ECER conference also addresses this issue by having a range of awards and general attitude of celebrating all forms of success by teams across the various competition elements and reframing ongoing failure to succeed, as determination and resilience.

As well as having complementary approaches such as competitions with research and presentations, or by including a competitive element within wider workshops; the ER4STEM workshops identified and implemented a variety of complementary approaches to foster creative STEM engagement. For example:

- ESI - Educational Robotics and Creativity workshop
 - This includes mind-mapping activities to provide a route for students to think more broadly about robotics, exploring and sharing their ideas about how robots are and could be used in everyday life.
- PRIA – Beebot Elementary School workshop
 - This workshop includes story telling activities over several phases: introduction, sketch and building and programming the robot.
- UoA – Robot Olympics
 - Using the history of the Olympic Games and the description of three ancient sports as the entry point to robotics activities.
- CU – Building Our Virtual World
 - Having already been introduced to SLurtle robots, students design and create their own part of the virtual world using SLurtles and other tools that are available to them in-world.

The majority of these more creative entry points were developed in Years 2 and 3 of the ER4STEM project. They were either new workshops or workshops that had already proven to be successful in Year 1 which were adapted to introduce alternative and creative ways to engage with robotics and STEM concepts. With the activity plans from all partners integrated together in the ER4STEM

curriculum (D2.4), we find that across ER4STEM there are multiple entry points to engage children at various ages and from different backgrounds with each element of STEM, plus A for Arts.

Across the ER4STEM curriculum and conference, we see various opportunities for students to connect robots to their personal interests. From the presentations given at the ECER conference (Appendix C), to children at ESI workshops identifying how robots could help them in their everyday lives. In the UoA workshop 'Insect Battle', students worked as a team with each member of the team coming from a specialist area and therefore able to work on an area of personal interest to them. At PRIA, the 'Save the World' and 'Robotic-Theatre' allowed students to adjust the task to their personal interests. For example, the robot shown in Figure 29 was constructed by two boys interested in soccer and the movie Monsters Inc. Over the course of the workshop they adapted their robot to score a goal and decorated it with drawings of characters from the movie.

Figure 29 Soccer Monster from Year 2 Beebot workshop

An important part of Constructionist theory is the construction of sharable artefacts, in order to explore, test and extend understanding through these artefacts and with others. Across the yearly evaluations we see both formal and informal opportunities for students to share their ideas through the robots and other artefacts that they create during the workshops and conferences. ECER is designed to provide formal opportunities for sharing through conference presentations in particular. But the environment, particularly the 'Pit Area' where all teams work on their robots and the shared testing areas, and the Alliance round, provide less structured opportunities to share ideas and to use robots to explore, test and extend understanding with a more knowledgeable other. For instance, observations from ECER in Year 1 noted older and more experienced students offering to help younger and inexperienced teams when they encountered a problem. Through the robot the older students would demonstrate what could be achieved, or would talk to the younger students and help them to identify the problem that they were encountering. In this way, the robot and activity facilitated communication between teams and opportunities to learn from each other.

Some workshops also included formal opportunities for students to present what they had created (e.g. PRIA Beebot workshop where students present their story expressed through the robot). However, there were also informal opportunities, similar to those offered in ECER, afforded by the design of the learning environment. For example, in the UoA Year 2 workshop described in D6.4 Appendix C, it was observed that from the beginning of the workshop students from different teams were communicating with each other and asking for ideas or help. For example, a girl from group 5 gets up and goes to another team to ask about something probably related to the circuit. This type of interaction was happening mostly between teams that were sitting next to each other and especially between group 5 and group 2. However, we can see that as the activity progressed the teams were becoming less willing to help and to share their work with others. For instance, at the end of session 1 a boy from group 4 goes to group 2 and says “that’s nice! Can I see how you did it” and they answer “No! It’s a secret”. Finally, after a lot of negotiation the boy sees their robot and examines how it is constructed. At the end of the whole workshop this group (group 2) blamed other groups for “stealing their work and ideas”. This highlights the importance of classroom orchestration and the parameters set by the tutor/teacher for the sharing of ideas.

At workshops run by CU, students were explicitly told that they could visit the spaces of others and were actively encouraged to do this by the class teacher. As described in Appendix O (this document), they engaged in a novel form of collaboration which meant that they were not collaborating with the people that they were sat next to. Each pair had a 40x40 meter space on a shared class island, providing them with a discrete space to work in but also allowing them to see and access the spaces of others. As a result, students were observed to look at the screens of others they were sat next to and to explore within the virtual world what other groups had created. So sharing occurred in both the physical and virtual world.

The final question raised in this objective is whether students learned basic scientific concepts during the workshops. The evaluation addressed this in two ways. The first was by asking students what they thought they had learned in the post-questionnaire and interviews, the second was to analyse the artefacts created by students including the robots, solutions to problems, worksheets, code, etc. The former proved to be less effective, with students’ answers to open questions being vague when asked what they learned “coding”, “robots” for example. For example, 356 answers to the question “*What have you learned about yourself?*” were coded as “*About Robots*” in the first and second year. Examples of answers are “*build robots*”, “*I learned about robots*” and “*to make a robot*”. Similarly, vague answers are found in the other two open questions. For example, 254 answers were coded as “*Positive experience working in a team*” and answers include “*better together*”, “*that is wonderful*”, “*was cool*” and “*that united we are stronger*”

Following the first year, recommendations for year 2 emphasised the importance of having specific learning objectives within activity plans so as to assess whether students had learned the intended concepts, as well as identifying ways of capturing evidence of learning. While there were some developments in Year 2, there were still areas for improvement identified, in particular ways of collecting evidence of learning and two workshops which focus on this in year 3 are analysed in Appendixes L and N. Appendix L described the use of worksheets to capture evidence of learning – if the student/team is able to complete the worksheet successfully the assumption is that they have learned something. In Appendix N an online book is created by students in which they have to demonstrate how they have achieved each of the learning objectives identified by the teacher. The case studies describe in more detail the success and limitation of these approaches, but overall we do find evidence for students learning various concepts across the ER4STEM workshops.

5.2.1 Conclusion

Based on the evidence collected through the evaluation discussed above, we can answer the questions stated in 5.1 for objective 1 as follows:

Research questions:

- Are there multiple entry points facilitated through ER4STEM?
 - Yes. In both workshops and conferences there are multiple ways for children to engage. These are represented in the ER4STEM curriculum map and advocated in the ER4STEM framework.
- Do the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interests?
 - Yes. While this is not possible in all workshop activities, across the curriculum we find numerous opportunities for students to connect robots to their personal interests.
- Do children share their ideas with/through these tangible artefacts?
 - Yes. Children share but this needs to be facilitated and supported by the teacher and the learning environment.
- Do they learn basic scientific concepts?
 - Broadly, yes. There are issues with evidencing that children have learnt something (discussed elsewhere) and activity plans need to provide specific, concrete and most importantly measurable objectives to be able to determine whether children have learnt what was intended. Most workshops were presented as an opportunity to learn about robotics rather than specific concepts with a few exceptions (e.g. AL – Engaging with robots in a fun way; ESI - Mathbot) and so it is perhaps unsurprising that the evidence for this was less clear.

Additionally:

- What complementary approaches were used in ER4STEM?
 - Competitions and presentations
 - Programming and story telling
 - Programming and art/design
 - Engineering and humanities
- Was existing content adapted?
 - Workshops implemented in Year 1 (largely workshops already run by project partners) were adapted according to the recommendations from the Year 1 evaluation, to introduce more creative opportunities to engage in robotics through multiple entry points, and to identify and trial ways to evidence learning (among other recommendations).
- Were all four areas of STEM, plus A for Arts, addressed?
 - Yes. The activity plans encompass these five areas and are clearly illustrated in the ER4STEM curriculum map.

Overall we can state with confidence that ER4STEM has met the first objective, to engage children by offering multiple entry points into creative STEM via robotics.

5.3 OBJECTIVE 2: ER4STEM WILL OFFER EDUCATIONAL METHODS FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS TO ENGAGE ALL YOUNG LEARNERS

5.3.1 Engaging all young learners

The ambition of ER4STEM to engage all young learners was achieved in a number of different ways and links to the first objective's ambition to engage children from very different backgrounds. One way to evaluate this is to look at the types of schools that participated in ER4STEM activities. While children participating in ECER were self-selecting and therefore already inclined towards STEM subjects and careers, the majority of students participating in ER4STEM workshops took part because their class was participating. Data collection did not include each individual child's socio-economic background, cultural background or additional learning need as this was not essential for the research and difficult to compare across countries. Therefore, school-level data acted as a proxy for this information.

The workshops themselves included children who had already chosen to pursue STEM subjects and careers, as well as those who had chosen not to. They included all children in every class that participated and so included children with high and low socio-economic backgrounds, living in rural and urban areas, and with various additional learning needs, including: registered deaf and blind students, children with physical disabilities requiring a wheelchair, children on the autistic spectrum, children with dyslexia and dyspraxia, children with behavioural needs and children for whom the local language was not their native/first language. In this way, ER4STEM engaged all young learners.

In Austria, four schools participated in workshops with TUW and 17 with PRIA over the three years of the project. While the language of instruction in these schools was usually German, both partners worked with one school where a second language was also used: French or English. In the school where English was used, this was the primary medium of instruction. In many schools English was the mandatory second language. The schools worked with children between the ages of 4 and 18. The schools were typically public schools (two private schools – one each partner), mixed gender and non-religious. They included technical high-schools, which students have chosen to attend due to their specialism and therefore we might presume these students already have an interest in STEM subjects. There was also one specialist music high school and three schools were grammar schools (one of which was in a rural area). Three of the schools were based in low socio-economic areas in a city. Six schools were in rural areas. One of the German-medium only schools had deaf children in class and approximately 48% non-native speakers of German.

In Bulgaria, five schools participated in workshops with ESI, one of which was a small (60 pupil) private school for the ages 5-19 where both Bulgarian and English were used as the medium of instruction. All other schools catered for children between the ages of 5 and 19 and had over 1000 students on roll. They were all urban, non-religious and mixed gender schools.

In Greece, seven schools participated in workshops with UoA. All the schools were mixed-gender, public schools and non-religious. One vocational high school was in a low socio-economic area and two were in rural areas (one primary and one high school).

In Malta, 13 schools participated in workshops with AL. In all but two schools both English and Maltese were the language of instruction. The two schools in which only English was spoken were both private, international schools. In total there were three private schools, all mixed-gender, all rural and the third school was religious (Roman Catholic). The other 10 schools included five single gender schools (1 male, 4 female only), all of which were church schools (Roman Catholic), two of which were in rural areas. The remaining 5 schools were all church schools (Roman Catholic), with two in rural areas. Church schools are run by religious or lay people who strongly maintain the ethos

of the church within the school. In the two international schools, there is no religion due to the wide range of religious beliefs of the students.

Finally, in the UK, four schools participated in workshops with CU. In all schools the medium of instruction was English but as all of these schools are in Wales, some students attending the schools may speak Welsh at home. All the schools were public schools, mixed gender and included 2 primaries and 2 secondary schools. One of the secondary schools was a Roman Catholic school. Based on the UK measure of poverty – entitlement to free school meals (eFSM) – all four schools were above the Welsh national average for the number of children who had free school meals (FSM). Therefore, all UK participants came from low socio-economic areas (FSM range: 30.7% - 65.6%). The church school (which participated the most in ER4STEM workshops) had a higher than national and local average for the number of children with English as an additional language (11.7%) and 30.2% were from an ethnic minority. Across the four schools there was a high percentage of children with recognised special educational needs; ranging from 34.1% to 65.7% of pupils in the school.

Additionally, CU and TUW worked with a school in Ireland and Italy, respectively. The school in Ireland was a new, public, mixed-gender secondary school with only one year group (2 classes) and non-denominational (which is rare in Ireland). There were children from a range of backgrounds and with a range of additional learning needs. The medium of instruction was English, the first language of the students attending the school. In Italy, the school was mixed-gender, non-religious and public.

Overall, ER4STEM workshops received an average of 4.49 stars out of a possible 5 in all three years. When asked why they were given this rating, the most common responses referred to a positive experience during the workshop. There were 1259 answers coded as *“Positive”* and the sub-code *“it was fun”* assigned 600 times in the first two years. Some examples are *“It was fun and teachers were helpful”*, *“slurtles was fun”*, *“it was a great idea”* and *“it was interesting”*. In addition, 112 answers mentioned that tutors/teachers were good. Those who did not enjoy the workshops often referred to their own disinterest in the subject, e.g. *“the workshop was alright but I’m not interested in computer science”*, or *“I don’t like maths”*. Moreover, the code with the highest number of answers that embraces negative aspects of the workshop is *“Activity”*, with 208 references in the first two years. This code includes sub-codes as the *“it was boring”* (e.g. *“It wasn’t so interesting and it was boring because I can do it”*), *“it was too long”* (e.g. *“it lasts a little bit too long”*).

When looking at the star rating by gender (Figure 30), we see that there were no significant differences between boys and girls across the three years. This would be comparable to the evidence from the qualitative data analysed in the case studies which showed that both girls and boys actively engaged in all of the workshops and conferences. So we can say that the activities appealed equally to boys and girls. Although there were periods of disengagement, isolation or exclusion of girls, this was also observed of boys and does not appear to have a gendered dimension in relation to the activities. Instead it appears to be more closely linked to the social dynamics within the groups. In the Year 1 and Year 2 evaluations (D6.3 and D6.4) we noted that the dominant gender (in terms of number) was more likely to exclude the other gender, regardless of whether the majority were male or female. We also saw instances of children choosing to isolate themselves from the rest of their team. It is interesting to note from the Year 3 evaluation earlier in this document, that girls typically expressed more enjoyment of working in teams than boys.

Figure 30 Boxplot of number of stars per year and gender. The points are consider as outliers.

All students who participated in ER4STEM activities participated in collaborative work. Typically students were placed in mixed-gender teams of 2 or 4 students. Multiple forms of collaboration were used across the workshops and three innovative approaches were trialled. The first, the jigsaw method, is not uncommon in education but we could not find evidence for it being used in educational robotics activities in the literature. This approach was implemented by TUW in Year 2 workshops. As discussed in the Year 2 evaluation (D6.4), it is very difficult to exclude or isolate individuals within teams if every member of the group is necessary for the competition of the task, as per the jigsaw approach to teamwork.

The second was distributed-collaboration, described in Appendix O. This approach was implemented within the SLurtle virtual world workshop Creating our Virtual World run by CU. In these workshops, students worked in pairs in their group's area of the class island in the virtual world, however they were not sat with each other. This meant that students were challenged to communicate and collaborate within the virtual world within their team but were able to communicate and share ideas and knowledge with those they sat next to in the classroom environment.

The third was to purposely create teams with students who had different specialist knowledge. This was possible with older students who had specialised their studies at vocational or technical high schools and one example of this is described in the Insect Battle workshop by UoA (Appendix E). Here the collaboration was dependent on each student sharing and applying their specialist knowledge to solve a group task, which could not be solved without each area of specialism. In the Insects Battle workshop described in Appendix E, the teams also included a first grade student who had not yet specialised. We see that the non-specialists were mentored by the older, more experienced students, but in one case they chose to disengage entirely from the workshop.

5.3.2 Attitudes to STEM subjects and careers

During workshops, tutors also took time to talk to children (individually, in teams and the whole class) about the collaboration, explaining why it was important and what to do if things went wrong. Tutors became role models for students. In some cases their own roles within a team were explained to the students, in others the fact that they were a scientist or worked in a STEM career was explained. It was noted in observations at the CU workshops that female students in particular asked the lead researcher to confirm that she had in fact created the virtual world (which they had been told by their male teacher), asking how long it took and exclaiming that she “must be very clever”.

Interviews and reflections also provided an opportunity for students to express their views and have these views challenged either by tutors or peers. One example is an interview from a workshop, conducted during the third project implementation year, which in our opinion made students reflect about the role of women in science. The following excerpt is taken from a focus group interview, conducted after the end of the PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm workshop, using the Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills workshop with new and recurring ER4STEM participants in Sofia, Bulgaria:

- Interviewer:** Ok, this is a honest answer. And how do you imagine a woman scientist looks like?
- C2:** Similarly.
- Interviewer:** Does she make the same or different experiments?
- C2:** Not so brave.
- Interviewer:** Not so brave?
- C2:** No, I mean... not so confident in the activity she does.
- Interviewer:** And why do you think this is?
- C2:** I don't know.
- Interviewer:** Why don't you know?
- C2:** I haven't heard about women scientists.

This interaction provided the interviewer with an opportunity to explore with the students in this group their assumptions of female scientists.

Gendered stereotypes in relation to scientists were clear. From the Draw-A-Scientist task, even when placing the female form of the word first, both boys and girls tended to draw a male scientist (see Appendix R and Year 1 evaluation D6.3). While younger children tended to draw a stereotypical male ‘mad scientist’, this was less common with older students. However, most partners reported that they had some interactions with female students commenting when there was a female tutor that it had in some way made a positive difference to their assumptions.

In terms of maintaining and increasing interest in STEM subjects and careers, we began by looking at the reasons why young people lose interest in STEM subjects. This is discussed in detail in Appendix 7 of D1.4 and a summary is provided here. The main reasons identified from a review of the literature on the loss of interest in STEM subjects were:

- Packed curricula
- Attitudes of peers towards a subject
- Perception of STEM subjects as difficult
- Instructionist pedagogy
- Emphasis on theory over practical experience (in curriculum and teaching)

Kudenko and Gras-Velazquez (2016) examined students’ responses to the question “I find school lessons in science and technology interesting” from over 7500 students in Europe. They found that those in Northern Europe were considerably less likely to find these lessons interesting than those in Southern Europe and in both geographic areas, girls were less likely to find them interesting than boys, although the divide is much bigger in Northern Europe (Figure 31). Overall, our own findings have supported this general trend. As noted in the Year 2 and Year 3 evaluations, children from Bulgaria, Greece and Malta tended to have the most positive attitudes towards STEM subjects and careers, whilst students from the UK and Austria were least interested in these subjects. In keeping with this trend, Kudenko and Gras-Velazquez (ibid) found that just 29% of the North European girls could imagine a career in STEM compared to 51% of the boys. Interestingly, the OECD suggests that there is also an East-West divide, with students in Austria more likely to be interested in STEM subjects and careers than those in the UK.

Figure 31 Pupils interest in science and technology by gender (Kudenko & Gras-Velazquez, 2016)

ER4STEM addresses the issues identified by emphasising practical experience over theoretical knowledge in both the curriculum but also the pedagogic approach. Using Constructionism as the underpinning pedagogical approach places the emphasis on children not only doing but also making for themselves, sharing their developing knowledge and understanding with others through tangible

artefacts which provide a locus for communication about various ideas and a route for teachers to introduce theoretical concepts. The luxury of a European project as opposed to a Government policy group is the ability to have a flexible, open and generic curriculum. The ER4STEM curriculum focuses on opportunities rather than learning specific content and allows teachers and students to focus on new areas depending on the interests of the learners rather than the demands of the curriculum. By providing multiple entry points, ER4STEM provides learners with multiple opportunities and ways to engage with robotics. Whilst they might find one aspect difficult, the creative (sometimes perceived as easier) opportunities provide motivation to engage with more complex tasks and ideas so as to achieve the desired outcome. While students may still perceive a subject to be difficult, they can also perceive it's value when it allows them to achieve something which is personally meaningful, and we see examples of this from individuals throughout the data collected.

Overall we can see that in each year of the project, workshops had a positive impact on children's attitudes towards STEM subjects. The impact of the workshops was calculated using an index that takes into account questions in the pre and post-questionnaires. This index is calculated from the difference between the post-questionnaire index and pre-questionnaire index. This is done in order to counter balance existing participants' bias and have a clear view on the participants who had a positive change. For example, someone who is already interested in STEM would have a high pre-questionnaire index and most probably also a post-questionnaire index because he/she would appreciate working on a STEM related activity. On the other hand, someone who is not interested would have a low pre-questionnaire index and a low post-questionnaire index. In both cases, the index would be close to 0, which would indicate that there was not any change in the motivation on STEM. However, positive indexes would show that there was a positive influence.

The pre-questionnaire index ($STEMF_{pre}$) covers participants' attitudes towards STEM and the post-questionnaire index ($STEMF_{post}$) tries to capture participants' change of interest towards STEM. Each index is calculated as follows:

$$STEMF_X = \frac{1}{|W|} \sum_{i=1}^{|W|} \left(\frac{1}{|n_i|} \sum_{j=1}^{|l_i|} \left(\frac{1}{|n_j|} \sum_{k=1}^{m_X} f(Question_{(l,j)}) \right) \right) \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where:

X = represents pre or post.

$|W|$ = is the number of workshops.

$|n_i|$ = number of participants who answered at least one question.

$|l_i|$ = number of participants in workshop i .

$|n_j|$ = number of questions answered by participant j .

m_X = questions used to calculate the index.

$$f(Question_{(l,j)}) \begin{cases} \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is likert} \rightarrow Value(Question_{(l,j)}) \\ \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is likert and inverted} \rightarrow 6 - Value(Question_{(l,j)}) \\ \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is yes or no} \begin{cases} \text{if yes} \rightarrow 5 \\ \text{if no} \rightarrow 1 \\ \text{else} \rightarrow NA \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

It is important to highlight that $STEMF_{post}$ questions in the first two years were only Yes/NA answers, while in the third year it was Yes/No/NA answers. This difference will make the third year indexes lower because a negative answer is converted to one. In addition, participants between 7 and 10 years old in the second year did not answer any of these questions.

Figure 32 depicts the difference between pre and post workshop, resulting in a boxplot of participants' index (amount of change between pre and post, where a positive number equals a positive change in attitude) per year and gender. As can be observed, across all three years there was a positive impact of the workshops on STEM attitudes. The difference between genders per year does not look big. However, a t-test per year reveals that there is a significant difference between genders in the first ($t(816.81)=2.75, p=0.006$) and third year ($t(1205.9)=-0.22, p=0.002$). This suggests that in the first there was a greater impact on girls than boys and in the third the other way around. While there is a higher number of participants with negative indexes in year three, this is due to the change in the format of the questionnaire. Nevertheless, half of the participants in the third year had a positive index higher than 0.2. This 0.2 is a number selected to consider certain error in the data and the answers. These results suggest that after the workshops more than half of the participants had a more positive attitude towards STEM. Remembering that many students already had a positive attitude, this is a notable result.

Figure 32 Boxplot of participants' index in STEM per year. The black points are indexes that are considered as outliers, while the grey points represent participants' index.

Figure 33 presents the indexes of participants per year divided by partner, which could be significant, in consideration that each partner implemented different activities and used different technologies. It is important to highlight that during the first year UoA used a Likert scale format for all the questions used to calculate the index, while the rest of the partners used yes/NA format. Despite this error, more than half of UoA's participants had a score higher than 0.2.

The change in the format of the questions in the post-questionnaire from yes/NA to yes/no/NA had as a result a reduction of the indexes in all partners, especially in TU Wien, which in previous years had the highest indexes. In addition, all partners had similar indexes in year 3, while in previous years there were big differences between their indexes.

Figure 33 Boxplot of participants' index in STEM per year and partner. The black points are indexes that are considered as outliers, while the grey points represent participants' index. CU in the first year of the project did not implement any workshop because they were developing their virtual world. The gap between UoA and the rest of the partners is because they use a Likert scale for the questions used to calculate the index while the other partners were using yes/NA questions.

There is a difference on careers preferences between males and females. Across the three years of the project, male students are more likely than female students to be interested in STEM careers before participating in the workshops. There is enough statistical evidence to support that the difference is significant in year one ($\chi^2(1,756) = 83.6, p = 0$) and two ($\chi^2(1,1388) = 60, p = 0$). The age group 14-18 has the highest percentage of participants interested in STEM careers, which is unexpected as there is usually a drop-off in students' interest in STEM careers as they get older. However, this most likely reflects the types of schools which ER4STEM engaged with for this age group: Technical high-schools. This highlights the difficulty of engaging children of this age within school, if the workshop is not directly relevant to the curriculum. This is likely due to the combination of requirement of many educational systems to specialise (in terms of subjects studied) around this age, and of course high-stakes assessment.

Across all three years of the project there is no statistically significant increase in the number of young people who changed their reported future career ambition from non-STEM to STEM subjects. Other research has shown that there can be an affect and so we need to consider other factors that might be relevant but not currently clear. One might be the length of the workshops and the time

post-workshop that the post-questionnaires were completed. Most partners delivered one or two-day workshops at the end of which the post-questionnaire was completed. This is insufficient time for an activity to have a meaningful impact on participants and so longer-term engagement with workshops and longitudinal data collection should be considered in the future.

5.3.3 Conclusion

Based on the evidence collected through the evaluation and the summary discussion above, we can answer the questions stated in 5.1 for objective 2 as follows:

Research questions:

- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM education?
 - Yes, particularly if the workshop targets a specific domain.
- Do the activities encourage interest in STEM careers?
 - There is interest in STEM the activities do not have a statistically significant impact.
- Do the approaches/activities appeal to girls?
 - Yes. There appears to be a fairly equal distribution of enjoyment of the activities between boys and girls. Girls tended to particularly enjoy teamwork.
- Do girls engage with challenges or let boys 'take over'?
 - Girls engage with the challenges. At times we see boys taking over, but not necessarily because the girls have 'let' them and as a result there can be a 'power struggle' at some point in the workshop. Equally we see instances of girls taking over and at some point the boys trying to regain control. Where there is no power struggle, the excluded child/children disengage and require some form of teacher/tutor intervention to support their re-engagement.
- Are girls interested in the STEM topics?
 - Yes. Overall from the questionnaires we can see that girls are interested in the workshops. However the specific STEM subject may remain uninteresting to them. For example, at CU workshops some students enjoyed the workshop but stated that they did not like the subject taught.
- Are popular gender stereotypes held? Are they changed?
 - Common gender stereotypes are held by students. Although it was not the aim of this project to uncover what these were in detail, we find evidence for widely held assumptions that scientists are male. Through interactions with female project team members we find some limited evidence that these stereotypes are changed. We also find girls expressing their sense of achievement and pride in being able to do something by the end of the workshop that they had not imagined they could do. Whether this latter point is linked to gender stereotypes or their own sense of self-efficacy (which may or may not be linked to gender) is unknown.
- Did they participate in collaborative work?
 - Yes. All students participated in collaborative activities.

Additionally:

- How did ER4STEM encourage young people to consider STEM subjects and careers?
 - Many robotics activities which students participate in are out of school, meaning that they are not accessible to all students. While some may have a natural interest in robotics and STEM and may therefore seek these opportunities, those whose parents do not have the socio-cultural capital or who grow up in a low socio-economic area may not have the opportunity to participate in such activities. Other

students who do have these opportunities may not realise that robotics or STEM careers could be of interest to them and may therefore not take part. Equally, some may be very interested but feel that familiar and peer pressure stops them from engaging.

- The vast majority of ER4STEM activities took place in schools and whole classes took part, not only those students who were already interested. As a result ALL young learners had an opportunity to engage with and be inspired by robotics activities. Learning about robots provides a different and stimulating way for students to engage with otherwise dry/boring concepts (e.g. angles) and to engage with topics that they would not otherwise have encountered in school.
- By introducing robotics to ALL young people and engaging with them about STEM subjects and careers opens the door for those who had not previously considered these subjects or careers before. The biggest potential impact is on the younger students who have not yet been required by the education system to specialise. Having female tutors also gave girls a role-model.
- Were the approaches used in a large amount of workshops in schools across 5 European countries?
 - In total 188 workshops were implemented in 5 European countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Malta and The UK. An additional two workshops were implemented in Ireland and Italy.
- Was equal access to STEM education and careers fostered?
 - Yes. As described above, positive female role models, along with mixed gender teams and workshops will all young people in a class supported notions that anyone could engage with STEM subjects and pursue a STEM career.
- What innovative approaches to collaborative work were trialled in workshops and conferences?
 - As described above, three innovative approaches to collaboration were trialled in the workshops: Jigsaw (new to robotics workshops), distributed-collaboration (in a virtual world) and purposely designed teams. Additionally, in the conference, the Alliance round (described in detail in Appendix B) is a competition round which requires students from two competing teams to work together.

Overall, we can state that ER4STEM has offered methods to engage all young learners.

5.4 OBJECTIVE 3: ER4STEM WILL STUDY REAL-WORLD SOCIETAL PROBLEMS AS PERCEIVED BY EACH CHILD AND RELATE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES TO EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES AND REQUIRED INNOVATIONS

To empower children to define problems that influence their lives and provide them with the necessary skills to solve these is on the surface a simple idea, but a complex one to implement. ER4STEM addresses this ambition in a number of ways. 1) The curriculum provides multiple pathways for students to engage with various activities, building up their domain knowledge and personal skills to enable them to study real-world problems and develop innovations. 2) In workshops teachers provide real-world societal problems as a stimulus and the ECER conference theme was linked to real-world societal problems. 3) The ECER conference provides a bespoke opportunity for students to conduct research and identify real-world societal problems as can be seen in the ECER presentations listed in Appendix C. Students then present their ideas to each other at ECER and two/three are selected to also be presented at the neighbouring Robotics in Education conference for academics. In

this way they are presenting their ideas and artefacts as ‘proper’ scientists. 4) Individual workshops introduce students to ways of working including teamwork, presenting their ideas and final solutions, design thinking (see Appendixes H and I), complex problem solving, and a range of other soft-skills.

In various workshops students had an opportunity to identify or define problems that influenced their lives. For example, the ESI workshop *Educational Robotics and Creativity*. In this workshop, students were asked to generate ideas about use of robots and to present them as Mind Maps. Students usually generate ideas related to their interests, for instance robots in their dream job, or robots in their home, robots to solve their own problems and support them in their goals. At PRIA workshops in year 2 and year 3 - *Robotic4Kids*, *Hedgehog* and *LEGOMindstorms Middleschool* – children were asked to identify problems and adapt the building and programming of their robot to create a model of a robot which could solve the issue they chose. The automatic parking system, building container houses and playground workshops by UoA all required learners to engage with a real-world problem which had been chosen for them but the children had to identify the problems within the task themselves. For example, how do you make a fun but safe playground ride? Children typically were unable to fully ‘solve’ these problems, but they were able to come up with a solution, whether it was a sketch, a working prototype or a set of logical ideas. Importantly, it was through these artefacts that they were able to communicate and share their ideas with others, both within and outside their teams.

As mentioned under Objective 2, children collaborated with others during workshops and conferences. Important ‘soft’ or ‘21st Century’ skills which were needed to accomplish this included communication (speaking and listening) skills, critical thinking, reflection and creativity. These skills were emphasized in the Year 1 evaluation (D6.3) and became a central set of recommendations for the Year 2 and Year 3 workshops. As already mentioned in the Industry Evaluation (section 4) these skills are of particular interest to those in industry who find that many graduates have the domain specific skills but lack the interpersonal and intrarelational skills that they need when working in teams in large organisations. This is against an educational backdrop in most countries where individual achievement is most important and children mostly do work in groups or teams.

5.4.1 Conclusion

Based on the evidence collected through the evaluation and the summary discussion above, we can answer the questions stated in 5.1 for objective 3 as follows:

Research questions:

- Did children identify and define problems that influence their lives?
 - Yes. There are opportunities in both workshops and conferences for children to identify and define problems that influence their lives.
- Were they equipped with the necessary skills to solve these?
 - Through the curriculum, students are introduced to a range of skills. Depending on their age and experience, children’s ability to ‘solve’ these problems will naturally be limited. Given these constraints, children do propose solutions to these problems in a variety of forms.
- Do they have an opportunity to present their ideas and artefacts to each other as ‘proper’ scientists?
 - Yes. The ECER conference provides a dedicated opportunity for students to present their ideas and solutions to each other and to adults, as ‘proper’ scientists. The papers that they write are scaffolded, introducing students to the formal way to

present a scientific paper. In workshops students have various opportunities to present their ideas to each other, both formally and informally.

- Do they develop ‘soft-skills’?
 - Yes. Across the ER4STEM workshops and conference students develop a wide range of soft-skills.
- Do they learn intrarelational (how well they know themselves) and interpersonal skills?
 - Yes. Across the data we see students self-reporting in questionnaires and during interviews that they have learned more about working with others. While it occurs less often, students also refer to intrarelational skills, particularly with reference to how they work in teams.

Additionally:

- How were conferences designed to allow young people to present their ideas and artefacts to each other as proper scientists?
 - An important part of ECER is the submission of papers by the participating students. Some of these papers relate to societal problems identified (or suggested by the call for papers) and others are concerned with the robots that are used by the students in the competition. Developing these robots involves ideas for its construction and mechanics as well as its programming. The students have the opportunity to focus in a paper on one or several aspects of their robots in order to present it to the other participants through their papers and if accepted through presentations just as researchers do at actual scientific conferences. Besides, their papers can also encompass new ideas regarding the competition or other aspects of educational robotics.
- How have perspectives of STEM fields been disseminated?
 - The perspectives have been disseminated via a white paper on the ER4STEM repository. This will be developed into an Open Access paper in the future.

Overall, ER4STEM provided multiple entry points for learners to explore real-world societal problems and how these might be addressed using robots. They were able to present their ideas and artefacts as, and to, ‘proper’ scientists.

5.5 OBJECTIVE 4: ER4STEM SETS OUT TO CREATE A CONTINUOUS STEM SCHEDULE BY LEVERAGING ON ALREADY EXISTING EUROPEAN APPROACHES OF INNOVATIVE SCIENCE EDUCATION METHODS AND MEASURES BASED ON ROBOTICS WITHIN ONE OPEN OPERATIONAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Within this objective there are two stated activities, which are addressed in turn:

5.5.1 Comparison of 10 current EU strategies to encourage STEM education against the needs of STEM professionals in industry.

This objective is addressed in detail in D1.4. In total 12 current EU strategies (at national or EU level) were analysed against the needs of STEM professionals in industry. One of the interesting findings was that all strategies identified the need for alignment between industry and education when it

comes to STEM. The Bulgarian ‘Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation of Republic of Bulgaria 2014-2020’ document identified a mismatch between industry needs and academic preparation and the UK Government strategy ‘Delivering STEM skills for the economy’ highlighted that only 24% of STEM graduates were working in a STEM occupation within 6 months in 2016. We cannot say whether these might be associated with issues in the education of young people in STEM subjects and preparation for STEM careers, however they highlight the importance of the work done within the ER4STEM project, with its original framing around the needs of industry to act as one driver within the framework.

Strategies include initiatives to improve teacher education in STEM and provide more opportunities to engage in STEM activities. We believe that throughout the three project years, we at ER4STEM have created a set of tools that can be effectively applied to benefit strategic initiatives, related to STEM education and could serve the successful planning, implementation and evaluation of educational robotics activities specifically.

Only four strategies and strategic initiatives in total, from two countries (Austria and Greece) mention educational robotics as educational tools to keep children motivated to learn STEM. Within **Schule 4.0. – jetzt wird’s digital**, educational robotics appears in the strategy two times with relation to child-friendly programming environments, robotics and creative digital design. Interestingly, part of the strategy is the organization of competitions. One of those competitions, the “computer creative wettbewerb” (“computer creative competition”) is about projects handed in by school students that are then rated by a jury. It is stated that projects regarding various topics can be handed in with robotics being one of these topics. Furthermore, the strategy names the establishment of Education Innovation Studios at the University Colleges of Teacher Education throughout Austria, which are meant for increasing teacher competences regarding child-appropriate programming environments, robotics (e.g. LEGO WeDo) and creative, digital designing. Another strategy, again from Austria, that considers educational robotics **Talentförderung in Niederösterreich** for fostering young talents specifically regarding STEM topics. Robotics was chosen as core domain as it represents a multi-disciplinary field. Two modules are offered: 1) Robot programming for 12 to 14 year-olds and 2) Robot construction for 14 to 16 year-olds. **ESERO**, a European strategy implemented in Greece, envisages *robotics and automation workshops for primary and secondary school teachers*. During the workshops, participants are guided through activities that can be performed in the classroom, such as creating robots using LEGO WeDo or Arduino platform, and using them to perform a ‘mission to Mars’ with specific discovery objectives. Last but not least, the Greek Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs’ strategic initiatives aim at involving a large number of teachers and students with new technologies, science and robotics. However, no specific initiatives were mentioned within the strategy review.

As per ER4STEM’s results, robotics allows ALL learners to engage with the four areas of STEM education through the design, creation and programming of tangible artefacts to create personally meaningful objects and address real-world societal needs. This is why we believe educational robotics and the ER4STEM Project could provide valuable tools and artifacts to support the strategies that already envisage robotics as part of their activities and initiative and further provide arguments for the inclusion of educational robotics as a tool to explore STEM concepts. As many of the reviewed strategies encompass not only the development of technical skills but also of soft skills that are of importance for professional life, multidisciplinary domains such as robotics, could provide support to achieving the objectives and core goals of the strategies related to STEM.

The strategies reviewed all aim to increase student’s interest in STEM and reflect on the needs of the industry as reported above in Section 4, which corresponds closely to ER4STEM’s objective to turn curious young children into young adults passionate about science and technology with a hands-on

use case: robotics. In the case of ER4STEM, the domain of robotics was chosen because it represents a multidisciplinary and highly innovative field encompassing physics, mathematics, informatics and even industrial design as well as social sciences. Our evaluation results further show that approaching STEM from a creative side creates multiple entry points to engage children from different backgrounds and with different interests.

This makes a compelling case for the integration of educational robotics as part of the strategic initiatives on a European and national level to increase interest in STEM education and careers. Based on the analysis of the 12 strategies and strategic initiatives reviewed and considering the results from the ER4STEM project, the analysis concluded that educational robotics could meet the needs of various European strategies: by serving as an effective instrument for teaching STEM disciplines in schools and informal educational settings. Moreover, educational robotics effectively addresses the needs for developing 21st century skills and the needs of industry as illustrated in Section 4 above. The educational robotics activities were well accepted by both girls and boys from a range of backgrounds. The potential provided by educational robotics could be more fully exploited within national and European strategies through:

- becoming part of the strategic educational activities in STEM related strategies on both European, national and regional levels.
- being promoted as an innovative way to engage and motivate students in STEM-related disciplines in schools.
- initiating and funding educational robotics initiatives for non-formal educational organizations, which could result in raising young learners' interest in STEM and support the development of soft skills and 21st century skills.
- being a highly multidisciplinary vehicle for learning - encompassing all STEM disciplines and requiring a plethora of soft skills, which could serve as a great instrument for the cultivation of 21st century skills to meet the needs of industry. Further research on educational robotics is needed in order to gain further perspective on this potential.
- qualification programs for teachers which provide opportunities to develop both pedagogic and technical knowledge, so they are supported in the introduction and integration of educational robotics in the schools.
- practical guidelines and validation/certification mechanism to assure the effective, efficient and informed use of educational robotics for STEM.
- inclusion of evaluation mechanisms for the educational initiatives and activities, carried under the strategies, as well as mechanisms and toolkits for the ethical sharing of results. Those mechanisms will provide the necessary feedback loop for evaluation of the results and effective strategic planning.

5.5.2 Evaluation of the repository

Through three events, 95 people evaluated the repository. Of these, 85 were teachers with the majority teaching high-school aged students. Only 28 already used robots in the classroom. Two online events and one face-to-face event in Lithuania were run to introduce people to the repository. At these events, the majority of participants were Turkish, followed by Greek, Romanian and Lithuania (Table 15).

Table 15. Countries of respondents

Country	Number of Respondents (N=77)
Turkey	21
Greece	11

Romania	11
Lithuania	8
Bulgaria	3
Italy	3
Ukraine	3
Austria	2
Macedonia	2
Malta	2
Portugal	2
Slovakia	2
Albania	1
Armenia	1
Belgium	1
Croatia	1
India	1
Serbia	1
Spain	1

When asked for their views on the ease of navigation and search, respondents tended to describe the repository as easy to use with few helpful comments on how it could be improved. Importantly, when asked if they would use the repository in the future and whether they would recommend it to their colleagues, all participants stated either ‘probably yes’ or ‘definitely yes’, with the main reasons given as “resources”, “interesting”, “learning from others”, “new ideas” and “relates to their job”.

The online seminar also resulted in the repository being translated into Turkish by one of the participants because they thought that it would be highly useful for their colleagues. To date, the repository has been accessed mostly in Greece.

5.6 OBJECTIVE 5: TO EVALUATE THE SUCCESS OF ER4STEM

To evaluate the success of ER4STEM, we proposed the following measures. This section presents the evidence for each measure:

- Number of children who participated in conferences and workshops
 - 510 children participated in conferences, with approximately 180 in Year 1, 200 in Year 2 and 130 in Year 3 (reported in D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3).
 - 4459 children participated in workshops, with 1213 in Year 1, 1570 in Year 2 and 1572 in Year 3 (reported in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3). This exceeds the originally proposed 4000 students in workshops over three years.
- Number of presenters at conferences and number of public announcements about the conferences
 - Over 3 years, 52 papers were presented by students at the ECER conference (see Appendix C)
- Participants’ satisfaction with the conferences and workshops
 - The average satisfaction score for the conferences was 4.14 out of 5 in Year 1, 4.44 in Year 2 and 3.96 in Year 3.

- The average satisfaction score for the workshops was 4.56 out of 5 in Year 1, 4.5 in Year 2 and 4.44 in Year 3.
- Number of children in the different age groups that reported increased interest in STEM, number of girls reported increased interest in STEM.
 - Of the 1077 children in the age group 6-10, 778 children reported an increased interest in STEM (STEMF>0.2)
 - Of the 1180 children in the age group 11-14, 997 children reported an increased interest in STEM (STEMF>0.2)
 - Of the 319 children in the age group 15-18, 241 children reported an increased interest in STEM (STEMF>0.2)
 - Overall, 1018 girls reported an increased interest in STEM (STEMF>0.2)
- Number of children pursuing STEM in tertiary education when applicable
 - Very few children who participated in ER4STEM workshops and conferences have gone into further education at this stage. Due to data protection and informed consent being obtained through parents and not students, we did not have a direct way to contact students who had left school. However, we are aware that some students who participated in ECER conferences have gone on to study STEM subjects in higher education.
- Number of models built, number of requirements created, number of technologies matched, number of innovations achieved.
 - 571 robots were built during workshops run by ESI, PRIA, TUW and UoA (examples appear at the end of this section)
 - 105 virtual world spaces were constructed (consisting of various objects) using SLurtles during workshops run by CU
 - Various other models were built throughout workshops and conferences, e.g. prototypes
 - 13 technologies were matched with workshop activity plans: Arduino, BBC MicroBit, Beebots, Dash and Dot, Finch, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO NXT, LEGO Technical, LEGO WeDO 2.0, Robot Arm, SLurtles and Thymio II. These were matched with 13 programming environments (note: not on a one-to-one basis, as reported in D2.4.
 - 6 innovations: ER4STEM Framework, ER4STEM Curriculum, ER4STEM Activity Plan Template, ER4STEM repository, Hedgehog and SLurtles (including the SLurtle virtual world)
 - Hedgehog (D5.3) was created and is evaluated in Koza et al. (2017). Areas for development include making the controller smaller, APIs for computer vision and control, and a dataflow programming environment.
 - SLurtles (D5.2) were created and evaluated in D6.4 and this deliverable. Additionally, a paper on their use is currently in progress. The main issue was around running the virtual world from a command line interface. Most teachers were uncomfortable with this (due to lack of experience and low sense of self-efficacy) and therefore a GUI has subsequently been developed and will be made available after the project ends.
 - Requirements:
 - 17 functional requirements identified from teacher workshops, reported in D5.4.
 - 10 functional requirements identified from partners, extracted from the use cases, reported in D5.4.

- 15 high-level technical requirements with a total of 65 low-level requirements (to achieve the functional requirements) reported in D5.4.
- Number of additional countries, municipalities, educational organisations involved/engaged/participated in conferences and workshops.
 - 2 for workshops: Ireland and Italy
 - 6 for conferences: Albania, Belgium, Croatia, Egypt, Kuwait, Poland
 - Educational organisations: Scientix (EU), Digital Volunteers (UK), Kuystendil Municipality (Bulgaria), Varna Free University (Bulgaria),
 - Non-scientific dissemination activities in Moldova
 - 19 countries through Repository dissemination activities: Turkey, Romania, Lithuania, Italy, Ukraine, Macedonia, Portugal, Slovakia, Albania, Armenia, Belgium, Croatia, Serbia, Spain and India.
- Number of peer reviewed articles related to the project published in scientific magazines or at scientific conferences
 - According to D8.2: 20 papers, 2 workshops and 2 posters were published in scientific conferences.
 - Additionally there were 2 keynote talks at conferences.
 - At this stage there are no published papers in journals as the project team prioritised conferences and non-scientific dissemination routes as these tend to have a higher short-term impact. To sustain longer-term impact through journal articles and other publications, there are 11 articles currently in progress.
- Number of educators and researchers that reported increased interest in using the methods developed in the project
 - There has been substantial interest in the ER4STEM approaches at various non-scientific and scientific dissemination events. Following the CU KidsMeet event 3 teachers expressed interest in SLurtle robotics; through the Repository information events XX teachers have expressed interest in the outcomes of the project and XX intend to use the repository in the future; ESI has had future requests from two schools and three non-formal educational institutions in Bulgaria, 10 schools in Moldova and 1 in Kuwait; beyond PRIA, where Hedgehog was developed, 1 teacher has bought 11 Hedgehogs in Austria, 1 teacher has 1 in Poland, 1 school student group put Hedgehog into an “intelligent” cuddly toy for their graduation thesis, 2 used them to control a 3D-printed robot arm and at 1 institute of Vienna University of Technology 2 Hedgehogs are used for controlling a small industry robot in a research project; and finally, 18 teachers attended ER4STEM events at ECER.
- Number of entries in each category of the repository
 - 1 curriculum with 6 pathways and linked to 20 activity plans
 - 3 ECER conferences

5.7 CONCLUSION

This report has demonstrated that the stated aims and objectives of ER4STEM have been met. The evaluation has highlighted emerging issues which cannot be resolved in this project and are discussed further in Section 6. Overall, educational robotics activities have been found to be effective at encouraging and maintaining interest in STEM education and careers. This research has been the first large-scale work to look not only at the outcomes of using robotics in STEM in education but to also critically examine the nature of these activities in action. Now further work is needed to increase the reach of ER4STEM activities and approaches and to rigorously test these in a variety of contexts.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This document has presented the evaluation of the third year of ER4STEM, examining the ECER conference and workshops implemented. While overall satisfaction has gone down slightly, this is not significant and we see that the implementation of these activities is increasingly robust, supported by research informed activity plans and framework which scaffold the development of these activities. By developing robust, research informed educational robotics activities teachers and researchers are more likely to be able to adopt the approaches used in ER4STEM in their own practice. This addresses a common issue in the existing literature on educational robotics, and that is the lack of rigour in reporting the design and implementation of educational robotics activities. This is an issue because, while the existing research literature supports our assertion that educational robotics can encourage young people to pursue STEM subjects and careers, without a robust way to communicate the design of these activities the research lack rigour.

ER4STEM activities maintain and increase interest in STEM subjects, across groups of learners. While there are some country specific variances, the three-year evaluation of the ER4STEM concept demonstrates that the approaches used are appropriate and help to address some of the recognised issues in STEM education. It highlights the importance of 21st Century/soft skills, with reflection, critical thinking, creativity and teamwork are all supported. As already discussed in this deliverable, ER4STEM has provided students with opportunities to develop these skills. This is against an educational backdrop in most countries where individual achievement is most important and children mostly do not work in groups or teams.

There are also still areas for development in evidencing learning in educational robotics. This is particularly difficult as, along with soft-skills, knowledge and skills from all four STEM subjects can be applied and developed. While a specific concept can be taught, practiced and assessed using robotics, it doesn't capture the potential complexity of knowledge and skills that can be gained from engaging in educational robotics activities. Additionally, ER4STEM advocates a team-based approach, not dissimilar to concepts within communal constructivism – that knowledge is constructed and held by the group rather than the individual. It is not necessarily helpful for a single individual to have all of the knowledge. More importantly it is not practical when working on advanced and complex problems in industry. In traditional education environments this is potentially particularly problematic when evidence comes from a team rather than an individual. This is down to where we believe and/or want knowledge to reside - at the level of the individual or at the level of the team. These points highlight issues around siloed teaching and testing of subjects, the low value placed on developing soft-skills in school curricula (even though these are skills sought by employers) and assessment of the individual throughout their education.

We find that the lowest scoring workshops happen when they are integrated into the standard school timetable as part of a single subject, e.g. CU SLurtle workshops in 50-minute ICT/CS lessons twice a week for 10 weeks. While high scoring workshops in schools involve the suspension of the timetable for a day of two half days. Interestingly, high scoring CU SLurtle workshops took place over three weeks. However, there are other relevant factors in these workshops – CU participants were less likely to state that they liked using computers and the workshops were run during computing lessons. These findings raise unanswered and unanswerable questions (in the context of this project) about the integration of robotics activities in a standard curriculum and standard school timetable. If the loss of the 'wow' factor is so notable, should robotics activities only be used as one-off events so as to capitalise on the motivational aspects?

Another way to look at those workshops at CU is that they resulted in the highest percentage of students wanting to participate in future activities like the ones they participated in. A major difference between those workshops and the ones run by ESI (highest star rating but lowest percentage wishing to do similar activities) is that the CU workshops focused on exploration, open challenges, self-directed learning and creating something personally meaningful. By comparison those at ESI included few open challenges and where students did construct artefacts they followed standardised instructions. So, is it about the design of the activities rather than the way they are integrated that is key to their introduction in mainstream curricula? Most likely, it is a combination of the two, which raises the importance of teacher professional development.

While the results from the ER4STM project have been impressive and have identified clear areas for educators to consider in the design of educational robotics activities, without sustained engagement with educators through dissemination events, initial and ongoing teacher professional development, there is a danger of an assumption that ER4STEM activities will bring about collaboration, sharing of ideas, critical thinking skills or an increased interest in STEM, by simply including group work, sharing time, and a complex problem in an activity with robots. There can be an assumption that children and young people already know how to work effectively in a team, yet they may never have been explicitly taught or had scaffolds from which they can learn, nor feedback on the effectiveness of their teamwork and how they might improve. Developing the flexibility to provide in-time knowledge and support requires a teacher to feel comfortable with their own knowledge and skills, which may also require time to develop.

The particular focus on girls within this project has allowed us to highlight the conventional discourse which positions girls as having some form of deficit which means that they need something 'different' from boys so as to engage them in robotics and STEM education. Or, as observed at least once in the project, that girls need to change to be more like boys. Instead, it is perhaps worthwhile exploring and questioning the assumptions of boys. While the girls were equally keen to get involved in the robotics activities, their opportunities were sometimes limited by the boys. This suggests that in a teamwork environment, appropriate scaffolds are needed to get students to stop and think about their actions, perhaps discussing them as a team before taking action. However, the research in Years 3, 2 and 1 have demonstrated that girls are also seen to take over and they are observed to exclude others. It is not uncommon for one gender to exclude another gender when working in mixed-gender teams. So perhaps, alternatively, instead of targeting a particular gender, a more holistic approach should be taken.

Describing certain types of robotics activities as particularly appealing to one gender or another can be an unhelpful dichotomy and potentially as problematic as concepts such as 'learning styles'. If students' preferences are always catered for and they are not provided with opportunities to engage with personally and conceptually more challenging or less 'instantly' interesting robotics activities, they will not have the opportunity to develop the wider range of skills and knowledge needed for industry and other career paths. Competitions are typically described as being of interest to boys rather than girls, but assumes a hegemonic notion of masculinity which can be also be exclusive to some groups of boys. By positioning an activity as particularly appealing to one group of people, the result is the 'othering' of those who are not members of that group, excluding them or requiring them to do more work to legitimately participate in those activities. The value of the ER4STEM approach from the outset, to provide multiple entry points to appeal to and inspire all young learners, provides a different way of thinking about activities in gender binaries. Instead, through ER4STEM there is a suit of activity plans which offers a variety of entry points and through the curriculum there are pathways to navigate between the plans providing opportunities to engage with alternative and

complementary approaches. There is surely value in all learners, over time, engaging with multiple approaches to educational robotics for STEM. This logic could be the focus of future research which aims to get more young people interested in STEM subjects and careers.

Finally, the research undertaken within the evaluation of the 3 years of this project has been ambitious. It is the first research to look, at scale at what happens during educational robotics activities and not just at the results of the activity. There is a pedagogic imperative to continue such work. While a workshop may have positive outcomes, as we see in the case studies, what is planned for does not always occur and to understand what works and in what circumstances, we need to carefully examine what happens and question what we see. We need ways to measure outcomes systematically and answer a range of emerging questions which include:

- How do free-form, self-organised sharing activities compare to teacher-driven and structured opportunities for learners to share what they have created?
- How does the chosen technology open-up or close-down opportunities for learning?
- How can teachers effectively assess both subject knowledge and soft-skills gained through educational robotics activities?
- How do we prepare students for the technical advancements of the future so that the STEM knowledge they gain is still relevant in 3-5 years' time?
- How can students engage in the secondary design of educational robotics, regarding new affordable and robust solutions?
- How can new advances in robotics technology realistically contribute to new special solutions with pedagogical added value?
- How can we create bridges between meanings gathered through students' experiences with educational robotics, present curriculum concepts as well as 21st century pedagogies and digital literacy?

These are just some questions that need to be explored. This emphasises the importance of interdisciplinary research in the area, drawing together those in STEM fields with social scientists. Given the radical changes of jobs with AI, big data, Internet of Things, etc., pupils need to learn a wide range of transferrable skills and knowledge. Robotics is the perfect, interdisciplinary tool to learn the skills of the 21st century. While technical innovations can help, without research informed pedagogic innovation, policy initiatives and implementation at scale – robotics workshops for every child in Europe – the transformative potential of robotics in education will not be realised.

7 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

AL	Across Limits (project partner)
CU	Cardiff University (project partner)
EC	European Commission
eFSM	Entitlement to Free School Meals
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM (project name)
ESI	European Software Institute (project partner)

FSM	Free School Meals
PRIA	Practical Robotics Institute of Austria (project partner)
REA	Research Executive Agency
SLurtles	Programmable robots in a virtual world
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TUW	Technical University of Vienna (project partner)
UoA	University of Athens (project partner)

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9 APPENDIX A: ECER 2018 CASE STUDY

9.1 CONTEXT

NTCH were an Austrian team who competed in the Botball robotics competition at ECER 2018. NTCH comprised of nine members, who had different roles within the team. Members had a range of experience with the ECER competition, with three members having attended before, and the two girls having been in focus groups for the ER4STEM project in their previous two years of attendance. A breakdown of the team members is shown in Table 16.

Table 16. Demographic, Experience and Roles of NTCH Team Members

Referred to as	Student Number	Gender	Age	Previous Experience at ECER	Main Team Role
Child 1	33193	Male	17	None	Worked on Robot 1 and delivered onsite presentation
Child 2	31048	Female	17	Attended previous two years	Team leader. Worked on Robot 2
Child 3	31007	Female	16	Attended previous two years	Worked on Robot 1
Child 4	32251	Male	17	Attended the previous year	Documentation (creating and delivering onsite presentation) and worked with Alliance Round team
Child 5	33158	Male	19	None	Documentation (creating and delivering student talks presentation)
Child 6	33157	Male	17	None	Documentation (creating and delivering student talks presentation)
Child 7	33151	Male	17	None	Worked on Robot 2
Child 8	33155	Male	16	None	Robot mechanic
Child 9	33169	Male	16	None	Documentation

The members were originally in two teams from two classes in the school, but decided to combine the teams so that they could get more work done:

“Child 2 (f): So then we went together because there’s more to do, the presentation part, the documentation part.

Child 1 (m): We thought it would be better to merge our teams because it would be better to work with multiple people.”

Tasks that the team members had to complete whilst at the competition included refining the mechanics and programming for two robots (shown in Figure 34), creating and delivering an onsite presentation, and creating and delivering a student talk presentation based on a paper written by the team prior to the competition.

Figure 34. NTCH's Robots (Robot 1 on right, Robot 2 on right)

The team prepared for the competition by meeting after school, although they found it difficult to coordinate everyone to meet at once. Therefore, they also used a WhatsApp group as another form of communication for competition preparation.

9.2 DATA ANALYSIS

The research team decided to focus data analysis on the NTCH team out of the total of four focus groups due to the returning two girls in the team, who had been the focus of reports in previous deliverables. Therefore, all data collected for NTCH was coded with an overall research focus on how NTCH worked as a team, whilst remaining open to other emergent themes. This data included observational notes, video data collected by the teams, interviews with the teams, and pre and post-competition questionnaires. Emergent themes were then structured into categories and sub-categories.

9.3 FINDINGS

This study focused on how NTCH functioned as a team whilst at the ECER competition. This section presents the findings of the data analysis, with categories acting as sub-sections: 'Leadership', 'Sub-Teams', 'Engagement' and 'External Interactions'. For each category, a visual representation of the relationship between it and any sub-categories are provided. Furthermore, codes within categories are shown in **bold**.

9.3.1 Leadership

The assigned team leader for the duration of the competition was Child 2 (f), largely due to the experience she had from previous competitions, which is explored in the sub-category 'Experience'. However, it was observed that Child 1 (m) had a sense of natural leadership within his interactions with other team members. This portrayal of leadership in both Child 1 and 2 are explored in the subcategory 'Control' and the linked subcategory 'Responsibility'. The relationship between this category of 'Leadership' and its subcategories is shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35. Representation of 'Leadership' Category

9.3.1.1 EXPERIENCE

The subcategory 'Experience' explores the impact that team members' previous experience at the competition has on how the team functioned, particularly through a respect for the knowledge gained from experience. Child 2 (f) had **previously attended the competition**, alongside Child 3 (f) and Child 4 (m). During interviews with the researcher, Child 2, 3 and 4 mentioned **what they had learnt** from these previous competitions at various points. This included practical skills relating to robotics as well as softer skills around teamwork. For example, upon being asked what she had learnt in previous competitions, Child 3 (f) stated: *"Well, erm, we are always, if someone has an idea or something like that, we always try to question it or something like that, because everyone starts to question the ideas of other people, because, so people don't always think of all the things and even if it's a really good idea we will question it, and yeah."* The previous experience of Child 2, 3 and 4 influenced how the 2018 team functioned, as their collective knowledge was brought forward and applied to the new team. For example, the decision to combine two teams to make the one large team of NTCH (9.1) was made based on the experience from the previous year of having too few team members.

Although Child 3 stated that everyone had an opportunity to question ideas, observations throughout the week demonstrated that this rarely happened, particularly by the less experienced members – although this could have occurred in unobservable forms such as pre-competition. While it was not explicitly stated by the team, it is implied that the new team members respected the knowledge of those who had experience of the competition and that this respect played a part in the leadership of the team.

9.3.1.2 CONTROL

This subcategory discusses three forms of control: delegation, micromanagement and directing. While Child 2 (f) was the assigned team leader and so coordinated other members' work, Child 1 (m) was observed taking control at various points. Both Child 2 and Child 1 attempted to control how the team performed by managing how the other team members worked, and so this section focuses on how these two students attempted to lead through control.

Child 2 acted as a coordinator, through **delegation** of tasks to different team members, which was observed at multiple points over the course of the week. Child 2's **coordination** meant that she oversaw the team members' work and ensured that it was completed to a desirable standard and on time. For example, Figure 36 shows Child 2 being shown the visual material that Child 5 (m) and 6 (m) have created for the team's Student Talk Presentation, and during the onsite presentation, Child 1(m) states: "So our team leader, our team leader is Child 2. She was also responsible for organising when do er when some deadlines are due for documentation. She also decide er she also was responsible for getting everyone to work."

Figure 36. Child 2 is shown other team members' work

Whilst the idea of Child 2's leadership being based on the **coordination** of the other members was also stated at various points in interviews, except for the moment captured in Figure 36, Child 2 was rarely observed to be overseeing the others' work during the course of the week. Instead she was mostly observed completing her own work on Robot 2.

Interestingly, it was mentioned in the post-competition interview that it was important not to **micromanage** in a team. When a discussion concerning **what the team had learnt from this year's** competition focused on the concept of not being **stressed**, students remarked that not micromanaging was important in remaining calm:

Child 7: "Don't try to micromanage everything"

Child 3: Yes
Interviewer: Ok
Child 7: Don't try and have your hands in everything
Interviewer: Delegate and trust people?
Child 7: Yes and give them more room to work"

Post-Competition Interview

Child 2 was not observed to portray qualities of micromanagement of the team in her role as assigned leader during the course of the competition, instead appearing to be comfortable with delegation and allowing team members to get on with their work. However, it is possible that micromanagement occurred and not been noticed by the researcher or in unobservable formats such as before the competition, or in their WhatsApp group. Overall throughout the week, Child 2 was observed mostly working on robot related tasks. On the other hand, Child 1 was involved in **multiple tasks** throughout the week, working on robot 1 and delivering the onsite presentation.

A final form of control of team member's work came in the form of directing and instructing other team members. Whilst Child 2 was rarely seen to be obviously instructing team members, Child 1 was regularly observed to be very physical in his directing, for example by pointing and obviously telling others what to do (Figure 37). In addition, Child 1 was involved in multiple tasks throughout the week, working on Robot 1 and delivering the onsite presentation. This allowed him to have control over multiple tasks, both through his own work and through directing others working on the same tasks.

Figure 37. Child 2 and 3 face Child 1 as he directs them (behind camera)

9.3.1.3 RESPONSIBILITY

By taking a leadership role, Child 2 (f) accepted a level of responsibility for the team. For example, when the team did not function as well as planned, Child 2 placed the **blame** on herself.

Child 2: I think to coordinate a team, so I have to make sure that everyone has something to do, and that there is a person for everything and that all. Yeah but, some are bored, so I've failed.

Child 1: Yeah but that's kind of not your fault because there's just not more to do."

She clearly states that it is her personal mistake and not a fault of the team as a whole. Child 1 (m) disagrees with this blame and reassures Child 2 that she should not take this responsibility.

When the team competes with their robots, it is in the competition rules that only two team members may be located at the competition table. In every round of the competition, Child 1 and Child 2 represent the team at the table (Figure 38), again taking responsibility – in this situation ensuring that the robots are correctly set up.

Figure 38. Child 1 and Child 2 represent the team at the competition table

Finally, it is observed that during the interviews and researcher drop-ins both Child 1 and Child 2 were comfortable **speaking on behalf of the team**. Whilst this reinforces the responsibility they took to represent the team through their leadership, this also resulted in some members rarely speaking in interviews. Did they agree with what Child 1 or Child 2 were saying, or was their opinion not represented in the interview? There is no evidence to confirm either.

9.3.2 Sub-Teams

NTCH divided themselves into assigned sub-teams, the members each focusing on a specific task the team needed to complete. This section explores the organisation of these sub-teams in the sub-section 'Division of Tasks', followed by reporting the **dynamics** in the sub-teams in the subsection 'Interactions within Sub-Teams' and finally exploring what 'Interactions between Sub-Teams' took place. The relationship between these sub-sections is shown in Figure 39. Overall, it was found that the large number of team members in NTCH resulted in a lack of work for some members, as well as a lack of **communication** between sub-teams due to **physical separation** of the team members.

Figure 39. Representation of ‘Sub-Teams’ category

9.3.2.1 DIVISION OF TASKS

This sub-section explores how NTCH divided tasks between the sub-teams, showing the organisation of their team and how this changed over time. Shown as a visual representation in Figure 40, the team’s main division of roles fell into that of a Documentation sub-team and a Robots sub-team. In an interview, upon being asked whether the work was split half and half between the documentation and the robots, Child 3 (f) said “No, it’s more about the robots, because (it’s harder for the robots)”. This implies that the robots sub-teams work had higher **priority** than that of the documentation. Furthermore, it was stated that “no-one wants to do the documentation” (Child 3) showing that although the team were subdivided by tasks, NTCH members preferred the concept of working on the robots.

Figure 40. Division of tasks between sub-teams and the assigned distribution of team members

Figure 40 also shows that within the clear divide of **documentation** and robots, the sub-teams had smaller working groups. In the robots sub team, there were two working groups, one for each robot,

which are connected by a small channel to show the **communication** required as the two robots would work together on the game table. Similarly, the **documentation** team had two working groups for different **presentations**. Each of these working groups had two team members, allowing a **division of work**, but still working alongside someone. Conversely, Child 8 (m) worked individually as the team's **mechanic**, with the assigned role to step in to help the robot working groups if mechanical changes were required. However, as discussed in section 9.3.3.2, this did not always entail much work and so the representation of the mechanical role in Figure 40 crosses into the **documentation** sub-team side as he sometimes spent time with those team members socially when there was less mechanical work available.

Although NTCH created a large team in order to divide tasks between roles (as described in 9.1), it became apparent early in the week that there were more team members than there were assignable roles. For example, as shown in Figure 40, although Child 9 (m) was supposedly on the **documentation** sub-team, there was little work available for him to complete as the tasks were covered by the other **documentation** sub-team members. This resulted in Child 9 making his own role, taking charge of the researcher's camera that had been given to the team. This lack of designated work can be contrasted with Child 1 (m), who delivered the onsite **presentation** even though he was primarily on the robot team, showing that there was some imbalance in the amount of work provided to different team members.

The lack of work for some members was recognised by the team by the time of the mid-week interview:

- “Interviewer: So is it perhaps a bit of an issue that you're such a big team?”*
Multiple: Yes
Child 3: Because last year it was like much easier, everybody had something to do
Child 2: But the problem was there was too much to do and we thought it would be better if there were more persons but it doesn't work.”
 ...
“Child 2: More people does not mean more work.”

Team members also confirmed this in the post-conference questionnaire, with Child 3 (f) answering the question of what she had learnt about working with other people with: *“people are more difficult to coordinate and there's always someone who doesn't have anything to do”*.

Finally, it should be noted that these roles and division into sub-teams was not completely static, but rather that Figure 40 shows team members' originally assigned roles. The fluidity of team members over time is explored in 9.3.3.

9.3.2.2 INTERACTIONS WITHIN SUB-TEAMS

Most of the interactions between members of NTCH would be with team members in the same sub-team or working group. This sub-section therefore explores the difference in interactions within three groups; between Child 1 (m) and Child 3 (f) in the robot 1 working group; between Child 2 (f) and Child 7 (m) in the robot 2 working group; and between Child 5 (m) and Child 6 (m) as the most core members of the documentation sub-team. These working relationships between individuals were not discussed in interviews, but are instead evidenced purely from observation.

Child 1 (m) and Child 3 (f)'s primary role was to work on robot 1 throughout the duration of the week, the only time they didn't work together was being on Wednesday morning whilst Child 1 delivered the onsite presentation. The pair spent almost all their time together and had a close working dynamic that included both working on all aspects of the robots – strategic, programming and mechanical. The pair communicated lots, including directing each other, discussing ideas or actively observing the other. Furthermore, they were often seen co-constructing the robot, as shown in Figure 5. Although Child 3 had a respectable amount of experience of the competition (see 9.3.1.1) and Child 1 had natural leadership qualities (see 9.3.1.2), the pair were never observed to come into any conflict in their working dynamics, instead adjusting their leadership qualities to work effectively together.

Figure 41. Child 1 and Child 3 co-construct Robot 1

Although they had essentially the same objectives as Child 1 and 3, just working on a different robot, Child 2 (f) and Child 7 (m) had a very different working style as a pair. Whereas Child 1 and 3 very much shared the role, working on most things together and taking turns, Child 2 and 7 instead divided the work between them. Child 7 mostly worked on the programming, whereas Child 2's work focussed on the physical robot. Furthermore, the two were often observed working separately, even sometimes physically distanced as is shown in Figure 42. This is an interesting comparison as both working groups seemed to have positive outcomes and work well, regardless of their very different working styles.

Figure 42. Child 7 (right) works alone whilst Child 2 is positioned with Child 1 and 3 (left)

Within the documentation team, the 'Student Talks Presentation' group, Child 5 (m) and Child 6 (m) completed their work almost entirely on their laptops, with the exception of when they practiced delivering the presentation together on Thursday. The pair appeared to divide the task of preparing the presentation between themselves, with one preparing the slides whilst the other wrote the script. The two of them sat side-by-side for the majority of the week, as shown in Figure 43, allowing easy communication and teamwork.

Figure 43. Child 5 and 6 (foreground) sit in their workspace for completing documentation

9.3.2.3 INTERACTIONS BETWEEN SUB-TEAMS

As the sub-teams were still part of the overall team of NTCH, it is also important to explore the interactions that took place between sub-teams during the course of the week. It was found that far fewer interactions took place between the sub-teams compared to within them, and that this **lack of**

communication was emphasised by a physical separation of the sub-teams by working in different locations.

A **lack of communication** between NTCH's sub-teams quickly emerged in the competition, with the mid-week interview revealing a clear example of the effects of bad communication:

- “Child 3: Yeah, the crash was bad communication, because the robot didn't do what it had to do.*
- Interviewer: Ok so when you say bad communication do you mean within the team? Or?*
- Multiple: Yeah*
- Interviewer: Ok, so expand on that, what do you mean by that?*
- Child 1: We tried testing them at the same time, but due to miscommunication, some of us thought we had already tested them together, while we didn't test them. And then when we had to group ourselves and get some points, we crashed*
- Child 2: They didn't work together.*
- Interviewer: So you tested the two robots separately and then when you actually came to the table*
- Child 3: Yeah but it was like a time thing too, because we wanted to test them together, but then we were on, upcoming”*

This example showed a very clear outcome from not fully communicating between the robot working groups. NTCH resolved this problem by having more communication between the two robot groups and changing the programming of the robots.

NTCH were also observed to show other forms of lacking interaction between sub-teams, which had less clear effects. For example, at the beginning of the week when the researcher would drop-in to the team, the documentation team would rarely communicate with the researcher, engage or listen to the other members when the robots were being discussed. This lack of engagement from the documentation team is also shown in Figure 44, where Child 5 (m) asks how the robot practice went in the form of a thumbs up/down gesture, after which no further conversation was had. This shows that although some communication took place between the sub-teams, the interactions were often superficial compared to those within sub-teams.

Figure 44. Superficial communication from Child 5 through hand gestures

It was also observed that the sub-teams had more limited interactions as they were often **physically separated**. As mentioned in 9.3.4.1, NTCH had a confidence within the competition space, which contributed to the robot working groups being very mobile and working in various spaces in the competition area. These workspaces are illustrated by the red crosses in Figure 45 which shows the various locations they moved to throughout the week. On the other hand, the documentation team largely remained seated at the designated table, occasionally moving to observe the robots during scheduled practices or competition rounds. Therefore, when the members were all working on their assigned tasks, the physical separation made it harder for sub-teams to interact with each other.

Figure 45. Location of NTCH workspaces throughout the course of the competition

9.3.3 Engagement

As previously mentioned in 9.3.2.1, some team members of NTCH completed more work than others, which they blamed on their **large team size** and a lack of assignable roles. In this section, the engagement of individual team members will be explored. Engagement is discussed in terms of being active or passive, and in terms of the flexibility of individuals in their roles. Further sub-categories within Engagement demonstrate how some individual engagement showed a ‘Change over Time’, and finally how engagement was affected by ‘Exclusion’. The relationship between these sub-sections are shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46. Representation of 'Engagement' category

It became apparent very early during the competition that some members of NTCH were more engaged than others, with the researcher beginning to investigate this concept from the first interview and the team members continuing to comment on it for the remainder of the week. At its simplest level, it seemed that those who were in the robot sub-team were far more engaged than those in the documentation sub-team and that this was purely down to a lack of balance in the division of tasks between the sub-teams. This was also how the team members described the situation, with Child 1 stating: *"Right now, the documentation team has got not as much to do as the others, so they're a bit bored I think?"*.

The initial assumption of the researcher was to categorise the actions of each member of the team by the task they were involved in during the competition. This was influenced by the physical location of the separate sub-teams, the responses during interviews and opportunistic observations. However, during data analysis, it became clear that some team members **changed roles**, moving from documentation to robotics or vice versa. So instead, the research team returned to the initial codes and aimed to identify new categories. In this process, the activity level of the student was noted as **changes in roles** and the question arose as to whether these two were interrelated. Recognising that these were not simple binaries, the decision was made to explore how each individual member of the team was positioned and perhaps moved along a continuum of active-passive engagement and how fluid-static they were in their roles. This resulted in Figure 47, which shows the relationship between the two continuums.

Whilst Figure 47 shows a considerable amount of information, there are some particularly important points to note. Firstly, the team stated during interviews that they believed the documentation sub-team were the least engaged members of the team and that overall the team didn't have enough work for everyone to do. However, Figure 47 shows that in fact, the majority of NTCH team members fell into the top half of the table and so were in some sense actively engaged in the competition. While the robot sub-team were the most continually active team members, there were only two team members who had very **passive roles** (Child 8 and 9) and one of these was technically a member of the robot sub-team. Secondly, Figure 47 shows that there were a number of changes in engagement of individuals over the course of the week, which is discussed further in the next sub-section.

Figure 47. A comparison of NTCH members' roles on the continuums active-passive engagement and fluid-static flexibility

9.3.3.1 CHANGE OVER TIME

Through analysing the engagement of NTCH members in Figure 47, it is shown that there are a number of instances in which individual's engagement changes over the duration of the competition. These changes had a variety of causes – some due to planned events internal to the team, some due to gradual disengagement and some due to factors that were **external to the team** and therefore out of their control. The latter will be discussed first.

In Figure 47 that the Alliance round caused a change in engagement for multiple team members – Child 2, 4 and 7. Whilst the Alliance round is fully discussed in the Alliances Report, it should be noted here that Child 2 and Child 7's lowered engagement was due to the **Alliance round** only using Robot 1, meaning they were no longer required to work on their robot (Robot 2). Whilst they had been very actively engaged throughout the week, the **Alliances** meant they had to become more flexible in order to still stay engaged. Child 2 changed her role to help on Robot 1, meaning she was still relatively engaged, although she was also observed having more time socialising or doing personal schoolwork. Child 7 became less engaged, again socialising with others, although he also took a new passive role in helping Child 5 and 6 practice their presentation (Figure 48).

Figure 48. Child 7 (left) helps Child 5 + 6 (right) practice their presentation

Other changes in engagement were caused by planned events internal to the team. For example, when Child 1 delivered the Onsite Presentation on the Wednesday morning, it was planned for Child 5 and 6 to replace Child 1 on the Robot 1 team. This change allowed Child 1 to focus fully on the presentation and for Child 5 and 6 to experience being more actively engaged in the robotics side of the competition. However, this was only a temporary change, with all three students returning to their previous roles once the presentation had finished.

Finally, whilst most changes in engagement had a **specific cause** that could be pinpointed, resulting in a sudden change, Child 9 (m) showed a more gradual disengagement over the course of the week. As previously mentioned, Child 9 was assigned a small workload, which resulted in him creating his own role, filming with the researcher's camera (Figure 49). However, as time passed, Child 9 was observed less in this role and instead socialised with the ECER volunteers or watched the competition. This may have been because neither his

original documentation role nor the created role of filming were particularly actively engaging, resulting in **boredom** and a gradual disengagement.

Figure 49. Child 9 sets up researcher's camera to film NTCH

9.3.3.2 EXCLUSION

It can be seen in Figure 47 that Child 8 (m) had a unique change in his engagement over the course of the week, as he undertook a repeating cycle of becoming more engaged, before then being subtly **excluded** and returning to an unengaged state. This state was very passive and included watching the robotics teams work, daydreaming, being on his phone, talking to other members and playing with spare unused robot parts (Figure 50). As was discussed in section 9.3.2.1, Child 8 had a specific static role as he was NTCH's mechanic. It was noted by other team member's in the mid-week interview that Child 8 did not have enough work available to complete:

Child 1: Child 8 is our main mechanical guy [he has really good abilities

Child 3: [he is already finished]

Child 1: But now our robots are pretty much finished so there's not much to build.

Interviewer: So it's only if there's odd little changes

Child 1: He's always asking if he can do something but there's nothing to do"

It is implied in this extract that Child 8 had more work to complete in the lead-up to the competition in originally creating the robots, but now has "nothing to do". Both from this extract and from observations by the researcher, it is evidenced that Child 8 was skilled in his role and very willing to complete work, but the other team members imply there was none available for him.

Figure 50. Child 8 being bored (left) and playing with robot pieces (right)

However, further observations by the researcher showed that on the occasions that there was **mechanical** work to be completed on either robot, Child 8 would at first become involved under one of the robotics team's instruction, but on multiple occasions would be **excluded** from the work by the robotics team over the course of a few minutes. An example can be seen in Figure 51, where Child 8 was seen making mechanical changes to Robot 2, with Child 1 (m), 2 (f) and 3 (f) actively observing. However, over a period of approximately five minutes, Child 8 was gradually excluded from his work, with the three robotics team members taking over, until Child 8 simply played with spare parts rather than contributing to the actual robots (Figure 52). This highlights two points – firstly there was not “*nothing to do*” as Child 1 (m) stated in the interview, but there was instead only occasional work for Child 8 in his static role. Secondly, it shows that exclusion had a part to play in Child 8's lack of engagement over the week. Although the exclusion didn't appear to take place in a malicious, or even very conscious manner, it still very much occurred and on multiple occasions. Of course it can be questioned how much Child 8's disengagement was due to this exclusion and how much it was due to any personality traits and work ethic – to what degree did he exclude himself.

Figure 51. Child 8 given role-specific mechanical work

Figure 52. Child 1, 2 and 3 exclude C8 (foreground playing with parts) from his work

9.3.4 External Interactions

While the majority of the **team interactions** happened internally between team members, NTCH as a team unit interacted with people who were external to the team. These external interactions affected the way NTCH themselves functioned as a team, giving them a heightened sense of confidence and inspiring them to achieve what other teams had. This section is subdivided into interactions with 'Non-Competitors' and 'Other Teams' (Figure 53). 'Other Teams' has been further categorized into '**Communication**', 'Observation' and '**Alliances**'. In Figure 53, '**Alliances**' is connected with a dashed arrow, as it is recognized that the concept of the alliance round does not fully fit into the sub-category of 'Other Teams', as this round required NTCH to work closely with their alliance team, merging to become one large team with a common goal. As the **alliances** are an interesting phenomena in the competition, NTCH's interaction with their alliance team is discussed in greater depth in the Alliances Report.

Figure 53. Representation of 'External Interactions' category

9.3.4.1 NON-COMPETITORS

As well as robotics teams, there were many non-competitors present at the competition, such as: hotel staff, researchers, viewing public and the staff and student **volunteers** from the company PRIA who organised the competition. This subsection will focus on NTCH's interactions with PRIA staff and **volunteers**, as these comprised the majority of the **team's interactions** with non-competitors. This will be explored in terms of interactions that had a practical basis and a social basis. It is important contextually to note that the members of NTCH were from a school associated with the organisation running the competition, PRIA, and therefore were familiar with the competition staff, as well as volunteers who were also students from the school. The subsection is thus concluded by exploring how this familiarity increased the team's **confidence** at the competition and affected how they functioned as a team.

NTCH often interacted with ECER staff and **volunteers** on a practical basis, evidencing in interviews that examples included asking questions about the competition and the **working space**, or asking for resources such as sellotape. Practical interactions were also observed at the competition tables, particularly with non-competitors who were acting as judges (Figure 54). These interactions were concerned with ensuring the team were abiding by the competition rules and asking the judges questions regarding scoring points or the robot setup on the table. Most interactions were a two-way dialogue between the members of NTCH representing the team at the table and the judges, although some interactions constituted of a one-way direction from the judges, with NTCH members respecting their authority within the competition.

Figure 54. Child 2 interacting with competition judges

NTCH also interacted with non-competitors in a social manner. As previously mentioned, the **competition volunteers** were students at the same school as the members of NTCH, with many of the **volunteers** actually based in the same class as them. During the course of the week, the **volunteers** were often observed sitting at the NTCH work table, not helping them with the competition, but instead talking and laughing together (Figure 55), or sitting on their mobile phones.

Figure 55. Members of NTCH socialising with competition volunteers

Overall, NTCH believed that previously knowing the **ECER volunteers** helped with their **confidence** at the competition, as there was a sense of **familiarity** with their surroundings. After agreeing in an interview that knowing the volunteers benefitted them, they expanded that having their friends volunteering “*makes it fun*” (Child 3 (f)), makes “*it[s] easier if you know the people because you are able to go up to them*” (Child 2 (f)) and creates “*the familiar environment*” (Child 1 (f)). NTCH also explained that the volunteers were likely to help the team if asked: “*Well if you’re like looking for sellotape or something like that, and you know them, they’re like*

ok I'll get that for you" (Child 3). It was often implied that this confidence from having a relationship with the volunteers and the PRIA staff gave NTCH an **advantage over others teams** who had to build a relationship with the non-competitors over the course of competition. Their **confidence** at the competition affected how NTCH worked as a team, for example having the **confidence** to work in areas outside of their designated working table. Furthermore, Child 1 gave an explicit example of the volunteers providing NTCH with perhaps an unfair **advantage over the other teams**: *"It helps us a bit with being the first at the free [practice] table, we got the information when it was ready so it was like grab your stuff and go in a minute"*.

9.3.4.2 OTHER TEAMS

As well as interacting with non-competitors, NTCH also interacted with **other teams** who were competing. This was in forms of communicating with the others teams and observing them. Again, these interactions generally helped NTCH within the competition, by providing **inspiration** and creating a practical and social network.

NTCH members, particularly but not exclusively those working on the robots, were often observed communicating with other teams. Whilst this was mostly with other Austrian teams, particularly those who also attended their school but were in other teams, NTCH also communicated with teams from other countries. Furthermore, in an interview, NTCH stated that it was actually very important to not be scared to communicate with the other teams and that they would give this advice to newer teams: *"Yeah because in our first year we were like very to ourselves and we weren't like 'have you got this, have your got a screwdriver, have you got, I don't know, this little piece and that'. And this year was like [another team] was taking stuff from us and we were taking stuff from them so."* (Child 3 – f). This form of team interaction clearly benefitted both NTCH and others teams in a very practical manner. However, NTCH were also observed to have more social interactions with other teams, conversing and laughing, for example in Figure 56 where Child 3 (f) was observed talking and laughing with another Austrian team whilst they tested their robot. Both this practical and social networking reinforces the aims of ECER of having good sportsmanship and bringing together teams from different places and backgrounds.

Figure 56. Child 3 (left) talks to another team at free practice table

Whilst NTCH often communicated with other teams, many of their interactions were in the form of passive observation of other teams. NTCH only ever talked positively about other teams, becoming **inspired** by their observations. Even when talking about a team who they believed they were likely to lose to in the double eliminations round, Child 3 (f) referred to respecting the design of the other team's robot: *"I think they have really interesting mechanical constructions. Like the one that had the thing that climbed up"*.

NTCH were particularly inspired by another Austrian team, which will be referred to as TH. Contextually it is important to note that NTCH had built a relationship with TH from having team members on both teams who had attended ECER in previous years. Child 2 (f) and Child 3 (f) were observed early in the competition on Monday having long conversation with a female member of TH whilst working on their robot (Figure 57). Furthermore, TH performed very well at the competition, winning a large number of awards at the end of the week. TH were a large team that had smaller sub-teams who competed in different competitions, but each time a sub-team won an award, the whole of TH went to collect the award. Observing TH's success had a big impact on NTCH, and in the final interview of the week NTCH explained how they were inspired to organize their team like TH in the following year's competition:

"Child 1 (m): And we are forming a really big team I think 15 to 20 people and we are going to compete in almost all the competitions.

Child 3 (f): But then the team will be split up into groups

Interviewer: Ah I see, so is that you've got inspiration from the other team [TH] to do that?

Child 1: Yeah because I would really like to do aerial and so next year I'm going to do aerial. Child 3, Child 2 and Child 7 want to do aerial too. But those two want to do Botball again, so they found others from other classes and teams so they can do it."

Figure 57. Female member of TH leans forward to talk to Child 3 (f) sat in the foreground (left)

A final form of interaction that NTCH had with other teams was during the alliance round of the competition. Here, NTCH were paired with a Polish team and had to work with them to score the most combined points with their robots. Therefore, interactions with the Polish team were very different than with any other team, as they strategized together and helped each other improve their robots. As they had a common goal, the Polish team became an extended part of the NTCH team and so there were more interactions between the teams than with non-alliance teams. As Child 4 (m) explained, NTCH directly supported the Polish team: *"Er I give them tips so*

they can improve the robot [(because)... and they had some missing parts they gave them. So it was good". As the alliance round of the competition was a particularly interesting phenomena in itself, more results of NTCH's interactions with the Polish team are discussed in the Alliances Report.

9.4 DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to analyse how NTCH functioned as a team during ECER 2018. This discussion will first explore the main two factors that link the findings of the study and had the biggest influence on the team's behaviour: the large size of NTCH as a team, comprising of many team members, and the experience that some team members had from previous competitions. Secondly, the discussion will explore how this study's findings compare to previous ER4STEM findings concerning the teams at ECER 2016 ('roboSpabs') that Child 2 and 3 took part in, and ECER 2017 that Child 2, 3 and 4 took part in (see Work Package 6.4).

NTCH's team size was very large, both in comparison to other team's at the competition, and in comparison to the team sizes that members had been part of in previous years. The members had assigned roles, of which some were adapted throughout the week. However, a primary concern for the team was based on there not being enough work for their team to complete in a way in which all team members were kept engaged. Although analysis revealed that most team members were engaged, only four team members were actively engaged with working on the robots for the majority of the week. Perhaps the actual robotics is viewed as the more 'fun' activity to be engaged with and by NTCH limiting the number of people who interacted with the robots, some members were left completing work that they perhaps did not think they would when they agreed to take part in a robotics competition. ECER includes elements of documentation and presentations to make the week a more rounded experience for the participants – not just purely about the robotics, but also exposing them to elements of science communication and academics. However, by NTCH dividing the team into a documentation sub-team and a robotics sub-team, individual members of the team did not undertake this rounded experience, instead specialising in a specific area. A recommendation could be that guidance is given by the organisers as to how large competition teams are, with larger teams only existing if the team is partaking in multiple competitions (such as Botball and Aerial). This was a conclusion that NTCH had come to themselves when planning their team for ECER 2019.

NTCH had a large amount of confidence as a team, not necessarily in the robots' performance, but in the experience of the competition itself. This was due in part from the experience that three of the team members had from the previous competition providing the team with learned tacit knowledge, and in part because of the team's relationship with the organisers through their school. NTCH were a strong example of a team who appeared to enjoy the competition for the experience and not just for how their robots performed. NTCH also interacted well with other teams, both taking inspiration from and helping others. A suggestion for future competitions could be that teams who have this more nurturing element, who are confident and don't carry negative emotion in competitiveness and rivalry and assigned a more official role in being a mentor to younger or newer teams. By creating more official links between the teams throughout the week and not just in the alliance round, the skills and behaviour of teams like NTCH could be more effectively used to support more vulnerable teams while they develop their own confidence and experience.

Finally, the results of this study will be compared to those of previous ECERs for the teams that consisted of some of the same members. This year's study focussed purely on how NTCH functioned as a team as a whole, whilst previous studies have focussed on how the team worked in a broader sense, exploring how they worked with their robots and areas such as the importance of gender. However, a number of conclusions can be made as to how the teams have changed and developed over the three years. The clearest change in 2018 was the

assignment of specific roles to team members. Whereas in previous years the teams have emphasised that all team members worked on all parts of the competition, including the documentation, NTCH saw a clear division of labour into specific roles. This may be due in part to the much larger team size in 2018, consisting of over twice as many team members as in previous years. The larger team size also resulted in a more definitive role of a leader – whilst previous years saw an officially titled leader but little actual leadership, NTCH required more coordination due to the division into sub-teams. Communication and interaction was also highlighted more than in previous years, again due to the size of the team. Some themes, however, continue to be present throughout the three years, such as the teams' inspiration for other teams at the competitions, which they then applied as a form of resilience to plan teams and goals for future competitions. Overall, NTCH and its predecessors have learnt and applied a considerable amount of knowledge concerning robotics, 21st century skills and the competition over the three year period.

10 APPENDIX B: ECER 2018 – ALLIANCE ROUND

10.1 CONTEXT

The Alliance round at ECER was a competition round for all teams that didn't reach the finals of Botball or PRIA Open, scoring less than the top four teams. In theory, the alliances were optional, but at ECER it was expected that all teams compete in it. The aims of the alliance round were twofold. Firstly, the competition organisers aimed to promote communication between teams that ordinarily would not encounter each other. In order to achieve this, teams were paired to form heterogeneous alliances - mixing up countries, competition type (Botball and PRIA Open) and mixing up teams that dropped out early with those who almost reached the finals. The second aim was to provide non-finalist teams with a purpose for the final two days of the competition, whilst the four finalist teams continued in the double elimination tournament. The Alliance round also created an opportunity for the non-finalist teams win trophies - specifically trophies that the finalists couldn't win. Therefore, even if there was a single dominating team overall, the Alliance trophy could be won by another team.

The rules for the alliance round taken from the Game Document were as follows:

“Alliance Logistics:

At selected tournaments, if a team is eliminated from the Double Elimination tournament before the Finals of Double Elimination play, then that team may sign up to play in Alliance Matches. Alliance Matches will pair up two teams to play the game collaboratively with the goal of scoring the most points. Each team will bring one robot to the table to run simultaneously. The teams will place their robots in any of the Starting Boxes (i.e. both on the same side or split between the two sides).

Alliance Scoring:

Alliance rounds will follow all of the same scoring rules as a regular Seeding round. The total Alliance score is (Your side's score) + (Ally side's score). The Alliance team with the highest combined score from a single run will win the Alliance Tournament. Alliance matches will be conducted until tournament officials suspend play (usually when the final Double Elimination rounds are near complete).”

Three out of the four teams that the researcher followed as focus groups during the competition week competed in the alliance round: NTCH, PV and VG. A breakdown of information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic, experience and alliance pairings of the three focus group teams

Team	Country	Alliance Partners	Team Members	Student Number	Gender	Age	Previous Experience at ECER
NTCH	Austria	Polish team – all younger males	Child 1	33193	Male	17	None
			Child 2	31048	Female	17	Attended previous two years
			Child 3	31007	Female	16	Attended previous two years
			Child 4	32251	Male	17	Attended the previous year
			Child 5	33158	Male	19	None
			Child 6	33157	Male	17	None
			Child 7	33151	Male	17	None
			Child 8	33155	Male	16	None
			Child 9	33169	Male	16	None
PV	Austria	Maltese team – all male	Child 1	31160	Male		Attended previous two years
			Child 2	31192	Male		Attended previous two years
			Child 3	31154	Female		Attended previous two years
			Child 4	31158	Male		None
			Child 5	31110	Male		Attended previous two years
VG	Bulgaria	Austrian team – all male	Child 1	23216	Female		Attend the previous year
			Child 2	23213	Male		Attend the previous year
			Child 3	23215	Male		Attend the previous year
			Child 4	23214	Male		Attend the previous year
			Child 5	23212	Male		Attend the previous year

For clarity in this report:

- A focus group will be referred to as ‘the team’ or their team name.
- The team assigned to work with a focus group during the Alliance round will be referred to as ‘the alliance partner’.
- The focus group and their alliance partner working together will be referred to as ‘the alliance partnership’.

10.2 DATA ANALYSIS

The Alliance round of the competition emerged intrinsically as an interesting phenomena during the data analysis for the NTCH report. Therefore, all data collected for the three teams out of the four focus groups who competed in the Alliance round was openly coded. This data included observational notes, video data collected

by the teams, interviews with the teams, and pre and post-competition questionnaires. Emergent themes were then structured into categories and sub-categories.

10.3 FINDINGS

This study focuses on how the teams NTCH, PV and VG functioned during the Alliance round of the ECER competition. In particular, the data analysis focussed on how successfully the Alliance round aims were met and how the teams and the alliance partnerships behaved during it. This section presents the findings of the data analysis, with categories acting as sub-sections: 'Forming an Alliance', 'Workload During The Alliance', and 'Opinion of The Alliance'. For each category, a visual representation of the relationship between it and any sub-categories are provided. Furthermore, codes within categories are shown in **bold**.

10.3.1 Forming an Alliance

As touched on in the NTCH report, during the Alliance round teams formed an extended team with their alliance partners as they worked together towards a common goal. As the teams and the alliance partners were already formed and had been working separately for the rest of the week prior to the round, this alliance partnership revealed interesting interactions between the two teams. Therefore, this section explores how the teams and alliance partners in each of the three alliance partnerships interacted and how well they worked as an extended team. This is discussed in terms of their 'Physical Location', 'Communication' in the alliance partnership and the 'Sense of Team' within the teams and between the alliance partnership. This is visualised in Figure 1. Overall, it was found that communication correlated to the physical location of the alliance partnership and so this link is shown in Figure 1 by a connecting line.

Figure 1. Representation of 'Forming an Alliance' Category

10.3.1.1 PHYSICAL LOCATION

The physical locations, or indeed the differences in physical locations, of the members from the teams and in the alliance partners were particularly noticeable during observation. Each of the alliance partnerships operated differently in their physical locations - these are discussed in terms of the location of the competitors in the pit area, the location of the competitors whilst at the test table and the location of the robots on the competition table.

When not testing their robots, the alliance teams worked in the pit area, at their assigned worktables. When the Alliance round began, team VG made a change in their **physical location whilst working**, leaving their own

worktable to relocate to their alliance partner's table, as is shown in Figure 2. VG used this as a base for the remainder of the round, sharing the space with their alliance partner.

Figure 2. VG work at their alliance partner's table

Team PV also moved their working base during the Alliance round, from their assigned BotBall Competition working table in the centre of the room, to **working on the floor** next to their Aerial Competition table at the edge of the room. PV Child 1 (m), 2 (m) and 5 (m) completed work on the robot in this new space, which created a **physical distance** from Child 3 (f) and Child 4 (m) who stayed at the original PV table or watched the competition. It appears that this move to the floor was made in order to have more space to work on their robot as they rebuilt it, as opposed to being physically closer to their alliance partners. In fact, PV were observed to remain physically distanced from their alliance partners during their time working on their robot, with only two observed moments in which the two were seen together, both of which consisted of a member of their alliance partner team briefly moving to their area to communicate with them. The distance between members of PV and their alliance partner is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Physical distance within PV team and with their alliance partners

NTCH remained in their same working areas during the Alliance round. However, Child 4 (m), who was working most closely with their alliance partners, physically left NTCH and spent the majority of his time at their alliance

partner's table. The two teams **physically came together** as a whole less often, although Figure 4 shows an observed moment in which the alliance partners came to NTCH's table to borrow robot parts, then continuing to work there for approximately ten minutes.

Figure 4. Alliance partners briefly work at NTCH's table

As well as observing differences in the distances between individuals whilst working during the alliance, the physical location of team members was also notable whilst teams were at the competition table, both during scheduled practice and in the official rounds of the competition. Each team would stand with their own team members while the alliance partners would **stand separately** within their own team. To put more simply, there was no mixing of the two teams in their physical location whilst at the competition table. The only exception to this was **Child 4 (m) in NTCH**, who would stand apart from his own team and locate himself instead with the alliance partners, as is shown in Figure 5. Child 4 worked closely with the alliance partners (further in 2.1.2 Communication) and this may have influenced his positioning at the competition table.

Figure 5. Child 4 positions himself with alliance partners at competition table

The physical location of the team members at the competition table related to the physical location of the team's robots on the competition table during the Alliance round. The rules for the Alliance round state that the each team in the partnership must use one robot, which may start on any of the four starting boxes on the table. All partnerships chose to place their robots on **opposite sides of the table** rather than working on the **same side**. This meant that the alliance partnerships didn't necessarily work well as an extended team, as they

could simply work separately on their own sides of the competition table and not interfere with each other's robots. This leads well into the following subcategory, communication.

10.3.1.2 COMMUNICATION

Communication is an important element of teamwork, and emerged as a significant theme throughout the competition, including the Alliance round. This subsection is structured by exploring how each team used, or struggled with, communication with their alliance partners. As an aim of the Alliance round was to promote communication between teams, it is highlighted that **language barriers** and the **physical location of the robot** on the competition table had a large role to play in the amount of communication and overall teamwork in the alliances partnerships.

Firstly, we will explore the communication that occurred between NTCH and their alliance partners. As has already been stated, Child 4 (m) worked closely with the alliance partners. This was by no accident, their alliance partners had poor English, but Child 4 was fluent in their native language of Polish. The importance of Child 4's **tacit language skill** was revealed in the final interview with NTCH:

- “Interviewer: Ok so, talking about that, with you working with the alliances, with your language barrier. So how did you guys find that?”*
- Child 1: We had a door*
- Child 2: We had a door*
- Child 1: Child 4*
- Interviewer: Very useful, yeah, so that was quite lucky wasn't it*
- Child 4: Yeah it was quite lucky*
- Interviewer: Yeah? I mean if they hadn't had you they might have found it a bit harder?*
- Child 3: Yes. Because I was trying to explain to them and it was really difficult to explain, I was like showing and they still didn't know what I was talking about”*

This extract highlights the difficulty of a **language barrier** within an alliance partnership. According to the competition organisers, the Polish team being paired with NTCH and Child 4 was a case of 'luck' and had not been planned based on his skill. As discussed in the NTCH report, Child 4 was given a new role because of the **language barrier** to communication in the alliance partnership, which he explained to the researcher: *“I'm now like overseeing the Polish kids now... I give them tips so they can improve the robot”*. Overall, NTCH appeared to have **good communication** with their alliance partner, but it was implied that this would not have been the case had Child 4 not been there.

Team PV was paired with a Maltese team and did not face any **language barrier** as both teams could adequately speak English. However, PV were observed to **lack of communication** with the alliance partners, which they admitted to the researcher:

- “Interviewer: So how are you co-ordinating with your other team, [the alliance?]*
- Child 2 (m): [Er we're both () (decide er) not co-ordinating with them.*
- Interviewer: Okay.*
- Child 2 (m): Yeah.*
- Interviewer: So you're just trying to get as many er points as possible?”*

PV later explained that they viewed '**coordinating**' with their alliance partners as unnecessary, as the team's robots were located on **opposite sides of the competition table** and so they did not need to coordinate how

their robots were programmed. Furthermore, it was observed that while the teams of the alliance partnership were at the competition table, they stood on opposite sides and showed no evidence of communication. This is a direct example of how the **physical location of the robots** on the test table reduced the amount of communication in the alliance partnership, therefore meaning the Alliance round aims were not well met. On the other hand, PV also stated that they did communicate with their team to “*help them with technical stuff*” (Child 5 (m)).

Finally, team VG also showed evidence for the effects that a **language barrier** and **physical location of the robot** can have on communication in an alliance partnership. VG were paired with an Austrian team and it was observed that they had the most alliance partnership communication out of the three focus teams. There were also two further observations made regarding this communication. Firstly, although VG and the alliance partners would communicate in the medium of English when talking between the two teams, they would both quickly revert back to communicating in their native languages when talking within their original teams rather than within the alliance partnership. This was likely because it was easier for them to use their first language, as the VG team members admitted to the researcher that they weren’t confident in their English. However, this meant that the two teams were unable to understand each other unless they were specifically directing communication at the other. Secondly, the alliance partnership appeared to believe at the beginning of the Alliance round that their two robots had to be physically located on the **same side of the competition table** when competing. During this period, they were evidenced to communicate a lot whilst at the competition table practicing, discussing how they could coordinate their robots: “*Will our robot interfere with yours?... It is important not to move this cube*”. A screenshot of the observational video from which this quote was taken is shown in Figure 6. However, once the teams realised that their robots could compete on opposite sides of the table, the level of **communication decreased** dramatically. The teams stood on their opposite sides and were observed to only give each other a thumbs up gesture when they were ready to start, but no other form of communication. This is clear evidence of the impact that the **physical location of the robot** on the competition table can make on communication in the alliance partnership and during the Alliance round overall.

Figure 6. VG communicate with alliance partners at competition table

10.3.1.3 SENSE OF TEAM

During the competition, each team developed a clear sense of self within their group. During the Alliance round this was then challenged as they are encouraged to extend their sense of self to form an alliance partnership. This subsection explores in what ways the teams had a sense of self, also comparing this with examples of where teams had a clear sense of ‘other’ which was portrayed through **competitiveness** and **rivalry**. Finally the subsection concludes by exploring to what extent, and how the teams extended their sense of self to include their alliance partners.

The three focus groups each gave evidence for having a sense of their team – a sense of commonality within the group that made them different and separate from the other teams at the competition. For example, VG arrived at the competition with a **Bulgarian flag** that they placed at their work table, noting that they were representing their country as the only Bulgarian team there. Team PV extended their sense of self further than just their own team, but to include other teams who attended the **same school** as them. They were often observed communicating with members from these teams, and Child 1(m) stated during an interview that they collaborated strategically with them: *“we’re just sharing information about the other teams”*. Furthermore, PV also explained that they had a sense of **rivalry** with the **Austrian teams** that were not from their school and were particularly **competitive** against them compared to the teams from other countries:

- “Child 3 (f): And and I think it’s a little competition between the Austrian teams for example the
[()] so
Interviewer: [Hmm, because there are a lot of Austrian teams.
Child 5 (m): [Yeah.
Child 3 (f): [Yeah and we want er er we want er to be better than ().
Interviewer: Okay.
Child 3 (f): [()
Interviewer: [So there’s a bit of rivalry there?
Child 3 (f): Yeah.”*

This **rivalry** and sense of other proved to be in some ways detrimental – in the final interview PV were clearly upset and one team member even refused to take part in the interview due to his emotion, as they were angry that a rival Austrian team had performed well. During the Alliance round, Austrian teams (as the country with the most attendees at the competition) were mostly paired with non-Austrian teams, so there was therefore no attempt from the competition organisers to intervene in this rivalry as the Austrians are given no chance to extend their sense of team to Austrians from other schools.

There were examples observed of the teams extending their sense of self to include their alliance partners. For example, VG took their **Bulgarian flag** with them to their alliance partner’s table when they began working there, as shown in Figure 7. This created a statement that they were still representing their country, but they were now together in an alliance partnership. Furthermore, the teams all referred to **helping their alliance team** in some way, and there was evidence of teamwork between the teams which Child 4 NTCH (m) summarised well: *“I was helping them, because they are our alliance partner we are like one alliance team so we can just help them”*.

Figure 7. VG have their Bulgarian flag on alliance partners work table

There was some evidence that the two teams still viewed themselves as separate, for example by still being most **proud of their own robot** and their own work. However, there was also evidence that they had **pride** for their alliance partners, as shown in Figure 8 when VG congratulated their alliance partners on their robot working successfully with a high five, smiling and saying “*great job boys*”. Overall, it was observed that those teams who communicated more with their alliance partners and had a closer physical location seemed to include their alliance partners more in their sense of self as a team.

Figure 8. VG congratulate their alliance partners on their robot's success

10.3.2 Workload During The Alliance

Compared to the previous days in the competition, during the seeding and the double elimination rounds, there was a considerable change in the workload of tasks for the teams in the Alliance round. This category explores the two elements to this change in workload as subcategories – the fact that the team's reduced from using two robots each to one, meaning there was 'less work available', and the fact that there was considerably 'more time available' to prepare and practice for the Alliance than the other competition rounds. These subcategories are visually represented in Figure 9. How this change in workload affected the teams' work and behaviour is explored throughout.

Figure 9. Representation of 'Workload During The Alliance' category

10.3.2.1 LESS WORK AVAILABLE

This subsection explores the impact that reducing to **one robot** per team during the alliance round had on the roles within the team and the behaviour of the team members. During the seeding and double elimination rounds of the competition, each team had two robots that they used on the competition table to score points. NTCH explained that it was most effective if only a few people work on a robot a one time, but that this can result in a lack of work for some team members: *"it's an issue, because it's like two robots and you can't have like four or five people working on one robot"* (Child 3 (f)). However, during the Alliance round, two robots were used in the alliance partnership, meaning that each team chose **one robot** to continue working with and one robot to stop working with. This resulted in **less work** overall for the team, as there was half the amount of robot-based work. Furthermore, as it was later on in the week, much of the documentation-based work, such as presentations, had been completed. This lack of work for some team members resulted in a **change of roles** or a change of behaviour in those members. For example on the first day of the Alliance round, only two members of VG remained at the competition, whilst the other three members took a day trip to a tourist area. Child 1 (f), who **left the competition for the day**, explained that she checked if there was any work they could complete before they left: *"... we asked them if they need some help with something and they said no you can go free... so actually we asked them, we they said no and everything okay... moments like that they just don't need us"*. In NTCH and PV it was observed that the lack of work to complete resulted in some team members socialising with the competition volunteers, **watching more of the other teams competing**, or reading books and completing school work (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Member of NTCH reads a book as he has no competition work to complete

10.3.2.2 MORE TIME AVAILABLE

As well as there being fewer tasks to complete during the Alliance round, there was also considerably **more practice time** in comparison to the rest of the competition. Whilst the teams had been officially competing multiple times each day previously in the week, the Alliance round provided the whole of the Thursday to alter and practice with their robots. As Child 1 (m) from NTCH stated: “[It] *wasn’t stressful at all because there was only practice.*” However, as well as creating a less stressful experience during the Alliance round, for both PV and NTCH the extra time encouraged them to take more **risks** with their robots. For NTCH, the extra time meant they considered taking a risk to complete the harder tasks on the competition table as they had **more time to prepare**:

“Child 3: ... we’re not sure whether now to do the poms just shoving in one direction.
 ...
 Child 3: Or if we [er
 Child 1: [Want to pick up one of those cubes.
 ...
 Child 1: Like today’s only practice so it’s (easy) ().
 ...
 Child 1: We have to decide whether it’s worth
 Child 3: The risk
 ...
 Interviewer: Interesting. So you’re deciding whether to take the risk then?”

This was a risk that they had not considered taking earlier in the week and in the extract Child 1 clearly states that they considered the risk due to the extended time that they had. For PV, the team took this risk-taking a step further by building an entirely **new robot** for the Alliance round. The majority of the team’s time during the Alliance round was spent building this robot, as is shown in Figure 11. Again, PV claimed that the extended time was their reasoning for taking a risk with their robot:

“Interviewer: Wow. But you’ve got quite a lot of time don’t you cos it’s all today in practice.
 Child 1 (m): Yeah.

Interviewer: *So that's good.*
 Child 2 (m): *That's why we are doing it."*

Figure 11. PV build a new robot from scratch

10.3.3 Opinion of The Alliance

Whilst both NTCH and VG gave evidence that they enjoyed the Alliance round of the competition, PV explicitly stated that they did not enjoy it. This section explores the differences between the teams' experiences in the competition and where this was evidenced to impact upon their opinion of the alliance round. The section is divided into the subsections 'positive experience' and 'negative experience', as is shown in Figure 12, to directly contrast the teams' experiences and the role that their emotions played in their opinion of the competition.

Figure 12. Representation of 'Opinion of The Alliance' category

1.1.1.1 ENJOYMENT

NTCH made a clear statement during an interview that the Alliance round was more **enjoyable** due the team being **less stressed** as there were no official competition rounds on the entirety of Thursday, which links to the concepts in Section 2.2.2 More Time Available. Furthermore, NTCH explained in their final interview that **performing well** in the Alliance round made the it enjoyable, and they highlighted their performance when explaining that they had **fun** at the competition:

“Child 3 (f): Well the seeding went, [the seeding didn’t go well]
 Child 4 (m): [It was better than last year
 Child 3: But the double elimination and alliance did.
 Interviewer: So some good some bad”

However, for VG the enjoyment of the Alliance round came from the relationship that they had built with their alliance partners. During their final interview the team explained that the **friendliness** within their alliance partnership meant that they enjoyed extending their team to work with their partners:

“Child 1 (f): With another team, and er yeah it was cool. We don’t have a problem with that, we we love to work with other teams.
 ...
 Child 2 (m): They were very friendly too, yeah.
 ...
 Child 3 (m): It was very friendly and, I don’t know, the things just [yeah
 Child 1 (f): [They were just er prepared and everything went good with them. We we were really happy to be with them in a team alliance.”

For VG, the relationship that they had built with the alliance partners meant that they were not just happy with the **success** of their own robot, but also with that of the alliance partners’. Whilst they had this extended sense of **pride**, VG also took **inspiration** from their alliance partners, with Child 1 (f) explaining: “their robot was interesting because one of the things we couldn’t do”, which they stated would influence how they built their robot for the next year’s competition. VG also mentioned feeling many **positive emotions**, using words like “love” and “happy” when talking about both the Alliance round and the competition in general.

10.3.3.1 DISLIKE

Out of the three focus teams, PV was the only team to state or even imply that they did **not enjoy** the Alliance round. As explained in Section 2.2.2 More Time Available, PV built a new robot for the Alliance round, and it was this robot’s underperformance that they claimed made the Alliance unenjoyable:

“Interviewer: Did you enjoy the alliance once you got into it or
 Child 5 (m): [No.
 Interviewer: [No?
 Child 3 (f): None of is
 Child 1 (m): We tried to build this robot but it failed completely I think.
 Child 5 (m): [Yeah.
 Interviewer: [So was that why you didn’t enjoy it because it didn’t work, or was it another reason that you didn’t enjoy it?
 Child 1 (m): I think basically because the robot didn’t work.”

PV as a team were very competitive throughout the competition, but equally didn't perform as well as they had hoped, or as well as they had done in previous years. This sense of **failure** had a large impact on creating **negative emotions** within the team members, which they then portrayed as a **negative attitude towards the competition** itself. This **frustration** led to them delivering some harsh critiques of the competition during their final interview, and explaining that they did not want to return again in the future.

A common overarching problem for some of the teams, including those who weren't focus groups, regarding the enjoyment of the Alliance round was the concept that they were only in the Alliance because they had **failed** to reach the finals of the double elimination. For the more competitive teams such a PV, failure to reach their goals meant they saw the Alliance round as not a real part of the competition and so they were **unmotivated**. NTCH stated that this was a problem that they also experienced with their alliance partner:

“Child 4 (m): I think often with the alliances the teams aren't that motivated, so these guys weren't motivated they needed our push
Interviewer: Oh I see, so it was you encouraging them?
Child 4: Yeah”

The competition organisers explained to the researcher that technically the Alliance round is optional to partake in, but that at ECER it is expected that all teams do. However, when some teams who are more emotionally involved and competitive in the rest of the competition are forced to take part in an Alliance round, it appeared that there needed to be a method of making them more motivated to take it seriously in order for the Alliance round to meet its aims more effectively.

10.4 DISCUSSION

As was stated in Section 1. Context, the aims of the alliance round were to encourage communication between teams who would not usually necessarily come into contact with each other, and to provide a purpose during the last two days of the competition for those who had not qualified for the double elimination finals. This study has focussed on how well the aims of the alliance round were met within three focus group teams during ECER 2018. In this discussion, a series of recommendations are made to improve how well these aims are met in the future, based on the evidence provided in Section 2. Findings.

Firstly, it has been evidenced that levels of communication varied between alliance partners, with further evidence that physical location of the robots on the competition table and of the team members themselves impacted on this communication. Strong evidence through the behaviour of team VG shows that the alliance partners communicated more when their robots were starting on the same side of the competition table. Competing on the same side of the table meant that they had to alter the programming of their robots so that they would not interfere with the other. This coordination resulted in more testing, more discussion and better teamwork between the two groups. By allowing alliances to compete on opposite sides of the table, there is little need to alter the robots' programming and even less need to coordinate with the other team, as PV stated. Therefore, to increase the amount of communication between the two teams, it is recommended that the rules of the alliance round are altered so that teams' robots must start on the same side of the competition table.

Recommendation 1: Alliance partners should work with their robots on the same side of the competition table.

For alliance teams to communicate at the competition, they had to be physically located close to each other. The team who appeared to communicate the most with their alliance partner was Team VG, who relocated their working area to share the pit area table of their alliance partners. This was only feasible because half of the VG team left the competition for the duration of the Thursday, meaning there was room for two remaining members to join at the alliance partner table. Other teams had to move to their alliance partners when they wanted to communicate, which resulted in less discussion taking place. As the alliance pairings were decided on the Wednesday afternoon, prior to the start of the alliance round on the Thursday morning, it is recommended for the future that the layout of the pit area be redistributed so that the teams are based at a new table on the Thursday morning. This would enable the competition organisers to position alliance partners' new working tables next to each other, which would encourage more communication between teams whilst working and would foster the teams to extend their sense of self to include their alliance partners within their team.

Recommendation 2: Pit area working tables should be redistributed on the Thursday morning.

Although the alliance round provided a purpose for the teams that did not qualify for the finals of the double elimination, the reduction to using one robot per team meant that this purpose did not provide a role for all team members, particularly in the larger teams. This reduction in workload could be countered by ensuring the teams still use both of their robots. As realistically, only a few people can work on a robot at one time, adding the second robot would simply provide work for those team members who lacked roles during the alliance round, creating more work for the team overall but not for the team members who were working on the original robot. Furthermore, combining this recommendation with Recommendation 1 (Alliance partners should work with their robots on the same side of the competition table) would result in the alliance partners both having team members and robots on both sides of the table, meaning more communication would need to take place concerning strategy and programming. This recommendation would therefore help improve how both alliance round aims are met by increasing communication and providing a purpose for more of the team.

Recommendation 3: Teams should continue to use two robots during the alliance round.

The final recommendation is based on the problem of rivalry within Austrian teams from different schools. A main reason for PV not enjoying the alliance round was the negative emotions that they had built up regarding the competition. Whilst some of these negative emotions were based on underperforming personally, some were based on comparing themselves to teams against whom who they had become rivals. However, the alliance round could be used as a tool for increasing the amount of good sportsmanship between teams who have developed a sense of rivalry. By pairing rival Austrian teams, there would be a chance for heightened communication between the teams, which may be a more positive outcome than pairing an Austrian team with a non-Austrian team. This may also result in teams such as PV enjoying the competition as negative emotions are released. However, pairing the alliance as such may also result in more hostility between the teams, bringing the bad sportsmanship into the alliance round in a way that would not occur if the pairings were more heterogeneous. Therefore, this recommendation is made lightly and flexibly, and would be subject to the

opinions of the competition organisers each year depending on the dynamics between the teams during that time.

Recommendation 4: If appropriate, teams from Austria can be paired in the alliance round.

Overall, the alliance round was successful in bringing together different teams and providing a purpose for these teams. Therefore, the aims of the alliance round were in some way met. However, vast improvements could be made, by encouraging more communication, effective teamwork and providing more work for the teams. The four recommendations made would create these changes, encouraging this behaviour within teams without directly instructing them to act a certain way.

11 APPENDIX C: ECER 2016-2018 PAPERS

This section details each of the papers presented at ECER, identifying those which address a real-world societal problem. For those that do, a summary of the paper is provided.

11.1 ECER 2016

Title	Real-life problem?	Summary
3D Printer Prusa i3	no	
3D Printing - Advancing Industry One Layer at a Time	no	
A Study of the Botball Kit and Suggestions for Improvement	no	
Botball Party	no	
BotWeb - RoboChat	no	
Evaluation of improving parts for a gripper	no	
fI0w - a Workflow Optimisation Tool	no	
Genetic algorithms for Botball applications	no	
Hacking the Wallaby	no	
Improving Botball	no	
LIDAR Sensors: Advanced Sensor Usage in Botball - A Concept	no	
Machine Learning for BotBall	no	
Making Robotics - Making software easier	no	
Mechanical jigs and fixtures – Solutions for more reliability and accuracy	no	
Our world view	no	
Organizing a Botball Event	no	
Photovoltaic plants – Energy to Infinity	yes	Discussion of photovoltaic power plants and the needs of energy in the near future. Also economic factors (e.g. amortization) are discussed.
Remote Monitoring and Controlling of Robotic Systems with MissionControl	no	
Robot – Programming, Assembling and Implementation of Ideas	no	
Sensors in Engineering	no	
Usage of sensors in Botball	no	

11.2 ECER 2017

Title	Real-life problem?	Summary
Botball Revolution - Print your own Parts	no	
Component limits – Evaluations on sensor reliability and overall accuracy	no	
fIOW - a development environment for the KIPR Wallaby	no	
How robots will revolutionize agriculture	yes	Most conventional farming is done by using pesticides a genetically modified plants that grow faster and more resistant. But this kind of farming is getting more difficult since the use of pesticides are banned. Special weeding-robots can help by removing the weeds.
Mathematics tools in GeoGebra for enabling interaction between students, concepts and the real world	no	
MissionEDU - Expanding Educational Robotics	no	
Programming Languages in Botball	no	
Referencing your robot on the gameboard	no	
Rethinking Automated Farming - An Arm to Fit Them All	no	
Robotics for Sustainable Agriculture	yes	This article gives an idea of the usefulness of robotics in agriculture nowadays, considering the possibilities for its future application and implementation. The project aims to achieve an agrarian revolution, relying on modern, greener and more efficient methods of cultivation.
Robotics for Sustainable Agriculture in Aquaponics	yes	Due to the increase of the world's population farms have to use steroids and fertilizers. Aquaponics combined with robotics could be the solution. The planned robot is waterproofed, has a carbon dioxide pump, oxygen pump, biofilter, and pH indicator.
Safety Measurements and Quality Issues in Botball	no	
Sensor based one-way communication in multiple mobile robot systems: an experiment	no	
Software implementation	no	
Team Project Open Botball Paper	no	
The KIPR Wallaby/Link in comparison to the Hedgehog	no	
The Use of Hydroponic Robots to Promote Sustainable Agriculture	yes	Hydroponics allows plants to grow without soil which could reduce starvation. This method could take agriculture to the next level by increasing the efficiency with hydroponic robots.
Path Planning and Finding the Robot Location Algorithms	no	

11.3 ECER 2018

Title	Real-life problem?	Summary
A comparative study of using colour sensors and Raspberry Pi camera to track colour detection	no	
A new concept in lifting technology	no	
Application of ET sensor	no	
Comparison of old and new KIPR Sensors	no	
Computer Vision in Botball - Potential & Limits	no	
Exploring the Wallaby	no	
Hedgehog vs Wallaby - Pros and Cons	no	
Mass Distribution of Moving Robots: an Experiment	no	
May the ocean be with you! Botball & Environment	yes	To work on innovative ideas to save the earth should be one of the major tasks of robotics competitions. The Team Talentehaus modified PRIAs underwater robot "Shark" to motivate young people to think about water pollution
Robotics in Medicine	yes	Robots are used for solving a lot of everyday problems. A specific field in which robots should be used more is medicine because people are getting older and older.
Sound on the iRobot Create	no	
The impact of Botball on Team Building	no	
The use of closed-loop control systems in Botball	no	

12 APPENDIX D: GREEK WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

12.1 CONTEXT

Workshop: UoA 432 - Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine

12.1.1 Description of the Activity

In this workshop students create physical models of temporary houses simulating the practices of professionals who design and build containers. Firstly students design virtual models of houses using a digital tool, then they create a robot similar to the real machine (Figure 1) which cuts solids' nets and finally they program their robot to draw cubes and other solids' nets on the paper. These drawings are cut and tiled in order to create physical models of container houses. In the end these models are placed on a maquette (a small 3D model) of a camp which is supposed to host people who have had their houses damaged due to a physical disaster.

Figure 58: The real CNC cutter on the left and the CNC Drawing machine on the right

The activity plan had the following objectives:

Subject related

- Develop spatial skills like spatial orientation and spatial visualization.
- Study solids' nets, 2d and 3d shapes properties fostered by their spatial skills.

Technology use related

- Programming with Logo and LEGO NXT MINDSTORMS programming environment

Social and action related

- Develop collaborative skills
- Take roles within groups
- Communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture

- Argue about what a camp needs, therefore what solids they need to create and for what reasons.

- Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there.
- Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses.
- Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models.
- Make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

The workshop was implemented in the 2nd public primary School of Kaisariani, Athens, Greece and the participants were 18 11year old students who attended the 6th grade. There were 10 boys and 8 girls. There were two 2-hour sessions and one 3-hour session.

Students worked in four groups of 4-5. Two groups were mixed gender, one group consisted of boys and the fourth group consisted of girls. During the workshop they were engaged in collaborative relationships, taking emergent roles in the group which were exchanged most of the time. They were encouraged to discuss, exchange and negotiate their ideas through dialogue. The tutor Support by the tutor intervened, monitoring and facilitating teams’ work when needed.

12.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

12.2.1 Data Collection

Data was collected through pre and post-questionnaires which were given to the students to answer before and after the workshop accordingly. 14 students answered the pre-questionnaire and 17 students answered the post-questionnaire. There were video recordings from the whole class and for the focus group in particular. Focus group consisted of four girls, only one of which had a little previous experience with robotics. After the workshop the students of the focus group were interviewed about their experience. Data collection also included notes from tutors’ observations and reflections.

12.2.2 Data Analysis

Data analysis for this particular workshop focused on:

- Girls’ interest in STEM
- Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM
- Evidence of learning

12.3 FINDINGS

This section includes findings about research questions concerning:

- Girls interest in STEM
- Changing Attitudes
- Evidence of learning

12.3.1 Girls’ interest in STEM

This section focuses on the issue of girls' interest in STEM topics and future careers. The data used for the analysis include the pre and post-questionnaires given to the students before and after the workshop accordingly and students' responses to the interview which followed the end of the workshop. Concerning their interest in STEM, their answers on their opinions about the skills and characteristics of the best scientist and their interest in science, maths and technology before and after the workshop were used, compared to their answers in the post-questionnaires about the job they would like to do in the future, their attitudes about the challenges they dealt with during the workshop, their interest about how things work and STEM subjects.

12.3.1.1 QUESTIONNAIRES

12.3.1.1.1 PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

In the pre-questionnaire only 1 out of 8 girls answered that she wants to follow a STEM career in the future as she wants to be a mathematician (43202). On the other hand, 4 out of 8 boys who answered the pre-questionnaire choose STEM careers: doctor, mechanic, scientist, and architect.

2 of the girls had built a robot before and 4 of them had previous experience of programming. All girls answered "I strongly agree" in the question "I like using the computer". When asked if they know about robots, 5 girls answered that they "disagree" and 3 of the girls answered "I don't agree nor disagree".

When asked about their favourite and least favourite subject, 6 out of 8 girls mention STEM subjects as their favorite. More precisely, 2 girls mentioned mathematics, 2 girls mentioned ICT, 1 girl choose both science and math and 1 girl chose both math and ICT. On the other-hand 1 of the girls included mathematics and 2 of them included physics as their least favourite subject. When asked to justify their answers 43209 and 43203 mention they chose science as their least favourite subject *"because we are not doing experiments"*.

As far as it concerns science most of the girls claim to like the subject as 3 of them "agree" and 2 of them "agree very much". Only one of the girls answered "disagree". On the other-hand only 3 boys answer positively in the question. Only 2 girls find science easy and 4 find it boring. Only 2 girls have fun in science classes. All girls agree on science being important as only one of them disagrees on the testament. Out of 8, 6 students answer positively when asked if they are good at science. Although only one girl answers positively when asked whether she would study science in the future.

Concerning math, 5 girls like mathematics and 3 answer "I don't agree nor disagree" on the question. Only 3 girls think that math is easy but only one has fun in math lessons. 2 girls think math is boring. All girls believe that math is important and think they are good at the subject. Finally, 3 girls would like to study math when they grow up.

When asked whether they liked using computers all girls answered positively. Out of 8 girls, 5 of them liked problem solving.

12.3.1.1.2 POST-QUESTIONNAIRE

After the workshop a post-questionnaire was given to the students in order to evaluate their experience. 7 girls answered the post-questionnaire. 6 girls found the problems that they were called to solve interesting and had fun during the workshop, while 2 of them answered "I don't agree nor disagree" in these questions and found the problems given difficult. These 2 answered neutrally when asked whether working with the robot was interesting and fun.

Concerning their participation all girls claimed they were engaged in programming and only 2 of them answered negatively when asked whether they constructed a robot during the workshop. When asked whether they abandoned the effort easily all girls answered negatively and only 2 girls were bored.

All girls answered they would like to engage in more challenges like this. Only 2 out of 7 girls answered negatively when asked whether they were interested in how things work. On the other hand 4 out of 7 mentioned they like mechanics. 1 student gave 4 stars to the workshop and all others rated their experience with 5 stars. Some of girls' comments were:

43202: *"Robots and the work done was amazing"*

43204: *"Working with robots is hard but interesting and fun"*

12.3.1.1.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Analysis of the data shows that the girls in this case have mostly positive attitudes about STEM subjects as 6 out of 8 girls mention as their favorite a STEM subject. Moreover it seems that girls also have positive attitudes toward their abilities in STEM subjects and think they are good at them. Although girls admit that these subjects are important and they have positive attitudes about their abilities, STEM future careers are not so popular among girls, as only one of them mentions she wants to follow a STEM career in the pre-questionnaire.

Relevant research also supports that "despite similar math achievement test scores for girls and boys, fewer girls choose to pursue math coursework or quantitative career paths" (Gunderson et. al., 2012). This phenomenon has been linked to factors such as individual agency as well as surrounding social systems, such as family, peers, teachers, and school systems (Brickhouse, Lowery, & Schultz, 2000). Brickhouse et al., (2000) claim that messages about the incompatibility of STEM success with female gender roles may lead girls and women to perceive science as alienating and inconsistent with their gender image expectations. As a consequence females may carry beliefs which indicate that it will not be possible to combine a particular career with a fulfilling personal life (Stake and Mares 2001), child bearing and rearing with her career (Lupart et al.2004).

12.3.2 Changing attitudes

By questionnaires and interview data analysis, it seemed that there were students who changed their attitudes concerning STEM careers and subjects.

12.3.2.1 QUESTIONNAIRES

12.3.2.1.1 FUTURE CAREERS

As far as it concerns students' future careers, only one of the girls (43204) changed her answer on what profession she would like to enter when she grows up. In the pre-questionnaire she said she wanted to be an arts teacher but after the workshop she noted she would like to be a topographer or a mechanic.

12.3.2.1.2 SCIENCE

Out of 7 girls who answered the post-questionnaire, 2 would like to further study sciences. The 2 students who answered that they don't like science in the pre-questionnaire sustain their attitude. 43202, while in the pre-

questionnaire agreed that science is boring, in the post-questionnaire answered positively when asked whether she would like to study further science. Also, another student 43204 who answered “I don’t agree nor disagree” when asked whether they liked science, in the post-questionnaire answered positively in the same question.

12.3.2.1.3 MATHEMATICS

Concerning math, 4 girls chose the subject as their favourite and 1 chose it as her less favourite. In the post-questionnaire the same girl answered she didn’t like math. Moreover, girl 43202, while in pre-questionnaire answered she found math boring, after the workshop answered she liked the subject. Finally, 43203 seemed to strengthen her attitude towards her abilities in mathematics as she answered neutrally when asked whether she was good at math, in the post-questionnaire answered positively in the same question. Out of 4 girls who answered that they didn’t have fun in math classes, 2 of them answered positively in the post-questionnaire when asked whether they liked math.

12.3.2.1.4 ICT

2 out of 8 girls answered in the post-questionnaire that they didn’t like using the computer and they didn’t want to know more about programming while in the pre-questionnaire they were positive as far as it concerned the use of the computer. Both answered in the post-questionnaire that they found it difficult to work as a team and one of them 43203 thought that working with the robot was difficult and that she got bored during the workshop.

12.3.2.1.5 Problem solving

43213 in the pre-questionnaire answered “I don’t agree nor disagree” as far as it concerned whether she liked problem solving and agreed that she needed help when it comes to solve a problem. However, in the post-questionnaire she says that the problems she dealt with during the workshop were interesting and fun and she is positive in dealing with similar challenges in the future.

12.3.2.2 INTERVIEWS

After the workshop, focus group was called to answer some questions and describe their experiences. When girls were asked about the most challenging task during the workshop 43203 and 43202 answer:

43202: *“The most difficult part was to program the robot.”*

43203: *“I would say it was programming but building the robot also.”*

When asked what they had learnt from the workshop girls answered:

43203: *“That we are capable of building a robot.”*

Concerning the characteristics of a good scientist 43210 and 43203 mentioned patience and persistence. 43203 added the ability of collaboration.

When asked whether their experience changed their attitudes 43210 says: “Now I think we have more confidence than before because finally we made it”. Moreover 43202 says: “we must not have doubts about

ourselves”. Finally girls added that they would like to repeat the workshop and agreed that robotics could help in increasing students’ interest in sciences.

12.3.2.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

It seems that workshop activities had a positive impact on some girls’ attitudes as 2 of them change their attitude positively towards physics, 3 of them appear to develop a positive attitude on whether they had fun during math lessons. Out of 7 girls who answered the questionnaire, 6 rated with 5 stars and one rated it with 4. Most of the girls 6 out of 8 found the workshop interesting and fun and all girls would like to deal with more challenges like this in the future.

While after the workshop some girls changed their attitudes positively towards STEM subjects, it seems to be difficult to change their attitude about a possible STEM careers, as only one of the girls adds a STEM profession to her preferences about her future career in the post-questionnaire. Although girls answered they would like to engage in more challenges like this and rated the workshop positively, they would not wish to study them further in the future.

12.3.3 Evidence of learning

This section refers to evidence of learning that took place during the activities of the workshop. Evidence of learning was expressed indirectly, through discussions and reflections of the students, and directly through students’ artefacts and programs. As indirect methods, descriptions of critical episodes during which students’ statements and descriptions were relevant to the activity plan’s subject objectives were used. As direct methods, students’ concrete images and programs were used as well as their artefacts.

It was observed that both spatial orientation and spatial visualization skills were developed during students’ work. “Spatial Orientation” and “Spatial Visualization” were the main categories used for the data analysis. Spatial orientation skills were favored by kinesthetic and dynamic imagery which was easy for the students to use in order to represent what they meant, due to the physical characteristics of the robot and mostly the orientation of robots’ parts’ wheels. The communication of students’ ideas through this kind of representation helped them adopt the right referring context in order to describe robots’ movements. Episodes during which this happened were included in the subcategory described as “Spatial Orientation and reference contexts through Dynamic and Kinesthetic imagery” (Figure 2).

Figure 59: Spatial Orientation and reference contexts through Dynamic and Kinesthetic Imagery

When this happened, students were able to mentally visualize these movements and their graphic result, activating this way their spatial visualization skills. Finally it seemed that using their spatial visualization skills helped them solve problems and come up with unexpected solutions to their problems, generating meaning about mathematical ideas. Episodes during which this happened were included in the subcategory describes as “Spatial visualization and problem solving” (Figure 3).

Spatial visualization skills also favored the development of pattern imagery, though which students were able to identify same movements that the robot had to make. Episodes during which pattern imagery was expressed were included in “Spatial visualization and pattern imagery” (Figure 3).

Figure 60: Spatial Visualization subcategories

During the activities, students were asked to program their robot to draw a cube net. In order to do this they had to use multiple representational systems. More precisely, they used their programs, robots’ movements and concrete images as representations of the cube net. In order to interpret one representation in another, students developed strategies to identify and match the elements of the representations accordingly. Episodes during which this kind of students’ strategies were used were included in the category described as “Using multiple representational systems – Matching representations” .

12.3.3.1 SPATIAL ORIENTATION AND REFERENCE CONTEXTS THROUGH DYNAMIC AND KINESTHETIC IMAGERY

12.3.3.1.11ST SESSION- ROBOT CONSTRUCTION

During the first session, after having watched photos and videos of a real CNC machine, students had to understand how it works, distinguishing its parts’ movements in order to construct a robot that would simulate the real machine. The robot would draw two-dimensional solids’ nets on an A3 page on which it would move.

The two-dimensional shape that the machine would draw would be cut and tiled resulting in the construction of a physical solid model of the actual object (container house). All teams distinguished the movements the machine did and quickly thought about how to connect the ready parts so that the resulting machine would be able to move accordingly. By the end of the session all groups had constructed functional robots, whose parts were moving on two axes and could draw cubes’ nets (Figure 4).

Figure 61: Students artifacts were drawing on two axes and could draw cubes' nets.

To build the robot which would resemble the real machine it was necessary for the students to be able to communicate their ideas about the movements of its parts and its construction, so that everyone would follow a common line during the construction phase. To do that, they were constantly sharing their intuitive ideas moving the robot's parts, expressing their dynamic imagery, making their mental images concrete and reflecting on them. Problems arising from disagreements about the construction of the robot were being resolved through this exchange of dynamic imagery. It seemed from the beginning that the physical characteristics of the tool, such as the orientation of the wheels, helped students communicate their ideas and express not only what they had understood but also their misconceptions. When these misconceptions were expressed students reflected on their ideas in order to make changes and new decisions.

Expression through dynamic and kinaesthetic imagery helped students of the focus group to describe more precisely the movements of the robots' parts in order to solve misconceptions about its movement and its construction. When trying to decide how to put together the robot's parts, students of the 2nd group watch the video and discuss. They have concluded that their robot would make two movements on two axis, but they are still worried about how this would be done and which of the parts will make which movement. Student S3 had not understood the way the third vehicle was going to move "right" and "left". These expressions confused her and made her doubt about the way they constructed the robot. She uses a dynamic imagery in order to express what she was thinking of. The misconception was made evident by the way S3 represented the movement of the third vehicle. This made it possible for another girl in the team to explain to her the right way the vehicle was going to move. S2 also uses a dynamic image but this time this has an impact on how she describes the direction of the vehicle as instead of "right" and "left" she used the expressions "back" and "forward".

Episode 1

S1: *It goes like this, did you see? These two will go forward and this one will move right and left.*

S3: *I can see that! But how is this going to turn?*

S2: *It won't.*

S1: *It will move like this, back and forward.*

Figure 5 : S3 expressed her misconception about the robots movements and S1 represents the right movement for the third vehicle.

S1 uses the vehicles in the right direction when she represents the tool's movement. The wheels' direction supports S1's spatial orientation with respect to the vehicle, helping her describe its movement. The initial statement *"These two will go forward and this one will move right and left"* confused S2 concerning the way the robot would move, as "right" and "left" undermine that the vehicle would have to turn. In the beginning of the episode, S1 uses the personal context to describe robot's movements, referring to the directions "right" and "left" with respect to her body. Having caused a misconception to S2, these expressions are replaced by a kinaesthetic representation in combination with the right reference context. 2nd session – Programming the robot

As described above when students discussed about the robot's movements, they were representing them with gestures expressing their mental images kinaesthetically. This made it easier for them to orient themselves with respect to the entities they wanted to move each time and to use the appropriate vocabulary that would describe the entity's movement respectively to its orientation. This facilitated their communication with regard to the concepts of the space in which the entity was moving as they could show exactly what they meant.

In a relevant episode during the 2nd session, while students began programming their robots to draw two dimensional solids nets on an A3 paper students reach the right conclusions expressing their dynamic imagery through kinaesthetic images.

Episode 2

S3: *So these are going to move back and forward and this one right and left, right?*

S4: *I suppose so...*

S3: *But this cannot turn... (she shows the part which moves on the rail)*

S4: *But look its position (she means its direction). We will move this back and forward, too.*

Figure 6: S4 represents the part's movements through a kinesthetic image.

As shown in Episode 3 below, team 4 is engaged in a similar discussion. Trying to program the robot, students discuss its movements.

Episode 3

S5: *These will move forward and then we will move this back so that it draws this line (he shows on the paper)*

S6: *(while programming) Which is going to go back;*

S5: C

S6: *But this is supposed to move right and left.*

S5: *It is right for us but for that it is back.*

Figure 7: S5 represents the robot's movements using a kinesthetic image.

Tool's physical characteristics lead to kinaesthetic imagery, supporting communication about spatial concepts and adoption of the appropriate reference context, helping to the development of spatial orientation skills by students.

12.3.3.2 SPATIAL VISUALISATION AND PROBLEM SOLVING

While working with robots, students faced problems that led them to creative solutions. Technical problems such as the small length of the machine's rail, resulting in the problems in designing the necessary width in the shape, caused the reflection of the students and led to new solutions. Through such processes a team ended up with a cube net different from the one it intended to design in the first place and another team found that all the line segments that would be drawn by the machine should be equal so that at the end the net would close creating a cube.

12.3.3.2.1 THE "DISCOVERY" OF THE CUBE NET

By the beginning of the third session students of the fourth group had decided that they would try to draw a

"cross net" with their machine (Figure 8).

Figure 8: The net students wanted to draw.

They have given the first three commands to the robot and they discuss how to continue. For the second command of the program that students have created, the vehicle B has moved back in a distance which has covered the length of the robot's rail. The vehicle B cannot move back because it has already reached the end of the rail.

Episode 4

Figure 9: The first three commands and their graphic result.

S6: Now we have to move vehicle B forward.

S7: So these (A and C) move forward, right? This (B) moves back...Then these (A and C) move back...and then B moves...

S6: Back...

S7: We cannot move it back...

S6: We can do this longer (4) so that it will be tiled like this (he shows how the net is going to be tiled in order to create a cube).

S7: So we will not make a "cross"...

S6: We can do this longer so we will cover this side also (he shows the line of the other headquarter of the cube).

Figure 10: The fourth command about movement 4 and its graphic result.

During this episode a difficulty because of the length of the robot's rail led to a new idea. Students imagined the right moves for the robot but they did not calculate the distance or the time they must move the vehicle on the rail so that it will be able to move again in the same direction. Necessarily, the strategy had to change. S6 proposed to draw a longer line "to cover this side". So they will not draw a "cross" net but another kind of a cube net.

The problem students faced led them to think about alternative solutions. Thinking about what movements the machine could make from the point where it had stopped, S6 came up with another shape which was going to create a cube.

12.3.3.2.2 THE "DISCOVERY" OF THE EQUALITY OF THE CUBE EDGES

Another group also faced a problem due to the robot structure. Students had already given the first three commands (Figure 11).

Figure 11: The first three movements and their graphic result.

Then the robot has to draw line (c). However, the vehicle which moves on axis x has no more space to move forward.

Episode 5

S2: We cannot do it like this, there is no space.

S3: There is a little...

S2: But it won't be right because they have to have the same length because afterwards we will tile it and they need to be the same in order for the cube to close.

S4: We will do it from the start and we will move the first less...

S2: And then we will add the same value so it will be the same and the cube will close.

S4: Yes, put here 2 seconds instead of 4 and then we will move it again for 2 seconds.

S2 imagines how the net will be folded and realizes that all lines must have the same length so that their cube closes. So students change their program.

Figure 12: Initial program.

Figure 13: Students change the duration of the first movement.

Motivated by the problem that occurred, students thought about the distance the third vehicle has to move. They realized that the distance had to be the same every time as they mentally visualized the net folding.

12.3.3.3 SPATIAL VISUALIZATION AND PATTERN IMAGERY

The students of the fourth group have run the first three commands and discuss how to continue.

Episode 6

Figure 14: The first three commands and their graphic result.

S7: It has to do the same movements.

S8: All this again? And how is it going to close? B should go forward (Figure 15).

Figure 15: The graphic result if B went forward.

S7: This way it will draw a square...We need an open cube.

S8: B should move right then...

S7: We can only move it back or forward.

S8: Back (Figure 16)!

Figure 16: The graphic result if B moved back.

S7: That is what I meant. B moves back and we are doing the same again, because then we will move these two (A and C).

S7 imagined the graphic result and realized that the robot draws a pattern. Spatial visualization of the vehicles' movements along with the virtual environment helped him identify the pattern. In the end he created the next two commands the same as command 2 and 3. The student identified the pattern through dynamic imagery and implicated his thought repeating the two commands in order to draw the same shape.

12.3.3.4 USING MULTIPLE REPRESENTATIONAL SYSTEMS - MATCHING REPRESENTATIONS

In order to draw the desirable shape, students had to imagine which move would result in which line of the net that the robot would draw. To do this, it was necessary to translate the mental dynamic imagery about the robot's movements into the corresponding schematic representation that would be drawn on the paper. This led students to constantly move from one representation to another to check if the result of each movement resulted in the desirable shape.

An example of the above is the work of group 3, which adopts an enhanced strategy. While girls discuss about the robot's movements, at first they use gestures to represent the movements of the vehicles so that they can come to a conclusion about the commands they are going to use and their sequence. However, this proves not to be enough, so they decide to create and use another, more concrete representation of their work. They draw the desirable net on the paper and for each line of that net, they represent kinaesthetically the robot's movement which will draw it and for each of these movements they make a decision about the command they are going to use.

Episode 7

S2: So, at first we have to do this line (1)...

S1: And then this one (2).

S2: Yes, so the small vehicle goes forward (1) and then the two bigger vehicles go forward (2)...

S1: Yes and then we have to go like this (3)... so the small vehicle goes forward again.

Figure 17: Movements 1, 2 and 3 corresponding to line segments each move draws.

In the above episode students facilitate their thinking using additional representations moving from one representational system to another. The schematic representation they designed on the paper guides them regarding the "steps" of the robot. DiSessa et al. (1991) conclude that when students are not only "consumers" of visual representations, but also their creators, who communicate and use them critically, they develop meta-representational knowledge, creating and using criteria concerning quality and adequacy of representations.

Their representation helps them to control step by step the result of each movement. Each command corresponds to a line and each line has a specific direction. The direction of each line corresponds to the entity which they orient each time. This continuous transition from the graphical representation to the visualization of the robot movements and then to the creation of the program, helps them adjust their orientation with respect to a different entity for each movement. This way students progressively build a mental representation, a dynamic image of the way in which the robot moves, thus developing their spatial orientation and visualisation skills.

12.3.3.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

During the activities, students developed strategies of spatial orientation and spatial visualization. Physical characteristics of the artefact helped students develop dynamic and kinesthetic imagery which played a very important role to the communication of the ideas and the establishment of the same vocabulary about spatial information. Robot's concrete nature helped them orient with respect to the entity they had to move each time. When this was achieved students could describe more precisely the movements of the robot in space. While in the beginning students refer to the robot's movement using the personal reference context, describing movements in space with respect to their body, at last, they manage to adopt the right reference context describing the robot's parts' movements with respect to the entity that they would program to move. So their spatial descriptions were more accurate and their communication easier and more efficient.

Spatial orientation skills and adoption of the right reference context when referring to the robot's movements helped students to easily program the robot and mentally manipulate three dimensional objects. When students developed spatial orientation skills, they were more able to mentally visualize the graphic result of these movements and to imagine the solid that would be created by the net that was drawn.

The development of the above skill of spatial visualization played an important role in cases where students faced problems which lead them to critical reflection and unexpected solutions. In 2 out of 4 teams problems relevant to the construction lead students to explore alternative solutions ending up to a “new” cube net and to the implication of the property of the cube edges equality in their program. We could say that students, engaged with artefacts in a realistic and purposeful context, which embody mathematical concepts, “discovered” mathematical ideas such as the cube net and the property of the cube’s lines’ equality and patterns.

They were also provided with multiple systems of representation and they were engaged in representational interpretation procedures. Their dynamic imagery about the robot’s movements was interpreted in a command and the command was interpreted in a graphic result. Becoming familiar with this correspondence they were able to develop their own strategies. 2 teams created their own representations as models of the desired graphic result. These representations guided their dynamic imagery about the robot’s movements and which was finally interpreted in a program.

12.4 CONCLUSIONS

Girls’ interest in stem

- Girls had mostly positive attitudes about STEM subjects as 6 out of 8 girls mentioned a STEM subject as their favorite.
- Girls also have positive attitudes toward their abilities in STEM subjects and think they are good at them.
- STEM future careers are not so popular among girls, as only one of them mentions she wants to follow a STEM career in the pre-questionnaire.

Changing attitudes

- It seems that workshop activities had a positive impact on some girls’ attitudes.
- Girls rated positively the workshop, most of them found it interesting and fun and all girls would like to deal with more challenges like this in the future.
- However, it seems to be difficult to change their attitude about a possible STEM careers, as only one of the girls adds a STEM profession to her preferences about her future career in the post-questionnaire.

Evidence of learning

- During the activities, students developed strategies of spatial orientation and spatial visualization.
- Physical characteristics of the artefact helped students develop dynamic and kinesthetic imagery and adopt the right reference context describing the robot’s parts’ movements.
- Dynamic and kinesthetic imagery as well as the right reference context helped them develop their spatial orientation skills.
- Spatial orientation favored spatial visualization skill development.
- The development of spatial visualization favored critical reflection and problem solving.

- Students, engaged with artefacts in a realistic and purposeful context, which embody mathematical concepts, “discovered” mathematical ideas such as the cube net and the property of the cube’s lines’ equality and patterns.
- They were also engaged in representational interpretation procedures.

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13 APENDIX E: GREEK WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

13.1 CONTEXT: WORKSHOP: 437 - "INSECTS' BATTLE"

13.1.1 Description of the Activity

This case study took place in a Vocational Technical School in Athens, Greece, with a group of 11 students aged sixteen and seventeen. The group was consisted of 11 males but one male out of eleven absent from the second session. The workshop was held over three sessions, three days in a row, lasting five hours for sessions one and two respectively and 3 hours for the last session- thirteen hours in total.

Students worked in three groups of three to four members, and each group had a computer and all the necessary materials in order to build their own Arduino robot. The group had little if any knowledge of Arduino, however three students were experts on general electronics and four students were experts on computer science & programming concepts. The students were distributed between groups, so that each group would consist of at least one expert on general electronics and at least one expert on computer science. The venue of the workshop was a computer lab of the Laboratory Center of the School and the social status and the social environment of the students is characterized as underprivileged.

A full description that is provided in the activity plan:

"This workshop is designed to engage students in creating the desired functionalities and characteristics of an Arduino robotic insect. To be more explicit, the students are going to explore the usage of a mini breadboard, build all the electronic circuits on it and amend a given Arduino program, so that they would create the form of robot-insects, all of which could create an autonomous robot that moves correctly. Subsequently, all the robots are going to participate in a special race, the "Insects' battle" and in turn they will measure the average velocity of the each robotic insect. The rationale behind the pedagogical design, as well as the designed activities of the specific workshop is that mixed-group of specialties of students confront problems and misconceptions on programming and on circuits and they are asked to discover and implement the solutions. The learning process is based on the combination of the specialties, hoping that the students are going to break the boundaries of their specialties-knowledge and move on further to the synergy".

The stated objectives of the workshop were:

- Subject related:
 - Study and use a mini breadboard.
 - Build the circuits of LED, Piezo & Sonar.
 - Build the circuits of Servo motors.
 - Amend the given Arduino program.
 - Create robot-insects all of which could be autonomous and move correctly.
 - Create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect.

- Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle"

- Measure the average velocity of each robotic insect.
-
- Technology use related:
-
- Programming with Arduino.
-
- Social and action related:
- Develop collaborative skills (exchange ideas, tips and advices).
- Take roles within groups.
- Develop problem solving skills.
-
- Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:
-
- Make assumptions.
 -
- Test possible solutions and choose the best solution.
 -
- Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas.
 -
- Encourage curiosity, tinkering and experimentation.
 -

As stated in the objectives, the students used several electronics parts (resistors, LEDs, sonar sensor, piezo (buzzer), mini-breadboard, servo motors and jumper wires), shown in Figure 1 and every day affordable materials in order to build their robotic insect.

Figure 1. Resistors, LEDs, sonar sensor, piezo (buzzer), mini-breadboard, servo motors and jumper wires

The programming software of Arduino is wiring C, shown in Figure2.

Figure 2. Arduino microcontroller and Wiring C programming software

The groups were NOT encouraged to split four or three different roles between their members, neither to swap roles between each activity that they completed. The students were free to choose the role which was the most suitable or challenging for them and were split into different roles by themselves. The tutor had to notice whether they took roles within the groups in relation to their speciality and whether they adjusted their knowledge of their discipline in order to affect and influence both their peers and the final result.

13.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

13.2.1 Data Collection

All 11 students who participated in the workshop gave consent to be included in research project. The tutor who ran the workshop is also a member of the UoA research team and therefore took a participant-researcher role, collecting and analysing the data.

This data included 13 hours video recordings of the focus group and the other two groups during all sessions, photos taken by the tutor, pre and post questionnaires, interview with the focus group, observational notes and reflections from the tutors, reflections from the focus group, the activity plan, artefacts of learning, materials provided for the activity and the final robotic insects; a robotic spider, a robotic scorpion and a robotic beetle. The camera for the video data was angled in such a way that all members of the groups and their robots can always be seen in shot, but there is no clear view of their computer screen, however the screens could be seen in some photographs taken by the tutor.

13.2.2 Participants

The students of Vocational Technical Schools in Greece get a specialty at the second year of their studies and they continue in their specialty class the third year as well. The first year the students get general education and inform both about the specialties of the school and their syllabus in order for themselves to make the best choice. At this workshop the researcher who is simultaneously a tutor of the school, wanted to create complex mixed groups of students in order to observe the way they would collaborate into their groups, whether they

had significant role in relation to their specialties, the way they would adapt knowledge of their specialties to build a robot, in other words the way Communities of Practice-CoPs (students from the same specialty) would transform to Communities of Interest-Cols (distinct mixed groups who have a common goal, they want to manage to build their robot) through the theory of Boundary Crossing. This complex pedagogical design was implemented by the researcher-tutor for second time. Another research with the same characteristics took place a previous year but the new component this year is that the researcher-tutor found very interesting to observe how the students of the first grade (A) without having a specialty could gain an equal position in their teams and with the help of the robot as a Boundary Object could belong to a Community of Interest. To sum up, the researcher-tutor observed during the workshop two systems: 1) whether the CoPs transform to Cols and 2) how the team of students of the first grade integrate into the Cols. So, the researcher provided a letter and numbering system in order to identify easily the CoPs and the Cols. All the students from the 1st grade are the A students. All the students from electrical sector are the E students and all the students from the computer science sector are the C students. The numbering has to do with the groups. Therefore, for the Group 1, there are one student for the first grade A1, one from electrical sector E1 and one from computer science sector C1. For the Group 2, there are one student for the first grade A2, two from electrical sector E2 & E2' and one from computer science sector C2. And finally for the Group 3, there are one student for the first grade A3, one from electrical sector E3 and two from computer science sector C3 & C3'.

13.2.2.1 FOCUS GROUP OR GROUP 1

The focus group analysed was a mixed-specialties and ages group, consisting of three boys, shown in Figure 92. The group had never worked together. The first boy was an electrician of 3rd grade (E1), the second boy was a PC technician of 2nd grade (C1) and the third boy (A1) had dropped out twice and was student of the 1st grade without specialty but absolutely amazing on tinkering.

Figure 3. Photographs taken of focus group members-group 1

13.2.2.2 GROUP 2

The second group analysed was a mixed-specialties and ages group, consisting of four boys, shown in Figure 92. Two boys were electricians of 2nd grade (E2 & E2'), the third boy was a PC technician of 2nd grade (C2) and the third boy (A2) was student of the 1st grade without specialty. The group was mostly divided into two sub-groups.

Figure 4. Photographs taken of second group members

13.2.2.3 GROUP 3

The third group analysed was a mixed-specialties and ages group, consisting of four boys, shown in Figure 92. The first boy was an Electrician of 2nd grade (E3), two boys were PC Technicians of 2nd grade (C3 & C3') and the fourth boy was student of the 1st grade (A3) without specialty. The boys took over roles concerning their specialties from the very beginning and they also had tightly cooperation within the group.

Figure 5. Photographs taken of third group members

13.2.3 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved looking for critical incidents, with the research questions concerning 'How have the teams collaborated (internally and externally)?', 'Who is excluded or chooses to isolate themselves?' and

'Evidence of Learning' being decided in advance of the analysis based on the research team's observations, the data collection and overall research priorities.

13.3 FINDINGS

This report structures its findings by three sections: 'How have the teams collaborated (internally and externally)?', 'Who is excluded or chooses to isolate themselves?' and 'Evidence of Learning'.

13.3.1 How the teams have collaborated (internally and externally)

This section explores the research question: 'How have the teams collaborated (internally and externally)?'. In several videos there were incidents of children sharing ideas between groups as well as among groups. Furthermore, interesting data emerged concerning the collaboration among the students of group 2 and between two members of the group 3 (E3 & A3) as well as between two students of the first grade A3 & A2.

13.3.1.1 BETWEEN GROUPS

The researcher noticed that only two out of eleven students didn't deal with the part of the robot that was in relation to their specialties. To be more explicit, the students from the computer science sector immediately went in front of their PCs to amend the program of Arduino, the students from the electrical sector (apart from E1 & E2) tried to build the electronic part of Arduino and the students from the grade A started constructing the robot. Therefore, when a student had had a problem on a specific part (e.g. the programming part) asked for help from his CoP- peers with the same specialty. The students seemed to cooperate into two main teams, on one hand into their groups (group 1 or group 2 or group 3) or in other words into their CoIs and on the other hand, into a tacit group of their specialty (group E, or group C or group A) or in other words into their CoPs.

The following critical incidents are from the tacit group C of the computer science sector. The student C1 (group 1) had had a problem on programming. He could neither modify the angles of the servo motor on the given program, nor amend the delays on it, so that both the velocity and the movement of the servos' couldn't move smoothly. After hours of tries C1 asked help from C3 (group 3) and the latter went and helped him for more or less one hour according to video recording, shown in Figure 92

Figure 6. Collaboration between members of CoP of computer science

Moreover, every time an obstacle on programming was emerged, the students C3, C3' (group 3) and C2 (group 2) were collaborating. Every time, C2 was asking for help, especially C3 gave a hint or advice and even more he went to his desk to help, shown in Figure 92

Figure 7. Collaboration between members of CoP of computer science

The same reaction was noticed between the two electricians E1 and E2. The two boys was dealing with the construction of their robots and despite the fact that they totally ignored the circuits, they collaborated on building the robot. To be more explicit, there is data recording that showed E1 to go to E2's desk and help him for more than 30 min with the stability of the robotic scorpion's legs, shown in Figure 92

Figure 8. Collaboration between members of CoP of electrician

There is another critical incident which proves that these boys exchanged ideas even after the workshop, when they returned home. Actually, on the second day of the workshop, E1 came to tutor by saying that the idea of the moving "tail" (post-abdomen) of the robotic scorpion was his idea, which was shared with E2 the previous night. The E2 student of the second group confirmed their conversation. E2 found the idea of the moving tail amazing therefore, during the second session E2 changed the stable part of Scorpion's tail to a moving part. Afterwards, he connected this part with a servo motor, so that the robot insect could simultaneously move both a pair of legs and the post-abdomen, shown in Figure 92

From video: M2U00001.MPG, Time: 9:50 & 20:48 (Group 1 & Group 2)

E1: I suggested E2 should tinker the tail (post-abdomen) of the Scorpion in order to move.

Tutor: When did you tell him this idea?

E1: Yesterday night...we were talking about the workshop and I shared this idea with him.

Tutor: Did you talk about Arduino electronic circuits too?

E1: No, not about Arduino, about the workshop in general and the constructions and during chatting I told him.

...

In the video 20180228_110249.mp4 the student E2 confirmed that the idea for the movement came from E1 through a call.

Tutor: Can I take screen shots of your chat room?

E2: We didn't talk on facebook, we were talking through Viber...

Tutor: ...and?

E2: I was sharing my ideas and fears about the construction and E1 helped me... ”

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. The E2 student implemented the sharing idea of his peer E1 from group 1: (a) the design the first day and (b) the design the second day of the workshop

A very interesting collaboration emerged between E3 & A3, which in turn affected on the cooperation of group A. The student A3 had no specialty and as expected worked with the E3 as his assistant. But the subgroup of them functioned more like teacher and student, shown in Figure 92. The E3 taught him how to use Voltmeter device in order to check the power of a battery, learned him a few terms of his specialty, like direct current and alternating current. The dialog is below:

From video: M2U00009.MPG, Time: 14:30 and Video: 20180301_085359.mp4.

"E3: The alternating current takes positive and negative values, on the other hand the direct current, which is used in a battery or a supplier of voltage, takes only positive values. So, look at this battery has 8,40 Volt and that one 8,62 Volt..."

...

A3: Oooh...great."

Figure 10. Photographs taken of the students E3 & A3 of the third group.

Subsequently, the A3 (group 3) in turn tried to transfer this knowledge to his peer A2 (group 2). They took the Voltmeter device and tried to measure the voltage of a battery, shown in Figure 92. The A3 followed the steps that had learned but he forgot to turn the voltmeter device to DC (Direct Current) and the "teacher" E3 intervened to correct the mistake. The recording video with this scene is M2U00006.MPG, time: 27:39.

"E3: What have you set the measurement mode of the device? To the alternating mode

A3: May I switch it?

E3: You have set it to the alternating mode and you want to measure the voltage of the battery. No..., Battery gives direct voltage.

...

The student of the 1st grade noticed the + and the - sign of the battery in order to put the wires of voltmeter device properly. The P1 observed this action and reacted.

E3: Doesn't matter where is the + and the - sign of the battery... 8,27Volt...excellent!"

Figure 11. Photographs taken of the students A3 & A2

The boys A3 and A2 had no idea before the workshop about the functionality and the usage of the Voltmeter, but when A3 having learned something new from the electrician's discipline, wanted to disseminate this knowledge to his peer A2.

Another critical incident was when E2' went to his peer E3 and shared an idea about the construction of the Scorpion. E2' had very bad cooperation with his group, especially with E2, so he tried to exchange an idea with E3 from group 3. The researcher after watching 13 hours of video recordings interprets his reaction as a need for expressing at least one idea to someone, because after that incident E2 gradually isolated. His idea was to cover the electronic part of the robot by building another layer of wooden surface. The E3 was sarcastic with him and he discouraged E2' from implementing his idea by explaining through a law of Physics, that the big weight decreases the velocity.

From video: 00016.MTS, Time: 2:10 (Group 2 & Group 3)

"E2": I was thinking to build another one layer of wooden surface and put all the electronic circuits there, so that you couldn't observe them.

E3: Yes, yes of course good idea to build another layer...Are you serious? Do you think you construct a building? It has to be light!

E2': Why to be light?

E3: Because we are going to have a race!!! "

After this conversation with E3, the E2' student realised the importance of the weight in the construction and he never referred his idea to his group (group 2). Again the researcher perceived that the boys had a tendency to share their ideas within their CoP.

13.3.1.2 WITHIN GROUPS

13.3.1.2.1 GROUP 1

During the first moments of the workshop, the members of group 1 seemed to cooperate very well. All together exchanged ideas about the construction and were trying to find and implement the best idea for their robot.

From video: 00012.MTS, Time: 7:30 (Group 1)

"E1: What do you think if we put the servos under the wooden layer and then the arduino on the wooden surface?

C1: Yes, and each servo with two legs...

A1: Ok but we need 3 servos, one in front, one in the middle and one back. "

The focus team was consistent with this idea and built their robot precisely as they said, shown in Figure 92

Figure 12. Group 1 implemented their sharing idea

Subsequently, A1 shared another idea about the construction. This boy was very good on tinkering but his peers didn't take advantage of his talent. E1 took the helm of his team from the very beginning and due to his chaotic personality was taking very strange decisions and was rejecting the ideas of the others. The following critical incident was another one rejection.

From video: 00013.MTS, Time: 20:00 (Group 1)

A1: We can put the materials in the peripheral of a cycle...I know it is difficult but ...

E1: It is a very good idea...

C1: Indeed...

E1: But we have to use wire and then to cut it there...I am not sure, but if you want... "

E1 even if he said "...if you want.." he never gave space for another idea. He had suggested to construct a rectangle and supported his idea. Therefore, the idea of A1 didn't implement on their robot. Eventually, this group developed a dysfunctional collaboration, as it is analysed at the paragraph below, and they failed to achieve a few learning objectives of the workshop.

13.3.1.2.2 GROUP 2

The students of group 2 didn't share ideas within their group. They never become a CoI. After examining hours of video recordings some dialogs emerged that could explain the lack of collaboration and the division into two sub-groups with only two main players-leaders. The E2 on the construction with assistant the A2 and the C2 on programming and electronic circuits with assistant the E2'. To be more explicit, the E2 even if he was electrician he neither dealt with the circuits, nor shared his knowledge in order to help his peers. He didn't also collaborate either with his peer from the same sector the E2'. He totally dedicated himself to construction. The problematic collaboration is illustrated below:

From video: M2U00002.MPG, Time: 7:50

"C2: Two jumper wires have to be connected into pin No5. How can I achieve that?"

E2: Do whatever you want... "

From video: M2U00005.MPG, Time: 20:00

"E2: What are you doing?"

E2': I am testing something...

E2: Can I do what I want to... I have been working for two hours on this design, don't destroy it.

E2': Ok ok ...stop. "

From video: 20180228_103309.mp4, Time: 00:49

"Tutor: You both, have you dealt with the electronic circuits?"

E2, A2: No, not at all...

E2: We build the robot... the others deal with that... "

Even if they never become a CoI, they managed to achieve almost all the learning objectives as we can see below. Was the value of the personalities and the knowledge of each separate member of this group which efficiently helped to attain their goals or the collaboration among the CoPs (E2 with E1 & C2 with C3)? This question remains without an answer until the next research.

13.3.1.2.3 GROUP 3

On the other hand, the members of group 3 took specific roles and backed up their peers whenever was needed. The two pc technicians C3 & C3' had developed an excellent collaboration, they made a debugging on the given programs and in turn they added all the debugging parts to a comprehensive program which it was used as the final program for their robot. Furthermore, they supported E3 who dealt with the construction and electronic circuits. The same reaction was recorded on behalf of E3. He built the electronic part and constructed the robot and whenever was needed was in front of the PC to evaluate and modify his work, shown in Figure 13. The data has demonstrated several boundary crossings on this team but the analysis of this theory is out of the scope of this report.

Figure 13. Group3 as Col 3

The student A3 was always beside the E3, but the lack of knowledge on the discipline of electronics forced him to be the assistant of E3. Despite being an assistant, the collaboration of the sub-group E3 & A3 hasn't had the characteristics of the master and the novice, but more like the teacher and the student. E3 with his expertise, his knowledge and his extroverted personality helped A3 to learn things from his discipline, as it is referred above, and feel equal member of their group expressing without any fear his ideas.

From video: 20180227_113415.mp4, Time: 00:00 (Group 3)

"A3: *What do you think if we put some more wooden sticks on the surface?*

E3: *Then it will be very heavy and it isn't useful...but if you want we can do it, there is not any problem.*

A3: *No problem...it was just an idea!*

E3: *We are a team, of course you can express an idea...*

A3: *Moreover, it is wrong that we stretched the paperclips, isn't it?*

E3: *No, it is ok because we need different heights."*

The A3 expressed himself to his peer, even if he made some constructional mistakes and his ideas couldn't implement. The robot of this team achieved all the learning objectives of the workshop and the robotic beetle was by far the quickest robot of the insects' battle.

13.3.2 Who is excluded or chooses to isolate themselves?

13.3.2.1 THE A1 STUDENT OF THE FIRST GROUP

The roles into the groups dramatically affects the dynamic of the teams and in turn the relationship of the boys during the workshop. Observing the video recordings of the focus group, it was crystal clear that the elder boy of the 3rd grade (E1) was the coordinator of his team. He defined the roles of the other two members and kept the role he wanted for himself. He had immature thinking during the workshop, never changed his mind, very stubborn and kind of chaotic. All the data from the video 00012.MTS confirm the above characteristics. Furthermore, even if the A1 student made some efforts to express his ideas, most of them were rejected by E1. The video 00015.MTS shows that the boy (A1) wasn't one with the initiative and power to intervene and change anything on the robot under these circumstances. He preferred to stay inactive waiting for his peers to come back and give him instructions and he never gained an equal position in the group, therefore he did almost nothing, shown in Figure 92

Figure 14. The A1 student inactive in the group 1

On the second day of the workshop E1 gave him work to do, to build the legs of their Spider.

From video: M2U00001.MPG, Time: 11:00

"E1: My idea is to build the legs using two materials, both wood and paperclips. This choice will create a better stability... This idea I think is good, however "the legs" is your part, so do whatever you want.

...

A1: What do you want me to do?..."

The A1 built the legs as the E1 suggested (shown in Figure 92) and after the break he never came back to the lab. He abandoned the workshop.

Figure 15. The shape of legs as the E1 suggested

His participation was encouraged by the tutor during the workshop, however the dynamic of the other members, as well as the lack of specific discipline were presumably the reasons made him to abandon his peers. During the interview, the other two students of the group stated that they didn't attain their goal to build an autonomous robot insect due to his absence:

From video: M2U00019.MPG, Time: 15:00 - Interview part

"E1: Because of his absence we couldn't collaborate correctly. We were forced to focus on one thing at the time and we had no time to exchange ideas. We stressed ourselves on the second and the third day with no reason..."

...

C1: We were only two. It was very difficult."

13.3.2.2 THE A2 & E2' STUDENTS OF THE SECOND GROUP

Eventually, both A2 and E2' students were the peripheral members of their group during the workshop. Group 2 was divided into two sub-groups from the very beginning. E2 took over the role of the leader on tinkering with the boy from the 1st grade (A2) as an assistant and the PC technician of 2nd grade (C2) took over the role of the master on programming with the second Electricians (E2') joined with him to help on electronic circuits. According to pre and post questionnaires analysis, E2' answered that even if prefers working alone to working into teams, he helped create the robot and the final programming. However, the data from the video recordings showed that he was an assistant in his group, with no specific role and no-one listened to his opinion. He mostly observed the processes, shown in Figure 92.

Figure 16. Photographs taken of A2 and E2' members of second group

On the other hand, A2 put his disappointment on the post questionnaires. Having used the 5-points Likert scale, he gave 5 stars (strongly agree) for the workshop and he said that he learned about working with other people that it is very interesting, however, he gave: "4 points (agree)- I worked on my own", "2 points (disagree) - I helped created a robot", "1 point (strongly disagree) - I helped programme a robot" and "2 points (disagree) - I was able to choose what I wanted to do". Consequently, the bad collaboration, the lack of specific role and the lack of knowledge caused the isolation of the boys. Watching the data recordings it is noticeable how the two boys had been gradually isolated by their peers from the processes of the workshop, shown in Figure 92

Figure 17. The isolation of the A2 & E2'

13.3.3 Evidence of Learning

This section explores how the workshop evidenced learning by the students and which learning objectives were evidenced to have been met. Evidence of learning can be shown through direct methods that provide definitive evidence that students have met the learning objectives. 'Direct Methods' data is taken from artefacts of learning. To be more explicit, the creation of a robotic insect, the functionality of the electronic part of the robot, the functionality of the servo motors, the amendment of the given Arduino program, the programming of Arduino microcontroller, the movement of the robot-insects so that they could be autonomous and move correctly and the measurement of the average velocity of each robotic insect, all of which are the learning objectives from the Activity Plan of the workshop and simultaneously are "direct" evidence of learning.

Each group worked through a series of steps described on activity information sheets and

Concerning the objective "Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle", the playful part of the workshop was very successful. The students were laughing during the race since the "spider" never started running, the "scorpion" was moving backwards and the "beetle" was running very fast! The following screen shots capture this special race, shown in Figure 92

Figure 22. The insect "battle"

shows which group met which learning objective. As can be seen by the majority green shading in the table, most groups evidenced meeting the learning objectives. The orange blocks, where students partially met the objective appeared to be due to the task not being completed fully, which may be because the group ran out of the time or the activity was completed by the tutor. The occasions few red block are shown, the group 1 did not manage to both move their robot and add an extra programming and the last objective about the measurement of the velocity was cancelled by the tutor. The tutor decided to ignore this objective because group 1 didn't manage to move the robotic spider, group 2 managed to move the robotic scorpion backwards and only group 3 with the robotic beetle manage to move correctly.

Table 17. Learning evidenced through coding produced for Groups (Green = objective met, Orange = partially met, Red = not met)

Robotic Insect	Learning Objectives	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Process				
1: Construction	Create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect	Orange	Green	Green
2: Electronic Circuits	Study and use a mini breadboard	Green	Green	Green
	Build the circuits of LED, Piezo & Sonar	Orange	Green	Green
	Build the circuits of Servo motors	Green	Green	Green

3: Programming	Amend the given Arduino program	Green	Green	Green
	Programming with Arduino	Red	Green	Green
4: Play & Passion	The robot-insects could be autonomous and move correctly	Red	Yellow	Green
	Examine which is the faster robotic insect during the "Insects' battle"	Green	Green	Green
5: Physics	Measure the average velocity of each robotic insect	Red	Red	Red

13.3.3.1 Direct Methods

This section will explore how direct methods were used to evidence the ‘Subject-related’ and ‘Technology-related’ learning objectives of the workshop and it will be analysed the

Concerning the objective "Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle", the playful part of the workshop was very successful. The students were laughing during the race since the "spider" never started running, the "scorpion" was moving backwards and the "beetle" was running very fast! The following screen shots capture this special race, shown in Figure 92

Figure 22. The insect "battle"

which shows which group met which learning objective.

Concerning the electronic circuits, group 1 partially met the objectives "Study and use a mini-breadboard" as well as "Build the circuits of LED, piezo, sonar sensor and build the circuits of servo motors"., Initially, the second day of the workshop the students C2 and C3 went to help C1 who was dealing with that part of robot but since they were all from the computer science sector, they couldn't find the problem on the circuits. Afterwards, an expert on electronic circuits E3 went to help C1. E3 found all the mistakes, amended the circuits and he made functional the electronic part of their robot, however the third day of the workshop C1 was desperate again with regard to the electronic part. There wasn't data to prove what went wrong again, whether C1 or E1 amended something on it. Eventually the intervention of the tutor made things work. Due to the fact that group 1 manage to meet this objective only after the intervention of the tutor, it is considered as partially met shown in Figure 92

Figure 18. The functionality of the electronic part of the robot partially met for group 1

The other two groups attained this goal, shown in Figure 5.

Figure 6. The functionality of the electronic part of the robot met for group 2 & 3

As far as the objective "Amend the given Arduino program" is concerned, all teams managed to amend it but concerning the objective "Programming with Arduino" only group 2 and 3 were able to program the Arduino microcontroller. Group 3 also managed to add programming for "Blink" from the Arduino library, whilst group 1 was out of time and couldn't add programming part into the given program. An example of this code is shown in Figure 92

Figure 20. All groups amended the given program but group 2 & 3 achieved to program too

With regard to the objective "Create the desired functionalities and characteristics of a robotic insect", the imagination and the creativity of the boys were noticeable. The extraordinary robotic spider, scorpion and beetle give prominence to the practical skills of these boys. Using paperclips, tongue depressors, coffee tubes, wooden sticks, glue along with the electronic parts created the following, shown in Figure 92

Figure 21. The construction of the groups: a robotic spider, a robotic scorpion and the robotic beetle

Concerning the objective "Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle", the playful part of the workshop was very successful. The students were laughing during the race since the "spider" never started running, the "scorpion" was moving backwards and the "beetle" was running very fast! The following screen shots capture this special race, shown in Figure 92

Figure 22. The insect "battle"

13.4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section provides concluding remarks for this report, by summarising the findings and stating recommendations for the future.

1.1.1 How the teams have collaborated (internally and externally)

- The boys were sharing ideas within their groups (Cols) as well as between groups but with their peers from the same specialty (CoPs). All the sharing ideas weren't implemented but those which finally did, critically influenced the constructions of the robotic insects.
- It was perceived that the dynamic of the CoPs (group E, group C & group A) on transferring knowledge, affected on the final artefacts and helped students to learn. This double collaboration at two levels (CoPs & Cols), with these special characteristics (Vocational Education) seems to function as catalyst which triggers the dissemination of knowledge.
-
- The students of the group 2 developed a dysfunctional collaboration. The distinct roles of leaders as masters and the assistances as novice learners, indicated the lack of trust among the sub-groups and the peers. However, they achieved almost all the predefined objectives. It seems that the collaboration between CoPs opened new roads to disseminate the knowledge.
-
- The students of the 1st grade- Group A couldn't easily integrate into their teams as equal members, because they were tacitly considered as novice learners. However, this workshop for group A (apart from A1) was a kind of apprenticeship, since E3 disseminated his knowledge on circuits with A3, A3 in turn tried to transfer these knowledge to his peer A2 and then together A3 & A2 practised with hands-on examples.

13.4.1.1 RECOMMENDATION

- The teams should consist of students only from second or third grade in order to have the expertise to support the complex process of building a robot with Arduino.

13.4.2 Who is excluded or chooses to isolate themselves?

- The elder boy of the 3rd grade E1 was the coordinator of group 1. He defined the roles of all members and seemed to be very active, but he had immature thinking during the workshop, was very stubborn and kind of chaotic. On the other hand, the boy of the 1st grade wasn't one with the initiative and power to intervene and change anything on the robot under these circumstances. Subsequently, he preferred to stay inactive, waiting for instructions, excluded from his group. As a result, after the break at the second session, he never came back to the lab and abandoned the workshop.
- As it has referred above, the students of the group 2 developed a dysfunctional collaboration. The distinct roles of leaders as masters and the assistances as novice learners, indicated the lack of trust among them. Therefore, the boy from the 1st grade A2 as well as the second electrician E2' were the peripheral members of their group. The lack of specific role and the lack of knowledge caused the isolation of these boys.

13.4.2.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

- When the roles and responsibilities haven't been properly allocated, the tutor should promptly intervene.

13.4.3 Evidence of Learning

- Overall, the majority of the learning objectives had evidence to show they were met. The problems occurred only to group 1 for the above reasons. The groups created noticeable robotic insects with functional both electronic and programming parts. Apart from the learning objective from the discipline of Physics, which was cancelled by the tutor because it was considered useless due to problematic movements of two out of three robots.

13.4.3.1 RECOMMENDATION

- The adaptation of the sub-group of the students of first grade (A1, A2 & A3) was very difficult. The lack of knowledge on electronics and programming forced them to take a role only at the part of construction the robot. However, they never became equal members of their groups and their opinions few times were important. The result was A1 to abandon the workshop and A2 & A3 participated more or less as assistants of the other students with specialties. Consequently, it seems that only students with knowledge on the disciplines of electronics and programming could equally integrate into such groups. This in turn allows the researcher to conclude that the best choice for the synthesis of the members of the teams at a Vocational Technical School is the mixed groups of at least one Electronic-Electrician and at least one PC technician, because the complementary disciplines lead to a successful Arduino robot.

14 APPENDIX F: MALTA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

14.1 CONTEXT

Workshop: CODE: AL-2-11-VER3 - Engaging with robots in a fun way

14.1.1 Description of the activity

This case study report refers to a workshop which was implemented in Verdala International School, Malta. In this workshop 19, 11-12 year old students participated, 7 girls and 12 boys. It included 2x 4hour sessions, which took place in the school gymnasium. Students worked in teams of two and mixed ability and gender were used as grouping criteria. Tutors supported students, intervening, monitoring and facilitating the process.

The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a pre-constructed robot and activities focused around programming Dash through commands and loop statements. Its programming environment includes drag and drop visuals. With respect to students' relevant prior knowledge, 8 boys had built a robot while 11 boys and 2 girls had a previous experience in programming.

During the workshop students had to solve 7 puzzles, going from the simplest to more complicated ones. The objectives of the activity plan designed for this workshop included:

Subject related

- Students program and learn mathematical concepts such as probability and random numbers.

Technology use related

- Students use Drag and Drop visuals.

Social and action related

- Students collaborate, share ideas with each other and learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups.

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture

- Students find multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles

During the activities students were expected to exchange ideas through dialogue and develop collaborative relationships within team members, taking and exchanging their roles when needed.

14.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In this section data collection and analysis procedures are presented.

14.2.1 Data Collection

The data set collected included video data of the whole class and the focus group, students' answers from the pre and post questionnaires and students' reflection sheets.

14.2.1.1 FOCUS GROUP

The focus group consisted of two students, one male (520314) and one female (520315). The girl (520315) had no previous experience with robots nor programming, while the boy (520314) had done some programming in the past. According to his answers in the pre-questionnaire, 520314 (m) seemed to have more positive attitudes towards STEM subjects and he wanted to follow a game designer career. 520315 (f) wanted to become a vet and she answered neutrally when asked whether she liked math and science. Both of them answered in the pre-questionnaire that they liked using computers.

When it comes to whether they like working with other people both of them answer neutrally but in the next question, concerning working in teams, 520314 (m) "strongly agreed" on preferring to work on his own and "didn't agree" when asked whether he liked working in a team. On the other hand 520315 (f) liked more working in team and she didn't prefer to work on her own.

14.2.2 Data Analysis

This analysis focused on the circumstances under which one gender 'takes-over' within groups and the implications of this. Analysis is presented through description of critical episodes during which one gender took over during the activities having as a result the disengagement, isolation and exclusion of a member in the group. The analysis also includes episodes during which tutors used strategies to re-engage a member. Analysis is structured over the category of "Engagement". It seemed that students engaged mostly individually and less collaboratively. To illustrate these types of engagement, subcategories of "One gender engagement" and "Collaborative engagement" were used. "One gender engagement" includes the subcategories of "Ownership", "Support" and "Other member Isolation, as it was noticed that ownership of the tablet and tutor's support favoured one gender engagement which finally caused "Other gender disengagement" and "Isolation". "Collaborative engagement" includes "Mediation", as it was noticed that when tutor acted as a mediator of students' communication, collaboration was favoured.

Figure 62: "Engagement" is referred to cases when "One gender Engagement" or "Collaborative Engagement" took place. "One gender Engagement" was favored by "Ownership" and "Support", most of the times causing "Other gender Disengagement" and finally "Isolation". "Collaborative Engagement" was favored by tutor's "Mediation".

14.3 FINDINGS

In this section, findings regarding the research question "In what circumstances did one gender 'take over' and what were the implications of this?" are presented. Video data and students' responses in the post questionnaire about their collaboration and their whole experience were used.

14.3.1 Video Data Analysis

14.3.1.1 ONE GENDER ENGAGEMENT

14.3.1.1.1 EPISODE 1

In the first session, 520314 (m) seemed to be really interested in the subject of the workshop, raising his hand willing to answer tutor's questions while 520315 (f) was sitting behind, listening carefully. As mentioned below, it is possible that their different initial reactions are linked to their differences regarding their attitudes towards STEM subjects and their previous experience with programming. More precisely, 520315 (f) mentioned in the pre-questionnaire that she didn't like science and math and she hadn't previous experience with programming, unlike her teammate.

When a tutor gave tablets to the students, 520314 (m) took the tablet and started exploring while 520315 (f) was still hesitating (Figure 1). However, when tutor explained that it is through the tablet that they would control the robot, she came closer to 520314 (m) and got engaged.

Figure 63: While 520314 (m) was engaged, 520315 (f) was more hesitant.

Figure 64: 520315 (f) started to be more interested, as she realizes the relation of the tablet and the robot.

A tutor, who was near the team, facilitated the inclusion of 520315 (f), pushing her closer to the tablet so she could see. This way the team came closer so both members could participate.

Figure 65: The tutor is encouraging 520315 (f) to participate.

After tutor's intervention 520315 (f) was encouraged to engage in the activity, willing to participate more. Even if 520314 (m) continued to hold the tablet on his side, she came closer and started touching tablet's screen, exploring the software (Figure 5).

Figure 66: After tutor's encouragement, 520315 (f) participates more.

Although both seemed to be engaged in what they were doing on the tablet, when they solved the first puzzle 520315 (f) started completing the test sheet while 520314 (m) went on to the next puzzle.

It seemed that in the beginning of the workshop 520315 (f) was not so willing to express her ideas and participate in programming. 520314 (m) was more active and took over from the beginning. However, the intervention of the tutor changed the attitude of 520315 (f) who was then more confident in participating. It is possible that girl's hesitation in the beginning was due to her attitudes towards science and math, as when asked whether she likes math and science she answered neutrally and mentioned science as her least favorite subject. Moreover 520315 (f) had no previous experience in programming and this might make her less confident as she also thought she needed help solving problems. However, in the pre-questionnaire she mentioned that she didn't like to work by herself.

On the other hand 520314 (m) had more positive attitudes about science and math, while he "agreed" that he liked science and he "strongly agreed" when it came to math. He had a previous experience with programming and in fact, he wanted to become a game designer. Though he might be more confident and that might be why he was so engaged at the beginning.

The engagement of the boy was expressed by the ownership of the tablet, while the girl was engaged through the support of the tutor.

14.3.1.1.2 EPISODE 2

Beginning the following puzzle, while 520314 (m) was programming, 520315 (f) decided to come closer to the tablet again. This time 520314 (m) gave her the tablet and explained to her what they had to do. 520315 (f) began to program and after 2 approximately 2 minutes 520314 (m) lost his interest and started playing with his cellphone. When later 520315 (f) had a question, she called the tutor for help. When the tutor gave some directions 520315 (f) seemed to understand more. Then tutor asked 520315 (f) to explain to her teammate what they had to do and when tutor left students were engaged in an active discussion for about 5 minutes. Then, 520315 (f) continued programming and both were discussing their ideas.

The tendency of 520314 (m) to isolate himself when he had made the necessary explanations might have lead 520315 (f) to ask tutor's help rather than discuss the problem with her teammate. Tutor's intervention brought the team again together to discuss their ideas but 520315 (f) had already taken over.

14.3.1.1.3 EPISODE 3

In another puzzle, students had to make Dash turn when a sound is heard. When a problem came up 520315 (f) asked again the tutor to come close. When tutor gave her feedback 520315 (f) changed the program by herself and after programming for approximately 5 minutes she decided to test it. She didn't include her mate in the decision making about their program but she asked him to make the sound for Dash in order to check if their program was right. 520315 (f) continued to make changes for the next 12 minutes and 520314 (m) seemed to get bored. When a part of the program was decided, 520315 (f) gave to 520314 (m) the tablet and wrote down their program sheet.

Even though students were expected to exchange their roles during the activities, 520315 (f), who got fully engaged in programming, worked separately from her team mate. Not only she preferred again to ask her questions and discussed with the tutor rather than 520314 (m), but also, when she had taken her feedback, she acted by herself not sharing her thoughts and decisions with him. This continued until the program was completed the first part of the program which she noted it on the sheet. 520315 (f) took responsibility for both tasks, coding and writing down the code, while 520314 (m) did not participate. Only when 520315 (f) left the tablet, 520314 (m) took over trying to complete the code, without having discussed with his teammate what had been already done.

14.3.1.1.4 EPISODE 4

Next day students seemed again uncomfortable with each other. While dealing with puzzle 7, they had to make Dash generate 5 numbers to create a 5-digit number. Students found it difficult to understand the puzzle so they asked tutor's help. Tutor explained to the team what they had to do and when he left, 520315 (f) started to program without discussing with her mate who was immediately disengaged and started playing with his cellphone.

Figure 67: 520315 (f) is programming while 520314 (m) watches his cellphone.

After a while 520315 (f) asked the tutor for help but the tutor didn't see her. Even if the boy came closer to help she got disappointed at the same time and she stopped trying. 520314 (m) took the tablet and tried to complete the program while his teammate was disengaged and finally isolated.

Figure 68: When 520314 (m) took over, 520315 (f) isolated herself.

For the next 15 minutes the boy was engaged, programming. When a tutor came closer to the team in order to check how things were going, 520315 (f) seemed to be interested again. When the tutor left, she asked 520314 (m) to give her the tablet but 520314 (m) continued to program so she got disengaged again. The boy then took over until the program was finished.

Figure 69: After tutor's help, 520315 (f) asked for the tablet.

Figure 70: 520315 (f) isolated herself again, as 520314 (m) went on programming by himself.

It seemed that, when one took over, the other was disengaged and isolated. And when somebody isolates themselves they became unapproachable to the other member. In this situation while 520314 (m) preferred to work alone, 520315 (f) asked the tutors for guidance. Even in situations when 520314 (m) was programming and 520315 (f) was isolated, tutor's intervention made her more active and participating.

14.3.1.2 COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT THROUGH MEDIATION

After a while 520314 (m) quitted his effort and 520315 (f) intervned and proposed something. He left the tablet to her and she began to program. After a while she raised her hand, possibly having faced a problem or having a question. 520314 (m) checked her program and tried to explain something to her but she kept asking tutor' advice. When the tutor came close to the team both members were encouraged to explain to him the problem. Tutor listened to 520315 (f) and then 520314 (m) took the tablet and showed him what he proposed. Tutor made questions to 520314 (m) about his proposal including 520315 (f) in the discussion. Students discussed in the presence of the tutor, who ended up listening both sides. It is noted that students are in a good mood, not fighting but feeling uncomfortable with each other. When tutor left, 520315 (f) tested the program which proved to have the desired result. 520314 (m) wrote the solution on the program sheet.

Once again 520315 (f) turned to the tutor for help instead of taking seriously boy's proposal. However, this time tutor didn't seem to give guidance but acted as a facilitator of their communication. Being a mediator between the two helped them express themselves better and in a more open way. This kind of role for the tutor seemed that encouraged the communication making it more effective/efficient, promoting this way better understanding between the members of the team. So the atmosphere became more collaborative as, right after, 520314 (m) took over noting their code and 520315 (f) waited for him to finish in order to go on in the next puzzle together.

14.3.2 Post questionnaire

In the post questionnaire both students answered neutrally about whether working in team was fun. While for 520315 (f) it was interesting but difficult for 520314 (m) it was just difficult, while when asked whether it was interesting he answered neutrally. When asked whether they worked on their own 520314 (m) answered "I don't agree" while 520315 (f) "answered "I agree". However when asked whether they worked as parts of the team 520314 (m) answered neutrally while 520315 (f) answered "I agree". When asked whether they feel that they are listened both students answered neutrally. 520315 (f) doesn't think that her team encouraged her, while 520314 (m) answered neutrally but answered positively when asked whether he liked sharing what he had done with other people. 520315 (f) answered this question neutrally. 520314 (m) admitted he gave up too quickly as he answered "I agree" to this question to which 520315 (f) answered "I don't agree". 520314 (m) also mentions that he learnt about himself that he is not a good teammate.

Students said they didn't have fun working together and this aligns with the video in which they seemed to be uncomfortable with each other and in a distance no matter who was programming.

Figure 71: Students sat in a distance, when 520314 (m) was engaged.

Figure 72: Students sat in a distance, when 520315 (f) was engaged.

It is possible that this situation was due to the initial negative attitude of 520314 (m) towards collaboration in combination with the unconfident attitude of 520315 (f). As 520315 (f) didn't feel encouraged by her teammate, in situations when she faced a problem, she asked tutor's help without engaging her teammate. When tutor acted as a facilitator of their work, 520315 (f) was taking over encouraged by the feedback but separately from 520314 (m) but when he facilitated their communication the members ended up discussing and take more account of each other.

In the first kind of situation 520314 (m) isolated himself, while 520315 (f) was more engaged. With respect to his role in the team 520314 (m) admits that he hadn't been a good teammate and that he hadn't helped anybody.

14.4 DISCUSSION

It can be concluded that in situations where somebody does not have a positive attitude towards collaboration, development of collaborative relationships within the team becomes difficult and more complicated. Disengagement and isolation of a member due to this uncomfortable interaction creates even more distance between members. In this particular situation the result was that students worked separately, as when the one was taking over the other one was disengaged and chose to isolate themselves.

In these situations the role of the tutor seemed to have an important impact. When the instructor gave explanations, the member that had already been engaged, took over. However when the instructor engaged in a discussion both members trying to mediate and thus facilitate their communication, students tended to feel more comfortable and ended up sharing ideas.

Apart from encouraging collaboration the role of the tutor seemed to be crucial in encouraging the participation of members who are not so confident. In this case study 520315 (f) is encouraged by tutors help and her engagement in programming increased as the workshop went on.

14.5 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion:

- Previous negative attitudes towards collaboration possibly led to difficulties in collaborative work.
- Differences in students' attitudes towards their abilities in STEM subjects made collaborative engagement difficult to achieve.
- Given the above, one gender engagement led to other gender disengagement and isolation.
- Ownership of the tablet and tutor's support favoured one gender engagement.
- Tutor in the role of mediator of students' communication favoured collaborative engagement.

15 APPENDIX G: MALTA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

15.1 CONTEXT

Workshop code: AL-3-5-StjosephSliema-14_05_2018-

Workshop title: Introducing Programming and Robotics with Dash and Dot

15.1.1 Description of the activity

“Introducing Programming and Robotics with Dash and Dot” workshop was implemented at the church school of St Joseph Sliema, as an extra-curricular activity on 14th of May 2018. It was led by one tutor with the teacher’s support.

The participants were 25 girls of the age of 9-10 years old. According to the pre-questionnaire students’ answers, only one of the girls did not have a previous experience with robots and 6 of them mentioned they had not programmed in the past. All girls liked using computers, though only 8 of them answered positively to the statement “I know a lot about robots”.

As mentioned in the Activity Plan: *“The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a pre-constructed robot and activities focused around programming Dash through commands and loop statements. Another objective was explaining to students that when searching for a solution programming gives you the advantage of finding multiple answers to activities, and, that some solutions are simpler and more straight forward than others.”*

During the workshop students had to solve 7 puzzles, going from the simplest to more complicated ones. The objectives of the activity plan designed for this workshop included:

Subject related

- Students program and learn mathematical concepts such as probability and random numbers.

Technology use related

- Students use Drag and Drop visuals.

Social and action related

- Students collaborate, share ideas with each other and learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups.

Argumentation and fostering of maker culture

- Students find multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles

Students seated on the floor, in groups of 2 or 3 sharing a tablet and a robot per group. Grouping was random. During the activities students were expected to exchange ideas through dialogue and develop collaborative relationships within team members, taking and exchanging their roles when needed.

15.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In this section data collection and analysis procedures are presented.

15.2.1 Data Collection

The data set collected included:

- video data of the whole class and the focus group,
- students' answers from the pre and post questionnaires,
- students' activity sheets and Draw a scientist sketches and
- students' answers to the interview which was given at the end of the workshop by the students of the focus group.

15.2.1.1 FOCUS GROUP

The focus group was Group 5 and consisted of two female students, 53354 and 53356. Both had previous experience with programming and robotics as they answered that they had built a Lego robot and had "*given instructions to it*" in the past.

According to their answers in the pre-questionnaire, both liked using computers. 53354 mentioned science as her favorite subject and that she liked math, while for 53356 math is the subject she liked the most and science is the one she liked the least, as she wrote "*it's not that interesting*". Regarding their future career, 53354 wanted to become a teacher while 53356 wanted to follow a news reporter career.

When it came to whether they liked working with other people both mentioned they learnt best with other people and they liked working with friends.

15.2.2 Data Analysis

This data analysis was focused on four research questions, referring to:

- Children sharing ideas with/through tangible artefacts
- Intra-relational skills
- Interpersonal skills
- Girls' interest in STEM topics

Examples of children sharing ideas with/through tangible artefacts are given through the description of incidents that took place during the workshop and were observed by the video data. Findings about the development of intra-relational and interpersonal skills arose from the analysis of the students' answers in the post-questionnaire in relevant questions, regarding to what they had learnt for themselves after the workshop and their views about working in team. Findings about girls' interest in STEM topics arose from questionnaires' data.

15.3 FINDINGS

15.3.1 Exchanging ideas between groups through artifacts

Findings regarding the exchange of ideas between groups through tangible artifacts arose from video data analysis. At the first step of video data analysis it was observed that groups tended to share their ideas in the context of:

- Amusement
- Communication of the achievement or demonstration of what it has been done
- Problems

The above situations consisted the analysis categorization (Figure 1).

Figure 73: The categories used for the analysis were "Amusement", "Communication of achievement", "Problems"

Regarding the category of "Amusement", descriptions of episodes during which students exchanged ideas in order to amuse themselves and others were used. In the same way, episodes during which groups interacted in order to demonstrate their achievements are described in the context of "Communication of the achievement" category. Finally, category "Problems" includes episodes where students faced problems and interacted with other groups in order to solve them.

1.1.1.1 GROUPS EXCHANGING IDEAS FOR AMUSEMENT

The episode described below is an example of groups sharing ideas through tangible artifacts in order to amuse themselves and others.

[Episode 1 \[Video data: GOPR0218\]](#)

In the beginning of the first session students had some time to experiment freely with Dash robot and explore his software. Group 5 discovered that there was a way to make Dash correspond to sounds, as the sound of “Hi” made Dash shake.

Figure 74: When 53354 was speaking to Dash, Dash was shaking.

53356 got enthusiastic and turned towards Group 8 to share the idea.

Figure 75: 53356 communicated the idea with a girl in Group 8.

Figure 76: The girl of the Group 8 tried the idea.

It is interesting that this interaction happened in the context of free experimentation with Dash and not in the context of solving a puzzle of the workshop. The process of this free experimentation seemed to favor a positive climate of play in the classroom and as girls played freely, distinction between groups loosened and groups were willing to exchange their ideas about what they discovered.

1.1.1.2 COMMUNICATION OF THE ACHIEVEMENT

During the following episode students' groups communicated their achievements.

Episode 2 [Video data: GOPR0218]

During this episode group 5 and group x had just achieved to solve puzzle 2 working separately.

Figure 77: Group 5 solved puzzle 2, while Group 7 worked separately.

Even if groups worked in their own spaces, when puzzle had been solved by both teams, 53356 decided to move their robot closer to the robot of the Group 7 so they can make them move together.

Figure 78: 53356 took the robot closer to the robot of Group 7 in order to share their achievement.

The above episode is an example of groups sharing ideas in order to communicate their achievements and share their success. During this interaction students of the focus group changed the way they were sitting. As it is also explained below, this interaction and the change that followed in the way students were sitting set the basis of the establishment of a communication culture between groups generally in the classroom, that favored a series of other interactions that went beyond communication of achievement, being more often stimulated by problems that groups faced.

1.1.1.3 PROBLEMS

This section includes the description of three episodes during which interactions between groups were oriented by problems groups faced as they were solving the puzzles.

Episode 3 [Video data: GOPR0218]

After having shared their achievement with Group 7 and while Group 7 wrote their code on the paper sheets, Group 11, which faces a problem with the solution of the puzzle was engaged in a discussion with 53356. For the next 3 minutes both of the girls of the focus group tried to give explanations at Group 11 in order to help them solve the puzzle.

Figure 79: Focus group and Group 11 shared ideas through Dash in order to help Group 11 solve the puzzle.

Interaction between focus group and Group 11 stimulated the interest of Group 8. A student from this group posed a question to 53356. They also seemed to face a problem dealing with puzzle 2. While 53356 showed something to Group 8, a girl from Group 7 also got engaged in the discussion.

Figure 80: Three groups are engaged in the discussion about the solution of the puzzle, using their robots to communicate their ideas.

The next minute their interaction becomes more intense as the three groups move closer to each other looking at their robots which are placed in the middle.

Figure 81: The three groups came closer and worked together.

The above episode offers an example of how, while working in a collaborative and communicative context, close to each other, a problem can become an opportunity of merging of the teams and the generalization/expansion of collaborative relationships in the class.

Episode 4 [Video data: GOPR0218]

Trying to solve the next puzzle focus group seemed to have difficulties and asked for help. At first girls of the focus group turned towards Group 7 and were engaged in a discussion.

Figure 82: Focus group and Group 7 were engaged in a discussion after 53356 posed a question.

After two minutes of active discussion 53356 decided to take the robot of her team closer to the space where Group 7 was working.

Figure 83: 53356 moved her group's Dash in a common space so both focus group and Group 7 could work together and 53354 turns towards Group 7.

For the next approximately 5 minutes girls worked altogether as one group discussing and experimenting with Dash.

Figure 84: Group x and focus group worked together to solve puzzle 3.

Episode 5 [Video data: GOPR0218]

Another episode relevant to the above took place while students solved puzzle 4. This time the focus group interacted with Group 8 in the same way. At first groups were engaged in a discussion about a problem Group 8 faced. After a while the girl of the focus group moved Dash in a common space between the groups.

Figure 85: The girl of the focus group moved Dash in a common place with group z.

For the next 2 minutes students discussed showing Dash and pointing to the direction they should move it.

Figure 86: Focus group interacted with group z in order to help solve a problem.

After having discussed the problem and the possible programming solutions, the girl of the focus group decided to move the tablet in the common place so groups can program their robots together.

Figure 87: Focus group moved the tablet in a common space with group z.

When, after approximately 3 minutes girls are testing the program the robot of the focus group has the desirable result so 53354 wrote down the solution. However the robot of Group 8 did not have the result expected so 53356 turned towards Group 8 and worked with them. At first, she tried to explain something showing Dash but later she moved closer to Group 8 and sat with them.

Figure 88: 53356 showed something to Group 8.

Figure 89: 53356 sat closer to Group 8 in order to help.

It seemed that having established a communicative climate between the groups due to previous interactions, group members were willing to get involved to other groups' work. We could also suppose that when a group, as focus group, is engaged in positive interactions with another group, possible interactions with other groups is also favored as the communicative climate between the groups is generalized in the class.

15.3.1.1 DISCUSSION

During the episodes described interaction between groups took place in the context of:

- Amusement
- Communication of the achievement or demonstration of what it has been done
- Problems

The process of this free experimentation seemed to favor a positive climate of play in the classroom, which loosened the distinction between the groups so that they were more willing to exchange their ideas about what they had discovered in order to amuse themselves. When an interaction with another group proved to be positive, efficient or even amusing, group was more willing to develop communicative relationships with additional groups. This way a communicative culture between groups developed in the context of which more interactions are favored. Having established a communicative and collaborative climate in the class, problems groups faced during the activities were an important stimuli of interaction.

15.3.2 Interpersonal skills

Inter-personal skills are skills people use to interact and communicate with others. For the analysis concerning inter-personal skills data from the pre and post-questionnaires were used. From the pre-questionnaire, students' answers to the questions:

- "I learn best with other people" and
- "I like working with my friends"

were taken into account in combination with students' answers in post-questionnaire questions:

- Working in team was interesting
- Working in team was fun
- I worked as part of a team
- I worked on my own
- I helped someone
- What have you learned about working with other people?

15.3.2.1 QUESTIONNAIRES' ANALYSIS

According to students' answers in the post-questionnaire, 20 of them thought that working in team was interesting and 18 of them mentioned it was fun. Moreover, most of the girls, 21 of them, answered "I strongly agree" when asked whether they worked as part of the team. In the question "I helped someone" only 2 students answered negatively. From the above we could assume that girls were engaged in teamwork and they considered this as a positive experience.

When asked about what they had learnt about working with other people, girls referred to the need of the distribution of the tasks so that all members participate equally, the need to share and hear everybody.

As we can see from the following statements, students acknowledged the need to be a team player while working with other people:

53350: *"we have to take turns"*

53352: *"to take turns"*

53361: *"one should take more turns"*

53369: *"we all take turns and have fun"*

They also thought that sharing is another important factor that favors collaborative work:

53355: *"you have to share"*

53362: *"have to share ideas"*

Moreover they developed positive attitudes towards working with other people:

53372: *"it helps you get along"*

53366: *"It's not so bad working in a team"*

Inter-personal skills concerning communication were also arose as in the question "I was good at listening" 13 students answered "I strongly agree" and 7 students answered "I agree". 53373 when asked about what she had learnt about working with other people, answered: *"you have to hear everybody"*.

15.3.3 Intra-relational skills

Intra-relational skills are skills related to the understanding of how an individual works. For this section data from post-questionnaire were used. Precisely students' answers in the question "What have you learned about yourself?" were considered relevant to the research question.

15.3.3.1 POST-QUESTIONNAIRE

After the workshop students had adopted positive attitudes towards working with others. Some of them mentioned collaborative work as a way of learning they were good at and preferred:

53359: *"I should work in a team"*

53371: *"I am capable to work in a team"*

53356: *"I'm good at working in a team"*

53364: *"I can work in a team"*

Moreover, characteristics like persistence and giving more attention to not so evident aspects of the problem were mentioned:

53360: *"not to give up"*

53361: *"there is more than meets the eye".*

15.3.3.2 INTERVIEW

During the interview with the focus group, tutor asked students how they thought they had learnt what they had learnt. Students answered:

53356: *"doing it step by step"*

53354: *"by observation"*

When asked what they had learn about themselves 53354 answered: *"That I like working in a team."*

For both of the students, activities with robots in the context of collaborative work helped them monitor the way they generated meanings and solved problems.

15.3.4 Girls' interest in STEM topics

15.3.4.1 PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

When asked about their future careers 6 girls mentioned a profession relevant to STEM. 53355 wanted to follow a Coding Teacher or an architect career and 53365 wanted to become a robotics teacher. 53360 and 53372 chose an accountant career, 53358 wanted to become a bioengineer and 53369 wanted to become an engineer.

Regarding to their attitudes towards STEM subjects, the majority of the girls, 19 of 25 mentioned that liked science, 16 of them liked math and 18 of them liked problem solving. Out of 25 girls, who answered the pre-questionnaire 22 of them mentioned at least one STEM subject (math, science, IT, technology) as their favorite and the 14 of them chose more than one STEM subject as their favorite. For 15 girls math is included in their

favorite subjects and 13 girls include science. Almost half of the girls, 12 of them, chose IT as their favorite subject and 6 of them chose technology.

Regarding to the reasons of their choices girls who have chosen STEM subjects refer to the following factors:

- Students' abilities
- Fun,
- Importance of the subject and
- Subjects characteristics/nature.

3 out of 22 girls who have chosen a STEM subject as their favorite refer to reasons relevant to their abilities to the subject/s. 533352, who chose math, science and IT along with English as her favorite subjects, mentioned *"I feel confident working these subjects"* and 53372 wrote that *"I am good at it and enjoy it"*. 53362 mentioned she chose math because it was *"easy for me"*. 6 girls mentioned fun as a factor of their preference and 1 of them, 53369, mentioned that *"these subjects are fun and important"*.

8 girls refer to characteristics of the subjects. When asked why science was their favorite subject, 53353 answers *"I like science for experiments"* and 53358 wrote that *"problem solving keeps me thinking"*. 53363 mentioned she chose math, science and IT as their favorite subjects because of *"hand motivation"*. 53370 wrote that math was her favorite subject because *"you learn how to work things in your mind"*. 53354 wrote that science is her favorite subject because *"I like to learn new things about the world"*.

Only 3 girls chose math as the subject they like the least and 5 of them chose science. Only 1 girl mentioned that the subject she likes the least is IT. Girls who chose math as their least favorite subject refer to their abilities. For example 53354 mentioned *"I am not good at it"* and 53367 wrote that math *"are hard"*. Interest and students' abilities were mentioned to justify their choice of science as the subject the like the least. 53356 answered that science *"is not that interesting"* and 53365 mentioned that *"sometimes I find it boring"*. 53362 and 53368 chose science as their least favorite subject because it is *"hard"*.

When asked about STEM subjects the majority of the girls seemed to have positive attitudes. About math 18 of the girls found it easy 20 girls answered they had fun during math lessons. All girls thought that math is important and only 2 of the girls answer negatively when asked whether they were good at math. 10 of the girls would like to study math in the future.

Concerning science, only 2 of the girls did not think it is easy and 20 of them answered they had fun during science lessons. All girls apart from one found science important and only one of them answered that she was not good at science. 13 girls answered they would like to study science in the future.

15.3.4.2 POST-QUESTIONNAIRE

Concerning their future careers there were students who added career preferences relevant to STEM in the post-workshop questionnaire. 53351, who mentioned she wanted to follow a nursery teacher career in the pre-questionnaire, in the post-workshop questionnaire adds the phrase *"Help to create robots"* as an additional option. Same way 53353, who mentioned she wanted to become a hairdresser in the pre-questionnaire, in the relevant post-questionnaire's question answers *"Scientist or hairdresser"*.

Most of the girls, 23 of them answer they found the problems they solved interesting and fun and only 2 of them found them difficult. Only for 1 girl, 53368, mentioned that working with robots was not interesting nor fun and 3 of them found it difficult. It is possible that the negative answers of 53368 about working with robots are due to her negative experience of collaboration as when asked whether working in team was interesting

and fun she answered “I strongly disagree”, while when asked whether it was difficult for her, she answered “I agree very much”.

Concerning their participation, all girls solved a problem during the activities and programmed a robot. According to their answers, none of the girls gave up quickly and all of them worked hard. When asked whether they would like to try to solve more challenges like this one only one girl, 53368, answered negatively and 5 girls answered that they are not more interested in studying science. 7 girls answered they did not think they are good at math and 4 of them mentioned the same for science. 20 girls answered that they would like to build and program robots to solve problems in the future and 22 of them would like to learn more about programming. 19 of the girls claimed they liked math and science and 18 of them they liked engineering.

In general, girls rated the workshop positively as 21 girls gave 5 stars, 2 of them gave 4 stars and 2 of them 3. 53356 who rated the workshop with 5 stars commented: *“I liked the lesson about robots and enjoyed working hand-on because at school we don't have them”* and 53366 mentioned *“I love engineering and STEM exercises”*. 53369 commented: *“I want to become an engineer and it is fun”*.

15.3.4.3 INTERVIEW

After the workshop, students of the focus group gave an interview about their experience. When asked what they had learn from the workshop 53356 answered:

“I have learnt how to program a robot and I find it very interesting.”

When asked what they had learnt about themselves 53354 answered: *“That I like robots!”*

Later, when asked why they think this kind of activities could help students be more interested in STEM 53356 mentioned:

“Like me, I was not really interested in science but now that I knew something different I am more interested in science because I know that it is fun.”

15.3.4.4 DRAW A SCIENTIST

In the beginning of the workshop girls were asked to draw a scientist while working. Out of the 23 sketches that were collected, 15 of them show a female scientist, 5 of them show both genders, one female and one male scientist, and only 3 of them show a male scientist.

By the above, we can assume that participants consider that a career in science is an option for females the same way it is for males.

15.4 CONCLUSIONS

15.4.1 Exchanging ideas between groups through artifacts

- Groups tended to share their ideas in the context of:
 - Amusement
 - Communication of the achievement or demonstration of what it has been done
 - Problems

- When the first interaction with another group was achieved, group was more willing to develop communicative relationships with additional groups.
- The process of this free experimentation seemed to favor a positive climate of play in the classroom, which loosened the distinction between the groups so that they were more willing to exchange their ideas about what they had discovered.
- The way students were sitting set the basis of the establishment of a communication culture between groups generally in the class.
- While working in a collaborative and communicative context, close to each other, problems seemed to be an opportunity for the groups to merge, establishing a communicative and collaborative climate in the class.
- When a group was engaged in positive interactions with another group, possible interactions with other groups were also favored.

15.4.2 Interpersonal skills

- Girls were engaged in teamwork and they considered this as a positive experience. Additionally they developed positive attitudes towards working with other people.
- Inter-personal skills mentioned by the girls referred to:
 - the need of the distribution of the tasks so that all members participate equally,
 - the need to share and
 - communicate with everybody
 - when you work in a team.

15.4.3 Intra-relational skills

- Some of the students mentioned collaborative work as a way of learning they are good at and prefer
- Characteristics like persistence and giving more attention to not so evident aspects, while one solves a problem were mentioned.
- Activities with robots, in the context of collaborative work, helped students monitor the way they generated meanings and solved problems.

15.4.4 Girls' interest in STEM

- In general, workshop's participants were interested in STEM subjects.
- The reasons of their choices girls who have included STEM subjects in their favorite subjects are relevant to the following factors:
 - Students' abilities
 - Fun,
 - Importance of the subject and
 - Subjects characteristics/nature.
- There were students who added career preferences relevant to STEM in the post-workshop questionnaire.
- Most of the girls found the problems they solved interesting and fun, they would like to try to solve more challenges like this one, they would like to build and program robots to solve problems in the future and to learn more about programming
- In general, girls rated the workshop positively.

- Participants consider that a career in science is an option for females the same way it is for males, as 15 of the “Draw a scientist” sketches showed a female scientist and 5 of them showed both male and female scientists.

16 APPENDIX H: TUW WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

16.1 CONTEXT CASE STUDY 1

Workshop: TUW_140218_20180214 ER4STEM Workshop Robot Elevator

In this case study, we investigated the ER4STEM Workshop Robot Elevator project in an Austrian university computer lab run by TU Wien. Over the course of five hours, 22 students aged seven to nine years old—12 girls and 10 boys from an elementary school—participated in the workshop. The students' primary language was German, but some students also spoke a second language at home: English, Polish, Croatian, Danish, Kurdish, Turkish, Russian, Afghan or Hindi. One girl and two boys had previously built a robot as part of a club activity. Two girls and one boy had built robots at home. Two male tutors from the university and one female teacher from the school oversaw the workshop and supported the students during the activity.

16.1.1 Case Study 1: Description of the activity

A full description of the activity is provided in the activity plan; the following is the activity summary:

This activity was designed for children aged seven to nine years old, including children with no prior knowledge of robotics or programming.

The workshop took place at the university, during regular school time, and was conducted in a computer lab with 12 computer stations. Each station included a mouse, a computer monitor, a keyboard and a Thymio robot. Working in pairs or groups of three students, the participants shared a monitor and the computer software. At the front of the room were a blackboard and a whiteboard with a projector.

The workshop lasted five hours over two phases of two hours and 30 minutes each. The children used a mechanical construction (Figure 1) in which a robot (Thymio) lifted, via deflection pulleys, a weight or some other object. During the first phase of the workshop, participants practiced exercises to learn how to control the robot to perform movements, use proximity sensors, follow a line (using the bottom sensors), use IR communication and use LED lighting.

Figure 90: Mechanical construction.

During the second phase, the participants received the mechanical construction, which was meant to guide them in the right direction. The goal was for the participants to understand and practice two basic concepts: minimising force on a winder with pulleys and with gear ratios.

Phase 1: Basic knowledge and exercises

In this phase, instruction was given regarding the technical functions of the Thymio robot. The teaching method was instructive. The tutors showed the children simple programming examples to introduce common commands.

The students chose their own partners and followed the exercises on the computer by reading the instructions and working with Thymio. They learned the robot's functions in a step-by-step fashion, including how to programme the robot using the programme Aseba (Blockly).

The students completed four exercises:

- Exercise 1 – Push buttons
- Exercise 2 – Horizontal sensors
- Exercise 3 – See a line
- Exercise 4 – What have you done today?

Through these exercises, the children learned how to use the robot's push buttons, how to elicit reactions from the horizontal and bottom sensors and how to write a program. The learning arrangement alternated between instructive and constructive teaching methods. To begin, the students were given instructions on paper, after which they tried in their pairs or groups to write a programme and use their robots. In the last exercise, they wrote an email on a blank sheet of paper about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop. The students' previous knowledge included how to use a computer.

Phase 2: Thymio elevator

In this phase, the students worked in different groups than in phase 1 and completed five exercises:

- Exercise 1 – Set up
- Exercise 2 – Exploration
- Exercise 3 – Control the distance
- Exercise 4 – Story
- Exercise 5 – What have you done today?

Phase 2 was divided into two parts. The first part involved hands-on learning and real-life problems and included exercises 1, 2 and 3. The students were to regulate an elevator using different control settings on the robot. The second part included exercise 4, which focused on using creativity to write a story about robots. It also included exercise 5, during which students wrote a message about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop.

The first exercise in phase 2 involved connecting all the learning materials and working through a real-life problem. The materials included a rope, Thymio, Lego bricks and the complete construction. The students had ten minutes to find a solution to lift the weight using the robot. At the end of the exercise, every group presented its solution, along with the solution's advantages and disadvantages, in plenum. After all the presentations were completed, the class was asked to select one solution and achieve consensus. If consensus could not be achieved, the tutors were to offer a suggestion.

Exercises 2 and 3 were linked to the solution chosen during exercise 1. The goal of exercise 2 was to help students understand the considerations and precautions involved in using the crane. The students explored two main limitations of the system: the maximum and minimum heights of the elevator.

During exercise 2, the students had to answer two questions:

1. Is it possible to move the robot forward for an unlimited distance? Why or why not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this problem?
2. Is it possible to move the robot backward for an unlimited distance? Why or why not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this problem?

In exercise 3 of phase 2, the students programmed the Thymio robot in the following required ways: The robot needed to begin moving if a hand came close to its front proximity sensor. When sensing a hand, the robot needed to move slowly and then speed up as the hand retracted. If no obstacle was detected, the robot needed to wait for further commands. The robot also needed to stop when its limit was reached. If the centre button on the robot was pushed, the robot needed to stop responding to commands.

During this exercise, the students needed to answer two questions before beginning to work on solving the problem:

- Does your current design allow you to complete this exercise? Why or why not? If no, how would you modify it to make it work?
- What considerations must you keep in mind during implementation?

In exercise 4, the students worked in groups to develop a story about using two robots and one crane. They were given paper and Lego blocks to create their robots' appearance. Finally, exercise 5 was similar to exercise 4 in phase 1. The students were asked to write an email or draw on a blank sheet of paper about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop.

The stated objectives of the workshop were:

- Subject-related:

Science:

- Investigate why and how pulleys affect the elevating mechanism.

Technology:

- Use a robot and properly employ its functions.

Engineering:

- Think about solutions for how to attach the robot to the system and think about where this kind of system is used.

Arts:

- Tell a story about what the robots are doing and create a design for the Thymio robots using Legos.

Mathematics:

- Understand basic physical and mathematics concepts of gear ratios and pulley mechanisms (e.g., bicycle gear ratios).

Other: Social skills

- The school classes were divided into groups. Each group had its own area of responsibility (e.g., design, programming, or other). The children were told to collaborate and organise the necessary exchange of information on their own.

As stated in the objectives, the students used a Thymio robot, which was programmed with an elevator construction, as shown in Figure 91.

Figure 91. Robot linked to the construction.

16.2 CASE STUDY 1: DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

16.2.1 Case Study 1: Data collection

Of the 22 students who participated in phase one of the workshop, 21 (10 males and 11 females) gave consent to be included in the research project and filled out the pre-questionnaire. Of the 26 students who participated in phase two of the workshop, 25 (10 males and 13 females) gave consent to be included in the research project, and 24 filled out the post-questionnaire. Their age range was 7 to 9. Two tutors from TU Wien taught and led the workshop.

16.2.1.1 CASE STUDY 1: FOCUS GROUP

The focus group selected for the phase one analysis was a mixed-gender pair, consisting of one boy and one girl (f12057, m12063). In phase two, the analysed focus group was a mixed-gender group, consisting of two boys and two girls (f12068, m12069, m12070, f13003), as shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92. Photograph of focus group members.

16.2.2 Case Study 1: Data analysis

The data analysis is based on the pre- and post-questionnaires, observations, the activity plan and video recordings of the focus group with the camera positioned in front of the students on the right-hand side of the blackboard.

The data analysis involved looking for particular incidents, with the research questions decided in advance based on the research team's observations, the data collection and overall research priorities:

- Which students' interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?
- Which students changed their attitudes in STEM?
- Are girls interested in STEM topics?
- What evidence is there of learning?
- Did one gender take over?

16.3 CASE STUDY 1: FINDINGS

This report structures its findings in two sections. The first section reports the questionnaire findings for the following questions: 'Which students' interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?', 'Are girls interested in STEM topics?' and 'What evidence is there of learning?' The second section reports the observation findings concerning the question 'Did one gender take over?'

16.3.1 Case Study 1: Findings in the questionnaires

The pre- and post-questionnaires provided useful background information about the students and evidence of increased learning and interest in STEM careers through the workshop. In total, 22 students completed the pre- and post-questionnaires.

16.3.1.1 CASE STUDY 1: WHAT EVIDENCE IS THERE OF LEARNING?

This section answers the question ‘What evidence is there of learning?’ based on the post-questionnaires, letters and observations. The question is answered using responses to the post-questionnaire question ‘What have you learned . . .?’ separated by gender, as presented in Table 18. Most of the students answered that they learned how to programme a robot and how to work with friends. In response to the question ‘What have you learned about yourself?’, 25% of the girls and 30% of the boys answered that they learned how to programme a robot. In response to the question ‘What have you learned about working with other people?’, two of the girls and one of the boys answered that they learned that working with friends was nice. Finally, in response to the question ‘What have you learned about robots?’, four of the girls and three of the boys answered that they learned programming.

Table 18: Post-questionnaire responses concerning what students learned during the workshop.

Statements	Female	Male	Total
What have you learned...			
...about yourself?			
To programme robots	3	3	6
To read	2	0	2
To work with a computer	0	2	2
To work together	1	1	2
To listen carefully	0	1	1
I am clever	0	1	1
That I should work together with others	1	0	1
...about working with other people?			
Working with friends is nice	2	1	3
Working together is more difficult	0	2	2
Teamwork	0	2	2
Listening	1	1	2
Programming	2	0	2
That one should not disturb the group	0	1	1
To help	1	0	1
Thinking together	0	1	1
That one must often work in teams	0	1	1
Nothing	1	0	1
...about robots?			
Programming	4	3	7
About Thymio	1	1	2
About computers (computer-to-robot)	2	0	2
Controlling a robot is difficult	0	2	2
Technical knowledge about sensors	0	1	1
That I can learn and remember things well	0	1	1

Figure 4 shows the students’ attitudes towards teamwork during the workshop. Of the 22 students, 18 strongly agreed that ‘Working in a team was fun’ and ‘Working in a team was interesting’.

Figure 93. Case study 1: Post-questionnaire perceptions of working in a team.

16.3.1.2 CASE STUDY 1: DISCUSSION—EVIDENCE OF LEARNING

A sub-question was: ‘What did learn students about teamwork?’

Table 1 is divided into three parts: learning about yourself, learning with other people and learning about robots. The first part involved the participants’ internal processes, and the results show that the students learned to work together, to listen carefully and that they should work together with others. The second part involved the participants’ external processes of learning with other people, and the results show that they learned that working with friends is nice, that working together is more difficult, that teamwork and listen are good, that one should not disturb the group, that helping and thinking together are good, and that one must often work in a team. The third part included no relevant results about teamwork. All answers about teamwork answered at the first part 50% girls and 50% boys and at the second part 26% girls and 74% boys. This shows that more boys than girls felt that they learned about teamwork through the workshop. Figure 4 shows that most students found teamwork to be interesting and fun. This result illustrates the workshop’s impact on teamwork.

The third part involved the participants’ processes of learning about robots. The students learned programming, about Thymio, about computers, that controlling a robot was difficult, technical knowledge about sensors and that they could learn and remember things well. The students learned with robots more than technical background, they learned with robots their personal learning performance.

16.3.1.3 CASE STUDY 1: WHAT ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS?

The section discusses responses to the statement ‘I am now more interested in studying science’ in the post-questionnaires.

Figure 94: Post-questionnaire: I am now more interested in studying science.

At the end of the workshop, seven girls and five boys said that they were more interested in studying science. Of the 12 students who answered the post-questionnaire statement 'I am now more interested in studying science' with 'yes', 2 answered the pre-questionnaire statement 'I like science' with 'neither'. Furthermore, of these 12 students, 4 girls and 1 boy had previously answered 'yes' to the statement 'Science is the subject I like the least' in the pre-questionnaire.

Between the two questionnaires, three students changed their answers to the question 'In the future, what job would you like to do?' One male student (9 years old) changed his answer from 'sport and science' on the pre-questionnaire to 'arts' on the post-questionnaire, one female student (7 years old) changed her answer from 'horsewoman' on the pre-questionnaire to 'sports' on the post-questionnaire and another male student (7 years old) changed his answer from 'science' on the pre-questionnaire to 'arts' on the post-questionnaire.

16.3.1.4 CASE STUDY 1: DISCUSSION—WHAT ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGE INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS?

One boy reported that his least-favourite subject before the workshop was science and that, after the workshop, he was interested in studying science. This change shows that the activities in the workshop encouraged interest in STEM careers. Furthermore, of the 22 participating students, 12 were interested in studying science after the workshop.

16.3.1.5 CASE STUDY 1: ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?

The findings concerning girls' interest in STEM are drawn from the pre-questionnaire responses (Figure 95 through 8) concerning girls' interest in math (Figure 95), a gender comparison in math (Figure 6), girls' interest in science (Figure 97) and a gender comparison in science (Figure 8), as well as from the post-questionnaire responses concerning girls' interest in STEM topics (Figure 99) and a gender comparison (Figure 100).

Figure 95 shows that girls rated the statement 'Math is important' most highly.

Figure 95: Case Study 1: Pre-Questionnaire: Girls' interest in math.

Figure 96 compares the students’ interest in math by gender. The values are mean values from the Likert scales. The means for the statements ‘Math is important’ and ‘I have to work on my own in math’ were nearly the same for both genders. For all other statements, the boys’ means were higher.

Figure 96: Case Study 1: Comparison of interest in math by gender.

The results for girls’ interest in science can be seen in Figure 97, which shows that girls agreed most strongly with the statements ‘Science is important’ and ‘My friends are good at science’.

Figure 97: Case Study 1: Pre-questionnaire: Girls' interest in science.

Figure 98 compares the students' interest in math by gender. The values are mean values from the Likert scales. The mean for the statement 'My friends are good at science' was almost the same for both genders. For all other statements, the mean was higher for boys.

Figure 98: Case Study 1: Comparison of interest in science by gender.

Figure 99 shows that 80% of the girls answered 'yes' to the statements 'I like engineering' and 'I would like to learn more about programming'. Furthermore, 100% of the girls answered 'yes' to the statement 'I like using the computer'. Finally, 81% of the girls answered 'yes' to the statement 'I like science', and 55% answered 'yes' to the statement 'I like math'.

Figure 99: Case Study 1: Post-questionnaire: Girls' interest in STEM topics.

Figure 100 shows that more girls were interested in studying science’ and ‘I would like to build and program robots to solve problems in the future’ than boys. All students (boys and girls) liked using computers.

Figure 100: Case Study 1: Comparison of interest in STEM topics after the workshop by gender (Part 1).

Figure 101 shows that, for all statements, more boys than girls answered ‘yes’.

Figure 101: Case Study 1: Comparison of interest in STEM topics after the workshop by gender (Part 2).

16.3.1.6 CASE STUDY 1: DISCUSSION—ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?

Figure 98 shows that the mean for the statement ‘My friends are good at math’ was higher for girls than for boys. This result could be interpreted as indicating that girls perceive their peer group or simply others to be better at math than they are. Figure 98 shows that the means for the statements ‘I am good at science’ and ‘I have fun in science lessons’ were higher for girls than for boys. This shows that, at the beginning of the workshop, the girls had more fun in science lessons and perceived themselves as being good at science. After the workshop, 81% of the girls said that they like science, but more boys answered ‘yes’ to the same statement. A gendered change happened after the workshop in math (see Figure 100). The results for girls and boys after the workshop were nearly identical; however, before the workshop, boys exhibited a higher mean in response to the statement ‘I am good at math’. This change in gender balance over the course of the workshop could indicate that the workshop positively influenced the girls’ perceptions of math.

16.3.1.7 CASE STUDY 1: WHICH STUDENTS CHANGED THEIR ATTITUDES CONCERNING STEM?

Five students said that math was their least-favourite subject, and six said that science was their least-favourite subject. Two girls said that their least-favourite subjects were math and science, but one of these answered ‘yes’ to ‘I like math’ and ‘I like science’ on the post-questionnaire.

Table 19. Case Study 1: Students changed their attitudes towards science.

Student ID	Gender	Pre <i>I like science</i> [5-item Likert scale]	Pre <i>Least-favourite subject</i>	Post <i>I am now more interested in studying science. [Yes/No]</i>	Post <i>I like science. [Yes/No]</i>
12055	Girl	Neither	Math, Science	Yes	Yes
12056	Girl	Neither		Yes	Yes
12057	Girl	Neither	Science		Yes
12064	Girl	Neither		Yes	No
13003	Girl	Strongly agree	Math, Science		Yes

Table 19 shows that three girls answered the question ‘I like science’ with ‘neither’ on the pre-questionnaires, but ‘yes’ on the post-questionnaires at the statement ‘I am now more interested in studying science.’. This result indicates changing attitudes towards STEM. Some girls also stated on the pre-questionnaire that their

least-favourite subject was science, but answered 'yes' to the statement 'I like science' on the post-questionnaire.

16.3.1.8 CASE STUDY 1: DID ONE GENDER TAKE OVER?

This section answers the question "Did one gender take over?" based on the observations.

First Incident:

The findings come from the focus group. The students sit on the floor and programme the robot on a maze. There are two boys and three girls. At the beginning, one boy programmes the robot (see Figure 102). After several seconds, the girl takes the robot and programmes it (see Figure 103).

Figure 102: Case Study 1: Boy programming a robot.

Figure 103: Case Study 1: Girl takes over.

There is a short moment when the girl takes the robot and programmes it. While the girl programmes the robot, the boy comments on her activity using negative gestures (see Figure 104).

Figure 104: Case Study 1: Negative gesture from boy.

Second Incident:

The group is sitting on the floor. One boy wants to programme the robot, but one girl (12056) takes the robot out of his hands (see Figure 105 and Figure 106).

Figure 105: Case Study 1: A girl takes the robot.

Figure 106: Case Study 1: A girl holds the robot.

16.3.1.9 DISCUSSION—DID ONE GENDER TAKE OVER?

The above-described incidents represent cases of gender takeover. In both cases, girls took over the situation, taking the robot away from the boys to programme it. In one case, the observation showed a negative reaction from a boy. In the other case, the boy exhibited no negative communication or reaction. The girls were friendly and respectful. Thus, the workshop empowered the girls to programme the robots through hands-on activities.

16.4 CONCLUSION

This case study shows the influence of the robot workshop on STEM topics and gender takeover. In the second observed incident, a girl took over the situation and programmed the robot. This girl answered the statement 'I like science' and 'I like using computer' with 'neither' on the pre-questionnaire, but 'yes' on the post-questionnaire. Similarly, three other girls changed their responses to the statement 'I like science' from 'neither' on the pre-questionnaire to 'yes' on the post-questionnaire. These post-questionnaire answers indicate learning based on self-assessment, which is relevant for girls' empowerment in teamwork and programming and shows a positive attitude towards teamwork. This result shows that the workshop fostered collaboration skills among the girls.

17 APPENDIX I: TUW WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

17.1 CONTEXT CASE STUDY 2

Workshop: TUW_220218_20180222 ER4STEM Workshop Robot Elevator

In this case study, we investigated the 'ER4STEM Workshop Robot Elevator' in Austria, run by TU Wien. Twenty-five students aged 7 to 9 years old—15 girls and 10 boys from an elementary school—participated in the workshop over 5 hours. The students' primary language was German, but some students spoke a second language at home: English, French, Spanish, Russian or Bulgarian. Two female and three male students previously had built a robot as part of a club activity. One girl and two boys had built a robot at home. Two male tutors from the university and one female teacher from the school oversaw the workshop and supported the students during the activity.

17.1.1 Case Study 2: Description of the Activity

A full description of the activity is provided in the activity plan; the following is the activity summary:

This activity was designed for children aged seven to nine years old, including children with no prior knowledge of robotics or programming.

The workshop took place at the university, during regular school time, and was conducted in a computer lab with 12 computer stations. Each station included a mouse, a computer monitor, a keyboard and a Thymio robot. Working in pairs or groups of three students, the participants shared a monitor and the computer software. At the front of the room were a blackboard and a whiteboard with a projector.

The workshop lasted five hours over two phases of two hours and 30 minutes each. The children used a mechanical construction (Figure 107) in which a robot (Thymio) lifted, via deflection pulleys, a weight or some other object. During the first phase of the workshop, participants practiced exercises to learn how to control the robot to perform movements, use proximity sensors, follow a line (using the bottom sensors), use IR communication and use LED lighting.

Figure 107: Case Study 2: Mechanical construction.

During the second phase, the participants received the mechanical construction, which was meant to guide them in the right direction. The goal was for the participants to understand and practice two basic concepts: minimising force on a winder with pulleys and with gear ratios.

Phase 1: Basic knowledge and exercises

In this phase, instruction was given regarding the technical functions of the Thymio robot. The teaching method was instructive. The tutors showed the children simple programming examples to introduce common commands.

The students chose their own partners and followed the exercises on the computer by reading the instructions and working with Thymio. They learned the robot's functions in a step-by-step fashion, including how to programme the robot using the programme Aseba (Blockly).

The students completed four exercises:

- Exercise 1 – Push buttons
- Exercise 2 – Horizontal sensors
- Exercise 3 – See a line
- Exercise 4 – What have you done today?

Through these exercises, the children learned how to use the robot's push buttons, how to elicit reactions from the horizontal and bottom sensors and how to write a program. The learning arrangement alternated between instructive and constructive teaching methods. To begin, the students were given instructions on paper, after which they tried in their pairs or groups to write a programme and use their robots. In the last exercise, they wrote an email on a blank sheet of paper about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop. The students' previous knowledge included how to use a computer.

Phase 2: Thymio elevator

In this phase, the students worked in different groups than in phase 1 and completed five exercises:

- Exercise 1 – Set up
- Exercise 2 – Exploration
- Exercise 3 – Control the distance
- Exercise 4 – Story
- Exercise 5 – What have you done today?

Phase 2 was divided into two parts. The first part involved hands-on learning and real-life problems and included exercises 1, 2 and 3. The students were to regulate an elevator using different control settings on the robot. The second part included exercise 4, which focused on using creativity to write a story about robots. It also included exercise 5, during which students wrote a message about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop.

The first exercise in phase 2 involved connecting all the learning materials and working through a real-life problem. The materials included a rope, Thymio, Lego bricks and the complete construction. The students had ten minutes to find a solution to lift the weight using the robot. At the end of the exercise, every group presented its solution, along with the solution's advantages and disadvantages, in plenum. After all the

presentations were completed, the class was asked to select one solution and achieve consensus. If consensus could not be achieved, the tutors were to offer a suggestion.

Exercises 2 and 3 were linked to the solution chosen during exercise 1. The goal of exercise 2 was to help students understand the considerations and precautions involved in using the crane. The students explored two main limitations of the system: the maximum and minimum heights of the elevator.

During exercise 2, the students had to answer two questions:

3. Is it possible to move the robot forward for an unlimited distance? Why or why not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this problem?
4. Is it possible to move the robot backward for an unlimited distance? Why or why not? If your answer was no, how would you solve this problem?

In exercise 3 of phase 2, the students programmed the Thymio robot in the following required ways: The robot needed to begin moving if a hand came close to its front proximity sensor. When sensing a hand, the robot needed to move slowly and then speed up as the hand retracted. If no obstacle was detected, the robot needed to wait for further commands. The robot also needed to stop when its limit was reached. If the centre button on the robot was pushed, the robot needed to stop responding to commands.

During this exercise, the students needed to answer two questions before beginning to work on solving the problem:

- Does your current design allow you to complete this exercise? Why or why not? If no, how would you modify it to make it work?
- What considerations must you keep in mind during implementation?

In exercise 4, the students worked in groups to develop a story about using two robots and one crane. They were given paper and Lego blocks to create their robots' appearance. Finally, exercise 5 was similar to exercise 4 in phase 1. The students were asked to write an email or draw on a blank sheet of paper about their activities, their learning outcomes during the workshop and their likes and dislikes concerning the workshop.

The stated objectives of the workshop were:

- Subject-related:

Science:

- Investigate why and how pulleys affect the elevating mechanism.

Technology:

- Use a robot and properly employ its functions.

Engineering:

- Think about solutions for how to attach the robot to the system and think about where this kind of system is used.

Arts:

- Tell a story about what the robots are doing and create a design for the Thymio robots using Legos.

Mathematics:

- Understand basic physical and mathematics concepts of gear ratios and pulley mechanisms (e.g., bicycle gear ratios).

Other: Social skills

- The school classes were divided into groups. Each group had its own area of responsibility (e.g., design, programming, or other). The children were told to collaborate and organise the necessary exchange of information on their own.

As stated in the objectives, the students used a Thymio robot, which was programmed with an elevator construction, as shown in Figure 108.

Figure 108. Case Study 2: Robot linked with the construction

17.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

17.2.1 Case Study 2: Data Collection

Out of the 25 students who participated in phase one of the workshop, 19 gave consent to be included in observation during the research project, and all 25 filled out the pre-questionnaires, 10 males and 15 females. Their age range was 7 to 9. Out of the 24 students who participated in phase two of the workshop, 18 consented to being included in observations for the research project, and 24 filled out the post-questionnaires, 9 males and 15 females. Three tutors from TU Wien taught and led the workshop, and three teachers provided oversight.

17.2.1.1 CASE STUDY 2: FOCUS GROUP

The analysed focus group for phase one was a pair, consisting of two boys (13008 and 13012 are 8 years old); in phase two, the analysed focus group was a group, consisting of four boys (13005, 130007, 13008, 13012), shown in Figure 109.

Figure 109. Case study 2: Photograph of focus group members

17.2.2 Case Study 2: Data Analysis

The data analysis was based on video recordings of the focus group. To make the recordings, a camera was placed in front of the students on the right-hand side of the blackboard. Data analysis also included pre- and post-questionnaires, a focus group interview (phase 2), observational notes and reflections from the tutors, the activity plan and learning artefacts.

Research questions were determined in advance based on the research team's observations, the data collection and overall research priorities. As such, data analysis involved looking for particular incidents based on the following research questions:

- Which students' interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?
- Which students changed their attitude in STEM?
- Are girls interested in STEM topics?
- What evidence is there of learning?

17.3 CASE STUDY 2: FINDINGS

This report structures its findings in two sections. The first section reports on our findings for the following question: 'What evidence is there of learning?' The second section details the questionnaire findings for the

following questions: ‘Which students’ had their interest in STEM careers encouraged during the workshop?’, ‘Which students changed their attitudes about STEM?’ and ‘Were girls interested in STEM topics?’

17.3.1 Case Study 2: What Evidence Is There of Learning?

This section explores the evidence of learning based on the post-questionnaires, letters and observations. Table 20 details students’ answers to the following post-questionnaire inquiry: ‘What have you learned . . .?’ The table separates the responses by female and male students. Most of the students answered that they learned that they are good at programming and that working with other people is difficult. 3 students replied that they learning nothing about robots. The percentage of the next results represent the percent of the gender group. The Post-questionnaires answered 15 girls and 9 boys. Two of the ten girls and two of the 9 boys answered that they were good at programming. 13% of the girls and 40% of the boys answered that they learned that working with others is difficult. One girl and two boys answered that they learned nothing about robots.

Table 20. Case study 2: Post-questionnaire responses to questions about what students learned during the workshop

Statements	Female	Male	Total
What have you learned...			
...about yourself?			
I am good at programming.	2	2	4
Working together	2	0	2
Solving problems	2	0	2
Nothing	0	2	2
Programming robots	1	0	1
Being creative, communicating with a robot	1	0	1
I have learned about robots.	0	1	1
I like robots.	0	1	1
...about working with other people?			
It is difficult.	2	2	4
We should work together.	4	0	4
That it is fun	3	0	3
Nothing	1	1	2
That I want to work by myself	1	0	1
That one has to work in a team	0	1	1
That one should share and not fight	1	0	1
That we can solve the problems together	1	0	1
That working together is better	1	0	1
Everybody should be nice to others	0	1	1
...about robots?			
Nothing	1	2	3
Robots make music.	2	0	2
Robots are useful.	1	1	2
That they are bad	1	1	2
Robots did not interest me.	1	0	1
Files	1	0	1
Robots are clever.	1	0	1
I can program robots.	1	0	1
I am clever.	1	0	1
That one has to program them first	0	1	1
That they are annoying	1	0	1
That they are useful	0	1	1
That they are very funny	1	0	1
They are things.	1	0	1

Figure 110 shows that 10 of 24 students strongly agreed with the statement that ‘working in a team was fun’, and 9 of 23 students strongly agreed that ‘working in a team was interesting’. These 10 students had a positive attitude in teamwork during the workshop and could be more motivated to work in teams in the future and thus to improve their collaboration skills.

Figure 110. Case study 2: Post-questionnaire perceptions of working on a team

Exercise four of the activity plan asked students to develop a story about two robots (Thymio) and one crane. Figure 111 shows an artefact of learning, an illustrated picture. A student drew a picture of a story with a crane and two Thymios. This image demonstrates the fostering of creativity in exercise 4 of phase 2.

Figure 111. Case study 2: Creativity during storytelling

Figure 112 and Figure 113 show a real situation from phase 1 of the workshop.

Figure 114 emerged from exercise 4 of phase 1, a response to this question: ‘What have you done today?’

Figure 112. Case study 2: Thymio pushes the button (Exercise 1)

Figure 113. Case study 3: Write a program for Thymio (Exercises 2 and 3)

Figure 114. Drawing from a student about his reflections on phase 1 of the workshop

Student (f12041) draw a picture about her activity (seen in Figure 114). This figure could be interpreted as the student using a computer and Thymio. Comparing the two illustrations shows that students held their own perceptions of the workshop, and that she (f12041) remembered clear details from the workshop. This could be a evidence for sustainable learning.

17.3.1.1 CASE STUDY 2: DISCUSSION ABOUT EVIDENCE OF LEARNING

A sub-question to this research asked, ‘What did students learn about teamwork?’

To answer this question, Table 20 is divided into three parts: learning about yourself, learning with other people and learning about robots. The first part involves the participants’ internal processes, and the results

show that the students learned to work together. The second part includes the students' external processes of learning with other people, and the results indicate that they learned that working with others is difficult, that they should work together, that working together is fun, that just one team member had to work, that a team member should share and not fight, that they could solve problems together, that working together is better and that everybody should be nice to others. The third part revealed no relevant results about teamwork. The answer about teamwork came at the first part just from girls, two girls reported that they learned to work together and at the second part more girls reported about team work than boys; 12 girls and 2 boys reported that they learned something about teamwork. The statements from girls were mostly positive. This result shows that more girls than boys felt that they learned about teamwork through the workshop. Figure 110 shows that most students found teamwork to be interesting and fun. This result illustrates the workshop's impact on teamwork.

The third part involved the participants' processes of learning about robots. Students reported that they learned about robots in several ways: robots made music, robots were useful, robots were bad, robots did not interest me, robots were clever, that one had to program them first, that they were annoying, that they were useful, that they were very funny and that they are things.

The third part shows attitudes about robots. The positive attitudes were very fun, useful and clever, while the negative attitudes about robots included that they were bad, annoying or did not interest me. Several students reported that robots have a character and can be clever or bad. The students developed different attitudes to robots during the workshop.

17.3.2 Case Study 2: Findings in Questionnaires

The pre- and post-questionnaires provided useful background information about the students and their interests in STEM careers after the workshop. 25 students completed the pre- and post-questionnaires.

17.3.2.1 CASE STUDY 2: WHICH ACTIVITIES ENCOURAGED INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS?

To respond to this question, we consider students' responses to this statement from the post-questionnaire: 'I am now more interested in studying science'.

Figure 115. Case study 2: Post-questionnaire: I am now more interested in studying science

13 of 24 students said that they were more interested in studying science at the end of the workshop (four boys, nine girls).

17.3.2.2 CASE STUDY 2: ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?

The findings concerning girls’ interest in STEM are drawn from the pre-questionnaire responses (Figure 116 through Figure 119) concerning girls’ interest in math (Figure 116), a gender comparison in math (Figure 117), girls’ interest in science (Figure 118) and a gender comparison in science (Figure 119). To respond to this question, we also consider post-questionnaire responses concerning girls’ interest in STEM topics (Figure 120) and a related gender comparison (Figure 121).

Figure 116. Case study 2: Pre-questionnaire: Girls and interest in math

Figure 117 compares the students’ interest in math by gender. The values are mean values from the Likert scales. The means for the statements ‘Math is important’ and ‘I have to work on my own in math’ were higher for girls than boys. The means for the statement ‘My friends are good at maths’ were nearly the same for both genders. For all other statements, the boys’ means were higher.

Figure 117. Case study 2: Comparison of gender interest in math

The results for girls’ interest in science can be seen in Figure 118, which shows that girls agreed most strongly with the statements ‘Science is important’ and ‘I have fun in science lessons’.

Figure 118. Case study 2: Pre-questionnaire: Girls and interest in science

Figure 119 compares the students’ interest in math by gender. The values are mean values from the Likert scales. The means for the statements ‘Science is easy’ and ‘My teacher says I am good at science’ were nearly the same for both genders. The means for the statements ‘I have fun in science lessons’, ‘I have to work on my own in science’, ‘I am good at science’ and ‘My friends are good at science’ were higher for girls than boys. For all other statements, the means were higher for boys.

Figure 119. Case study 2: Comparison of gender interest in science

Figure 120 shows that 85% of the girls answered ‘yes’ to the statements ‘I like engineering’ and ‘I like science’. Furthermore, 53% of the girls answered ‘yes’ to the statement ‘I like maths’. Finally, 60% of the girls answered ‘yes’ to the statement ‘I like using computers’, and 80% answered ‘yes’ to the statement ‘I think I am good at maths’.

Figure 120. Case study 2: Post-questionnaire: Girls and their Interest in STEM topics

Figure 121 shows that more girls were interested in studying science than boys. In addition, more girls agreed with the statement ‘I think I am good at maths’.

Figure 121. Case study 2: Comparison of gender interest in STEM topics after the workshop part 1

Figure 122 shows that more girls said yes at the statement ‘I understanding how robots can be used to solve a problem’ than boys.

Figure 122. Case study 2: Comparison of gender interest in STEM topics after the workshop part 2

17.3.2.3 CASE STUDY 2: DISCUSSION—ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?

Figure 117 shows that the mean for the statement ‘Math is important’ was higher for girls than for boys. This result could be interpreted as indicating that girls plan more for a STEM career than boys. Figure 119 shows that the means for the statements ‘I have fun in science lessons’, ‘I have to work on my own in science’, ‘I am good at science’ and ‘My friends are good at science’ were higher for girls than boys. This finding shows that, at the beginning of the workshop, girls found science lessons to be fun and perceived themselves as being good at science and working alone on science more than boys. Girls believe that they are good at science, and that their peer groups are good at science. After the workshop, 84,6% of the girls said that they like science, but more boys answered ‘yes’ to the same statement. As a result, a gendered change happened after the workshop in terms of science (see Figure 15 compare with Figure 122). At the beginning of the workshop was the mean from the boys higher than from girls. After the workshop more girls said ‘Yes’ at the statement ‘I think I am good at science’ than boys.

17.3.2.4 CASE STUDY 2: WHICH STUDENTS CHANGED THEIR ATTITUDE IN STEM?

Three students said that math was their least-favourite subject, and one said that science was their least-favourite subject.

Table 21. Case study 2: Students changed their attitudes towards science

Student ID	Gender	Pre	Pre	Pre	Post	Post	Post
		<i>I like math [5-item Likert scale]</i>	<i>I like science [5-item Likert scale]</i>	<i>Least-favourite subject</i>	<i>I am now more interested in studying science. [Yes/No]</i>	<i>I like math [5-item Likert scale]</i>	<i>I like science. [Yes/No]</i>
12027	Boy	Strongly disagree	Neither	Math	No	No	Yes
12029	Boy	Strongly agree	Neither	Science	No	Yes	No
12030	Boy	Neither	Neither		Yes	Yes	Yes
12031	Boy	Disagree	Neither	Math	No	No	Yes
12036	Boy	Strongly Agree	Neither		No	Yes	Yes

12037	Boy	Strongly Disagree	Neither	Math	No	No	No
12048	Girl	Agree	Neither	Math	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 21 shows that six boys answered the question 'I like science' with 'neither' on the pre-questionnaires, but four of them chose 'yes' on the post-questionnaires at the statement 'I like science.'. This result indicates their changing attitudes towards STEM. On the pre-questionnaire, one of the girls also replied to the statement 'I like science' with 'neither', but chose 'yes' on the post-questionnaire.

17.4 CASE STUDY 2: CONCLUSION

This brief overview has responded to four research questions: 'Which students had their interest in STEM careers encouraged during the workshop?', 'Which students changed their attitudes about STEM?', 'Were girls interested in STEM topics?' and 'What evidence is there of learning?'. The main findings were that gender change by girls happened in science. That the students had positive attitudes in teamwork. Five students (4 boys, 1 girl) changed their attitudes about science. 13 students considered a STEM career. They also demonstrated both positive and negative attitudes about robots. More boys were interested in STEM topics than girls, but more girls were interested in studying science. At the first phase of the workshop were more gender-mixed at the groups than in the second phase. The tutors have to lead that in all phases are gender-mixed at the groups.

18 APPENDIX J: PRIA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

1.1 CONTEXT CASE STUDY 1

Workshop: PRIA_170928 ER4STEM Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop

In this case study, we investigated the ‘Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop’ in Austria, run by PRIA. Eighteen students aged 8–11 years (6 girls and 12 boys) from an elementary school participated in the workshop in two sessions with a total of 8 hours. The primary language at school was German, and all the students spoke another language at home, namely Susu, Turkish, Polish, Pakistani, Bengali, Arabic, Slovakian, Arabian, Serbian, Croatian or Bosnian. Most had previously built a robot at home and programmed a robot as part of a club activity. The activity plan was designed for use in schools in a low socioeconomic area. The workshop was led by four tutors. The robotics kit was Hedgehog, and the programming language was Python.

1.1.1 Case Study 1: Description of the Activity

A full description of the activity is provided in the activity plan; the following is the activity summary:

This activity was designed for children who have never encountered robotics and/or programming. The prior knowledge required comprises basic reading skills and understanding of the necessary numeric values; basic knowledge of working with computers was advantageous. The workshop was suitable for children aged 8–11 years old. It was used in schools in a low socioeconomic area, and a large percentage of the students had German as their second language. The aim of the workshop was to familiarise the students with the concepts of design thinking, as well as robotics and programming. It consisted of two main sessions held by the workshop tutors in an open space for testing and building the robots, with notebooks or computers, and took place indoors. The first session focussed on giving the students an introduction to design thinking and considered what type of robot they could build. The second session explained the basics of programming. The goal was to drive the robot. During the activities, the students were expected to observe, communicate, build a robot, program a robot, discuss their ideas with a classmate and present their work in front of their peers. The workshop was divided into two parts. The following slogan for the learning process was used in the first phase: ‘I can create something in a small amount of time’. In the second part, the goal was that the students would try out their code and adapt it to the task.

They used Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller. The workshop should develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. The students learning outcomes were visual or python program for the hedgehog controller.

PART 1:

The **first activity** was named “Introduction on the lego mindstorm EV3 set” and lasts 10 minutes. The orchestration happened in a plenum discussion. The tutor and all students gave a short introduction about their name, age, knowledge, robots, etc.). The teaching method was instruction and the expected forms of students dialogue were instruction and discussion.

The **second activity** was named “Clapping Game – Errors Happen” and lasts 10 to 15 minutes. The orchestration happens in pairs and classwork. The tutors made the task of the game more complicated after a while to attain more mistakes and the game rules were changed after some time, too. The aim of the activity

was to give the students the feeling, that making mistakes is not bad but rather something which is ok to happen to promote a more freely idea development process. The teaching method was demonstration with exercises.

The **third activity** was named “Design and make glasses for a scientist.” and lasts 50 to 60 minutes. The orchestration happens in work alone and share your ideas in pairs. The students were asked about what they know about scientists and what characteristics a scientist needs to have. Afterwards the students got different materials and the task to create a pair of glasses in 2 minutes. The time restriction should help them in trying out the first ideas which came to their mind. After they built the glasses they are asked to improve their glasses to be suitable for a scientist with the same time restriction as before. Finally, the students were asked to explain their creation to their partner from the previous task. If the students had ideas they were not able to build they were also encouraged to explain these parts to their partners. This activity supported the stated objectives Engineering, Art and Life skills. The expected student constructions was a pair of glasses suitable for a scientist made of the given materials. The expected forms of student dialogue were reciprocal explanation and exchange of their ideas (in pairs). The teaching method was problem based learning.

Figure 123. Students design glasses in team Case 1

The **fourth activity** was named “Design a robot with some restrictions” and lasts 20 minutes. The students were asked to form pairs and were then presented with three stacks of cards. Each student pair had to draw a card from each stack. The stacks represented three attributes of a robot they must design. They had a limited time to design and build their robot with the different handicraft materials they were given. This activity supported the stated objectives within Engineering, Art and Life skills. The expected student constructions was a prototype of a robot. The expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and exchange of ideas. The teaching method was problem based learning.

The **fifth activity** was named “Present your ideas” and lasts 30 minutes. The orchestration was classroom presentation. The students should present their robot for the whole class. Each team got 2 to 3 minutes time for their talk. Everything they weren't able to build could be explained. The activity supported the stated objectives within Engineering, Science and Life skills. The expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and collaboration within the group. The teaching method was instruction, experimentation and problem based learning.

The **sixth activity** was named “What is a robot – a 3 step plan” and lasts 40 minutes. The orchestration was classwork. The tutor presented what engineers think a robot is and the three core steps in designing a robot: 1. Functionality: which problems should the robot solve? Where can you use a robot assistant; 2. Design: how does the robot looks like? How big is it? Which materials should be used?, 3. Communication: how can you tell the robot what you want? What are the possibilities? The activity supported the stated objectives Engineering, Science and Life skills. The expected forms of student dialogue was discussion and the teaching method was instruction with discussion.

The **seventh activity** was named “What robot do you want to build in the lab” and lasts 60 minutes. The orchestration were individual work and class work. The tutor explained what parts are available to build a robot in the lab. Then the students should imagine a robot they want to build according to the 3 core steps: functionality, design and communication.

PART 2:

The **first activity** was named “Hedgehog demo robot and programming environment” and lasts 40 minutes to 1 hour. The orchestration was work in groups and classwork. During this phase, the students were introduced to various definitions associated with programming, robotic and the hedgehog controller. First the term “programming” was explained and afterwards the terms “Hedgehog Controller” and “Programming Environment” were discussed. Furthermore, the students learnt how to work with the Hedgehog demonstration robot and how to program the controller step by step. The activity supported the stated objective Technology and the expected forms of student dialogue was discussion. The teaching method were instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

The **second activity** was named “Driving activities” and lasts 2 to 3 hours. The orchestration were working in groups and classwork. During this phase, the students had to solve different driving tasks. Expected student constructions was programs, which fulfill the given tasks and the expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and collaboration within the group. The teaching methods were instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

Figure 124. Students work with robot Case 1

The **third activity** was named “Additional activities” and lasts depending on the pacing of the students, approximately 0 - 2 hour. The orchestration were working in groups and classwork. Depending on the pace of learning of the students, additional exercises were possible to be done by the different groups. Which activities as well as the number of executed activities were decided by the PRIA tutors. The expected student constructions was programs which fulfill the given tasks. The expected forms of student dialogue was presentation to their fellow students and the teaching methods are instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

The subject related at Engineering was the understand that the product design process starts with a basic idea which must be refined subsequently. Gain some resilience against making errors and use what is available. The subject related at Technology was the understand what a robot is and of what parts it consists (motors, sensors, controller) and the understanding of basic programming concepts, like sequences. The subject relates at Art was express your ideas through built artefacts which have a beauty of their own. The subject relates at Science was discuss your ideas and get feedback from your peers, observe your robot and adjust your program based on your observations. The subject related at Societal Issues were discussion on “How robots can make the world a better place” and in course of thematizing current societal issues. The subject related at Life skills were problem solving, working in Teams and presenting.

1.2 CASE STUDY 1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

All 18 students (12 males and 6 females) who participated in phase 1 of the workshop had informed consent to be included in the research project. Four tutors led the workshop. The data analysis was based on video recordings of the focus group, pre and post questionnaires, a focus group interview, reflections from the tutors, reflections from the focus group, the activity plan and artefacts of learning.

The data analysis involved looking for specific incidents, with the research following general research questions, as follows:

- Are there new pedagogical strategies in the workshop?
- What evidence is there of learning?
- Which students' interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?
- Which students changed their attitude in STEM?
- Are girls interested in STEM topics?

These were delineated before the analysis based on the research team's observations, data collection and overall research priorities.

1.3 CASE STUDY 1 FINDINGS

This report structures its findings by three sections: The first section analyses the activity plan to answer the following question, "Are there new pedagogical strategies at the workshop?"; the second section analyses observations and questionnaires for the following question "What evidence is there of learning?"; and the third section analyses questionnaires and interview to answer the following questions "What activities encourage interest in STEM careers?", "Which students changed their attitude to STEM?" and "Are girls interested in STEM topics?".

1.3.1 New Pedagogical Strategies

This section addresses '**Are there new pedagogical strategies in the workshop?**'. A new pedagogical strategy is a new pedagogical design at the robotic context. This activity plan could include a **new pedagogical strategy**, because it involves a combination of problem-based learning linked with robotics and design thinking (Figure 125).

Figure 125. Case study 1: New pedagogical strategy.

The activity plan included elements with the approach of new pedagogical practise. The context was constructionism learning theory, while the method of learning is problem-based learning. The learning techniques were teamwork and design thinking. The means of teaching were computers, robots and handcraft materials. The activity plan was developed in different steps, which were analogous to the steps of problem-based learning. Table 1 compares problem-based learning and the activity plan.

Table 22: Comparison of Problem-based Learning with the Activity Plan

Steps	Problem-based learning	Part/activity	Activity plan
Step 1	Explore the issue	Part 1/activity 4	Design a Robot with Some Restrictions
Step 2	State what is known	Part 1/activity 6	What is a robot? A Three-step Plan
Step 3	Define the issues	Part 1/activity 7	What Robot Do You Want to Build in the Lab?
Step 4	Research the knowledge	Part 2/activity 1	Hedgehog Demo Robot and Programming Environment
Step 5	Investigate solutions	Part 2/activity 2	Driving Activities
Step 6	Present and support the chosen solution	Part 1/activity 5	Present Your Ideas
Step 7	Review your performance	Post questionnaires	'What Did I Learn...?'

The comparison showed that the activity plan was structured according to the problem-based learning steps. The innovative part of the activity plan in this context was that a new pedagogical strategy was employed in educational robotics. The combination of design thinking and problem based learning was innovative.

The students started with design thinking, thereby achieving different learning levels. Every students built an artefact linked to real-life problems and tailored to their different skill levels. This pedagogical design gave the opportunity to achieve differentiation in the groups. The different artefacts in the same context are shown in Figure 126.

Figure 126. Case study 1: Different artefacts.

The glasses were developed in the same context, but the other artefacts were developed in different tasks. The tutors reported about their successful observations of part 1. All of them agreed that it was successful for the students to design and build robot prototypes; during the task, to appreciate everyone, all the students had the chance to present their ideas, and this was also evaluated positively by the tutors.

PRIA_170928_Tutor_Reflection

What was the most successful part of today's session? Why?

Tutor 1: 'Students had the most fun when turning their ideas into actual design prototypes and building them'.

Tutor 2: 'Building the prototype robots with the constraints the students had to deal with from the cards they had drawn'.

Tutor 3: 'What I feel was the greatest success of today is that they actually followed the one, most important rule we gave them at the beginning of the workshop: "There are no bad ideas – if you think that somebody should do something in a different way, don't say, 'That's a really stupid way to do it', but say, 'Alright, that looks pretty good but it could be even better by adding this...'" There was a task where they had to present their ideas to their neighbour. During this part, nobody was rude, and everyone appreciated the others' work. That was the biggest success to me'.

Tutor 4: 'The most successful thing was the fact that the children had fun and were motivated throughout the tasks'.

A sub-question was as follows: 'How did the students react to the new pedagogical concept?' Figure 127 shows that most of the students had fun with the robots and solving problems. All the students reported that the tasks were interesting.

Figure 127. Case study 1: Working with robots and solving problems.

1.3.2 Case Study 1: Discussion about New Pedagogical Strategies

Can we say that problem-based learning is a new pedagogical strategy? No. Can we say that design thinking is a new pedagogical strategy? No.

A **new pedagogical strategy** also means a new way to teach students in robotics workshops. The students became more familiar with their creativity skills and teamwork during the third activity, ‘Design and Make Glasses for a Scientist’, followed by the fourth activity to design a robot with some restrictions. The new pedagogical strategy is leading students from general topics to the development of robots and subsequent programming of a robot. The aims of the workshop were to familiarise the students with the concept of design thinking and robotics and programming.

The activity plan in part 1 shows that the activities started with exploration and went on to define issues. The workshop began with activities that needed no technical knowledge; it then led the children from hands-on activities to the context of robotics and programming with special technology knowledge.

1.3.3 Case Study 1: Evidence of Learning

This section explores **‘What evidence is there of learning?’**, based on the observation and post questionnaires.

Observation

The students learned to create a robot in the fourth activity, ‘Design a Robot with Some Requirements’. The requirements were that the robot was for a brother or sister, it must have a favourable price, and it would be used for going to sleep (see

Figure 128). The students worked in pairs. Figure 129 shows the result from a pair of students.

Figure 128. Case study 1: Group 4, activity 4.

Every student built the glasses and a prototype robot in teams. They developed their robots with handcraft materials based on three restrictions. The students demonstrated their practical skills while employing different materials for building the robot, and they linked their personal life problems with the restrictions.

Figure 129. Case Study 1: Group 4's glasses and robot.

Another result concerning evidence of learning was found in the post questionnaire. Table 23 presents an overview of the responses to the question 'What have you learned...?', separated by gender.

Table 23. Case Study 1: Post Questionnaire Responses to Questions about What Students Learned at the Workshop

Statement	Female	Male	Total
What have you learned...			
...About yourself?			
Programming robots	0	2	2
I am good at such things	1	0	1
Robots	2	3	5
Working together	0	1	1
That there is something in me	0	1	1
That I am interested in a lot of robots	0	1	1
...About working with other people?			
Working better in teams	2	1	3
How to work together	0	1	1
Building robots	0	1	1
Helping other people	1	0	1
Working together was bad	0	1	1
Working together was nice	2	0	2
Do not argue and solve everything	1	0	1
Learning with a computer	0	1	1
How to turn with the robot car	0	1	1

...About robots?			
Programming a robot	3	5	8
Robots help	1	1	2
Building a robot	1	0	1
Robots are interesting	1	0	1

Most of the students answered that they learned how to program a robot, about robots and that it was better working in a team. A further sub-question concerning these results is what attitude the students had towards teamwork. Figure 110 shows that most of the students were interested and had fun working in a team.

Figure 130. Case study 1: Post questionnaire perceptions of working in a team.

1.3.4 Case Study 1: Discussion about Evidence of Learning

Evidence of learning was shown in the questionnaires, artefacts and observation. The observation illustrated that the case study group of two students learned to work in a team and that robotics was an interesting topic for them. They showed their learning results as artefact (glasses and robots; Figures 5 and 6). Other results were found in the post questionnaires, which showed that the students learned to program a robot and work in a team, with positive attitudes toward teamwork.

The analysis of the learning outcomes as artefact is complicated. What can we say about the students' learning? Did they learn to build a prototype or a product? Yes, we can say that there is a product and the students presented it.

The creation of environments that promote creativity is also made possible by defining clear goals in the activity, balancing knowledge and challenges and creating a climate where students are not worried that they may fail. The activity plan fostered these points; thus, we could say that the activity plan, students' motivation to build the robot (seen in the Tutor Reflections and Questionnaires) and learning artefacts showed that the

workshop fostered creativity. A possible list of evidence of learning includes programming, building a robot and fostering students' creativity and collaboration.

1.3.5 Case Study 1: Findings in the questionnaires and interviews

This section explores 'Which students' interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?', 'Which students changed their attitude in STEM?' and 'Are girls interested in STEM topics?'. Evidence was gathered from the questionnaires and interviews.

1.3.5.1 CASE STUDY 1: 'WHICH STUDENTS CHANGED THEIR ATTITUDES IN STEM?'

The pre and post questionnaires provided useful information about the students in the workshop, their interest in STEM careers and girls' interest in STEM. Sixteen students completed the pre and post questionnaires. Eight changed their answers between the two questionnaires in response to the question 'In the future, what job would you like to do?'

Table 24. Case Study 1: Changing Their Provisional Career

Student ID	Gender	Age	Pre	Post
32016	Girl	8	Doctor	Making Robots
32017	Boy	9	Teacher	Computer Engineer
32021	Girl	9	Hairdresser	Seamstress
32025	Girl	8	Hairdresser	Vet
32026	Boy	8	Construction Worker	Car Mechanic
32029	Boy	9	Builder	Police Officer
32035	Boy	9	Firefighter	Police Officer
32037	Boy	8	Teacher	Police Officer

One female student changed her answer from 'doctor' on the pre-questionnaire to 'I will make robots' on the post questionnaire. A male student changed his answer from 'teacher' on the pre questionnaire to 'computer engineer' on the post questionnaire.

Two boys responded to the statement 'I like science' with 'Strongly Disagree' before the workshop and 'Yes' after the workshop. Both boys responded to the statement 'I am now more interested in studying science' with 'Yes' after the workshop.

Table 25. Case Study 1: Students Changed Their Attitude toward Science

Student ID	Gender	Pre <i>I like science [5 liker- scale]</i>	Pre <i>Least favourite subject</i>	Post <i>I am now more interested in studying science. [Yes/No]</i>	Post <i>I like science. [Yes/No]</i>
32029	Boy	Strongly disagree	Science, Information Technology (IT)	Yes	Yes
32030	Boy	Strongly disagree	Science, IT	Yes	Yes

1.3.5.2 CASE STUDY 1: 'WHICH STUDENTS' INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS WAS ENCOURAGED DURING THE WORKSHOP?'

This was answered via the question, 'I am now more interested in studying science', from the post questionnaires and Interviews.

Figure 131. Case study 1: Post questionnaire, 'I am now more interested in studying science'.

Ten of 14 students said that they were more interested in studying science at the end of the workshop (six boys, four girls). Two boys (m32029, m32030) of the 10 students answered the statement 'I like science' with 'Strongly Disagree' and answered 'Yes' to the statement that science is the subject they like the least in the pre questionnaires. The same boys answered 'Yes' to 'I like science' in the post questionnaires. The results from the interviews supported this result.

Interview: Child 1 (f32022), child 2 (f32023)

Interviewer: *'Were you already informed about science, mathematics and technology before the workshop?'*

Child 2: *'Yes'.*

Child 1: *'Yes, because my father works with technology from time to time'.*

Interviewer: *'Mhm, and that has always interested you?'*

Child 1: *'Yes'.*

Interviewer: *'Okay. And now that you have come here and completed the workshop, did the workshop change your mind about it in any way?'*

Child 2: *'About what?'*

Interviewer: *'About technology, science and math'.*

Child 2: *'Yes'.*

Interviewer: *'Already'.*

- Child 2: *'In the beginning, I thought it would be boring.'*
- Child 1: *'Me too.'*
- Child 2: *'But then I really got to know technology, and it's interesting and fun, yes.'*
- Interviewer: *'Okay, great. Do you think that working with robots would also help other kids become more interested in technology?'*
- Child 1, 2: *'Yes.'*
- Interviewer: *'– And science. Okay, why do you believe that?'*
- Child 2: *'Because many children do not like activities with math, because it is boring or difficult. But if you become more familiar with math, you will never forget it, you will like it.'*
- Interviewer: *'Mhm, so you have it in good memory?'*
- Child 2: *'Yes.'*

The girl (32023) stated that she became more familiar with technology during the workshop and that technology is interesting and funny. She agreed that working with robots would help other children become more interested in technology because, if children became more familiar with math, they will never forget it. The children will like it. The girl reported that she would remember what she had learned.

1.3.5.3 CASE STUDY 1: 'ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?'

This question was addressed via three sections from the post questionnaires, as follows: interest in math (see The findings concerning girls' interest in STEM are drawn from the pre-questionnaire responses (Figure 95 through 8) concerning girls' interest in math (Figure 95), a gender comparison in math (Figure 6), girls' interest in science (Figure 97) and a gender comparison in science (Figure 8), as well as from the post-questionnaire responses concerning girls' interest in STEM topics (Figure 99) and a gender comparison (Figure 100).

Figure 95 shows that girls rated the statement 'Math is important' most highly.

Figure 95), interest in science (see from Figure 133) and interest in STEM topics (see in Figure 134).

Figure 132. Case study 1: Pre questionnaire, girls' interest in math.

The findings concerning girls’ interest in STEM are drawn from the pre-questionnaire responses (Figure 95 through 8) concerning girls’ interest in math (Figure 95), a gender comparison in math (Figure 6), girls’ interest in science (Figure 97) and a gender comparison in science(Figure 8), as well as from the post-questionnaire responses concerning girls’ interest in STEM topics (Figure 99) and a gender comparison (Figure 100).

Figure 95 shows that girls rated the statement 'Math is important' most highly.

Figure 95 shows that all the girls said that math is important, three said that math is easy and four liked math.

Figure 133. Case study 1: Pre-questionnaire, girls’ interest in science.

Figure 133 shows that all the girls said that science is important, two girls said that science is easy and all the girls liked science.

Figure 134. Case study 1: Post questionnaire, girls’ interest in STEM topics.

Figure 134 shows that most of the girls liked engineering, using computers and science. All of them liked using computers and math after the workshop.

1.3.6 Case Study 1: Discussion on Changing Attitudes in STEM

The pre questionnaires showed that a lot of girls had a positive attitude toward STEM. It was a challenge to increase the interest of STEM among the girls, because the level of interest was already high. However, the post questionnaire results showed that all the girls liked computers and math after the workshop. The interview supported the finding that girls had a positive attitude to STEM during the workshop.

Why did some students change their prospective career to select more technical jobs? There are different points that may be made to explain this. The students' peer groups talked more about technical topics during the workshop, so the workshop may have indirectly influenced their attitudes and interest in STEM careers. As Figure 4 showed the feeling concerning this topic, all the students were interested in the problems at the workshop and working with robots and ten of the 12 students had fun with problem solving and working with robots. Interest and good feelings are necessary to generate future motivation. The results cannot say undoubtedly that the students will enter STEM careers, but the workshop influenced them making their attitude toward STEM more positive and fostering their motivation to pursue these interests in their future studies.

1.4 CONCLUSION

The case study evaluation provided results in the forms of tutor reflections, interviews, observations, questionnaires and learning artefacts. The findings showed that the combination of robotics, problem-based learning and design thinking fostered a motivating climate for hands-on work; for example, the students built a robot prototype and glasses, and they programmed the robot. The positive attitude toward teamwork will make it easy for the students to work in teams again. Evidence of learning in collaboration is difficult to find,

but the evaluation showed that the case fostered a positive experience with collaborative working and engagement in working in team for the future.

19 APPENDIX K: PRIA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

1.5 CONTEXT CASE STUDY 2

Workshop: PRIA_171005 ER4STEM Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop

In this case study, we investigated the ‘Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop’ in Austria, run by PRIA. 25 students aged 8 to 10 years old—15 girls and 10 boys from an elementary school—participated in the workshop in two sessions with in sum 8 hours. The primary language of the school was German, 12 of them speak another language at home: Albanian, Arabic, Hungarian, Italian, Polish, Romanian, Serbian and Turkish. 2 boys had previously built a robot and program a robot as part of a club activity. The workshop were let from 4 Tutors. The robotic kit is a hedgehog and the programming language is python.

1.5.1 Case Study 2: Description of the Activity

A full description of the activity is provided in the activity plan; the following is the activity summary:

This activity was designed for children who have never encountered robotics and/or programming. The prior knowledge required comprises basic reading skills and understanding of the necessary numeric values; basic knowledge of working with computers was advantageous. The workshop was suitable for children aged 8–11 years old. It was used in schools in a low socioeconomic area, and a large percentage of the students had German as their second language. The aim of the workshop was to familiarise the students with the concepts of design thinking, as well as robotics and programming. It consisted of two main sessions held by the workshop tutors in an open space for testing and building the robots, with notebooks or computers, and took place indoors. The first session focussed on giving the students an introduction to design thinking and considered what type of robot they could build. The second session explained the basics of programming. The goal was to drive the robot. During the activities, the students were expected to observe, communicate, build a robot, program a robot, discuss their ideas with a classmate and present their work in front of their peers. The workshop was divided into two parts. The following slogan for the learning process was used in the first phase: ‘I can create something in a small amount of time’. In the second part, the goal was that the students would try out their code and adapt it to the task.

They used Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller. The workshop should develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. The students learning outcomes were visual or python program for the hedgehog controller.

PART 1:

The **first activity** was named “Introduction on the lego mindstorm EV3 set” and lasts 10 minutes. The orchestration happened in a plenum discussion. The tutor and all students gave a short introduction about their name, age, knowledge, robots, etc.). The teaching method was instruction and the expected forms of students dialogue were instruction and discussion.

The **second activity** was named “Clapping Game – Errors Happen” and lasts 10 to 15 minutes. The orchestration happens in pairs and classwork. The tutors made the task of the game more complicated after a while to attain more mistakes and the game rules were changed after some time, too. The aim of the activity

was to give the students the feeling, that making mistakes is not bad but rather something which is ok to happen to promote a more freely idea development process. The teaching method was demonstration with exercises.

The **third activity** was named “Design and make glasses for a scientist.” and lasts 50 to 60 minutes. The orchestration happens in work alone and share your ideas in pairs. The students were asked about what they know about scientists and what characteristics a scientist needs to have. Afterwards the students got different materials and the task to create a pair of glasses in 2 minutes. The time restriction should help them in trying out the first ideas which came to their mind. After they built the glasses they are asked to improve their glasses to be suitable for a scientist with the same time restriction as before. Finally, the students were asked to explain their creation to their partner from the previous task. If the students had ideas they were not able to build they were also encouraged to explain these parts to their partners. This activity supported the stated objectives Engineering, Art and Life skills. The expected student constructions was a pair of glasses suitable for a scientist made of the given materials. The expected forms of student dialogue were reciprocal explanation and exchange of their ideas (in pairs). The teaching method was problem based learning.

Figure 135. Students design glasses in team Case 1

The **fourth activity** was named “Design a robot with some restrictions” and lasts 20 minutes. The students were asked to form pairs and were then presented with three stacks of cards. Each student pair had to draw a card from each stack. The stacks represented three attributes of a robot they must design. They had a limited time to design and build their robot with the different handicraft materials they were given. This activity supported the stated objectives within Engineering, Art and Life skills. The expected student constructions was a prototype of a robot. The expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and exchange of ideas. The teaching method was problem based learning.

The **fifth activity** was named “Present your ideas” and lasts 30 minutes. The orchestration was classroom presentation. The students should present their robot for the whole class. Each team got 2 to 3 minutes time for their talk. Everything they weren't able to build could be explained. The activity supported the stated objectives within Engineering, Science and Life skills. The expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and collaboration within the group. The teaching method was instruction, experimentation and problem based learning.

The **sixth activity** was named “What is a robot – a 3 step plan” and lasts 40 minutes. The orchestration was classwork. The tutor presented what engineers think a robot is and the three core steps in designing a robot: 1. Functionality: which problems should the robot solve? Where can you use a robot assistant; 2. Design: how does the robot looks like? How big is it? Which materials should be used?, 3. Communication: how can you tell the robot what you want? What are the possibilities? The activity supported the stated objectives Engineering, Science and Life skills. The expected forms of student dialogue was discussion and the teaching method was instruction with discussion.

The **seventh activity** was named “What robot do you want to build in the lab” and lasts 60 minutes. The orchestration were individual work and class work. The tutor explained what parts are available to build a robot in the lab. Then the students should imagine a robot they want to build according to the 3 core steps: functionality, design and communication.

PART 2:

The **first activity** was named “Hedgehog demo robot and programming environment” and lasts 40 minutes to 1 hour. The orchestration was work in groups and classwork. During this phase, the students were introduced to various definitions associated with programming, robotic and the hedgehog controller. First the term “programming” was explained and afterwards the terms “Hedgehog Controller” and “Programming Environment” were discussed. Furthermore, the students learnt how to work with the Hedgehog demonstration robot and how to program the controller step by step. The activity supported the stated objective Technology and the expected forms of student dialogue was discussion. The teaching method were instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

The **second activity** was named “Driving activities” and lasts 2 to 3 hours. The orchestration were working in groups and classwork. During this phase, the students had to solve different driving tasks. Expected student constructions was programs, which fulfill the given tasks and the expected forms of student dialogue were discussion and collaboration within the group. The teaching methods were instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

Figure 136. Students work with robot Case 1

The **third activity** was named “Additional activities” and lasts depending on the pacing of the students, approximately 0 - 2 hour. The orchestration were working in groups and classwork. Depending on the pace of learning of the students, additional exercises were possible to be done by the different groups. Which activities as well as the number of executed activities were decided by the PRIA tutors. The expected student constructions was programs which fulfill the given tasks. The expected forms of student dialogue was presentation to their fellow students and the teaching methods are instruction, demonstration by example and experimentation.

The subject related at Engineering was the understand that the product design process starts with a basic idea which must be refined subsequently. Gain some resilience against making errors and use what is available. The subject related at Technology was the understand what a robot is and of what parts it consists (motors, sensors, controller) and the understanding of basic programming concepts, like sequences. The subject relates at Art was express your ideas through built artefacts which have a beauty of their own. The subject relates at Science was discuss your ideas and get feedback from your peers, observe your robot and adjust your program based on your observations. The subject related at Societal Issues were discussion on “How robots can make

the world a better place” and in course of thematizing current societal issues. The subject related at Life skills were problem solving, working in Teams and presenting.

1.6 CASE STUDY 2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

All 25 students who participated in phase one of the workshop had informed consent to be included in research project – 15 girls and 10 boys. Four tutors led the workshop. The data analysis was based from video recordings of the focus group and fix camera at the phase two, pre and post questionnaires, an interview with the focus group, observational notes and reflections from the tutors, reflections from the focus group, the activity plan and artefacts of learning.

The data analysis involved looking for particular incidents, with the research questions concerning ‘**Evidence of learning**’, ‘**STEM Career**’ and ‘**Changing and sustaining attitudes to STEM**’, being decided in advance of the analysis based on the research teams observations, the data collection and overall research priorities.

1.7 CASE STUDY 2: FINDINGS

This report’s findings are structured in three sections. The first section analyses the activity plan to answer following question, ‘**What did the students learn during the workshop?**’; and the second section analyses the questionnaires and interviews to answer the following questions, ‘**Which students changed their attitudes toward STEM?**’, ‘**Which students’ interest in STEM careers was encouraged during the workshop?**’ and ‘**Are girls interested in STEM topics?**’.

1.7.1 Case Study 2: Evidence of Learning

This section explores **What evidence is there of learning?**’, based on the observations, interview and post questionnaires. Three girls were involved in the interview, and the interviewer was a female tutor.

The girls reported that they learned programming during the experience via trial and error. Moreover, they reported that the hands-on activities and programming were cool. This interview shows that children like hands-on activities combined with robots and that they need their own free learning space to develop their skills during their experience in the workshops. This result confirms the approach of constructionist learning, illustrating that it is best when nobody stops the children’s activities, interests and curiosity.

Interview:

Results from the learning evidence during the workshop.

Interviewer: ‘*What did you learn today? Something about programming or robots?*’

Child 2: ‘*Programming*’.

Child 3: ‘*Yes*’.

Child 2: ‘*To program*’.

Child 3: ‘*Yes, right. Forwards, backwards, right and left turn*’.

Child 2: *'And to work with the computer'.*

Interviewer: *'Very good. How did you learn that, when you were listening or trying it?'*

Child 2: *'By trying it...'*

Child 1: *'By trying it'.*

Child 3: *'By trying it'.*

Child 2: *'...And a little bit with listening'.*

Why are the activities interesting for other children?

Interviewer: *'Okay, do you think the activities with robots today would awaken an interest in engineering, science and math in other children?'*

Child 1, 2, 3: *'Yes'.*

Interviewer: *'Yes. Why?'*

Child 2: *'Because it is cool'.*

Interviewer: *'Are activities with robots cool?'*

Child 1: *'Yes, and if we can do hands-on activities and it functions afterwards, then I like it more, if we can do more like that'.*

Interviewer: *'Okay, if you can do something with your hands'.*

Child 2: *'Because children likely want to play with computers, but if their parents stop that activity, they can play with the computer in a useful way during the workshop'.*

Interviewer: *'This is a good proposal'.*

Child 3: *'...And the programming, um the robots and the programming'.*

Interviewer: *'Programming is cool?'*

Child 3: *'Yes'.*

Table 23 presents an overview of the responses to the question 'What have you learned...?', separated by gender.

Table 26. Case Study 2: Post Questionnaire Responses to Questions about What Students Learned at the Workshop

Statement	Female	Male	Total
What have you learned...			
...About yourself?			
Programming	5	4	9
You can do many things with robots	1	1	2
Nothing	1	1	2
I am good in technology-related subjects	1	1	2

Working on a computer	2	0	2
Technology is fun and interesting	1	0	1
Never give up	1	0	1
That I cannot do everything by myself	1	0	1
I am clever	0	1	1
...About working with other people?			
Fun	2	2	4
Working together	0	3	3
I can work with other people	2	0	2
Controlling a robot	1	0	1
Working better in a team	0	1	1
Very funny	1	0	1
Good	1	0	1
I did the work	1	0	1
It is more fun than working alone	1	0	1
Sometimes you need help	1	0	1
Take it easy	1	0	1
Everyone always wants the easiest way	0	1	1
You should be fair	1	0	1
you should never work alone	0	1	1
...About robots?			
Programming	3	3	6
Cool	4	0	4
They can do a lot of things	4	0	4
Controlling robot with computer	1	2	3
Very complicated	1	0	1
Helping other people	0	1	1

Most of the students wrote that they learned programming, fun with other people and working together.

Observation

Group 6 (m33025, m33024) learned to create a robot in the fourth activity, 'Design a Robot with Some Requirements'. The requirements were that the robot was for a brother or sister, it had to hate their mom and it had to be an aeroplane (see Figure 137).

Figure 137. Case study 2: Group 6, activity 4.

The results from group 5 (f33017, f33013) for activity 4 are shown in Figure 138. The students learned to create a robot as a team and show the results of their problem solving.

Figure 138. Case study 2: Group 5, create a superstar in the universe for mom.

The aim of the workshop was to foster design thinking, and Figure 137 and Figure 138 show the results from students during the design thinking process in the context of robotics. A follow-up question was how the students felt about the teamwork. Table 6 shows that the students had fun with other people, and

Figure 139 shows that most of the students were interested and had fun working in a team.

Figure 139. Case study 2: Post questionnaire perceptions of working in a team.

The comparison with feeling and working in team shows that the workshop fostering collaborative working through these positive experience

1.7.2 Case Study 2: Discussion about Evidence of Learning

Evidence of learning was shown with different data. The observation shows that the case with the two students learned to work in a team and that robotics was an interesting topic for them. They showed their problem-

solving with an artefact (glasses and robot; Figure 137 and Figure 138). Other results were found in the post questionnaires, which showed that the students learned to program a robot.

This evaluation is more than an explanation of learning evidence, because the evaluation obtained an answer to the question of why this was the case during the interview. The students reported that they learned by trying, and this made hands-on activities more fun. This result is linked with the post questionnaires, which shows that the most students reported to learnt programming.

1.7.3 Case Study 2: Findings in the Questionnaires

This section explores ‘What activities encourage interest in STEM careers?’, ‘Which students changed their attitude in STEM?’ and ‘Are girls interested in STEM topics?’. Evidence was gathered from the questionnaires.

1.7.3.1 CASE STUDY 2: ‘WHICH STUDENTS CHANGED THEIR ATTITUDES IN STEM?’

The pre and post questionnaires provided useful background information about the students and their interest in STEM careers in the workshop, as well as girls’ interest in STEM. Twenty-five students completed the pre and post questionnaires. One student (f33010) changed her answer between the two questionnaires in response to the question ‘In the future, what job would you like to do?’ The girl (9 years old) changed her answer from ‘police officer’ on the pre questionnaire to ‘astronaut’ on the post questionnaire.

One student (f33012) responded to the statement ‘I like science’ with ‘Disagree’ before the workshop and ‘Yes’ after the workshop. Another girl (f33022) answered the statement ‘I like science’ with ‘Strongly Disagree’ before the workshop and ‘Yes’ after the workshop. One boy and one girl said that they were more interested in studying science after the workshop. These students (f33012, m33015) responded to the item, ‘I now more interested in study science’, with ‘Yes’ on the post questionnaires, but before the workshop, they responded ‘Neither’ and ‘Disagree’.

Table 27. Case Study 2: Students Changed Their Attitude toward Science

Student ID	Gender	Pre I like science [5 Likert-Scale]	Pre Least favourite subject	Post I am now more interested in studying science [Yes/No]	Post I like science [Yes/No]
33012	Girl	Disagree	Science	Yes	Yes
33015	Boy	Neither	Science	Yes	Yes
33022	Girl	Strongly disagree	Information Technology (IT)	No	Yes

1.7.3.2 CASE STUDY 2: WHICH STUDENTS’ INTEREST IN STEM CAREERS WAS ENCOURAGED DURING THE WORKSHOP?’

This question was answered with the question ‘I am now more interested in studying science’ from the post questionnaires and interview.

Figure 140. Case study 2: Post questionnaire, I am now more interested in studying science.

Eleven of 25 students stated that they were more interested in studying science at the end of the workshop (four boys, seven girls).

1.7.3.3 CASE STUDY 2: ARE GIRLS INTERESTED IN STEM TOPICS?

This question was answered via the questionnaires. Fifteen girls participated in the workshop. Thirteen of them liked math and thought that they and their friends were good at maths. All of them thought math is important (Figure 141).

Figure 141. Case Study 2: Pre questionnaire, interest in math.

Figure 142 shows that 13 of 15 girls said that science is important. Eleven girls liked science, and more girls thought that they and their friends were good at science.

Figure 142. Case study 2: Pre questionnaire, interest in science.

Figure 143 shows that all the girls like engineering, while 10 of the 15 girls liked using computers and science. Twelve of 15 girls liked math.

Figure 143. Case study 2: Post questionnaire, girls' interest in STEM topics.

1.7.4 Case Study 2: Discussion about Changing Attitudes in STEM, Girls' Interest in STEM and STEM Career

One girl changed her preferred job from police officer to a job with a more technical and scientific background – astronaut. In addition, two girls changed their attitudes toward science. Approximately 50% of the students are more interested in studying science. All these results show the change of attitudes towards STEM during the workshop. Table 26 illustrates the attitudes towards robots after the workshop, showing that the students thought robots are cool. Eleven students were more interested in studying science after the workshop. Approximately 80% of the girls liked math and science before the workshop, but all of them like engineering, science and math afterward. All the girls were interested in studying science after the workshop, and the workshop influenced all the girls in terms of fostering positive attitudes toward STEM. Thirteen students are more interested in studying science, suggesting that the workshop could be a first step toward a STEM career. Although many girls were interested in STEM at the beginning of the workshop, interest in STEM was achieved for all the girls by the end.

1.8 CONCLUSION

The new pedagogical strategy with problem-based learning and design thinking may increase students' interest in STEM. Via this strategy, students learn about programming and engage in teamwork. Although it is not easy to find clear evidence for the results of teamwork, the artefacts the students produced in the workshop show that they developed positive attitude toward teamwork; moreover, in the open-ended questions, they reported that they learned about working together. Table 6 shows that they had fun with other people. Thus, we could interpret that the workshop positively affected the development of collaboration skills. The evaluation of the questionnaires showed that the workshop activities influenced the interest in STEM. All the girls liked engineering after the workshops and related their positive experience in the interview. The

comparison from interviews, questionnaires, observations and tutor reflections strengthens the results. For example, the positive attitude toward teamwork in the closed-ended questions showed the same result as the open questions. The positive attitude toward STEM in the questionnaires supported the results of the interviews.

20 APPENDIX L: BULGARIA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

20.1 CONTEXT

Workshop: 01_PRW2-3-125-4a Visualising Mathematics with the Mathbot

20.1.1 Description of the Activity

This case study took place in a public general education school in Bulgaria with a group of 26 students aged nine and ten. The group was mixed gender with 13 males and 13 females, however one female was absent from the first session, and two males absent from the second session. The workshop was held over two sessions, a week apart, lasting three hours per sessions and six hours in total. Students worked in groups of two to four members, and each group had their own robot and computer. The group had completed the ER4STEM workshop 'Educational Robotics and Creativity' a year previously, meaning the first session was based on an expectation that the students would have a basic knowledge of robotic elements and Scratch programming.

A full description is provided in the activity plan; this is the summary of the activity:

"The goal of this workshop is to introduce and exercise mathematical concepts, which are covered in the national school curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade in Bulgarian schools, using programming and robotics.

Participants play 5 different games with the robot. Every game builds on the previous one and is broken down into quests, through which they exercise their knowledge on mathematics and adopt new mathematical concepts by exercising them. Children program to make the robot move and they make the robot move to solve a mathematical problem."

The stated objectives of the workshop were:

- Subject related:
 - Mathematics:
 - Learn about and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors;
 - Engage students in brief discussions on different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another;
 - Exercise the use of measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
 - Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory;
 - Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal numbers without going into theory;
 - Technology:
 - Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts;
 - Students understand that robots are programmable;
 - Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot
 - Students gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors;
 - Students learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED of the Finch in Scratch in order to produce different colours and sequence of colours;

- Students understand that different sensors serve different purpose;
- Students understand that sensors are controllable and programmable
- Technology use related
 - Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.
- Social and action related
 - Develop problem solving skills;
 - Exercise effective communication skills;
 - Encourage flexibility and adaptability;
 - Foster collaboration skills;
- Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:
 - Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas.
 - Encourage curiosity, tinkering and experimentation;
 - The games require the decision-making within a team;
 - Identifying and solving problems;
 - Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.
 - Exercise logical thinking;

As stated in the objectives, the students used a Finch robot with the programming software Scratch2, shown in Figure 91.

Figure 144. Finch robot and Scratch2 programming software

The groups were encouraged to split four different roles between their members and to swap roles between each activity that they completed. The roles were explained in the 'workshop rules' that were provided to the children and consisted of:

- One person who writes the code
- One person who makes sure the rules are followed
- One person who holds the cable and helps with the code

- One person who makes sure everything is correct and reads the activity task

20.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

20.2.1 Data Collection

Out of the 26 students who participated in the workshop, 23 students gave consent to be included in research project – 11 males and 12 females. The tutors who ran the workshop, who were Bulgarian project partners from ESICEE, collected data.

Although a full dataset was not provided, with only 50 minutes of video data from the first session, a large amount of useful data was still delivered. This data included video recordings of the focus group during the first session, photos taken by the tutors, pre and post questionnaires, an interview with the focus group, observational notes and reflections from the tutors, reflections from the focus group, the activity plan, artefacts of learning and artefacts provided for the activity. The camera for the video data was angled in such a way that all four members of the focus group and their robot can always be seen in shot, but there is no view of their computer screen – although the screen could be seen in some photographs taken by the tutors, such as Figure 92.

20.2.1.1 FOCUS GROUP

The focus group analysed was a mixed-gender group, consisting of two boys and two girls, shown in Figure 92. The group had also worked together a year previously when last participating in an ER4STEM workshop, as this was encouraged by the tutors. During an interview, the students stated that they found it easier to work together this year, as last year was the first time they had worked in that group:

“C4: Previous year we worked together for the first time.

...

C1: I think that it becomes better every time, because we get to know each other... And we get to know each other better and cooperate better and everything is going better.”

Figure 145. Photograph taken of focus group members

20.2.2 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved looking for particular incidents, with the research questions concerning ‘One Gender Taking Over’, ‘Evidence of Learning’ and ‘Differentiation’ being decided in advance of the analysis based on the research teams observations, the data collection and overall research priorities. The section on ‘One Gender Taking Over’ was coded using emergent themes, which were the structured into categories and sub-categories.

20.3 FINDINGS

This report structures its findings by three sections: ‘One Gender Taking Over’, ‘Evidence of Learning’ and ‘Differentiated Activities’. For the section ‘One Gender Taking Over’, a visual representation of the relationship between the section’s categories and sub-categories is provided and codes are shown in **bold**.

20.3.1 One Gender Taking Over

This section explores the research question: *“In what circumstances did one gender ‘take over’ and what were the implications of this?”* The category ‘Power and Control’ is discussed in terms of the use of ‘Objects’ and the ‘Physicality’ of participants in the focus group. The relationship of these subcategories is shown in Figure 146. The two sub-categories are linked with a connecting line, as the use of objects and the physicality of the team members were found to be in some ways related. Evidence was taken from the video footage recorded of the focus group during the first session, the group member’s questionnaire answers, the interview conducted with the group and the tutor’s observational notes.

Figure 146. Representation of 'Power and Control' Category

20.3.1.1 POWER AND CONTROL

The tutor running the session stated in her observational notes that the boys appeared to take more of a lead on the activities, but were conscientious of including the girls:

“The girls were participating less than the boys, I feel, but the boys were very generous in terms of rotating and giving turns. What I observed as a pattern with them was that the boys were doing the new tasks, sort of ‘researching’ them first, and when they managed to do the tasks, they were giving turn to the girls, telling them what to do and all. The girls were very confused, when for the last task, I told them to reverse turns and to begin with the tasks first. They didn’t really know what to do, so they asked the boys for validation of their ideas.”

This observation implies that because the tutor intervened in the leadership the boys were taking quite late on in the workshop, this power dynamic had been ingrained to some extent into the working relationship of the group, meaning the girls were somewhat “confused” as to how they should lead a task. Unfortunately, this moment was not captured in the video data and so this observation cannot be triangulated. However, evidence of this potential presumed authority of the boys over the girls was observed in Child 3’s behaviour – at one point she is seen approaching the keyboard, ready to contribute, but then realises that Child 1 (m) approaches the keyboard at the same time and so suddenly steps back, appearing to control herself from taking over.

It should be noted that the group made no specific mention of gender in their interview or in their questionnaires. In fact, Child 3 (f) stated in her post-workshop questionnaire that she had enjoyed working in a team, and this opinion was also portrayed by other group members in their interview:

*“Interviewer: OK, I have a last question. If we have a workshop again next year, would you work together?
 C2: Yes, why not.
 C3: Yes.”*

C1: *Yes, definitely. According to me they are pleasant schoolmates, I can't say anything bad about anyone of them. They are just wonderful people and... Everybody listens to the others and nobody underestimates the others and their ideas and that's why working with them is very pleasant."*

However, in the group interview the previous year, the group had a lot more to comment on how they worked as a team, how they could improve, and the role gender played in their team:

"C2: *Yes, but it was just hard to take turns, everybody steps in whenever they feel like it and at the end we get mad and start shouting at each other.*

C4: *That happens most often with the boys.*

C2: *(indistinguishable), it's not just our fault.*

...

C3: *Well, I really liked us working together, it was unexpected that us of all people (stressed "us", as them as a group of people couldn't usually get along) could do it.*

...

C3: *I learned that they work harder than we do. When we were programming they argued who would sit in front of the computer at first and we (C3&C4) just watched.*

Interviewer: *And next time if you're working together again, will you let them program a little bit more? [To C1 & C2]*

C1 & C2: *Yes."*

In this interview extract, the girls claim that the boys both behaved differently in the team to them and took a more active role in the tasks. This is also observable in the previous year's video footage, with the boys engaging more than the girls did. The boys agree that in the future they will ensure they share the ability to participate in the workshop with the girls, however according to the tutor observation from the second workshop, this did not necessarily happen. Whilst the tutor observed that the boys would lead the activities more overall, analysis of the video data has revealed that the girls, in particular Child 4, would use other methods of control to gain power within the group.

20.3.1.2 OBJECTS

The team had multiple objects that were used as **tools** in the workshop, such as the robot, computer keyboard, computer mouse and instruction sheet. This section explores how these objects were used as a control mechanism, through location and ownership. As the group members worked on opposite sides of the table (as discussed in 20.3.1.3), they often had to either lean to **reach** these objects in order to use them, or to move the objects themselves closer to a group member. This can be seen in Figure 147, where the computer keyboard has been moved closer to Child 1 (m).

Figure 147. Keyboard is moved closer to Child 1 whilst he uses it

In theory, the movement of tools should have corresponded with which individual was assuming which **role**, which as stated in the activity plan, should have changed after each game. However, team members would often seem to take over each other's roles, resulting in individuals physically taking away the tool that another team member was using. This is shown in Figure 9 where Child 4 (f) reaches to take the keyboard away from Child 2 (m) whilst he is distracted by Child 3 (f) talking to him.

Figure 148. Child 4 (f) moves keyboard away from Child 2 (m)

Another example is shown in Figure 10, where both Child 2 (m) and 3 (f) both trying to hold the robot, whilst Child 2 also presses buttons on the keyboard at the same time as Child 4 (f).

Figure 149. Team members try to contribute to and take over other member's roles

The majority of these interactions (15 out of 17 interactions), where one group member takes a tool off another member happened between the genders, rather than for example, one of the girls taking the robot off the other girl. However, there were also some instances where this intervention would occur within the gender, for example in Figure 150 where the boys are both trying to do that same role at the keyboard while the girls both hold the cable. It is therefore uncertain whether this was a gendered interaction or not.

Figure 150. Multiple members assume the same role, shared within the gender groups

As well as taking tools off each other in order to use them, there were instances where one child would take a tool off another child for no apparent reason other than to have **ownership** over the object. Out of 17 interactions in which one student would take a tool off of another, 11 instances appeared to be based on ownership and control rather than for practical use. The majority of these interactions happened between Child 1 (m) and Child 4 (f), and Child 4 would take a tool away from him but then not actually appear to use it for anything. For example, Figure 24 shows a screenshot taken moments after Child 4 (f) had taken ownership of the instruction sheet tool, yet here and for the following few minutes she did not use it.

Figure 151. Child 4 takes ownership of instruction sheet but doesn't use it

Interactions between Child 1 and Child 4, taking tools off each other was a repeating occurrence, which seemed to escalate as the session progressed. One minute and five seconds after Figure 24, Child 4 began to show **frustration** at Child 1 taking the tool, as is shown in Figure 152, with Child 4 showing her annoyance with a hand gesture. Fifteen minutes after this, a point was reached where Child 4 realised that Child 1 wanted to take the information sheet and so she held on tight enough that he physically could not, shown in Figure 153.

Figure 152. Child 4 (f) (offshot) shows frustration with hand gesture at Child 1 (m) taking the information sheet

Figure 153. Child 4 (f) holds the sheet tightly so that Child 1 (m) can't take it away

Whilst no form of arguing seemed to take place between Child 1 and 4, the two team members were clearly very aware of each other and the **power dynamic** they had at play over this piece of paper. This control through ownership is also seen through other objects, such as the robot. However, as this case of taking over is between two individuals, it is uncertain whether the dynamic is related to their gender, or whether it is due to individual character and pre-existing relationships.

However, as time went on, the team appeared to share the information sheet more. This also corresponded with the games becoming harder, during which the team also appeared to have more **discussion**. For example, when completing the harder activity of making the robot complete a sequence of action from just the push of

one button on the keyboard, Child 4 (f) was seen to hold the information sheet in a way that other team members could also read it at the same time. This is shown in Figure 154. However, she still holds onto the sheet, so although she is sharing the object, she has maintained an element of power by controlling whether the boys can see it or not.

Figure 154. Child 4 (f) shares the instruction sheet with the boys.

20.3.1.3 PHYSICALITY

As well as creating a level of control through ownership and location of the tools that were used in the workshop, individuals in the team also used physicality and their body location and position to exercise control. As is shown in Figure 92, for example, the group worked with the two boys on one side of the table sitting next to each other, and the two girls sitting on the **opposite side of the table** sitting next to each other. The four members stayed sitting in these seats for the vast majority of the session. The group had worked in this same physical set-up in the previous year's workshop. The split of the genders into **separate physical positions** on opposite sides of the table meant it was easier for the students of the same gender to communicate and share tools.

As well as being physically located in different places, the team members were also observed to use their physicality as a form of control by physically intervening in what another team member was doing. It is difficult to interpret from video observation why these interventions took place – if the team member in question was doing something wrong or whether it was done in jest. However, this action was purely observed with the boys, Child 1 and Child 2, trying to stop Child 4 (f) from behaving in a certain way. Examples included Child 2 wagging his finger to tell Child 4 off when she tried to use the keyboard, Child 1 making Child 4 put the robot down on the table and Child 1 **physically moving** Child 4's arm multiple times when it was in the robot's way, the latter of which is shown in Figure 155.

Figure 155. Before and after Child 1 (m) physically intervenes what Child 4 (f) is doing

20.3.2

Evidence of Learning

This section explores how the workshop evidenced learning by the students and what learning objectives (see 20.1.1) were evidenced to have been met. Overall, the majority of the learning objectives had evidence to show they were met. Evidence of learning can be shown through indirect methods that imply that learning has occurred, or through direct methods that provide definitive evidence that students have met the learning objectives. This section will be structured by first exploring evidence of learning through ‘Direct Methods’, followed by exploring the evidence through ‘Indirect Methods’. ‘Direct Methods’ data is taken from artefacts of learning – including worksheets completed by the students and the code create in Scratch2 by each group to programme their robot. ‘Indirect Methods’ data is taken from mid-point reflections, video observations, tutor observations and student questionnaire answers

20.3.2.1 *Direct Methods*

This section will explore how direct methods were used to evidence the ‘Subject-related’ and ‘Technology-related’ learning objectives of the workshop. In the post-activity report, the tutor stated that the children had evidenced learning a lot. For example:

- “They used measuring tools such as ruler and protractor;
- Students used positive and negative numbers;
- Students used whole numbers and decimal numbers in order to achieve their desired outcomes;
- Students gained a better understanding of what a robot is and now know some common robotic parts”

However, the tutors did not consider where this learning was actually evidenced, for example in artefacts of learning produced by the students. This section therefore considers what evidence is provided through the worksheets and codes and finally explores other possible methods for evidencing learning in future workshops.

During the course of the workshop, the student groups had two worksheets that were completed: one exploring the anatomy of the Finch robot (shown in Figure 156) and another that was used to practice using a protractor to measure angles (completed example shown in Figure 157). The former provides evidence of the students understanding what a robot is and knowing common robot parts. Six out of the seven groups completed the worksheet entirely correctly, and the final group only got one label wrong. Therefore, there is strong evidence for the students understanding their robot’s anatomy. The latter sheet provides evidence for the students learning how to measure angles – although it is evidenced that they had learnt how to use the protractor, not all answers were accurate and many groups completed only some of the exercises. The students have demonstrated that they understand how to use a protractor, but would need further practice or guidance to gain speed and accuracy.

OUR ROBOT

**CHECK OUT THE LIST OF ELEMENTS BELOW.
CAN YOU FIND THEIR PLACE ON THE DIAGRAM
OF THE ROBOT? THE PICTURES ARE YOUR HINTS!**

USB port	INFRARED PROXIMITY SENSOR	ACCELEROMETER <small>Measures the acceleration and helps the robot to orient itself in space</small>
LED lights <small>An element that emits light – sometimes in different colors.</small>	TEMPERATURE SENSOR	LIGHT SENSOR

Figure 156. 'Anatomy of our Robot' worksheet

Figure 157. Example of part of a completed 'Measuring Angles' worksheet

Although the worksheets evidenced the achievement of a few specific learning objectives, the majority of evidence was provided by the programmes produced for the robot by the students on the software Scratch2, which were saved as evidence of learning. An example of this coding is shown in Figure 158.

Figure 158. Example of code created by students to programme the Finch robot

As explained previously, each group worked through a series of 'games' described on activity information sheets, with each game building on the knowledge learnt in previous game.

Concerning the objective "Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle", the playful part of the workshop was very successful. The students were laughing during the race since the "spider" never started

running, the "scorpion" was moving backwards and the "beetle" was running very fast! The following screen shots capture this special race, shown in Figure 92

Figure 22. The insect "battle"

shows what learning objectives could be evidenced through code in each game, and whether the groups met these objectives. As can be seen by the majority green shading in the table, most groups evidenced meeting the learning objectives. The orange blocks, where students partially met the objective appeared to be due to the task not being completed fully, which may be because the group ran out of the time (see Section 20.3.3). The one occasion a red block is shown, the group did not save any code that formed a sequence – although an issue may be here that they deleted a code that they formed before saving it.

Table 28. Learning evidenced through coding produced in games. (Green = objective met, Orange = partially met, Red = not met)

Game	Learning Objectives	Group	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7
		1						

1: Movement	Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers	Green						
	Understand that robots are programmable	Green						
2: Colours	Learn more about LEDs and how to program the LED	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Green
3: Smart Movement	Apply sequences of actions to program their robot.	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
4: Measurement & Time	None evidenced through codes alone	Light Blue						
5: Precise Programming & Angle Measurement	None evidenced through codes alone	Light Blue						

However, as is shown in

Concerning the objective "Examine which is the faster robotic insect at the "Insects' battle", the playful part of the workshop was very successful. The students were laughing during the race since the "spider" never started running, the "scorpion" was moving backwards and the "beetle" was running very fast! The following screen shots capture this special race, shown in Figure 92

Figure 22. The insect "battle"

, the codes alone for Game 4 & 5 did not provide enough evidence to prove that learning objectives were met. These two games were based on the learning objectives related to measuring angles. However, the games themselves involved the students having to experiment with the code they were creating to make the robots draw the right angles, which resulted in not all of the attempts the groups made being saved onto the Scratch2 coding files. Furthermore, other artefacts of learning other than the codes were produced in these games, consisting of the angles and lines that the robots drew on a sheet of paper, however these sheets of paper were not retained.

Finally, although there was some effective evidence of learning for the groups as a whole, there was no evidence for individual learning. Whilst many of the workshops run in ER4STEM are based on group work due to the multiple benefits of collaboration etc., it is still important to ensure that all individuals are learning and that there is evidence of this learning. Although a group may achieve the learning objectives overall, there may be one student who does not understand or who was perhaps unengaged or excluded within the work. On the other hand, it is likely that this workshop is implemented within a wider suite of educational activities and so there may be opportunity for individuals to demonstrate their knowledge in other lessons or workshops.

20.3.2.2 INDIRECT METHODS:

The more indirect methods evidenced the 'Social and action-related' and 'Argumentation and fostering of mater culture' learning objectives for the workshops. These learning objectives are considered as '21st century skills', which are often developed over a longer period than a single workshop and so can be harder to evidence as being learnt. In this workshop, evidence of learning objectives concerning for example communication, problem-solving and decision-making being met was provided through focus group videos, interviews and student questionnaires. For example, Student 22025 (f) answered the questions "What have you learned about working with other people?" in the post-workshop questionnaire "We have to listen to each other!" This

provides evidence for learning about communication. Furthermore, although the video observations in 20.3.1 have focussed on evidence of one gender taking over, there is also evidence to show that the group are implementing interpersonal skills through discussion and collaboration, particularly as the games got harder.

20.3.3 Differentiated Activities

Both workshops had differentiated activities in the form of extension exercises. If a group completed the core activities but still had time left, they had extension exercises available to complete (see Figure 159). These extensions were included for every 'game' that the groups had to complete. The differentiation was therefore based on pace of learning rather than differentiation by task, as students did not learn anything new by completing the extension tasks, but rather were provided with more opportunity to practice their new knowledge.

Figure 159. Example of extension exercises (note: translated from Bulgarian)

One of the tutors stated in his reflection that five out of the six groups of students had moved onto the extension exercises in at least one of the games in the first session. However, the final group would often require more time than was set to complete the compulsory tasks. Furthermore, the tutors also stated in the post-activity report that they believed the workshop could be improved in the future by allowing more time for the students to experiment and explore the tasks. Therefore, the differentiation by pace worked well in providing more work for those groups that learnt more quickly, however the workshop needed refining in terms of its timing in order to ensure all groups could complete the compulsory tasks.

The extension exercises were not mentioned by any of the students in their post-workshop questionnaires answers or in their mid-point reflections, and were also not mentioned in the focus group interview. Therefore, there is no evidence to suggest the students formed opinions towards the differentiated activities.

20.4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section provides concluding remarks for this report, by summarising the findings and stating recommendations for the future.

20.4.1 One Gender Taking Over

- Although the boys were observed to take the lead on the activities, the girls had other mechanisms for creating their own form of control, which would then be further countered by control from the boys.

This power was created through the use and control of tools and through physicality in individual's bodies.

- It is difficult to interpret whether the way individuals act and interact is due to their gender or their personal character.
- The team worked better with fewer cases of genders taking over as the tasks got harder. This suggests that the team perhaps found the early tasks too easy and that they cooperated and collaborated more when they had an optimal amount of challenge in their learning.

Recommendation:

- It would be interesting in the future to position teams of an equal split of genders so that it wasn't 'boys vs girls' on either side of the work table, and to observe what gendered interactions take place.

20.4.2 Evidence of Learning

- Overall, the majority of the learning objectives had evidence to show they were met. However, the difficulty in meeting the learning objectives and ensuring there is evidence to prove this comes partially from the large number of learning objectives that have been created. Furthermore, objectives, both in education and in management, are recognised that being effective if they are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Timely (S.M.A.R.T.).
- The codes created by the students on Scratch2 provided a lot of evidence of learning, but not all coding attempts were saved.
- Overall, evidence for 21st century skills were all taken from sources that are only being recorded during the ER4STEM project due to the research nature of the project, and so evidence such as focus group videos would be unlikely to exist in a normal classroom or workshop setting.
- Evidence gathering needs to be considered in terms of the individual even though the students are working in groups.

Recommendations:

- In the future the workshop should have its learning objectives refined so that there are fewer and so they are all S.M.A.R.T.
- It would be worthwhile to investigate a way for students to show both their final codes and the codes that they developed through experimentation.
- These codes should be triangulated with other forms of evidence. Some of these were already created as artefacts, such as the angles drawn by their robots, which need to be retained as forms of evidence.
- Methods should be considered for capturing evidence of learning soft-skills in a way that would be more sustainable in the future, rather than relying on video data and interviews. For example, the reflection activities are often used in education and so this could be expanded further than a three question 'mid-point reflection' and into an activity such as: design a leaflet for students who haven't worked with the finch robot before and include information on how to complete the work as a team.
- Overall, it is recommended that ways for individuals to evidence their work in included, for example by personal reflection or personal worksheets.

20.4.3 Differentiation

- The differentiation provided was effective in differentiating by pace and allowing groups to be supported to reaching a higher level of learning.

Recommendation:

- The timing of the activities should be refined to ensure that the lower ability students are able to complete the learning objectives.

21 APPENDIX M: BULGARIA WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

21.1 CONTEXT

Workshop: 14_PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm: Education Robotics For Sustainability and Life Skills

21.1.1 Description of the Activity

This case study took place in a public general education school in Bulgaria with a group of 27 students aged eleven and twelve. The group was mixed gender with 20 males and 7 females, however one male was absent from the first session. The workshop was held over two sessions, four days apart, lasting two hours per sessions and four hours in total. Students worked in groups of three to five members, and each group had their own robot and computer. Seven participants had completed the ER4STEM workshop ‘Visualising Mathematics with the Mathbot’ a year previously, of which six of these participants had also completed the ER4STEM workshop ‘Educational Robotics for Creativity’ two years previously. Alongside this recurring participation, the group also participated in robotics workshops run by ESICEE as part of their curriculum for the year, outside of ER4STEM. Furthermore, ten participants had programming lessons writing in the programming languages JavaScript or C++, four participants had attended extracurricular robotics clubs and six participants had used robots at home. Overall, the group were of high ability and were familiar with the style of work and teamwork involved in the workshop, were familiar with the tutors running the workshop and were only unfamiliar with the type of robot being used. The workshop and any programming took place in the medium of Bulgarian.

A full description is provided in the activity plan; this is the summary of the activity:

*“The goal of this workshop is to introduce and exercise a multidisciplinary approach towards building general awareness on a variety of aspects of everyday life. Such aspects might be **ecological thinking, applications of robotics, mathematical argumentation and coordinate system knowledge.**”*

Participants play a set of games with the robotics arm. Every game introduces a problem, be it a mathematical problem, requiring the students to program the robot in order to place an item on a specific place of a coordinate system or be it a real-life problem engaging students in a game of sorting and recycling reusable materials. Through robot-enabled games, children cooperatively program robots to solve everyday life problems and improve on digital fluency skills and proportional thinking.”

The stated objectives of the workshop were:

- Subject related:
 - Mathematics:
 - Learn more about coordinate systems in the 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional space;
 - Showcase the difference between whole numbers and fractions without going into theory;
 - Proportions between time, distance and movement;
 - Technology:
 - Exercise very basic Scratch programming skills;
 - Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts;
 - Students understand that robots are programmable;
 - Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot;

- Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative real-life problem solving;
- Develop creative thinking skills to find different applications of robotics and programming in other fields
- Technology use related
 - Programming the [RobotArm](#) kit by [CBiS Education](#) through the visual programming software [Scratch](#) with the help of a basic HTTP server customized by ESI CEE.
- Social and action related
 - Develop problem solving skills;
 - Exercise effective communication skills;
 - Encourage flexibility and adaptability;
 - Foster collaboration skills;
- Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:
 - Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas.
 - Encourage curiosity;
 - Encourage tinkering and experimentation;
 - The games require the decision-making process within a team;
 - Identifying and solving problems;
 - Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.
 - Exercise logical thinking;

As stated in the objectives, the students used a RobotArm with the programming software Scratch2, shown in Figure 91.

Figure 160. RobotArm and Scratch2 programming software

The groups were encouraged to rotate the roles that individuals had within the group, in order to allow everyone to gain experience and work successfully as a group.

21.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

21.2.1 Data Collection

Out of the 27 students who participated in the workshop, 26 students gave consent to be included in research project – 20 males and 6 females. The tutors who ran the workshop, who were Bulgarian project partners from ESICEE, collected data. Although a full dataset was not provided, with only 50 minutes of video data from the first session, a large amount of useful data was still delivered. This data included video recordings, photos taken by the tutors, pre and post questionnaires, an interview with participants, observational notes and reflections from the tutors, mid-point reflections by participants, the activity plan, artefacts of learning and artefacts provided from the activity.

21.2.2 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved looking for particular incidents, focusing on; innovative approaches to collaboration; innovative ways to develop soft-skills; developing interpersonal skills; developing intra-relational skills; sharing ideas through tangible artefacts; and students relating robotics to problems that influence their lives. These were decided in advance of the analysis based on the research team's observations, the data collection and overall research priorities. Data was coded using emergent codes.

21.2.2.1 VIDEO DATA

The video data shows the work of a focus group (Group 5) consisting of three males in the first session (23038, 23041 and 21255) and four males in the second session, with student 23033 joining from another group – it is unknown why he switched groups. However, the video data also has a good view of the majority of other participants, shown in Figure 161, and so the behaviour and interactions of participants in general are analysed as well as the focus group.

Figure 161. View of Focus Group and many other participants in video data

21.2.2.2 INTERVIEW

The four participants in the focus group were due to participate in a post-workshop interview with one of the tutors. However, at the end of the session some members of the focus group didn't want to take part as they had an exam later on in the day. Therefore, only two participants from the focus group took part in the interview (23033 and 23028) with four other participants (21012, 21001, 23045 and 23032) from other groups forming a total of six students. Two of the participants (21012 and 21001) were recurring participants and had attended ER4STEM workshop in the previous two years. All the student in the interview group were male.

21.3 FINDINGS

This report structures its findings by sections: 'Innovative Approach to Collaboration', 'Soft-Skills', 'Sharing Ideas through Tangible Artefacts' and 'Students relating robotics to problems that influence their lives'.

21.3.1 Innovative Approach to Collaboration

This section explores an innovative approach that was designed in the activity plan in order to allow the students to work together in a collaborative manner. This approach was in the form of a game at the end of the workshop, which was based on the knowledge that students had gained during the workshop. Previously, students had been working in groups of 3-4 participants, but during this final game individuals from each team took it in turns to play collaboratively alongside members from the other teams, whilst the other participants watched and supported. Overall, it is found that this meta-collaborative game was successful in engaging most, but not all, students and taught them the importance of working in a team.

The game was based on the simulation of a waste separation station, with students using the robots to separate textile (felt balls), bio waste (coffee capsules) and plastic (bottle caps). The game is explained in the activity plan as such:

"The setting of the game consists of 2-4 tables merged together with a sufficient amount of chairs around them so that 2-4 teams could work on them. Every team has their own computer and robotic arm (in case of PCs that can't be easily moved, USB extension cables will be needed). Arms are placed on the same game board. The game board could be one of the sheets they previously worked on but should now be divided into three segments, similarly to as shown on the diagram below.

This way Arm 3 will be responsible for collecting textile (in our case felt balls), Arm 2 will collect bio waste (in our case it is represented by the coffee capsules) and Arm 1 will collect plastic (bottle caps). Elements are collected from all over the field and placed in respectively marked rectangle.

All elements are scattered in the middle of the field in a way that will prevent every arm being able to collect all objects of the material it is responsible for collecting, without relying on somebody else helping them out by pushing or dropping an element they need within their range.

The teams have 7 minutes for actual waste collection and 3 minutes to discuss or come up with a strategy before the game and to put the arm in a starting position of their choice. After the game, a collaborative reflection lead by the tutors takes place.

Score is formed by how many items are overall collected by all teams.”

Whilst during the whole workshop, the students have been working collaboratively together in teams to learn about and explore with the robot, by designing the final game to include each team to work together in one giant team, a form of meta-collaboration takes place. The students work both within their team (with one student taking the lead and the others supporting) and also within the whole class (using the robots collaboratively to achieve the most points they can). The game took place in a new game area that was shared between the teams, meaning that no one team had ownership over the environment or tools other than their robot. A photo taken whilst the students played the game is shown in Figure 16, which illustrates this shared space and the interest that the students are taking in the game.

Figure 162. Students playing the collaborative game

During the interview, the participants explained that the final game had taught them a lot about the importance of teamwork and collaborating with others. Upon being asked what they would remember from the entire workshop, students mentioned the collaborative game:

"21001 (m): The activities with the arm and the main game with the recycling because you gave us problems that were difficult to solve by yourself and everything had to be happening in a team.

...

23032 (m): I learned from this activity with the arm that it is better to play in a team with someone, to help each other, it is better than to work alone and that it will be hard to make something similar alone. With friends you are able to do much more.

21012 (m): I also liked the last game because I understood that it is better to work in team than to work alone because in a certain moment, for example in this game with the waste, our team had to collect bottle caps and when we collected all nearby bottle caps, we needed help to collect the bottle caps that were not within our reach and thus I realized how important it is to have a team."

In comparison, it is stated in the activity plan that it is also possible to play this final game in a competitive manner, with scoring taking place for each individual team. The tutor noted in the post-activity report that the game was far more successful when played collaboratively in this workshop, than when it had been played competitively in previous workshops: *"it felt very much better, a lot less tense and I think the students appreciated the experience more."* Having this direct comparison of a collaborative and competitive approach to the activity provides some evidence of the benefits of encouraging students to work together collaboratively.

However, although many of the students commented on their enjoyment of the game, the video and photo data also suggests that not all students engaged well with the game. Figure 163 shows that while the majority of students are at the game table, there are also a number of students not watching or engaging and sitting away from the table, on either side of the picture. This was confirmed in the tutor's observational notes, stating: *"5-6 people, mainly girls, were not really participating in the game in the end, saying that they are not interested in playing, even though most of them tried at least once. However, students, who were not so interested all supported those who were. Furthermore, they shared that they learnt new things in mathematics or other subjects and were generally positive and happy to have participated in our workshop."* The tutor is correct that all students gave positive feedback of the overall workshop in their post-activity questionnaires – with all students rating their enjoyment of the workshop as a '4' or '5' out of 5 stars. This suggests that students who were disengaged enjoyed the workshop overall and learnt despite their apparent disengagement in this activity.

Figure 163. Some students didn't engage with the collaborative game

21.3.2 Soft-Skills

21.3.2.1 INNOVATIVE WAY TO DEVELOP SOFT-SKILLS

The soft-skills that were developed during the workshop overall are discussed in 21.3.2.2 and 21.3.2.3. However, through the innovative approach to collaboration discussed in 21.3.1, was also created an innovative opportunity within the workshop for soft-skills to be developed. As has already been discussed, the final game provided a unique opportunity for teamwork and meta-collaboration, which multiple students referred to as important for showing the benefits of teamwork, shown in the quotes above. However, what has not already been discussed is how this teamwork was developed through communication.

As is stated in the activity plan and in 21.3.1, the teams were given time to strategize as a large group before the game began. This allowed for ideas to be shared across the different teams. Unfortunately, this period of strategizing was not recorded in the video data and there is no evidence recorded that refers to soft-skills that were developed specifically during this innovative activity.

Furthermore, the students used the previous activities in the workshop not only to learn about the robot arm, but to develop their soft-skills such as communicating and listening in their individual teams. When it came to the time of the final game, these skills were then put into practice in a more difficult circumstance they were having to communicate and listen with people who they had not built up a relationship with within their original team.

Just as during the course of the workshop the activities using the robot required more skill and got harder, so did the activities in terms of their soft-skills.

Soft-skills will continue to be discussed in the following two sub-sections, 21.3.2.2 and 21.3.2.3.

21.3.2.2 DEVELOPING INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

Most of the soft-skills developed during the workshop were interpersonal skills – those relating to relationships and communicating between students. The students mentioned that they developed these skills through teamwork in the post-workshop questionnaires and in their mid-point reflections. This section explores the positive development of these skills through teamwork, but also some of the more negative things students claimed to have learnt about teamwork.

Most of the soft-skills that students referred to having developed were the communication and listening skills required to work in a team. For example, in the post-workshop questionnaire student 23034 (f) said *“You have to give chance to the others and we have to listen to each other”*. Here, the student also touches on another common theme mentioned by students – to compromise with each other and ensure that team members took turns in their roles. Some students explained the consequences they had learnt from not taking turns in their roles, such as in Group 4’s mid-point reflection: *“The most difficult part was generally related to teamwork, how we take turns, who works. We got bored at one point as only two of us worked and the others didn’t have anything to do.”* Students not engaging due to the groups not taking turns in their roles was also noted by the tutor in their observations, stating that she felt that in Group 5 (focus group) *“only one of the students worked consistently and the others were mostly observing and giving advice or providing feedback on the robot’s behaviour”*. A final common skill mentioned was a developed understanding of helping each other: *“To listen to each other and to help each other”* (Student 21001 m – post-workshop questionnaire). Overall there is a clear sense that these skills are interlinked by teamwork, through students’ often referring to the importance of multiple interpersonal skills.

As well as noting the soft-skills that they had developed during the workshop through teamwork, five students in their post-workshop questionnaire and one group in their mid-point reflection commented on more negative experiences they had with teamwork. For example, Group 5 (focus group) stated in their mid-point reflection that *“Our biggest challenge was to not fight when one of us did something stupid and pushed over all the capsules.”* Another example comes from student 23044 (m), who stated in their post-activity questionnaire that *“Some (people) are lazy, some are not.”* Overall, it should be considered that these negative experiences of working with other students will still have developed their interpersonal skills, but perhaps in skills such as conflict resolution and underperformance. A good example of this comes from Group 3’s mid-point reflection, in which they explain the importance of teamwork despite the difficulties that can come from being in a mixed ability group: *“Some of us are good and some of us are not, but sometimes, we have to work together and everyone needs to have a purpose in the team, otherwise they just goof around, get bored and piss off the others that work.”*

21.3.2.3 DEVELOPING INTRA-RELATIONAL SKILLS

Intra-relational skills refers to how an individual understands oneself, and so this section explores how the workshop enabled the students to develop an understanding of how they work, particularly within a team, and how they can improve this in the future. Most of the soft-skills developed fell into the category of interpersonal skills (21.3.2.2) rather than intra-personal skills. For example, when asked in the post-workshop questionnaire *“What have you learnt about yourself”*, students would refer to working in a team or their ability to work with robots. One exception was student 23045’s (m) answer – I have learnt that *“I am worth something”*.

Presumably this participant is referring to the fact that they themselves can contribute to how a team works. This statement implies a feeling of self-worth, self-belief and confidence. Another example of development of an intra-relational skill comes from Group 5’s mid-point reflection, where the team stated that they had learnt that it was important to be patient with one-another. Whilst this is an element of interpersonal skills, the

concept of patience also involves an element of self-control – of remaining calm and controlling your own emotions in order to work effectively with others. This perhaps highlights the close link between interpersonal and intra-relational skills.

21.3.3 Sharing Ideas through Tangible Artefacts

This section explores how the students explained their ideas with each other using the robotic arm as an artefact to help in this process. One of the techniques that the students used to understand how the robot arm worked was to compare it to their own arm. This was explained by Group 4 in their mid-point reflection:

“Initially, our challenge was to learn how to manipulate the arm, to tell which part of the arm is which button on the screen. Afterwards, we started comparing to our own arms and it became easier to understand how to control it smoothly and got used to it.”

The group state that comparing the robot to their own arm helped them to develop their own understanding as a group. However, the video and photo data also shows that on multiple occasions (more than 10 incidences) that individuals would use their own arm to communicate to another group member how they believed the robot arm needed to move. An example of this is shown in Figure 164, where two participants are modelling the position of the robot arm with their own arms. One boy shows the upright position of the arm, whilst the other also uses his fingers to represent the position of the gripper section of the arm.

Figure 164. Two boys show what they want to robot arm to do using their own arms as model

As well as modelling the robot arm on their own arm, participants would also point to specific parts of the robot, or to coordinates in the paper that the robot was placed on to explain their ideas. An example of this occurring during the group work session is shown in Figure 165, whilst Figure 166 shows multiple students pointing to their robots during the collaborative game at the end of the session. In the short video footage provided, participants were pointing to the robots and using their arms to model the robot more during the game – often making these gestures every few seconds. Presumably this was due to the high pace nature of the game and the communication within the team to try and complete the task.

Figure 165 Child pointing to a part of the robot

Figure 166. Multiple individuals explain their ideas using the robots during the collaborative game

Using the robot as an artefact to explain ideas was not a behaviour restricted to just the participants, but was also used by the workshop tutors to explain ideas to students. Figure 167 shows the tutor using her hands to gesture how the robot should move within its 3D coordinates to the focus group and all three students watch her hands and the robot.

Figure 167. Tutor explains an idea with the students, gesturing to the robot arm to explain

Finally, as well as using the artefacts to share their ideas whilst learning, the students in the post-workshop interview also suggested using showcasing of their own artefacts as a way to improve the workshop in the future. Firstly, the students explained that they thought it would be useful if they could also build the robot arm, as well as understand how this one works. They then went on to explain that they would want to display the robot that they had created to the other teams:

- 21012: *If we can experiment with our knowledge and skills to create more things and more interesting things with the given materials, but not solving specific tasks. I mean, if we can invent new things and share our inventions thereupon we'll feel more freedom and we'll have more fun.*
- Interviewer: *What would you like to share and with whom – you mean to share your experiences, or...?*
- 21012: *No, the team to share what it has invented and made with the others.*
- Interviewer: *How do you imagine this happening – for example everyone gathering around your table or you all go to a special table where demonstrations happen?*
- 21012: *To go to a special table, like this one, for example, because it is spacious and all can get together around it and see it (the result).*
- Interviewer: *So, you mean not your teams' working table but going somewhere else to show something?*
- 21012: *Yes."*

This concept of using a shared space in similar to how a shared space was used in the final collaborative game (21.3.1), which allowed for all student to congregate in a space where no one team felt more ownership over the area than another. Although it may be unrealistic to create a workshop where students of this age could build a robotic arm, the students have noted here that they appreciate chances for creativity and freedom, as well as the opportunity to display their work to students outside of their team.

21.3.4 Students relating robotics to problems that influence their lives

This section explores the research question *“Do students identify and define problems that influence their lives during the workshop”*. It was found that whilst students did not clearly define and identify problems, they did relate the use of the robot to their own lives, making it personally meaningful and undertaking playful exploration. Furthermore, they considered the wider implications for use of the robot, for issues that perhaps didn't affect them personally, but that they identified as societal problems. As explored in 21.3.1, the activity plan sets out for each group to take part in a collaborative game, which was based on a simulation of a waste separation station. In the tutor reflection, the tutor stated that *“The collaborative game was a huge success and could be further improved on in order to teach other real life principles.”*

Whilst the students did not directly refer to the game and its real-life scenario, students did commonly refer to real-life applications of robots in the interview and in their mid-point reflections. For example, Group 6 stated in their mid-point reflection that they had learnt *“that every robot serves different purpose and while some robots have wheels and serve the purpose of moving, in the two-dimensional space, there are other robots, like this arm or even drones”*. Group 2 stated that *“We saw a new robot that was different than the other robots we have worked with. We also seen other applications of robotics.”* Two themes can be noted here: that the robot arm was different to the other robots the students had worked with, and that robots have applications in real life. Group 1 further expanded on these concepts:

“We worked with a robot that is, how should we say... more realistic, more down to earth. The other robots look like toys or cars, but this one simulates a human arm and is a smaller copy of a robot that is used in engineering about a lot of things. So we saw something that looked like robotics more than the Finch robot, for example.”

The students found that they could connect to the realism of this robot and its applications, which made it personally meaningful. This personal connection was observed in the video and photo data through playful exploration, in which groups would use the robot to pick up their own belongings, such as a phone (Figure 20), lipbalm (Figure 21), to squeeze their nose (Figure 22) or to attempt to write something with a pen (Figure 23).

Figure 168. Robot holding a phone

Figure 169. Robot holding lipbalm

Figure 170. Robot squeezing a student's nose

Figure 171. Robot holding a pencil

Regarding making the robot hold a pen – which was observed in multiple groups - Group 4 reflected that they were most proud of *“When we picked up a pen with the robotic arm and tried to write something. It wasn’t successful but it is something we’d remember.”* The interviewees even explored how they could be successful in using the robot to write with a pen by making it even more *“realistic”* by having more grippers. In this example, the students identify a problem by themselves and find a hypothetical but realistic creative solution:

- “23033 (m): We can add more fingers to the arm and move these fingers.*
Interviewer: So, you would like more functional arm with more degrees of freedom? (C2) What will be the advantage if the robotic arm is like a real human arm, with more fingers?
23033: For example, the arm can take a pen and write with it. To try writing a letter or word and it will be interesting because you should consider very precisely how many seconds it should write when you program it, for example, for a “w”.”

Finally, participants mentioned in four different sources (mid-point reflections and the interview) that they could relate and apply what they had learnt in the workshop to other subjects. This largely included mathematics, through their new knowledge of 3D coordinates. However, participants in the interview expanded that they thought their knowledge of the robot could be applied to many of their other school subjects.

“23038 (m): Well, in mathematics and information technology it could help us. If we can learn also how the robot is built, it can help for the subjects of technology and entrepreneurship.

...

23032 (m): Yes, for the engineering, according my opinion, it is very useful because we know the purposes of the robot’s components and also, this is based on the human arm, in the case with the robotic arm. Or the human body, in relation to other robots, and thus we could learn about the human system before we have biology classes.

21012 (m): According to me, for this workshop we needed knowledge in mathematics to know the coordinates, how to deal with such type of systems; we needed knowledge in Human and Nature to know the place and functions of the parts of the human body, we needed knowledge on information technology for the programming. And this workshop developed our knowledge in these sciences.”

21.4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section provides concluding remarks for this report, by summarising the findings and stating any recommendations for the future.

21.4.1 Innovative Approach to Collaboration

- A collaborative game between the teams at the end of the workshop allowed for meta-collaboration. This was successful as the students claimed it was fun but also that they learnt a lot about the importance of teamwork.
- The tutor had a direct comparison of the success of the game having also led it in a competitive manner during a different workshop, which was not as effective.
- However, not all of the students engaged with the game, with some sitting out or not taking their turn.

Recommendations

- To develop the game further, refining its rules and aims – as suggested by the tutor.
- To develop more defined roles for the group members who are not controlling the robot during that round, to try to encourage students to stay engaged with the game and the workshop.

21.4.2 Innovative way to develop soft-skills

- The innovative approach to collaboration also allowed for an innovative approach to developing soft-skills, through the time in the game that was allotted to strategizing between the teams.

Recommendation:

- This form of meta-communication and meta-collaboration should be implemented in other workshops and further investigated.

21.4.3 Developing Interpersonal skills

- Most of the skills that students referenced to having developed were interpersonal skills related to teamwork.
- Whilst many students had a positive experience in their learning through teamwork, some students complained that other team members underperformed, messed around or argued. However, the students will still have developed their interpersonal skills through these negative experiences.

Recommendation:

- The tutors could state and explain the type of interpersonal skills that are used in teamwork to the students, including ones like conflict management and managing underperformance.

21.4.4 Developing Intra-relational skills

- Although students may have developed many intra-relational skills, they rarely commented on these in their reflections or questionnaires.
- However, some students did mention the development of patience, and a development of self-worth within a team.

Recommendation:

- If it desired for students to reflect on how they have developed their inter-relational skills, the tutors need to explain this more explicitly. This may be beneficial not only for evidencing this development, but for making the students more self-aware.

21.4.5 Sharing Ideas through Tangible Artefacts

- Students would relate the robot arm to their own arm as a model, both for personally understanding how it worked and for explaining to other team members how they thought the robot should move.
- Students would also point to certain parts of the robot whilst explaining their ideas.
- These behaviours were observed most often during the final collaborative game, presumably because of the heightened pressure of the activity.
- This behaviour was also observed in the tutor, who would use the robot as a tool for explanation when students wanted help.
- An interview participant suggested that the workshop could be improved by allowing for teams to display their own creativity and the ideas that they have formed to each other.

Recommendations:

- This behaviour could be encouraged if students are struggling to explain their thoughts in future workshops.
- Consider a way to incorporate creative showcasing in a shared space as suggested by a student – not only in this workshop but in others too.

21.4.6 Students relating robotics to problems that influence their lives

- The activity plan related the robot arm to a scenario of a real life application, which the students reacted well to.
- The students were able to relate the robot arm and what they had learnt to other applications, including to their other school subjects.
- The students appreciated the ‘realism’ of the robot in comparison to other robots they had used in the past, for example the Finch robot.
- The students made the robot pick up their own belongings, or to try write using a pen. This playful exploration resulted in the students being engaged with the robot by making its application personally meaningful.

Recommendations:

- A further session could be spent in which students design a robot arm which much solve a problem – explaining its application and how it works. This would allow students to develop their creativity, allow for showcasing to each other and would help develop their knowledge of the different parts of the robot.
- Some teachers (although not the tutors in this workshop) may interpret playful exploration with the robot as being bad behaviour. However, it is important to allow children to do this, in order to encourage their engagement and ideas around robot applications.

22 APPENDIX N: UK WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 1

22.1 CONTEXT

This case study explores the use of the online presentation programme ‘Sway’ to evidence students’ learning in the Cardiff University SLurtle Virtual Robotics workshops at Mary Immaculate High School in Wales.

22.1.1 The Participants

Between September 2017 and July 2018 all Year 9 students (age 14 to 15) at Mary Immaculate High School participated in workshops using SLurtle virtual robots as part of their timetabled ICT lessons. The students took part in two workshops over one school term, through 50-minute lessons held twice a week, every week of the term. Two classes ran simultaneously each term – each led by a teacher and supported by the research team. The classes worked on a carousel system meaning that the teachers taught a different group of students each term. In total, 161 pupils took part in the two workshops each, a breakdown of class sizes for all 12 workshops is shown in Table 29.

Table 29. Number of students who partook in workshops. Blue = T631. Red = T632.

	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5	Class 6
Term 1 – workshop 1	23 participants	22 participants				
Term 1 – workshop 2						
Christmas Break						
Term 2 – workshop 1			29 participants	24 participants		
Term 2 – workshop 2						
Easter Break						
Term 3 – workshop 1					32 participants	31 participants
Term 3 – workshop 2						

The school was located in a low socio-economic area of Wales, with 30.1% of students qualifying for Free School Meals (UK measurement of deprivation) – higher than the Welsh (17%) and local area (20.5%) average. Furthermore, the school had a higher than the Welsh and local average for the proportion of Ethnic Minority students (31.4%) and higher than the Welsh average for students with English as an Additional Language (8.5%). 34.1% of students were classified as having Special Educational Needs (the Welsh and local average is unknown). Average attendance rates of students at the school were measured as 93.9% - just lower than the Welsh average of 94.1% and local authority average of 94.2%. All school data was measured in 2017 and is publicly available (<http://mylocalschool.wales.gov.uk/School/6814607?lang=en>). The classes were mixed genders and to some degree mixed ability.

Teacher T631, a specialist Computer Science teacher who had participated in SLurtle robotics workshop in the previous year and lead teacher for the workshop, taught classes shown in blue. Teacher T632, who specialised in a humanities subject, had no previous experience of SLurtles or virtual worlds and was less confident

teaching the workshops, taught classes shown in pink. The classes were generally split so that T631 taught the higher ability students.

22.1.2 Description of the activity

Here is provided a brief description of the two workshops that each year 9 student completed based on activities plans MIHS_Y2_T1 and MIHS_Y2_T2.

22.1.2.1 WORKSHOP 1

The first workshop focuses on familiarising students with the virtual world and SLurtles. Through this workshop they learn how to navigate and interact with the virtual world; how to programme and control a SLurtle; demonstrate their mathematical knowledge by programming SLurtles; learn how to use loops in programmes; and apply this knowledge to create complex constructions in the virtual world. Alongside this, they are introduced to effective team-working and communication in the virtual world.

22.1.2.1.1 FIRST STEPS IN THE VIRTUAL WORLD

In advance of the first lesson, students had a basic, default avatar created for them. When they first log into the virtual world, all students arrive at the same point on the 'hello_world' island. This is an orientation island where students can freely explore how to control their avatar and interact with the virtual world and each other, or they can follow a prescribed path with instructions. It includes a house where students can collect various outfits for their avatars which can be mixed and matched. There are various activities for students to engage in and once they are ready as a class, they travel through one of the doors next to the house to teleport to their class island. See Deliverable 5.2 for more details about the virtual world.

22.1.2.1.2 INTRODUCTION TO SLURTLES

Each class island (Figure 172) is an identical space which is primarily comprised of a flat building space for students. Here students are introduced to SLurtle robots and the Scratch4OS programming environment.

Figure 172 Class island

SLurtles are programmable robots in the virtual world. They can be programmed using the graphical block-based programming environment Scratch for Open Sim (Scratch4OS). Once programmed, SLurtles can move about the virtual world and using specific commands can be programmed to create objects, which in turn can be programmed to be interactive (Figure 173).

Figure 173 Staircase built by programming a SLurtle (top of staircase) using the Scratch4OS script shown.

Students are initially introduced to SLurtle through a teacher demonstration, showing how to transfer the code from Scratch4OS to the SLurtle to make it move. The students are then invited to take a SLurtle and experiment with the various programming commands in Scratch4OS to discover what they can programme the SLurtle to do. Once they have gained these basic skills, in pairs, students are given a series of challenges to complete using the SLurtle. Using the 'pen' command and applying their mathematical knowledge of 2D they programme the SLurtle to create a series of shapes. The final two challenges (to create a star and a 3D cube) are used to extend the more able students (see Figure 174). Following the challenges, the teacher provides further instruction on how to create more complex objects, including a staircase and an interactive dancefloor. To create the latter, the SLurtle is programmed to create the dancefloor and then each tile of the floor is programmed to use sensors to detect the presence of an avatar and make a corresponding change in colour.

Challenges

1. Programme the SLurtle to draw the outline of a square with 1 meter sides.
2. Programme the SLurtle to draw the outline of a triangle with 1 meter sides.
3. Programme the SLurtle to draw the outline of a pentagon with 1 meter sides.
4. Programme the SLurtle to draw a star.
5. Programme the SLurtle to draw the outline of a cube.

Figure 174 SLurtle challenge sheet

22.1.2.2 WORKSHOP 2

Ahead of the second workshop, the class island is cleared and each group is given a dedicated 40x40 meter space with their group number on it. In this workshop, the whole class will create a virtual world island with each group responsible for their own space. Students are provided with brainstorming and planning time face-to-face to develop an idea for what will be in their space. Working collaboratively or cooperatively, using SLurtles, Scratch4OS and other building tools, students work together to create their installation in their group space over several weeks.

As they are on a shared class island, students are able to walk/fly around the island and view the installations of other groups. Via the teacher's computer and projection screen, the teacher is able to draw the whole-class' attention to particular installations and students can demonstrate to the whole class how they have created something.

22.1.3 Sways

Having participated in the SLurtle robotics workshops in Year 2, the lead teacher (T631) developed Sway books to accompany the SLurtle virtual robotics workshops in the third year of the ER4STEM project, following the recommendation from D6.4 regarding the evidencing of learning.

Sway (known fully as 'Office Sway') is an online presentation program by Microsoft Office, released in 2015. Users can create a presentable website using text and media. The Sway website is stored on Microsoft's servers, which were accessed through the student's Microsoft account, connected to their school email address.

T631 created a template Sway website, the structure of which is presented in 22.3.1. This template was used to generate a Sway for each student who would then update their personal Sway each week to create an

online exercise book that recorded their progress against lesson learning objectives. Although the students each took part in two workshops, the Sway was designed to be used throughout the term across both workshops. The Sways are also used in ICT lessons with the Year 7 and Year 8 classes at the school and so has been applied to activities other than the ER4STEM workshop.

The learning objectives set in the Sways were different from the learning objectives set for the overall workshop in the activity plans created by the researcher. It should be noted that as T631 created the Sway templates, although with guidance from the researcher, the Sways may have been influenced by his own priorities of trying to meet set learning outcomes of the Welsh curriculum set by the Welsh Government. These priorities were not necessarily aligned with the aims of ER4STEM, for example focussing less on evidencing the development of 21st century skills and more on aligning the workshop with the Computer Science curriculum. Therefore, it was to be expected that some recommendations made in 22.4 will be due to the difference in priorities between the teacher and ER4STEM.

22.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

22.2.1 Data Collection

161 students in total participated in workshops using SLurtle virtual robots and completed a Sway alongside this – out of these 161 students, 133 students gave consent to be included in the research project. The Cardiff University research team, with the support of the two class teachers, collected data in class lessons across the course of the year, in each of the 12 workshops. Relevant data for this report included observational notes, three opportunistic interviews with six students and interviews with the two teachers at the end of the school year, post-workshop questionnaires, the template Sway website from each term, and each students' completed Sway as artefacts of learning.

22.2.2 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved exploring a pre-determined research question 'how was students' learning evidenced', decided in advance based on the overall research priorities and the research team's observations during the workshops, whilst remaining open to emergent themes. To achieve this, the Sways and interviews were coded using the constant comparative approach. Other data sets were treated as secondary data.

Sways were only analysed from one class which in general was of a higher ability (631), but across the three groups of students in the three terms. Sways were randomly sampled from the first term and coded until saturation was reached at 11 Sways. This process was repeated for term 2, with saturation reached at 5 Sways, and term 3, with saturation reached at 7 Sways.

In order to compare evidence of learning within the Sways to student's self-reported learning in the post-workshop questionnaires, the only questionnaires analysed were those completed by students who's Sways were sampled. . Students completed two post-workshop questionnaires – one halfway through the term after the first workshop and the other at the end of the term after the second workshop. The five students in Term 2 were an exception to this, only completing one post-workshop questionnaire at the end of the term. Furthermore, student 63124 (Term 1) and 63197 (Term 3) only completed the first questionnaire and not the second, and students 63110 (Term 1) and 63194 (Term 3) did not complete either questionnaires, which is assumed to be due to absence.

22.3 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings are structured into sections based on each of the datasets: ‘Sways – Development of Templates’, ‘Sways – Evidence of Learning’, ‘Post-Workshop Questionnaires’, ‘Interviews with Teachers’ and ‘Interviews with Students’.

22.3.1 Sways – Development of Templates

Two versions of the Sway templates were used – an initial trial Sway used in the first term, which will be referred to as Sway 1.0, and a redrafted template used in the second and third term, which will be referred to as Sway 2.0. This section will describe the structure and contents of these Sways, as well as the developmental changes between Sway 1.0 and 2.0, and the reasons behind these changes.

22.3.1.1 SWAY 1.0

Sway 1.0 took the format of a book, with multiple pages that were organised into chapters. A tab at the bottom of each page allowed access to a contents page (shown in Figure 175), creating quick access to each chapter, but not individual pages within the chapters.

Figure 175. Contents page of Sway 1.0

Opening with an introductory page to the project, each following chapter contained two weeks (aka four lessons) worth of material, and were correspondingly titled, e.g. ‘Week 1 and 2’. Each chapter contained three learning objectives for the fortnight, structured into ‘All students should’, ‘Most students should’, and ‘Some students should’ learning objectives, allowing for differentiation and creating a baseline for students. This form of differentiated learning objectives was a technique adopted throughout the school’s teaching and thus had been incorporated into the Sway by the teacher. An example of this learning objective section taken from the ‘Week 1 & 2’ chapter is shown in Figure 176.

Learning Objectives

- ALL will complete the pre-project questionnaire in a sensible and efficient manner
- MOST will illustrate an image of what they believe a typical scientist looks like
- SOME will analyse and explain the various skills they're going to need in order to complete the forthcoming virtual robotics project

WWW

EBI

Figure 176: Sway 1.0 Template - Week 1 & 2 Learning Objectives

Below each chapter's learning objectives was a space for students to explain how they had met these learning objectives (shown in Figure 176). This was structured into a space entitled 'WWW', an acronym for 'What Went Well' and 'EBI', an acronym for 'Even Better If'. This encouraged students to not only explain how they had met the learning objectives, but also reflect on what they could have done better or how they could improve in the future. Again, WWW and EBI were a school-wide technique used in teaching.

After the learning objectives, WWW and EBI, each chapter had a space for each student to upload screenshots that they had taken in the virtual world, which they had the option to individually caption. An example of this is shown in Figure 177.

Figure 177. Photos inserted with captions in 63103's (f) Sway

Most chapters included some form of guidance on using the virtual world, using presentations or videos (see Figure 178).

Figure 178. Guidance video from 'Week 5 & 6' chapter of Sway 1.0

Finally, each chapter closed with a section for teacher feedback. This comprised of a teacher written WWW and EBI, commenting on the student's Sway entries, and a student written 'DIRT' – Dedicated Improvement Reflection Time. In the DIRT, students commented on the teacher's feedback, reflecting on how they could improve the work from that chapter and/or apply this improvement to future chapters. A completed example is shown in Figure 179.

Figure 179. Completed teacher feedback section from 63102 (m) chapter 'Week 1 & 2'.

22.3.1.2 SWAY 2.0

Two key changes were made to the Sways in Sway 2.0 – the structure and the learning objectives. In terms of the structure, the Sway was changed from being an online book with multiple pages and chapters, to being one long webpage that could be scrolled through. The guidance resources and teacher feedback were located in one section at the bottom of the page, rather than interspersed throughout the different weeks. According to the teacher who designed the Sways, these structural changes were made so that students could access different areas of the Sway more easily.

Rather than the learning objectives being organised into sections corresponding to two weeks' worth of lessons, they were divided as follows: Week 1 – Getting Started, Week 2 – Exploration, Week 3 – Scratch for OpenSim, Week 4 – Algorithms, Week 5 – Planning, Weeks 6, 7, 8, and 9 – Implementation and Week 10 – Completion. Figure 180 shows a section of the Sway 2.0 template – note the space to upload photos and the length of the scroll bar on the right hand side due to the book being on one long page.

Figure 180: Sway 2.0 Template - Week 1 Learning Objectives

In terms of the changes to the learning objectives themselves, in Sway 2.0 the learning objectives were no longer differentiated, due to the whole school moving away from the ‘All, Most, Some’ system. Whilst some learning objectives remained the same, but slightly rephrased, others were removed and some new learning objectives were added. Table 30 lists the two sets of learning objectives of Sway 1.0 and Sway 2.0, allowing for a comparison of the objectives and of the structure of lessons in the term.

Table 30. List of learning objectives from Sway 1.0 and Sway 2.0

Sway 1.0		Sway 2.0	
Week	Learning Objectives	Week	Learning Objectives
Weeks 1 & 2	ALL will complete the pre-project questionnaire in a sensible and efficient manner	Week 1 – Getting Started	Identify what a virtual world is
	MOST will illustrate an image of what they believe a typical scientist looks like		Navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner
	SOME will analyse and explain the various skills they’re going to need in order to complete the forthcoming virtual robotics project		Design an avatar to represent yourself
Weeks 3 & 4	ALL will identify what a virtual world is	Week 2 – Exploration	Continue to navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner
			Discover each of the key tools and features within the Firestorm software
	MOST will navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and		Assess the advantages and disadvantages of the parameters which exist within this project
Weeks 3 & 4	ALL will identify what a virtual world is	Week 3 – Scratch for OpenSim	Recognise some of the skills which are needed to develop a virtual world
			MOST will navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and

	efficient manner		different objects
	SOME will create an avatar for their virtual world in preparation for next week's set of lessons		Independently create a variety of programming scripts
		Week 4 – Algorithms	Identify what an algorithm is
			Examine each of the different types of algorithms which exist
			Compile programming scripts which solve a variety of different algorithms
Weeks 5 & 6	ALL will recognise some of the different skills which are needed in order to develop a virtual world	Week 5 – Planning	Produce a design for the section of the virtual world you would like to create
	MOST will examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects in their world		Analyse the skills that are needed to develop your section of the virtual world
	SOME will independently create a piece of code which will allow them to create lines and squares in their work		Justify how your design encompasses key Computer Science topics
Weeks 7 & 8	ALL will draw a diagram of the virtual world they would like to create	Weeks 6, 7, 8, and 9 – Implementation	Develop your section of the virtual world within the parameters you've been given
	MOST will examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects in their world		Implement a wide range of complex and interactive features
	SOME will independently create a piece of code which will allow them to create lines and squares in their work		Evaluate and document the effectiveness of any changes you make
Weeks 9 & 10	ALL will identify the main types of operations which can make up an algorithm	Week 10 – Completion	Complete your section of the virtual world
	MOST will work through each of the given challenges in a semi-independent manner		Examine in a critical manner how you've performed in this project
	SOME will modify and enhance the idea they've come up with last lesson as to how they would like their area of the class island to look		Assess how your work could be further & improved
Weeks 11 & 12	ALL will modify and enhance the idea they've come up in the previous lessons as to how they would like their area of the class island to look		
	MOST will work through and modify each of the given challenges in a semi-independent manner		
	SOME will explain the work they've produced by linking key		

	Computer Science topics together		
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The teacher feedback section was edited so that only on three sections (Week 3, Week 6 and Week 10) were teacher feedback given and the remaining sections were assigned to peer feedback.

Finally, minor changes were made in the form of visual alterations, such as the colour scheme, the background pattern and the example photos used in headings of the template.

22.3.2 Sways – Evidence of Learning

Having described the overall development, structure and contents of the Sways, this section will now explore the results of analysing the Sways completed by the students. Firstly, how students evidenced their learning is explored, followed by presenting what the students did and did not evidence as having learnt purely through their Sways. The teacher feedback section from the first term are then reported and the impact of this dialogue is described. Finally, student engagement with the Sways across the three terms is then discussed.

22.3.2.1 HOW LEARNING WAS EVIDENCED

Upon analysis of the students' entries in the Sways, it was realised that the types of evidence of learning, or lack of, that students provided could be categorised as 'no engagement', 'parroted', 'weak forms of evidence' and 'strong forms of evidence', which will be discussed in turn here. Finally, the section concludes with a brief discussion on topics that became apparent from this analysis: firstly, how the learning objectives affect evidencing learning and secondly, the concept of assessment culture within British secondary schools.

22.3.2.1.1 NO ENGAGEMENT

Students would often not engage with particular learning objectives, either not attempting to complete them, or not evidencing completing them in their Sways. In term 1, there were 36 occasions of no engagement with 11 learning objectives (out of 11 Sways and across 18 learning objectives) with an overall lack of engagement with 18.2% of the learning objectives. In term 2 there were 33 occasions with 15 learning objectives (5 Sways, 21 learning objectives) with an overall lack of engagement with 31.4% of the learning objectives. In term 3 there were 110 occasions with 20 learning objectives (7 Sways, 21 learning objectives) with an overall lack of engagement with 74.8% of the learning objectives. The reasons for the decrease in engagement with the Sway across the course of the year will be discussed in 22.3.2.4. When students did not engage with a learning objective they ignored the objective and made no mention of it in their work, or by mentioning the learning objective in their 'EBI'. For example, student 63142 (f) said "*i need to learn how to Assess the advantages and disadvantages of the parameters which exist within this project*" in her EBI (Week 2 – Exploration) referring to the third learning objective for the week. This shows she has recognised that she did not achieve the learning objective.

In term 1 and 2 it was found that learning objectives that were less well engaged with were generally the harder or more specific ones, such as "All will identify the main types of operations which can make up an algorithm" (Sway 1.0, Weeks 9 & 10). However, in term 3 large sections of the Sway were simply incomplete, rather than individual learning objectives being ignored, suggesting that the Sways were not being engaged with overall rather than the students not completing the harder objectives. An example of this overall disengagement is shown in Figure 181. However, the researcher has no evidence that the student engaged with the task and the student may have been absent for this lesson – although this was one of multiple unengaged sections in his Sway.

Weeks 6, 7, 8 and 9 - Implementation

Learning Objectives

- Develop your section of the virtual world within the parameters you've been given
- Implement a wide range of complex and interactive features
- Evaluate and document the effectiveness of any changes you make

Pupil Reflection

WWW

EBI

Write here.

Figure 181. Entire section of Sway not engaged with (63193 - m)

22.3.2.1.2 PARROTING

Students would often 'parrot' back the learning objective in their written entries of their Sway – aka they would repeat the exact phrasing of the learning objective. This parroting occurred in three different ways. The first form of parroting was also a form of not engaging with the learning objective – the students would parrot the learning objective when recognising that they had not completed it by mentioning it in their 'EBI', which is discussed and evidenced in 22.3.2.1.1. In the second form, the students would parrot back the learning objective to state that they had met it, but not actually provide any other evidence to show that they had, with an example shown in Figure 182. Whilst these two types of parroting failed to provide evidence of learning, the final type involved students first reciting which learning objective they had met and then expanding on how they had met this objective, providing both written evidence and screenshots. In Figure 183, 63147 (f) has provided this format in her written answer for all three learning objectives and provided further screenshots as evidence. By parroting the learning objectives, the student is signposting the teacher to her evidence, which is a strong technique that is transferable to exam technique and job applications. This leads into the discussion in 22.3.2.1.6 of how assessment culture affects the techniques students use in completing their Sways.

Learning Objectives

- ALL will complete the pre-project questionnaire in a sensible and efficient manner
- MOST will illustrate an image of what they believe a typical scientist looks like
- SOME will analyse and explain the various skills they're going to need in order to complete the forthcoming virtual robotics project

WWW

I have completed the first objective because i completed the pre project questionnaire in an effective manner. I have completed the second objective because i drew what i thought a typical scientist looked like. I completed the third objective because i wrote about the skills I will need for this project.

EBI

To improve i must explain why i need these skills and explain why i think that a scientist looks like this.

Figure 182. 63103 (f) parrots the learning objectives but provides no evidence of meeting them

Week 1 - Getting Started

Learning Objectives

- Identify what a virtual world is
- Navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner
- Design an avatar to represent yourself

Pupil Reflection

WWW

Firstly, I think I have achieved the first learning objective because I can identify what a virtual world is. A virtual world is very different from a computer game, there is no rules or % certain goal. You have free reign to do whatever you want. Secondly, I think I have achieved the second learning object because I was able to navigate the virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner. I have done this by exploring the world and discovering new things. Finally, I think I have also achieved the third learning objective as I have designed an avatar to represent myself. I have done this by customizing the looks and clothes of my avatar.

EBI

To improve, next time I need to come into lesson and focus immediately. Also find out how to get money because you can buy some things.

Figure 183. 63147 (f, Term 2) parrots the learning objectives and then expands to give evidence of having met it.

22.3.2.1.3 WEAK FORMS OF EVIDENCE

When students provided evidence of learning, the evidence varied as to how well it genuinely proved the students had met a learning objective. This section explores different types of evidence that were found in Sway entries which were classified as ‘weak’ and how these can be problematic. Three types of weaker evidence are discussed; partial evidence; indirect evidence through self-reporting; and partner work.

Partial evidence was seen where students would show some evidence of meeting the learning objective, but that more evidence was needed to fully show that they had met it. This was most obvious in how students presented their programming. For example in Figure 184, the student has captioned a photo with “*I am about to enter new script into my slurtle*”. The photo shows a SLurtle before it has been programmed, so there is no evidence of what the SLurtle is going to build. Furthermore, the code itself is not included in the screenshot. Therefore, whilst this photo does provide evidence that the student understands the idea that they need to programme the SLurtle, there is no evidence as to their ability to programme the SLurtle in terms of practical skills or their ability to write a suitable programme. This student may be extremely high ability and have programmed the SLurtle to build complex blocks using her mathematical knowledge, or equally she may never have managed to programme the SLurtle at all.

Figure 184. 63105 (f – Term 1, Weeks 5 & 6) provides partial evidence of programming her virtual robot

Another weak form of evidence used by students was a self-reported description of what they did during the lesson in the WWW section of the Sway. Continuing with the example above in Figure 184, the student’s accompanying WWW section said:

*“ALL will recognise some of the different skills which are needed in order to develop a virtual world
 MOST will examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects in their world
 SOME will independently create a piece of code which will allow them to create lines and squares in their work*

WWW

I have almost completed all the learning objectives for weeks 5 and 6. I have completed the first learning objective because I have tried to develop my skills by watching the videos in the book and also I have been experimenting with the scratch by open sim and trying to figure out new code I can try/use

for the virtual world. I have tried to work with my partner Ed so we know what each other are doing and I'm trying to improve my skills so that I know what I need to do. I have learnt how to make a line of different blocks but I am trying to work independently so that I can do it by myself. I have made a powerpoint on 'scratch 4 opensim' with code to make basic things so in my next lesson I will be trying the code out to see if it works."

The student here describes how she has met each of the learning objectives. Although she has claimed, for example, to have programmed her SLurtle to build lines and squares, Figure 184 was the only screenshot provided, and so there is no actual evidence of this being completed. On the other hand, the benefit of self-reporting is that the students reflect upon what they have learnt, which is particularly effective when considering 21st century skills, such as the teamwork mentioned above – *"I have tried to work with my partner Ed"*. However, when considering programming to build objects or create interactive features in the world, a purely descriptive report will not provide full evidence in the Sway that the student has completed this task.

Finally, one form of weaker evidence was a result the group work in the workshop. Students worked in pairs during the second workshop, to build a shared space within the virtual world with interactive features. However, this can make it difficult to show how much the individual student has learnt and how they have worked within the pair. From the Sways alone, most learning objectives evidence pair work rather than individual work. For example, if a student inserts a screenshot of blocks that have been built using a SLurtle, without screenshots of their code in S4OS as mentioned above, there is no evidence as to whether that student or their partner programmed the SLurtle. Furthermore, whilst the benefit of pair work is enabling students to develop their 21st century skills in, for example, teamwork, leadership and creativity, there is no evidence in the Sways to show how the pair worked together other than self-reporting.

22.3.2.1.4 STRONG FORMS OF EVIDENCE

This section explores the different types of strong evidence that were found in Sway entries, which were; fully evidencing programming; providing definitions; and evidencing misunderstandings.

As has been described in 22.3.2.1.3, true evidence of students programming the SLurtles could only be provided if screenshots were taken that showed each step of the process. Meaning, strong evidence was given if a student showed the code they had programming blocks they had created in S4OS, the script being inputted into the SLurtles, and the resulting blocks or interactive feature that the SLurtle had then created. In term 2, all of the sampled Sways included this stronger evidence related to programming, whereas only two did in term 1 and none did in term 3. This suggests that the students in term 2 may have been verbally encouraged to provide this evidence by the class teacher, as no such instruction is provided in the Sway template. An example of this stronger evidence is shown in Figure 185, although the student has still not provided evidence of what the SLurtle then built, and has written a weaker WWW and EBI.

Figure 185. Student 63143 (f - Term 2, Week 3) provides strong evidence of programming

Some learning objectives related to students needing to “identify” what something was:

- “Identify what a virtual world is” (Sway 1.0 Weeks 3 & 4, and Sway 2.0 Week 1)
- “Identify what an algorithm is” (Sway 2.0 Week 4)

For these two objectives, 76% of the sampled Sway entries of term 1 and 2 provided a definition of what they had been told to identify. For example, student 63147 (f – Term 2) said: “I achieved task one by identifying what an algorithm is by finding the meaning; ‘a process or set of rules to be followed in calculations or other problem-solving operations, especially by a computer.’”. By providing this definition, there is clear evidence that 63147 has met the learning objective. However, 22.3.2.2 will explore whether the students have actually learnt this definition. 63147 continued to say: “I found this out by searching it and discussing it within the class.” Whilst this is a positive comment in terms of the student conducting her own research, it is questionable as to whether she will remember this definition if it has been copied and pasted from a search engine result. This problem was also highlighted by 63143 (m – Term 2) who, after having written a definition of an algorithm in his WWW, wrote in his EBI: “i want to rember what the types of algorithms are without the help of others”. This suggests that although the student evidenced having met the learning objective, they have not necessarily learnt it in an effective, memorable manner.

Finally, stronger evidence also allows a teacher to see not only where a student has met a learning objective, but also where there is some form of misunderstanding or mistake. For example, the aforementioned strong evidence for programming of providing the different stages of programming a SLurtle also allows a teacher to see if a student has a misunderstanding in the code that they have generated. For example, if a student were to programme the SLurtle to draw a circle, and provided a photo of only the circle that had been built, the teacher would have no evidence of the script that was used to create it. However, if the student also provided the script, the teacher would be able to evaluate whether the student had understood (or equally, misunderstood) the relationship between the angle the SLurtle turned by and the number of times it turned. Furthermore, in the second example of strong evidence, in providing a definition, a teacher can clearly assess whether the student has provided the correct definition or not.

22.3.2.1.5 TYPES OF LEARNING OBJECTIVES

During the analysis it was noted that the learning objectives in the Sways could be categorised into different types, and that the type of learning objective affected how students engaged with it and what evidence they supplied.

As discussed above, students engaged well with specific learning objectives where they could provide a clear answer, such as: *“Identify what a virtual world is”* (Sway 2.0, Week 1). However, students did not engage as well with specific learning objectives that were harder and higher ability, such as: *“Justify how your design encompasses key Computer Science topics”* (Sway 2.0, Week 5). In Term 2, just one out of the five students sampled engaged with this learning objective, saying in her WWW: *“I have achieved the final learning objective as I know that my design will need to have code to make certain things, which uses algorithms. Algorithms are a key computer science topic.”* (63146 - f). The rest of the students ignored the objective. These two learning objectives can be compared with each other using Bloom’s Taxonomy (1956) to consider their complexity. ‘Identify’ in this context is a verb relating to knowledge, requiring the student to remember and understand a definition. However, ‘justify’ requires students to use reasoning skills – analysing, evaluating and explaining in their answer, which are far more complex than identifying. Whilst it is to be expected that higher ability learning objectives will be less likely to be achieved by the majority and this provides a form of differentiation, students may have engaged more with the objective if there had been more support in the Sway, from the teacher, and through class discussion during the lesson as to how the objective could be achieved.

Equally, some learning objectives were quite vague, making them easy to achieve, such as: *“Navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner”* (Sway 2.0, Week 1). Students could easily evidence this learning objective through screenshots showing where they had explored in the virtual world.

Finally, some learning objectives were actually specific tasks, rather than the student learning something specific, such as: *“Produce a design for the section of the virtual world you would like to create”* (Sway 2.0, Week 5). These learning objectives were well engaged with, with 81% of students in Term 1 and Term 2 providing evidence of completing it, by uploading the diagrams they had produced. In comparison to other learning objectives, the students had a clear instruction as to what they must do to achieve the learning objective.

22.3.2.1.6 ASSESSMENT CULTURE AND TECHNIQUE

Over recent years, the UK education system has often been commented on for [over-testing pupils](https://www.tes.com/news/whether-students-take-too-many-tests-misses-point-testing-has-elevated-assessment-above) (<https://www.tes.com/news/whether-students-take-too-many-tests-misses-point-testing-has-elevated-assessment-above>). Whether good or bad, it is certainly true that the majority of secondary school pupils are very much used to being constantly assessed, in both formative and summative manners. This presence of assessment culture was noticed during the analysis of the Sways, in which the majority of the students displayed some form a technique in answering their WWWs.

Many of the students, both higher and lower ability, would repeat or use the wording of the stated learning objective in their answer. In some cases, the students would state which learning objective they had apparently achieved, but not actually provide any evidence to show they had done so. For example, where the learning objective was *“Identify what an algorithm is”* student 63111 (m) stated: *“I have completed task one by identifying what a algorithm is”*. Other examples of this parroting were reported in 22.3.2.1.2. These examples suggest that the students have picked up the assessment technique of clearly stating which learning objective they are referring to, but have not developed the technique of ensuring they then evidence *how* they have completed this objective. Furthermore, one student (63107 – m) even referred to the Sway as a marked assessment: *“I could have included more detail on my description of the typical scientist as this would give me*

more marks for it.” This is an interesting statement, as the Draw-a-Scientist activity was not marked. The Sway is quite an unusual form of evidencing learning in a UK school, as the teacher has not assigned a marking system to it, of which the students seem to be accustomed.

22.3.2.2 WHAT DID STUDENTS LEARN?

Whilst the previous section focused on student engagement with Sways and how they evidenced their learning, this section will explore which learning objectives the students actually gave evidence of having met and which they did not. The three terms are reported separately, due to the differences in engagement between them.

Table 31 shows which learning objectives were shown to be met in the Term 1 sample of 11 students. ‘No Evidence’ refers to the number of students who either had no engagement with the objective or no evidence being provided to show the student had met it. ‘Evidence’ refers to the number of students who provided weak or strong evidence for having met the learning objective. Sway entries that had previously been identified as ‘parroting’ were categorised as to whether the entry provided evidence or not. Learning objectives highlighted in bright green are those where more than 75% of the sample had evidenced meeting the learning objective. As can be seen, this was applicable to three learning objectives. These three learning objectives were specific and students could easily evidence them, for example by uploading a photo of the drawing of a scientist.

Interestingly, the learning objectives that were classified as ‘ALL’ mostly had the least amount of evidence provided by students, suggesting that the teacher may have had incorrect assumptions about the ability of the students, or that student found these objectives harder to provide evidence for even if they did achieve them. On average, learning objectives were evidenced as being met 47% of the time.

Table 31. Number of students in Term 1 who evidenced meeting the learning objectives in their Sway (1.0).

Week	Learning Objectives	No Evidence	Evidence
Weeks 1 & 2	ALL will complete the pre-project questionnaire in a sensible and efficient manner	8	3
	MOST will illustrate an image of what they believe a typical scientist looks like	0	11
	SOME will analyse and explain the various skills they’re going to need in order to complete the forthcoming virtual robotics project	6	5
Weeks 3 & 4	ALL will identify what a virtual world is	6	5
	MOST will navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner	3	8
	SOME will create an avatar for their virtual world in preparation for next week’s set of lessons	2	9
Weeks 5 & 6	ALL will recognise some of the different skills which are needed in order to develop a virtual world	6	5
	MOST will examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects in their world	5	6
	SOME will independently create a piece of code which will allow them to create lines and squares in their work	6	5
Weeks 7 & 8	ALL will draw a diagram of the virtual world they would like to create	2	9
	MOST will examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects in their world	7	4
	SOME will independently create a piece of code which will allow them to create lines and squares in their work	6	5
Weeks 9 &	ALL will identify the main types of operations which can	8	3

10	make up an algorithm		
	MOST will work through each of the given challenges in a semi- independent manner	7	4
	SOME will modify and enhance the idea they've come up with last lesson as to how they would like their area of the class island to look	3	8
Weeks 11 & 12	ALL will modify and enhance the idea they've come up in the previous lessons as to how they would like their area of the class island to look	10	1
	MOST will work through and modify each of the given challenges in a semi-independent manner	10	1
	SOME will explain the work they've produced by linking key Computer Science topics together	10	1

Table 32 shows which learning objectives were shown to be met in the Term 2 sample of 5 students. Learning objectives highlighted in bright green are those where more than 75% of the sample had evidenced meeting the learning objective. As can be seen, this was applicable to eight of the learning objectives. These objectives are mostly based on broad tasks that the students were doing in the lesson, that could be easily evidenced through screenshots. On average, learning objectives were evidenced as being met 70% of the time. Students appear to evidence meeting the learning objectives more in Term 2 than Term 1, although it should be noted that the small sample sizes, and the difference in sample sizes in the two terms.

Table 32. Number of students in Term 2 who evidenced meeting the learning objectives in their Sway (2.0).

Week	Learning Objectives	No Evidence	Evidence
Week 1 – Getting Started	Identify what a virtual world is	1	4
	Navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner	0	5
	Design an avatar to represent yourself	0	5
Week 2 – Exploration	Continue to navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner	2	3
	Discover each of the key tools and features within the Firestorm software	1	4
	Assess the advantages and disadvantages of the parameters which exist within this project	4	1
Week 3 – Scratch for OpenSim	Recognise some of the skills which are needed to develop a virtual world	2	3
	Examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects	2	3
	Independently create a variety of programming scripts	2	3
Week 4 – Algorithms	Identify what an algorithm is	1	4
	Examine each of the different types of algorithms which exist	3	2
	Compile programming scripts which solve a variety of different algorithms	5	0
Week 5 – Planning	Produce a design for the section of the virtual world you would like to create	1	4
	Analyse the skills that are needed to develop your section of the virtual world	1	4
	Justify how your design encompasses key Computer Science topics	4	1
Weeks 6, 7, 8,	Develop your section of the virtual world within the	0	5

and 9 – Implementation	parameters you've been given		
	Implement a wide range of complex and interactive features	2	3
	Evaluate and document the effectiveness of any changes you make	5	0
Week 10 – Completion	Complete your section of the virtual world	2	3
	Examine in a critical manner how you've performed in this project	2	3
	Assess how your work could be further improved	2	3

Table 33 shows which learning objectives were shown to be met in the Term 3 sample of 7 students. Learning objectives highlighted in bright green are those where more than 75% of the sample had evidenced meeting the learning objective. As can be seen, this was applicable to three of the learning objectives. These objectives were based on the simplest task that the students completed across the course of the whole workshop – being on the virtual world. On average, learning objectives were evidenced as being met 24% of the time. This large drop is largely due to the lack of engagement with the Sways by pupils during this term, also observed by the researcher.

Table 33. Number of students in Term 3 who evidenced meeting the learning objectives in their Sway (2.0).

Week	Learning Objectives	No Evidence	Evidence
Week 1 – Getting Started	Identify what a virtual world is	1	6
	Navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner	3	4
	Design an avatar to represent yourself	4	3
Week 2 – Exploration	Continue to navigate the given virtual world in a sensible and efficient manner	1	6
	Discover each of the key tools and features within the Firestorm software	1	6
	Assess the advantages and disadvantages of the parameters which exist within this project	5	2
Week 3 – Scratch for OpenSim	Recognise some of the skills which are needed to develop a virtual world	7	0
	Examine how to use Scratch for OpenSim to create a variety of different objects	7	0
	Independently create a variety of programming scripts	7	0
Week 4 – Algorithms	Identify what an algorithm is	6	1
	Examine each of the different types of algorithms which exist	6	1
	Compile programming scripts which solve a variety of different algorithms	7	0
Week 5 – Planning	Produce a design for the section of the virtual world you would like to create	6	1
	Analyse the skills that are needed to develop your section of the virtual world	7	0
	Justify how your design encompasses key Computer Science topics	7	0
Weeks 6, 7, 8, and 9 – Implementation	Develop your section of the virtual world within the parameters you've been given	7	0
	Implement a wide range of complex and interactive features	7	0
	Evaluate and document the effectiveness of any changes you make	7	0

Week 10 – Completion	Complete your section of the virtual world	7	0
	Examine in a critical manner how you've performed in this project	7	0
	Assess how your work could be further improved	7	0

22.3.2.3 FEEDBACK

This section explores the impact that teacher feedback has on student engagement with the Sways and how, in the first term, a student-teacher dialogue was created through the teacher feedback section. As previously described in 22.3.1 and shown in Figure 179, the Teacher Feedback section consisted of a teacher-written WWW and EBI, and a student DIRT. Analysing the Teacher Feedback section of the Sways in term 1 showed that a short dialogue was often created between the student and the teacher, through the EBI and the DIRT. To explore this dialogue concept, findings of the teacher EBI is presented and the students' DIRTs explored.

If the student had not met the learning objective(s) the teacher EBI would state how the student could improve to meet the objectives, encourage them to work on this area, or ask them to provide more detail. For example, to 63102's (m) Week 3 & 4 entry, the teacher said: *"EBI: From reading the WWW and EBI you've put together, I can't see any mention of whether you achieved learning objective three or not. Please can you clarify this for me and tell me either how you achieved it or how you're going to achieve it in the next few lessons."* If the student had evidenced meeting the learning objectives, the teacher would use the EBI as an opportunity to push the student to achieve something beyond the learning objective. For example in the case of 63122 (m) the teacher said: *"EBI: From looking at the additional drawing you have produced I can see you have analysed some of the different skills you feel are required in this project. However to improve, please can you explain why you have listed some of those skills."* This extension activity acts as another form of differentiation for the higher ability students.

As stated, DIRT stands for 'Dedicated Improvement Reflection Time'. The DIRT allowed the students the chance to reflect on their teacher's feedback on their Sway, and consider how they would improve their previous and future work. The students would also use their DIRT as a platform for replying directly to the teacher and his comments, particularly from the EBI. While only some lower ability students would use the DIRT to explain how they would improve, higher ability students would mostly reply to the teacher's question or complete set work during DIRT. For example, when the teacher asked 63102 (m) to *"explain to me as to what the advantages of using this program are as opposed to typing manually"*, the student replied in the DIRT with *"DIRT: The advantages are very good as instead of writing 500+ lines of code it does it in a spit second"*. However, in the case of 63104 (m) who often had missing work in his Sway, he repeatedly used the DIRT section to apologise to the teacher and explain why the book was incomplete: *"thank you sir for feedback sorry most of my pictures got deleted and i tried to put some back in"*. This shows that there was some form of dialogue between the teacher and students regardless of the student's ability. Overall, those who did not complete the DIRT section, or take part in a dialogue with the teacher were those students who did not engage well with the Sways overall.

As described in 22.3.1, both Sway 1.0 and Sway 2.0 had sections for the teacher to provide feedback to the students on each section of their Sway. A key observation to note is that T631 only provided feedback to the students in term 1 (Sway 1.0) with term 2 and 3's sections remaining blank. Furthermore, as is discussed in 22.3.2.4, the students in term 3 engaged with the Sways less than in term 2 and those in term 2 engaged less than the students in term 1. Whilst there is a correlation between providing teacher feedback and student engagement, there is no strong evidence to prove that the former causes the latter. The lead teacher openly

admitted that they were not ‘marking’ the Sways in term 3 due to having other priorities at the school. However, it is also possible that the structural change in the Sways, moving the Teacher Feedback section to the end of the book in Sway 2.0 rather than interspersed throughout, resulted in it being less prominent and easier to forget about. Furthermore, whilst feedback was provided and a dialogue created in term 1, it should also be noted that observations by the researcher from the first term explain that the teacher only began providing feedback in the latter half of the term, and assigned one lesson for the students to complete their DIRTs from all sections at once. Therefore, whilst solely examining the Sways there would appear to be an ongoing dialogue between the student and teacher, and indeed, there was the potential for this to occur, in reality this dialogue was very short-lived and static in time.

While a sections were provided in way 2.0 for peer feedback, there is no evidence from the sample to suggest that these were engaged with at any point in the workshops.

22.3.2.4 ENGAGEMENT WITH SWAYS

This section presents a profile of engagement, looking longitudinally at engagement with the Sways in each school term and across the school year. Potential factors that may have impacted engagement are also explored.

As with any mixed ability class, students varied in the quality of work they produced in their Sways and the level that they engaged with them. However, as has been noted in 22.3.2.1.1, the percentage of learning objectives that were not engaged with in the Sways increased from 18.2% of learning objectives in term one, to 31.4% in term 2, to 74.8% in term 3. This section will first compare the characteristics of ‘well engaged’ Sways and ‘badly engaged’ Sways, using two students as examples. This section ends by considering the different factors that may have influenced the decrease in student’s engagement with the Sways from term one to term three.

Student 63146 (f) was noted by the researcher as having created strong, detailed entries throughout her Sway. In comparison, 63194 (m) did not complete the Sway to a very high standard. Table 34 explores the differences in how these two students completed – or partially completed – their Sways. Overall, it would appear that a considerable amount more ‘effort’ has been put into 63146’s Sway, with 63194 generally completing less work. Although the quality of work produced by students will partially be due to their academic ability, the incomplete nature of 63194’s Sway suggests that he did not engage well with it. Whilst Table 34 compares two Sways that were quite different from each other, the overall Sway entries by the students created a spectrum of engagement and quality of work – as opposed to simply ‘well engaged’ or ‘badly engaged’.

Table 34: Comparing the characteristics of a well engaged and a badly engaged Sway.

63146 (Female – Term 2)	63194 (Male – Term 3)
Mostly completed all learning objectives and expanded beyond the objectives.	Mostly completed only one or two learning objectives.
Created entries in all chapters of the Sway.	Stopped creating entries after the first three weeks. In these first weeks, some parts are incomplete (e.g. missing EBI).
Provided multiple photos, with captions explaining their context.	Provided a few uncaptioned photos.
Explains how they have met the learning objective by giving an account of what they have done, or providing definitions of new terminology.	States that they have met the learning objective but does not evidence or explain how.

Has written multiple full sentences for each week.	Has written one short sentence for some of the weeks.
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Multiple factors may have caused the decrease in Sway engagement over the course of the year. Firstly, section 22.3.2.3 explored the lack of teacher feedback in term 2 and 3, which correlates with the decrease in engagement with the Sways over these terms. This may be due to a lack of motivation to fill them in if they felt there was no consequence for not doing so as they were not monitored. Secondly, the Sways were least engaged with by class 631 during the final term, which was a term with a considerable amount of disruption, due to the class often being led by supply (substitute) teachers. Furthermore, observational notes explain that during the final term, S4OS worked only on the students' computers and not the teachers, where it had been working for the other two terms. This resulted in the teacher being unable to demonstrate the coding element of the workshop to the class and unable to demonstrate how to evidence this coding and may have therefore put less of an emphasis on coding the SLurtles overall. The impact that this had is seen when comparing the student Sways in term 2 to that of term 3, with term 2 being more prevalent in evidencing coding.

Different terms in the school year also place different levels of pressure on students and teachers, with the final term seeing students completing exams in other subjects and teachers prioritising older students completing their GCSEs. Furthermore, the students in year 9 completed ICT lessons in a carousel structure with two other lessons, taking part in ICT lessons for only one out of the three terms of the year. Therefore, those students completing the workshop in the final term had not had an ICT lesson for approximately 9 months, resulting in them not being used to the teacher or the lessons themselves. Another factor that may have affected engagement was the time allocated to completing the Sways, with the first term having allocated lessons every fourth session for completing the Sways, and the final term having the students encouraged to complete a little bit of their Sways each lesson alongside working on the virtual world. The better engagement in the first term suggests that perhaps the former encouraged students to complete their Sways to a higher standard as they could focus solely on it. Finally, engagement with the Sways, or the quality of work produced would also have been influenced by the ability of the student, the attendance of the student and whether the student spoke English as an Additional Language (EAL) or had Special Educational Needs (SEN). However, these were not recorded for individuals in the data collection.

22.3.3 Post-Workshop Questionnaires

This section explores the answers by the students who produced the sampled Sways to four questions from the post-workshop questionnaire that was conducted for each workshop: *"What have you learned today?"*, *"What have you learned about yourself?"*, *"What have you learned about working with other people?"*, and *"What have you learned about working with robots"*. These results of what the students self-reported as having learnt in the questionnaire are then compared to what they had evidenced learning in their Sways, as presented in 22.3.2.2. It should be noted that the questionnaires were in place for research purposes, and would not usually be conducted if the workshop was taking place as a normal lesson, whereas the Sways would be. As stated in 22.2.2, students in Term 2 only completed one post-workshop questionnaire after Workshop 2.

22.3.3.1 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED TODAY?

Students were not asked this question in the second post-workshop questionnaire of Term 1, for unknown reasons.

Bearing in mind the open nature of this question, nine out of ten students in Term 1 and four out of five students in Term 2 stated that **they had learnt how to code or programme**. Some students stated this simply, such as 63103 (f – Term 1): *“I have learnt how to code”*. However, 63109 (Term 1 – f) expanded to discuss the working technique she had used in the workshop: *“I have learnt that trial and error is a crucial part and needs to be used often when coding and trying to get certain things to work”*. 63107 (m) from Term 1, who did not mention coding, instead talked about his **change in perception of STEM**: *“I realised we use maths and science in a lot more things than I thought we did.”* However, 63141 (m) from Term 2, who did not mention coding, instead stated that he had learnt *“nothing”*.

Term 3 students answered this question very differently, with none of the five students mentioning coding or programming in either of the two post-workshop questionnaires. **Creating an avatar** was mentioned twice, **building in the virtual world** once, **using Firestorm** (the software used for the virtual world) once, and *“how things work”* (63182 – f) in general once. One student (63111 – m) also stated that he had learnt *“nothing”* after the first workshop. Interestingly, this same student then stated that he had learnt *“building robots”* after the second workshop, thereby evidencing a misunderstanding as the robots in the virtual world were pre-built and were only programmed. Finally, two students mentioned the open nature of the project, stating:

63192 (m): *“That it takes A LOT of try and error and A LOT of time”* (Workshop 1)

“That there are lots of different possibilities” (Workshop 2)

63195 (f): *“how to experiment”* (Workshop 1)

22.3.3.2 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT YOURSELF?

Two students did not answer this question in Term 1 after Workshop 2, and one student did not in Term 3 after Workshop 2.

In Term 1, coding was again referenced in six (out of 18) answers, but in comparison to 22.3.3.1, students referred to their **ability with coding** – e.g. that they were good at coding. One student (63103 f) again said they had learnt: *“nothing”*. 63122 (m) stated that he **enjoyed the tasks** in the workshops and the **independence** he was given: *“i enjoy designing my area of the world on my own”*. Four students referred to being **resilient or persevering**, one student stated that they can **be calm** and one student stated they could **work well independently and in a team**. Whilst most students stated what skills they had, two students stated themselves as being weaker in an area:

63105 (f): *“im dopey”* (Workshop 1)

63107 (m): *“I need to be more resilient”* (Workshop 2)

In Term 2, all five answers were very short. One student stated they had learnt nothing (63146 – f). 63141 (m) said *“robot”*, which doesn't seem to make sense with the question that was asked. 63142 (f) said *“determined”* which could be interpreted as her saying that she has learnt that she is **determined**. As in Term 1, the skills that students lacked was again mentioned, by 63147 (f) who claimed she had **low patience**. 63143 (m) said *“i like minecraft”*. Minecraft is a sandbox video game that is comparable to a virtual world. This answer could be interpreted in a number of ways; that the student is mistaken and believes the virtual world is on Minecraft; that the student prefers Minecraft to the virtual world; or that the student is stating this answer as a random fact.

Finally, in Term 3, answers that the student had **learnt nothing** were given four times, and one student answers saying they **didn't know** what they had learnt. Three students mentioned what they enjoyed, such as **learning how things are made, building, and sharing with other people**. Again, one student mentioned being **good at team work**. However, 63192 (m) referred to teamwork in a more negative light after workshop 1. It could be interpreted that he is using the anonymity of the questionnaire to rant about a situation that has annoyed him. Also, it can be noted that he is using an informal internet or texting style of writing:

"That people still think im not very usefull... Altho I still was probably the most usefull person in the group :/ they were sorry, and as a good friend i said its fineeeeeee!"

22.3.3.3 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT WORKING WITH OTHER PEOPLE?

One student did not answer this question in Term 1 after Workshop 1 and one student didn't after Workshop 2. Overall, students either stated their opinion towards teamwork, or stated skills that they believed were useful in teamwork.

In Term 1, two students claimed to have **learnt nothing** about working with other people – one of these was 63103 who had stated the same in the previous question. One student (63102 - m) talked about teamwork in a positive manner in both their answers: *"I've learned that's very fun and you do like 2 x the work"*, *"That we can work together well"*. However, three students expressed a negative view of teamwork, with two students stating that other people *"are useless"* and one of these students (63122 – m) expanding in his second questionnaire that *"they missed most of the lessons and did near to nothing"*. Two students gave a mixed opinion of teamwork, with 63103 (f) saying *"some are good but others copy"* and 63104 (m) saying *"It is annoying but it gets easier"*. Those students who did not place an opinion in their answer instead stated what skills they had learnt were necessary for teamwork, such as **communicating, listening** (both 63107 - m) and **compromising** (63109 - f).

In Term 2, the students again gave very brief answers. Two students gave a positive opinion towards teamwork, again referencing it being **fun, quicker** and **helpful**. Two students gave a negative opinion, stating it was **hard**, and 63147 (f) stated: *"I prefer working on my own"*. One student mentioned a skill involved in teamwork: *"I need to be patient"* (63146 – f).

Finally, in Term 3, two students stated after the first workshop that they had **learnt nothing** about working with people. Whilst one of these students stated the same after the second workshop, 63195 (f) stated after the second workshop that she had learnt *"I like working with a team"*. Again, some students gave positive opinions about teamwork, with entries mentioning it being, for example, **helpful** and **fun**. 63192 (m) gave a negative opinion, saying after the first workshop *"their selfish. and either make you do the work or not let you do it at all. But i still love"*, and after the second workshop *"That i would rather work on my own"*. Only one student mentioned a skill involved with teamwork – **communication**.

22.3.3.4 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT WORKING WITH ROBOTS

Students were not asked this question in the first post-workshop questionnaire of Term 1, for unknown reasons.

In Term 1, five students stated that they had learnt that robots were **hard to use, or complicated**. Three students talked about robots in a positive manner, talking about **their uses**, or in the case of 63119 (m) saying: *"they are good unlike people"*.

In Term 2, two students gave **unrelated answers** (“*they like oranges*” and “*robot*”) and one student stated they had **learnt nothing**. 63142 (f) said they were “*interesting*” and 63147 (f) said they were “*complicated*”.

Finally, in Term 3 (the only set of students to answer the question after both workshops), no students gave a negative opinion towards robotics – an interesting result when this was the group that were less engaged and did not complete as much coding as the other students, as perhaps they did not work with robots enough to discover these opinions. There were six answers that gave a positive opinion towards robots, such as them being “*amazing*” or “*cool*”. Three students said they had **learnt nothing** after the second workshop. Finally, one student 63182 (f) evidenced a **misunderstanding** of robotics, referring to their avatar rather than the SLurtle: “*you can change the clothes*”.

22.3.3.5 COMPARISON WITH EVIDENCE OF LEARNING IN SWAYS

The results of the questionnaires have been reported so the answers that the students self-reported as having learnt can be compared to what was evidenced in their Sways. This section will discuss the open nature of the questionnaire questions, the often mentioned learning of coding, 21st century skills and the anonymity of the questionnaires.

Firstly, a main difference between the questionnaires and the Sways is the anonymity that is given in the questionnaires. Students often gave negative opinions or stated that they had learnt nothing. Whilst students may not engage well with the Sway, or may fail to provide evidence of learning, there were no results of the students explicitly stating negative opinions or saying they had learnt nothing in the Sway. When compared to what T631 mentioned about using the Sways as a research tool for gathering opinions of the project in the following section, 22.3.4, this result highlights the difference that anonymity makes in, not necessarily students being honest, but in students saying what they are thinking. The Sways and the questionnaires were created for two different audiences and students were aware that while their teacher would read their Sways, the teacher would not see the results of the questionnaire.

As has been mentioned, the questions in the questionnaire were of an open nature, allowing students to answer with what they considered important or with how they interpreted the question, knowing they would not be read by the class teacher. In comparison, the learning objectives of the Sway, although not always very specific, were considerably more specific than the open questions. The responses to the specific learning objectives are definitely positive, but as has been seen in the variety of the self-reporting in the questionnaire answers, it may be beneficial to include some open questions for reflection in the Sways, where students can self-report their learning without necessarily considering exam technique and assessment culture. Of course, the reflection may not be as honest as in the questionnaires as students want to please the teacher and perhaps only reflect on the positive work they have completed.

Programming and coding were the most commonly referenced skill self-reported as being learnt. However, when this is compared to the Sway entries, coding was poorly evidenced; both in strong and weak forms of evidence. Therefore, although students are aware of the concept of coding and believe that they have learnt about it, they are not providing evidence in their Sways. This could be due to a lack of instruction as to how to evidence this learning, time or other factors.

Finally, although the questions were open, they referred to areas such as working with others and learning about oneself. This encouraged students to discuss 21st century skills. The questionnaires therefore had more references to 21st century skills than in the Sways, although some students instead used the questionnaires as an opportunity to give their opinion rather than talk about how they had developed these skills. Although 21st

century skills were encouraged by some learning objectives in the Sway, the students identified skills they thought they might use, whereas in the questionnaires they reported which skills they believe they had actually developed or learnt.

22.3.4 Interviews with Teachers

This section explores the results of analysing the interviews conducted with the two class teachers regarding the use and development of the Sways. It should also be noted that both of the teachers were very positive towards the use of the Sways, perhaps trying to influence the researcher's results, discussing the books mostly in a general manner and not specific to the ER4STEM workshop. The interviews with the teachers had three key themes, which will be explored in turn in this section: the 'Benefits of Online Books', how the Sways allow effective 'Evidence of Learning, Reflection and Research' and finally the teachers' 'Perceptions of Students' Opinions and Engagement' towards using the Sways.

22.3.4.1 BENEFITS OF ONLINE BOOKS

The most prominent theme mentioned by both teachers was the benefit of using the Sways as online exercise books in comparison traditional paper books. T631 referred to the difficulties related to evidencing in ICT lessons that were bypassed by using online books:

- T631: I really looked at why, why first of all were in computer rooms, why we using exercise books, why are we doing things on paper?*
- Interviewer: Yeah (laughter).*
- T631: Why have we got queues at printers, it's stupid, it's not time effective.*
- Interviewer: Yeah.*
- T631: So, what I actually did was create e-exercise books."*

T632 echoed these views, adding the logistical benefits of having online books that saved automatically and that could be accessed by anyone with the link – teacher or peer. Furthermore, both teachers focussed on the ease of inserting screenshots from the virtual world into the Sways as what the researcher has recognised as an artefact of learning. However, as well as the practical benefits of using online books, T631 explained that using the Sways was an additional way to develop the students' ICT skills. He particularly felt that by using the Sways, even the lower ability students, or those who had no interest in continuing on to specialise in computer science would still develop transferable skills through learning how to use the Sways:

- T631: And then you got the ones who are never gonna study IT but then what they're picking up is just general basic IT skills in the lesson.*
- Interviewer: Yeah.*
- T631: Even if it's logging into the school e-mail account and Sway... I could say, I'm just prioritising Computer Science students but that won't be right*
- Interviewer: Hmm.*
- T631: You've got to really create something for those (other students)... what have they got out of these lessons?... Basic IT skills*

22.3.4.2 EVIDENCE OF LEARNING, REFLECTION AND RESEARCH

Both teachers were very clear that the primary reason for using the Sways was to provide evidence of learning, but also to allow the students to reflect and to be used as a research tool in the ER4STEM project. Regarding the former, T631 explained that he aimed to use the Sways instead of doing a class plenary at the end of the lesson, as the Sway encapsulated their reflective nature. T632 added that the reflective nature of the Sways also allowed the students to consider and explain their full thought processes whilst learning. Regarding being used as a research tool, T631 believed the Sways allowed a platform for the students to be open and honest about the project:

- Interviewer:* *So it's not just evidence of learning, it's also evidence for how, for the research... And how to improve the project and*
- T631:* *That's what I mean, I thought it was a really good way of doing it... Cos obviously we (only) do so much in interviews...But with questions you can obviously lead them, you know, you know the difference between the way we can lead them (or not). But with that it's just leave it to them, be completely honest.*

However, in the analysis of the Sways themselves (explored in 22.3.2), the students very rarely used the Sway as an opportunity to give feedback on the project itself – in the template they are not encouraged to do so. Furthermore, if the students did evaluate the project in their Sways, their stated opinions may not be as honest as the teacher believes they would, as the Sways are not anonymous and the students would create their work being mindful the audience of their writing was their teacher.

22.3.4.3 PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS' OPINIONS AND ENGAGEMENT

Both teachers' perceptions of what they believed the students thought of using the Sways was touched upon very briefly during the interview, even though they were asked directly "*What do you think... the students themselves think of the Sways?*" Although T631 did not explicitly say that he believed the students did not like them, he implied that they did not appreciate the benefits of the Sways, saying: "*I think they forget you know in terms of that, you know, they'd come in two and a half years ago that they would be printing out a millions screenshots, standing round the printer*".

Both teachers also stated that it was difficult for the students to remember to fill in the Sways, or in some cases for the teachers to remember to remind the students to fill them in. In the earlier terms, every fourth lesson was designated to completing the Sways, whereas the final term in which the teachers were interviewed took the approach of continuously filling out the Sways each lesson. Whilst this had been a conscious change by T631 to try and improve student engagement with the Sways, T632 believed that he would be more comfortable and students would engage better with the Sways if they returned to a more structured pattern for filling them in and provided more direct instruction to the students:

- "T632:* *Er, I, personally from the classes I teach, I think it would be better to have it more sort of... just more er structured. Er, so they enjoy the freedom... But I think the lower ability need to have that you know or, like 'this task for ten minutes...Okay, stop, where are we, what, what do we need to do...Next task for ten minutes'*
- ...
- Interviewer:* *Okay, what, and doing that with the Sways as well?*
- T632:* *Er, yes I think so... I think so, cos er I think in that lesson just now I think I said you know oh let's get this, get the screenshots done... Er, and I'm not sure how many actually did the WWWs and EBIs... So it would have been good to stop and (check)"*

22.3.5 Interviews with Students

This section explores the results of analysing three interviews conducted with a total of six students from the two classes of the final term, regarding their opinions of the Sways. Overall, the students were more critical of the Sways than the teachers were, however they still provided positive feedback and some interesting ideas for how they believed the Sways could be improved. Therefore, the results are discussed in terms of: the students' 'Positive Opinions' and 'Negative Opinions' towards the Sways, and finally their 'Ideas for Improvement' in the future.

22.3.5.1 POSITIVE OPINIONS

Students noted a number of positive perceptions about the use of the Sways, which centred on three areas; evidencing learning and reflecting; the benefit of online books; and teacher feedback.

All the interviewed students recognised the Sways as a method for evidencing their learning and creativity in the virtual world to their teacher. However, 631102 (m) also recognised that marking their development was also useful on a personal basis: *“Well, it could be good to look back at the images and see the progress you made”*. Other students found that they also found the reflective nature of the Sways useful on a personal level, with 632160 (m) stating: *“it lets us like reflect on like what we’ve done while, and like how we can improve... so it’s good”*.

Similarly to the teachers' opinions, these largely centred on the benefits of the book being online. This was mostly based around the ability to easily insert screenshots from the virtual world into their Sway. However, two of the girls from class 631 emphasised that the book being online allowed their teacher to leave feedback and create a dialogue with the students:

“631100 (f): It’s er when you have the book it’s like you write stuff in it and then the teacher can check it and maybe like make little notes on it and all sorts.

...

631103 (f): Like that, it’s just one of those things that like a book, except the teacher can mark”

It is interesting that the students should comment on the teacher feedback being a benefit when they were in the class that did not receive any teacher feedback – perhaps this was their opinion from the use of the Sways in previous classes outside of the workshop.

Finally, the students remarked on the guidance for the virtual world that was available on the Sway, with 631102 (m) stating that it was useful to be given instructions and objective, whilst 631103 (f) explained that she found the video tutorials helpful.

The use of an online book in the form of the Sway means that technology has augmented that functionality of the students' evidence of learning compared to a paper exercise book. However, the Sway itself provides no functional benefit in comparison to any other online documentation package, provided for example by Microsoft Office Online (e.g. Word, PowerPoint) other than the aesthetics. This means that opinions stated by the students, (and the teachers) are not necessarily anything specific to the Sway, and instead refer to any form of evidencing learning, student reflection, or online documentation.

22.3.5.2 NEGATIVE OPINIONS

Whilst the students did have positive comments about using the Sways, they also had some negative opinions. These opinions centred on three areas; forgetting to complete the Sways; the repetitive nature of the Sways; and the act of completing the Sways taking away from the positive qualities and time spent in the virtual world.

The students comments that it was difficult to remember to fill out the Sways helps to explain the lack of engagement and incomplete nature of the Sways in the term 3 workshops that the interviewed students attended. Student 632156 (m) explained that it was particularly frustrating when he forgot to take screenshots of his artefacts in the virtual world that had then further developed and changed: *“It takes a while to build and you have to like keep taking photos throughout the process... you sometimes forget and then it er, messes you up I guess...you have stuff left out... and it’s ended up maybe not completed.”* This comment suggests that 632156 understood how he could create a Sway completed to a high standard but that forgetting to take screenshots and to complete the Sway prevented him from doing so.

The negative comments from the students regarding the repetitive and boring nature of the Sways were centred on the tasks that they had been set to complete. Students commented that they did not enjoy having to do the same tasks for each chapter: *“They’re not that interesting... it’s quite repetitive as well, like we do the same thing like log on, just you fill this out, fill that out, put images in”* (632160 – m). However, the students went further than just stating that the Sways were boring, by claiming that filling in the Sways actually took away from the creative and independent nature of the workshops in the virtual world:

- 631108 (m): *It takes away creativity.*
 631102 (m): *[Yeah.*
 Interviewer: *[It gets in the way?*
 631108: *You have to focus on that rather than like learning yourself, (type thing).*
 Interviewer: *Okay. Okay so do you find, you, so it gets in the way?*
 631108: *Yeah.*

In the above quote, the students suggest that completing the Sway books limits the ER4STEM aims of providing students with workshops that develop their independence and creativity.

There were mixed views on the need to evidence learning within the students who were interviewed, and even within the opinions of one student. 631103 (f) first stated that she didn’t believe the Sways were necessary as they were not a piece of summative coursework: *“Yeah they are very annoying... if it was GCSE then fair enough, but it’s not GCSE.”* However, she then went on to compare the Sways necessity to her other subjects, saying: *“It’s necessary cos it’s just like, it’s like in all the other subjects we actually have a book that we have to write in”*. Overall, it seems important to make the Sways more engaging, in order to make the necessary task of evidencing learning an activity that does not take away from the rest of the workshop.

22.3.5.3 IDEAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

Finally, the students offered a few innovative ideas for how they believe the Sways could be improved to make them more engaging. Three ideas were suggested: peer-assessment, having more freedom in the learning objectives, and being able to embed features other than photos into the Sway. The peer assessment suggestion was made by 631103 (f) who upon being asked about improving the Sways said: *“Maybe let your friends look at it, like be able to edit it so they can tell you if you need to improve or anything like that...So you get peer, peer assessment”*. This comment is particularly interesting when there was actually a section for peer feedback included within Sway 2.0 that was not used. The student appears to not be aware of this section. As well as the student believing peer assessment would improve the Sway, peer assessment could also fit in well with ER4STEM’s aims of developing 21st century skills in students.

With regards to creating broader learning objectives, 631108 (m) claimed he didn't think learning objectives were necessary at all, saying:

- 631108: Maybe you don't have objectives, you just like say what you've think you've done... Instead of like I have done whatever the target is.*
- Interviewer: Uh huh. Right okay, so rather than saying you need to do this... And then you're saying how you've done it... You're saying instead what you've done. Okay, so you quite like that sort of openness about the project?*
- 631108: (Agrees multiple times throughout) Yeah".*

This suggestion takes the freedom that the students have in the virtual world and applies it further to the learning objectives themselves. However, there is a difference between having freedom in your creativity as a student and having no set aim for the lesson.

Finally, student 632160 (m) suggested that the repetitive nature of the Sways could be removed by teaching the students to embed different multimedia rather than just their screenshots, thus creating variety in their Sway content: *"I think they could like add different ways of doing it... Like, we just not put just images in, maybe like somehow record it in another way".*

22.4 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section provides concluding remarks for this report, by summarising the findings and stating recommendations for the future. The findings are discussed in the following sections: 'Online Workbooks', 'Evidence of Learning', 'Motivation and Engagement', and 'Unexpected Findings'.

22.4.1 Online Workbooks

Overall, the use online workbooks was found to be effective as a replacement of paper books for monitoring student progress against objectives, particularly due to the nature of the activities being on the computer and in a virtual world, allowing students to easily insert screenshots to evidence their learning through an artefact. Teachers could easily provide feedback at any time without having to collect the books from the students. The teachers believed that using online books also allowed students to develop their ICT skills in the workshop, by learning how to email, embed, download and upload files. The students enjoyed these IT based tasks, and one students requested that they learn how to upload more multimedia into their Sway. Finally, students and teachers both appreciated the tutorials and guidance sections, which allowed students to be independent in their learning but helped them gain confidence in the virtual world and programming.

Recommendation:

- Consider allowing students to incorporate more multimedia into their Sways.

22.4.2 Evidence of Learning

The Sways had mixed results for how effectively the students evidenced their learning. On the one hand, the Sways had the potential to be an effective technique for evidencing learning, particularly as the students could easily upload screenshots of their work. Furthermore, the use of learning objectives clearly showed students what they were going to learn and then what they needed to evidence. On the other hand, it was found that

many students would state that they had met the learning objectives, without providing any evidence that they had done so, sometimes by parroting back the learning objective.

Students would use different forms of evidence, some of which was weak, and some which was stronger and would allow for evidencing misunderstanding as well as learning. This was particularly true with the learning objectives relating to coding and programming, even though this was the most commonly mentioned answer in the post-workshop questionnaires as to what the students had learnt.

Regarding soft skills, students only identified what 21st century skills they believed they would need for the future sessions of the project, but did not reflect on what skills they had actually learnt and developed as they did in the post-workshop questionnaires. This is most probably because they were directly asked about teamwork and personal development in the latter.

Finally, it was found the types of learning objectives themselves would impact on how well students engaged with them or provided evidence of learning. Vague objectives were easily met, whilst those that were specific and higher ability were often ignored, possibly due to a lack of guidance as to how to complete them.

Recommendations:

- For the teacher/Sway template to be more explicit in stating the type of evidence that needs to be uploaded, and how they can evidence particular learning objectives. For example, stating that students need to upload at least one screenshot of their code in Scratch for that lesson.
- Include more learning objectives or reflective questions around soft skills.

22.4.3 Motivation and Engagement

Student engagement with the Sways was found to decrease over the three terms that the workshops were held. This is believed to be in part by the teacher feedback only being delivered in the first term. Teacher feedback firstly meant that students knew their work was being monitored, but also allowed a dialogue between the students and teacher. Student interviews revealed that students found the teacher feedback function of the online books a useful concept, even though those students in question had never received any feedback.

Another potential factor that affected student engagement was timing. How and when the Sways were filled out appears to be a factor, with students in the first and second term filling out their Sways every fourth lesson and students in the third term continually adding to the books. Students from the final term explained that they easily forgot to fill out their Sways or to take screenshots.

Students also gave feedback that they found the structure of the Sway very repetitive and therefore boring. One student believed that not having learning objectives would allow the students to have more freedom and therefore to better engage with the Sways, however the researcher believes that this would not be the case, particularly due to the already very free and creative nature of the virtual world workshop.

There was found to be an element of assessment culture within the students in how they filled in their Sways. From observational notes it was found that there were also a number of external variables that were likely to affect student engagement, such as time of year and teacher commitments. Although these could not be altered, they are important factors to bear in mind in the future for their impact on engagement. Finally, there was still found to be a great degree of variance within the students of one workshop in how well they completed their Sways, as naturally occurs in mixed-ability classes.

Recommendations:

- For the teacher to give regular feedback to the students on their Sways and to understand the impact feedback has on student engagement.
- For the teacher feedback section of the Sways to be interspersed throughout the chapters as in Sway 1.0 rather than put at the end where it is easily forgotten as in Sway 2.0.
- To carefully consider and experiment further with how often the students fill out their Sways – if it is every lesson the students need to be reminded often so that they don't forget.
- Develop the structure of the Sway to make it less repetitive, considering making the activities vary between weeks/chapters.
- Be aware of assessment culture and highlight to students how the Sway is similar and different to other forms of assessment. Aka, encourage them to use good technique in answering questions, but ensure they understand that it is not a formative piece of coursework with set marks.
- Show the students examples of good Sways, so that they can gain ideas and know what to aim for.

22.4.4 Unexpected Findings

A number of findings were found that relate to the aims of ER4STEM but that were not expected before data analysis. Firstly, the template of Sway 1.0 had differentiated learning objectives in the form of 'All, Most, Some'. However, these were removed in Sway 2.0 due to a school wide move away from the use of these differentiated learning objectives. Differentiation was also found in the Teacher's Feedback sections in Sway 1.0, where the teacher would sometimes set higher ability students extension activities that could be evidenced in their DIRT section.

Secondly, a student suggested that the Sways could be improved by incorporating peer assessment, which would allow for students to share their artefacts of learning and potentially explain ideas of learning or improvement to each other through them.

Thirdly, the Sways allowed for a considerable amount of reflection and identification of skills through the use of WWWs and EBIs, which has the potential in the future to be used for students to consider how they developed their intrarelational and interpersonal skills.

Finally, the teacher believed that the Sways were an effective way to gain honest feedback about the workshop from the students. However, it was found that students did not actually use the Sways for this purpose and the difference in the amount of opinions given in the questionnaires compared to in the Sways shows the importance of anonymity for students giving honest feedback. Of course, encouraging this feedback in the Sways in the future would allow for the workshops to continue to be developed in the future on a teacher or school level, once the ER4STEM project has finished.

Recommendations:

- For methods of differentiation to be included in the Sways, either through the learning objectives as in Sway 1.0, through setting extension activities in Teacher Feedback, or through a different innovative method.
- To incorporate peer assessment into the workshops using the Sways.
- To change the template to ensure students not only reflect on and evidence their technological work, but also the development of their intrarelational and interpersonal skills (relating to recommendations in 22.4.2).

- To be aware of the Sways as a potential research and workshop feedback methodology on a teacher/school level, particularly as the ER4STEM project comes to a close, but also to consider the lack of anonymity in the Sways.

22.5 BIBLIOGRAPHY

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23 APPENDIX O: UK WORKSHOP CASE STUDY 2

23.1 CONTEXT

This case study explores an innovative approach to collaboration used in the Virtual Robotics workshops held by Cardiff University in Mary Immaculate High School in the second year of the ER4STEM project; physically-distributed collaboration.

23.1.1 The Participants

Between March 2017 and July 2017, a Year 7 class (age 11 to 12) at Mary Immaculate High School in Wales participated in workshop using SLurtle virtual robots as part of their ICT lessons. This class had twenty-one students – twelve of whom were female and nine of whom were male. The students took part in three workshops over the course of one and a half school terms, with two 50-minute lessons being held on the Tuesday and Thursday of every second week. There was therefore a considerable gap of a week and a half after every second session before the next session. One workshop was planned to run in each half term, with the first half term hosting six lessons, the second half term hosting four lessons and the final half term hosting eight lessons. In reality, the second and third workshop were merged into one-another, partially due to the unequal split of lessons in each half term.

The school was located in a low socio-economic area, with higher levels than the Welsh and local area average of students qualifying for Free School Meals (UK measurement of deprivation) at 30.1% of students. Furthermore, the school had a higher than the Welsh and local average for the proportion of Ethnic Minority students (31.4%) and higher than the Welsh average for students with English as an Additional Language (8.5%). 34.1% of students were classified as having Special Educational Needs (the Welsh and local average is unknown). Average attendance rates of students at the school were measured as 93.9% - just lower than the Welsh average of 94.1% and local authority average of 94.2%. All school data was measured in 2017 and is publicly available. The class was mixed gender and was the highest ability class of the year group.

23.1.2 Description of the activity

Here is provided a brief description of the three planned workshops based on activities plan 'SLurtles Introduction & Orientation' and 'Building Our Virtual World'. It should be noted that these workshops were the first live pilot of SLurtles, the SLurtle virtual world (based on a locally run OpenSim environment) and virtual robotics activities in a school and with children, having previously only been used with adults in the publicly accessible Second Life.

23.1.2.1 WORKSHOP 1 – HALF TERM 1 – SLURTLES INTRODUCTION & ORIENTATION PART A

The first workshop focuses on familiarising students with the virtual world and SLurtles. Through this workshop they learn how to navigate and interact with the virtual world and how to programme and control a SLurtle.

23.1.2.1.1 FIRST STEPS IN THE VIRTUAL WORLD

In advance of the first lesson, students had a basic, default avatar created for them. When they first log into the virtual world, all students arrive at the same point on the 'hello_world' island. This is an orientation island where students can freely explore how to control their avatar and interact with the virtual world and each

other, or they can follow a prescribed path with instructions. It includes a house where students can collect various outfits for their avatars which can be mixed and matched. There are various activities for students to engage in and once they are ready as a class, they travel through one of the doors next to the house to teleport to their class island.

23.1.2.1.2 INTRODUCTION TO SLURTLES

Each class island is an identical space which is primarily comprised of a flat building space for students. Here students are introduced to SLurtle robots and the Scratch4OS programming environment. SLurtles are programmable robots in the virtual world and are based on a prototype which was successfully implemented with adult learners (teachers engaging in programming for the first time). They can be programmed using the graphical block-based programming environment Scratch for Open Sim (Scratch4OS). Once programmed, SLurtles can move about the virtual world and using specific commands can be programmed to create objects, which in turn can be programmed to be interactive.

Students are initially introduced to SLurtle through a teacher demonstration, showing how to transfer the code from Scratch4OS to the SLurtle to make it move. The students are then invited to take a SLurtle and experiment with the various programming commands in Scratch4OS to discover what they can programme the SLurtle to do.

23.1.2.2 WORKSHOP 2 – HALF TERM 2 - SLURTLES INTRODUCTION & ORIENTATION PART B

Using the basic programming skills they have gained in Workshop 1, students are given a series of challenges to complete using the SLurtle. Using the 'pen' command and applying their mathematical knowledge of 2D they programme the SLurtle to create a series of shapes. The final two challenges (to create a star and a 3D cube) are used to extend the more able students. Following the challenges, the teacher provides further instruction on how to create more complex objects, including a staircase and an interactive dancefloor. To create the latter, the SLurtle is programmed to create the dancefloor and then each tile of the floor is programmed to use sensors to detect the presence of an avatar and make a corresponding change in colour. Overall, the students demonstrate their mathematical knowledge by programming SLurtles; learn how to use loops in programmes; and apply this knowledge to create complex constructions in the virtual world.

23.1.2.3 WORKSHOP 3 – HALF TERM 3 – BUILDING OUR VIRTUAL WORLD

Ahead of the third workshop, the class island is cleared and each group is given a dedicated 40x40 meter space with their group number on it. In this workshop, the whole class will create a virtual world island with each group responsible for their own space. Students are provided with brainstorming and planning time face-to-face to develop an idea for what will be in their space. Working collaboratively or cooperatively, using SLurtles, Scratch4OS and other building tools, students work together to create their installation in their group space over several weeks.

As they are on a shared class island, students are able to walk/fly around the island and view the installations of other groups. Via the teacher's computer and projection screen, the teacher is able to draw the whole-class' attention to particular installations and students can demonstrate to the whole class how they have created something.

23.1.3 Approach to Collaboration: Physically-Distributed Collaboration

In the third workshop, an innovative approach to collaboration was used. Whilst in the first and second workshop, any group work had taken place in partners between students that were sat next to each other in the classroom, the third workshop saw pairings of students who were physically sat on opposite sides of the classroom. The teacher assigned these pairs at the end of the first workshop - ensuring where possible that the groups were mixed gendered. Whilst these teams were physically separated in the real world, the pairs were assigned a 40x40 meter shared space, specific to their group, on the class island in the virtual world. Pairs were encouraged to communicate via the virtual world through an online chat feature, although some time was allocated for planning their work face-to-face.

This form of collaboration, with students separated in the physical world but working together through avatars and the online chat feature in the virtual world was implemented in order to explore the potential of the approach. If successful, this approach would allow, in the future, students to collaborate with students in different classes or even different schools.

23.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

23.2.1 Data Collection

Twenty-one students participated in the workshops, with all giving permission to be involved in the research project. The Cardiff University research team, with the support of the class teacher, collected data in class lessons across the course of all three workshops. Data that was relevant to this case study includes, observational notes, video observations, one pre-workshop questionnaire and two post-workshop questionnaires (conducted after the first and third workshops), an interview with the teacher during the third workshop, and seven opportunistic interviews with thirteen students – nine girls and four boys. Of these student interviews, three interviews with six students in pairs were held at the end of the first workshop and four interviews with nine students were held at the end of the third workshop (two girls took part in interviews on both occasions). Three female interviewees did not have their student numbers recorded during the interview and so their identities in terms of the research are unknown. The interviews in the third term partially focussed on the students' reports of their experience with the innovative form of collaboration. As during the physically-distributed collaboration the partners were physically separated, there is little video data that capture the pair-work to triangulate with interview data.

23.2.2 Data Analysis

The data analysis involved exploring a pre-determined research question concerning an innovative approach to collaboration, decided in advance based on the overall research priorities and the aim of the research. Data from interviews and observations were coded using emergent codes, which were then structured into categories and sub-categories. The relevant results of the questionnaires, concerning teamwork and what the students had learnt, were analysed and presented separately. Where averages were calculated, the sample size used was the total number of responses to that question.

23.3 FINDINGS

This report structures its findings in two sections: 'Teamwork in Virtual Robotics', 'Local Support Networks from Outside the Team'. Codes are shown in **bold**.

23.3.1 Teamwork in Virtual Robotics

This section explores how the students worked as a team in their pairs during the virtual robotics activities. The teamwork in this physically-distributed collaboration is explored in terms of four sub-categories. This first, 'Forms of Teamwork' explores the methods that students self-reported in interviews as having used to work in their pairs, which were found to sit on a spectrum between collaboration and cooperation. The second, 'Learning to Collaborate' is structured into the sub-sections 'What did Students Learn?', 'Making Decisions', 'Improving over Time' and 'Skill Recognition'. Overall, this section finds that students learnt interpersonal and intrarelational skills during the course of the workshop, which enabled them to understand their partner's skills and improve their work as a team. The third section, 'Location of Collaboration' explores when the students collaborated in the 'Virtual World' and in the 'Physical World' and any differences in these forms of teamwork. Here it is found that students found it easier to communicate in the physical world and in some instances would do so when they were supposed to be working together exclusively in the virtual world. Finally, the fourth section, 'Opinions Towards Teamwork' explores the results of the post-workshop questionnaires concerning the students' opinions towards teamwork. In particular, the student opinions towards 'normal' partner work recorded in the post-workshop 1 questionnaire are compared to their opinions towards the physically-distributed collaboration recorded in the post-workshop 2 questionnaire.

The relationship of these sub-categories to this category of 'Teamwork in Virtual Robotics' is shown in Figure 186.

Figure 186. Representation of 'Teamwork in Virtual Robotics' Category

23.3.1.1 FORMS OF TEAMWORK

Student interviews revealed that students used different forms of teamwork in the pairs. One pair described their teamwork as purely cooperative – splitting their area in half and working individually with little **communication** or **planning** as to what they were going to build. In comparison to **cooperation, collaboration** in the virtual world is described as partners synchronising and coordinating their work to create their shared vision for their area in the virtual world. However, no examples of purely collaborative work was reported, with pairs instead sat on a spectrum between the two extreme forms of teamwork – working cooperatively to form an overall collaboration. This section will now explore these different forms of teamwork found along this spectrum, which is visually represented in Figure 187. The section will also briefly explore how some partnerships saw an imbalance in how the pair completed their work.

Figure 187. A visual representation of the spectrum of teamwork between cooperation and collaboration

The team who worked together in a highly cooperative manner explained that they separated their area of the virtual world into two: “Well, I think like we do like half the house each, whatever you want on that side, and the other side whatever the other person wants” (62212 - m). Here, there appeared to be no collaborative **planning**, instead building ‘whatever they want’ individually. Whilst they were still working together as they were bound by their 40m x 40m space, they were choosing to cooperate by both letting the other create whatever they want in their half, but are not pooling their efforts to work in synchrony.

Other students who were interviewed worked together in a more collaborative manner; however, each still described elements of **cooperation** within their teamwork. For example, a female student interviewed in the third workshop (number unknown), explained that in one area of their space, her and her partner built whatever they individually wanted to: “So on the bottom floor, we’d both be doing our thing, like adding in our own ideas and just making anything really.” Although the ‘bottom floor’ was created collaboratively with both students working on it, the girl explains that the pair cooperated with each other, allowing each other to create whatever they wanted (“just making anything really”) without discussing or **planning** it.

The researcher observed one pair (numbers unknown) who built different items that they wanted in their house, therefore building cooperatively, but would decide on their creations in a complementary fashion to what the other student was building. For example, one student decided to build a sofa because they felt it was needed after the other student had built a TV. Therefore, the students were aware of what the other was doing in the virtual world, and shaped their own work around this.

Student 62204 (f) explained another example of cooperation within a collaboration, as she and her partner 62222 (f) **distributed roles** by **splitting the work** within their creation between them: “Yeah, she was doing like, you did the house and then I had to like décor the house, like put stuff in there and everything.” Whilst here they have split tasks between them and are working individually on different parts of their creation, they are working together to build an overall shared creation.

Students 62220(m) and 62218 (f) who worked together took a similar approach, again dividing which aspects of their creation they took the lead on. In this quote, however, the students have also explained the collaborative

process for ensuring that their overall creation was agreeable to what both members of the partnership envisioned:

- “62218 (f): *So, all I really did was just like make the building, like the structure. And he put things inside and outside. But, so it was like his sort of type of decoration.*
- 62220 (m): *Yeah.*
- 62218 (f): *But my like colours that I would want in a house, or something like that.”*

Overall, the key difference that appeared to make students work collaboratively in their area of the virtual world was through collaborating during the **planning** stages of their work. Whilst students 62220 (m) and 62218 (f) explained in the paragraph above that they mostly worked in a cooperative manner and split tasks between the two of them, they then went on to explain that they worked collaboratively during planning to decide the logistics of this task division:

- “Interviewer: *Yeah? So, how did you find that bit? How did you plan what you were going to do?*
- 62220 (m): *Um.*
- 62218 (f): *I think it was when we’d met up to talk about what we were doing.*
- 62220 (m): *Yeah.*
- 62218 (f): *We planned mostly on who was going to do what. So, I think that was our planning.”*

Even if they are working cooperatively during the implementation of their plan, the acts of **communicating**, discussing and joint decision making during the planning stages resulted in overall collaboration. As previously stated, collaboration is working as a team towards a shared vision – this joint **planning** resulted in an overall shared vision, even if the tasks within their creation may have been approached cooperatively. Unfortunately, there are no detailed observations of how students worked as a team during the planning period.

Finally, in some pairs, students reported their cooperative teamwork as being unevenly divided between the two students. In one example, a female student (number unknown) claimed that although in theory they had worked cooperatively in her pair, she did the majority of the work out of the two students as their difference in abilities meant she often helped her partner: “*I was working on upstairs and he was working on downstairs. But sometimes, he didn’t really know what to do, so I had to help him out, then I just basically did most of the work.*” Another unknown female explained that she had done most of the work due to differences of opinion between her and her partner: “*Honestly... we didn’t get along at all. So, we were just arguing, but I did most of the work.*” In a final example, one student (62218 – f) took a leadership role in their pairs work, **giving instruction** to her partner 62220 (m), who explained: “*She basically told me what to do... I just copy everything she sends and I paste it.*” Overall, it is noted that some imbalance in the work completed by different members of the team is natural in any form of teamwork, particularly in partnerships. Positive elements can be taken from this, such as the opportunity for the development of leadership skills, as well as more negative elements, such as the opportunity for less engaged students to ‘coast’. The teacher and the researcher noted both these positive and negative elements during their interview.

23.3.1.2 LEARNING TO COLLABORATE

As described in 23.1.3, the teacher assigned pairs that were physically separated and, where possible, mixed genders. Due to the class being in their first year at the secondary school, it was common for the students not to know their partner well or not to have worked with them before. This amplified the degree to which students had to learn how to work in a team with their partner. This section explores the concept of the students learning to collaborate, through the sub-sections: ‘What Did Students Learn?’, ‘Making Decisions’, ‘Improving over Time’ and ‘Skill Recognition’.

23.3.1.2.1 WHAT DID STUDENTS LEARN?

In this section, the post-workshop question results are presented, concerning the answers students gave to the questions “*What have you learned today?*” and “*What have you learned about working with other people?*”. Only the post-workshop questionnaire from workshop 3 is presented, to ensure the results focus on the innovative approach to collaboration.

In response to the question “*What have you learned today?*” only one student (62208 – f) mentioned teamwork, stating: “*I have learnt how to programme a robot, how to work as a team, how to think outside the box, be more confident in trying things I haven’t done before. This project has developed my learning ability*”. Other answers to this question focussed on programming and robotics, although student 62203 (m) discussed his work ethic: “*I have learnt that I need to try harder to achieve my goals*”.

The question “*What have you learned about working with other people?*” was answered by 15 students. Four of these students gave a positive opinion about working with others in their answer (although two gave the same answer, for an unknown reason, if any), explaining that it benefitted their work:

- 62201 (m): “*it is easier and more interesting*”
- 62203 (m): “*i have learned that it is alot easier to learn with other people*”
- 62214 (f): “*that two brains are better than one*”
- 62216 (f): “*That two brains are better than one*”

Three students described teamwork as being difficult, for example with 62219 (m) saying: “*its hard to work as a team where the other person dont listen all the time*”. In this answer, 62219 has also mentioned listening skills, which was also mentioned by a further two students, and general **communication** mentioned by two others. One of these students specifically explained that communication was made difficult by the physical separation of their partnership: “*that its difficult when you arent close to eachother and talking to eachother*” (62212 – m).

Two students mentioned that it was possible for other students to view their creations in the virtual world, with 62221 (m) explaining that he found this useful for gaining inspiration and asking for help: “*you can see there work and ask how to do it*”. Another student also mentioned helping each other in their work: “*to help eachother and give each other advice*” (62206 – f).

Finally, four of the students discussed the concept that they often had different ideas than their partner, but all four students also highlighted intrapersonal skills that helped in bypassing any difficulties associated with this, such as listening, compromise and patience:

- 62204 (f): “*That you can’t always get your way*”.
- 62207 (f): “*that you need to listen to other peoples ideas and use them all*”.
- 62208 (f): “*i have learned to be patient as their ideas might help you, and to share ideas together as their ideas are alsop benifital*”.
- 62213 (f): “*Not always do things go your way, you have to cooperate and understand each other*”.

23.3.1.2.2 MAKING DECISIONS

Whilst some students mentioned learning skills related to making decisions, such as compromise and listening, in their answers to the post-workshop questionnaire, this concept was also commonly discussed in the post-workshop interviews.

All but one of the students in the third term interviews stated that working with someone new meant that the two students in the pair had **different ideas**. Whilst not necessarily true, the students believed that their friends would have more similar ideas to their own in comparison to the random pairings, with 62218 (f) saying: *“Yeah, cos then you’ve (friends) got more in common, so like if you wanted to build something, you’d both be able to build something you like... But we (partner) don’t have much in common, so it would be like we’re building two different things in one, and trying to mix it together.”* Her partner, 62220 (m) furthered this, by stating that working with a friend would result in a better outcome of their final product: *“I think they’d make better things if they knew each other.”*

The students often gave examples of their pairing’s differences in opinions:

- 62222 (f): *“You’ve got like your ideas and then the person have got their ideas... She got a different style than me... I wanted floor, green. She want the floor yellow. That’s a little bit like hard.”*
- Student (f): *“I wanted to do just like a normal house with like loads of floors, but he wanted to do a castle.”*
- 62221 (m): *“We both had different ideas, so she had like this like forest-y thing and like a knight and stuff. And I was going to build a castle and stuff like that.”*

For some students, **differences in ideas** were not overcome and instead resulted in **arguments** within the pair: *“We didn’t get along at all... we were just arguing”* (unknown female student). However, another student, 62209 (m), planned at the end of the first term, when the pairs were assigned, that him and his future partner would **not argue**:

“We’ve added things that we like, like we don’t argue over why we’ve put stuff that we wanted in. We just add things that we would like to put in, and we don’t complain about it, and we actually think it’s a good idea that we’ve done it.”

This pair decided to accept whatever ideas the other student had and allow them to build it. During the third term, three pairs of interviewed students explained that they took a more active form of **compromising** in order to overcome their differences in ideas. For example, the unknown female student who said she had wanted a normal house with lots of floors but that her partner wanted to build a castle followed up her comment with: *“So, I said okay, like we’ll do like floors and then we’ll a castle, like floors inside the castle.”* Rather than allowing their partner to build anything, they have come to an agreement over how they can combine both of their ideas.

23.3.1.2.3 IMPROVING OVER TIME

Unsurprisingly, there was evidence from the interviews to suggest that the collaboration between the partners improved and became easier over time, as both students learnt how to work together and developed the soft-skills such as patience and compromise, mentioned in the post-workshop questionnaire answers. Again, regarding the compromising approach used by students that was discussed in the previous section, one pair explained that compromising was something that was developed during the course of the workshop, and that whilst it was **difficult at the start**, compromise made working together easier:

- “62221 (m): It was a bit rough at the start because we weren’t used to talking to each other, cos we’ve got our own groups of friends. And like cos we started working together, we both had different ideas...”*
- Interviewer: What about for you? How did you find it?*
- 62202 (f): Yeah, I think it’s got better. And then I think we’ve kind of compromised with the ideas, and yeah.”*

As well as learning how to compromise over the course of the workshop, students also reported in the interviews having learnt the skills of patience and **perseverance** as important in their partnership.

Whilst students developed their skills, they also built a relationship with their partner – no longer being someone they did not know by the end of the workshop. This was well summarised by teacher, who said:

“I think the teamwork as well, in terms of the pupils talk to each properly, which then means that when they’ve got a problem, they’re not going off by themselves, or getting like, oh I can’t do it. They’re asking each other for help, they’ve built up relationships with each other.”

A prime example of this relationship was seen in one female student, whose number is unknown, who at the start of the workshop protested against being partnered with a student. However, over the course of the workshop, she developed a working relationship that was **better than expected**, which resulted in her being proud of their partnership and their work:

“I was just proud that me and (name removed) got along, Miss. Cos I was thinking that we weren’t going to get along, and nothing was going to get down. So, I’m actually just happy that we spoke and actually designed something.”

23.3.1.2.4 SKILL RECOGNITION

Finally, the development of a working relationship over the course of the workshop also resulted in the students recognising not only their own **skills** but also the **skills** of their partner. Student 62220 (m) recognised his partners **skills** very bluntly when asked how he had found their partnership, saying: *“It was good cos she’s smart...yeah, she’s smart”*. However, this comment was drawn upon in an informal interview between the researcher and the teacher in the third term:

“Interviewer: So, actually that recognition of their own skills and the skills of others, and how best to deploy them are incredibly valuable skills. You know, not feeling that I have to do everything, or wouldn’t normally work together. And 62220 (m) said, it was all right actually, she’s really clever... so 62218 (f) did the programming because she knew how to do some of that stuff.”

Participant: But they distributed the roles, you see, which was really clever, and what we need to look at more with team work is, right, who’s good at this, you do that, you do that.”

The recognition of each other’s strengths allowed the students to cooperate effectively in their team.

23.3.1.3 LOCATION OF COLLABORATION

The factor that makes this workshop’s form of collaboration innovative was that the partners were collaborating in the virtual world, but were sat **physically separated** in different parts of the classroom. All of the interviewed students explained that this form of collaboration had an added level of difficulty compared to normal partner work. For example:

*Interviewer: How did it work then with the fact that you were sat on opposite sides of the room...
62218 (f): It made it harder.*

This section explores how the students collaborated depending on their location, comparing their experience collaborating in the 'Virtual World' with that of the 'Physical World'. Although the section is structured in terms of these locations, the results show that **communication**, or difficulties in communication, was an overarching theme in the collaborations.

23.3.1.3.1 VIRTUAL WORLD

When working on the virtual world, partners each had their own avatar that they would use to work in a 40x40 meter, shared designated area. Students were encouraged to use the **online chat** feature to communicate to each other in the virtual world.

For some students, communicating in the virtual world was a challenge that was hard to overcome, such as for 62221 (m), who struggled to understand how the chat feature functioned: *"We had to kind of communicate through the chat thing, and that weren't working because you had to be right next to the person, so they could see it. And, so it was a bit difficult to chat with them and see the ideas."* He also briefly mentions the difficulty of explaining ideas, which require a clear description, in the chat feature. This was also mentioned by student 62204 (f): *"I guess I really just wanted what she wanted, and it was harder in text because I couldn't, I didn't really get what she wanted. But then when she came round, I got it. Because we were writing down on the whiteboards and then I'm like, I understood fully what she wanted to do."* She implies that her and her partner did not realise they had **similar ideas** until they were given an opportunity to communicate in the physical world. Although they had tried to collaborate in the virtual world, the heightened difficulty of providing clear written descriptions and negotiating on the chat feature became a barrier to their collaboration.

However, the teacher recognised that, similarly to how working with someone new amplified the need to develop teamwork skills, challenging students in their collaboration with the location of their partnership encouraged them to develop their 21st century skills in **online communication**:

"It's been built up in a virtual manner, because we've done some of the lessons where they have to talk to each other online... So, I think those transferable skills, I think those are really valuable"

On the other hand, it was found that not all students used the online chat feature to discuss their ideas. For example, as was previously discussed in **Error! Reference source not found.**, some students would build in separate areas of their space in the virtual world, putting in their own ideas and not discussing what they were making with their partner. Another example is seen when student 62220 (m) explained that his partner (62218 – f) used the online chat feature to send him pre-built items from other areas in the virtual world to put into their space:

*"Interviewer: So, how did you work that out? Cos you must have kind of negotiated who's doing what?
62220 (m): Cos she basically told me what to do.
Interviewer: (Laughs).
62218 (f): I just copy everything she sends and I paste it."*

Here, although the students are communicating through the online chat feature, little negotiation or discussion seems to have occurred, instead with one partner leading their creation and appropriating the chat function to send programmes to the other student. Finally, some students move from discussing their ideas in the virtual world into the physical world, as is discussed in the following section.

23.3.1.3.2 PHYSICAL WORLD

Students would collaborate in the physical world in two ways – **sitting next to each other** with permission from the teacher during sections of the lesson that were designated to planning, and communicating in the physical world when they were supposed to be communicating via the online chat feature in the virtual world.

Sitting next to each other in order to plan their work occurred once at the start of the third workshop, where students made their overall plan for what they would construct in their area in the virtual world. Students also sat next to each other on a couple of extra occasions at the start of a lesson, in which the pair would plan what they wanted to complete during that session. During these periods, one student would move from their computer to their partner's desk, while the partner remained in their seat, as shown in Figure 188, where two girls have moved from their desk at the forefront of the figure to their partner's desk in the middle of the room. Importantly, the students not only moved their collaboration from the virtual world to the physical world, but also removed their **physical separation** in the physical world, making it possible to communicate without shouting across the room.

Figure 188. Two girls move to the desk of two boys to collaborate with them in the physical world

The students explained that they found these moments of collaboration in the physical world easier than collaboration in the virtual world, as it was easier to communicate. For example, student 62221 (m) said: *“So, it was easier if moved together like we did... Because we were next to each other, so we could communicate more, so we could see each other’s different ideas. Cos, we were on the computer and (name removed) was sat next to me, and we were both talking about what we could do and how to improve it, and like what to build.”* Whilst the students saw the benefits of working in a team in the virtual world, claiming they could get more work done (62218 – f), they found it hard to make decisions, communicate and plan their collaboration exclusively in the virtual world.

Whilst there were designated parts of the workshop for collaborating in the physical world, evidence suggests that multiple students also **communicated in the physical world** during periods when they were supposed to communicate purely in the virtual world. This evidence partially came from students revealing in their interview that they communicated with their partner in the physical world but that it was difficult due to their physical separation. An unknown female said: *“you just kept shouting backwards and forwards, like oh you have to do this, no I’m not doing that. So it was quite difficult.”* Furthermore, another unknown female said:

“Like being far away from them half way through then you have then like just shout over and then they’re not doing what you want, because it’s totally different is quite annoying.” On these occasions of communication in the physical world during periods not designated to that form of collaboration, the students’ barrier of **physical separation** had not been removed, thus meaning they still found communication hard.

This ‘shouting’ across the room by a student to their partner was captured in one of the video observations made during the second term. At the beginning of the lesson on May 4th 2017, the teacher instructs the pupils that they are not allowed to talk in the physical world for the rest of the lesson and may only collaborate with their partner in the virtual world using the online chat feature to communicate. Over the course of the rest of the lesson, the noise levels of chatter between friends slowly increases. At 14:44 on the video recording shown in Figure 189, one of the students begins to lean backwards on her chair so that she is closer to her partner and begins to communicate with him in the physical world. Note that the teacher is close behind her at this point but does not tell her to stop, either not noticing or choosing not to intervene. As the noise levels continue to raise in the room, the pair get more confident in their physical world communication, with the girl shouting across: *“(Name), we need a door... go get us a door!”*

Figure 189. Girl leans across to talk to her partner (off screen on the right) in the physical world

Interestingly, in the following lesson on May 16th, this pattern repeated itself, with another pair of students, one of whom was just off shot of the camera but who could be heard, gradually communicating more in the physical world after having been told to only communicate in the virtual world. However, during this lesson, a student sitting next to one of the pair eventually tells them off, saying: *“Use the chat!”* and looking visibly frustrated by the shouting, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 190. "Talk in the chat!" girl says to another girl behind her (off camera).

This interaction shows that there were differences between students with how much they communicated in the virtual and physical world. This difference could be due to a number of things, such as behaviour, ability to follow instruction, ability to communicate their ideas, or finding 'chatting' in the virtual world too difficult.

23.3.1.4 OPINIONS TOWARDS TEAMWORK

This final section of the category 'Teamwork in Virtual Robotics' explores the answers that students gave to questions in the pre-workshop and two post-workshop questionnaires regarding their opinions towards teamwork. It is found that the students on average changed their opinions after taking part in the third workshop, where they had worked in a physically-distributed collaboration.

Firstly, the results of the pre-workshop questionnaire for questions regarding teamwork are presented in Figure 191. The students stated how strongly they agreed or disagreed with three statements, with 1 being 'Strongly Disagree', 3 being 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', and 5 being 'Strongly Agree'. On average, students had a positive attitude towards teamwork before they took part in the workshop. For the statements 'I learn best with other people' and 'I like working in teams' the mean average scores were both 4.1. Furthermore, for these statements, no students answered with 'Strongly Disagree'. For the statement 'I like working on my own' the average mean score was 2.9, however as can be seen in Figure 191, the scores given by students had a wide range. Whilst the mode was similar to the mean average, showing that most students (nine) were indifferent about working on their own, six students agreed or strongly agreed that they enjoyed working alone and another six disagreed or strongly disagreed. There is therefore more disparity in the answers given by students.

Figure 191. A graph showing the number of each answer to the pre-workshop questions concerning opinions on teamwork.

Next, the results of the two post-workshop questionnaires for questions regarding teamwork are discussed. The students again stated how strongly they agreed with a number of statements, ten of which related to their experiences of their collaboration or in generally supporting others through sharing their work or helping fellow students. As the students completed two post-workshop questionnaires – one after the first workshop and one after the final workshop – it is possible to track how students opinions of teamwork changed after collaborating in the innovative form that has been explored in this report, with the more ‘normal’ partner work that they had completed in the first workshop. This change in opinions is presented in Figure 192, where the average answer for each question in both workshops is presented, alongside the difference between the two.

Figure 192. A graph showing the changes in average answers to questions regarding students' opinions of teamwork after working in a physically separated collaboration.

Whilst a small difference can be seen in the answers to each question between the two workshops, these are overall marginal, particularly considering the sample size. However, the larger drop of 0.9 to the questions 'working in a team was fun' is more notable. Factors that may have affected this drop could be the difficulty of the task, or no longer working with their friends, however no data was collected that can be triangulated with this decrease. Although there was a decrease in the score given for this question after the physically-distributed collaboration, it can also be seen that the students still averagely ranked the teamwork as being fun, agreeing with the statement with an average score of 3.4.

23.3.2 Local Support Networks from Outside the Team (Sitting with Friends)

Whilst the students collaborated with their partner who was physically separated from them in the classroom, most students sat **next to their friends** for the majority of the workshop. During a discussion between the researcher and the teacher, this was noted as having been an effective arrangement for the class:

“Researcher: Allowing them to sit with their friends but have a partner on the other side of the room, seems to work really well.

Participant: Yeah, it has actually when you point that out... You know, providing it's a good class, friendship groups if it's productive and you've got different cliques in your class then... it's worked, it has. And like you say though, but the paired workers worked by not being next to the person.”

This positivity was also mentioned by the students during interviews and was notable in the video observations. This section therefore explores how sitting with friends allowed students to have support in a different way from the support that they received in their partners, which is presented in term of ‘Social Support’ and ‘Technical Support’.

23.3.2.1 SOCIAL SUPPORT

As occurs often both inside and outside of classrooms, friends were observed socialising during lessons, occasionally chatting about topics that were not relevant to the virtual world. However, this form of chatting was actually very rare, with the majority of communication between those sat next to each other concerning what they were doing in the virtual world. Students would still socialise, but it was related to the virtual world, or even in the virtual world. For example, students 62209 (m) and 62212 (m) who were sat next to each other dressed their **avatar**'s in the virtual world in the same recognisable outfit so that they could find each other easily:

“62209 (m): We started getting more pieces and becoming Transformers, Optimus Prime.

Interviewer: Yeah, cool. I think you're the only ones in there that look like that... So you're really easy to spot on the island, yeah?

...

62209 (m): It's really good because like, sometimes people will get mixed up with who's the partner if they don't look at the number. But they know, they know that we're Optimus Prime, it's only two people, so they'll know who it is because we've told them as well.

62212 (m): Yeah.

Interviewer: And if you're looking for each other...

62209 (m): We'll find each other... We don't have to fly around just looking for each other, we can just look and see each other straight away.”

Here, the boys put matching costumes on their avatars, which was fun and social, but also had a logistical benefit for each other and their partners in recognising them in the virtual world.

It was also seen in the video observations that students were often keen to share their creations and work in the virtual world with their friends. For example, on a recording made on July 3rd, towards the end of the third workshop, a male student is heard off camera saying: “(Name) *do you like my virtual world?*” A female student then leans from the edge of the camera to off shot to look at his screen, saying: “*Ah, it's good*”. The male student does not seem to require any help, but simply wants to show-off his work to a friend who in return gives praise.

23.3.2.2 TECHNICAL SUPPORT

Whilst many of the interactions between friends were of a social manner, students also reported that they were more comfortable asking their friends for **help** than they were their partners. An unknown female explained this in an interview, saying:

Student (f): Like I feel more comfortable to talk to her, than I would with my partner, like asking questions.

Interviewer: Right, okay, so you could work with your partner, but if you were stuck on something, you could ask your friend?

Student (f): Yeah.

This helping between friends who were sitting next to each other was also seen in the video observations. For example, Figure 193 shows a screenshot taken from a recording on March 23rd, towards the end of the first workshop. Here, the one girl can be seen pointing at the other's screen, explaining how to do something in the virtual world whilst the other student follows her instruction.

Figure 193. One student helps another - pointing at their screen to give direction

When not explicitly helping each other, students were often seen observing each other's work – not in the virtual world, but physically looking at their friend's screen, observing how they view the virtual world, as shown in Figure 194. Whilst this could be one student simply watching, it may also be that the student is gaining inspiration, or learning through observation. Furthermore, students could also look at each other's work in the virtual world, by exploring other pairs' 40m x 40m areas on the island. This was actively encouraged by the teacher.

Figure 194. On student (background) watches the other's screen (foreground)

Finally, it was observed that if one student asked for help from the teacher, the person next to them would often listen into what the teacher was saying, for example in the screenshot taken from the video on June 20th in Figure 195. This may be because they had a similar problem, because they were trying to learn in case they encountered a similar problem in the future, or because they were invested in their friend's difficulties.

Figure 195. Student (f - background) watches whilst the teacher (researcher) helps another student (m - foreground)

23.4 DISCUSSION

This section discusses the findings of this report, in terms of 'What has been learnt about this form of collaboration?' and in terms of 'What did students learn through this collaboration?' For both sub-sections, recommendations for the future are provided.

23.4.1 What has been learnt about this form of collaboration?

23.4.1.1 IT IS CHALLENGING

Physically-distributed collaboration was found to be challenging for the students, which they self-reported in interviews and in the questionnaire. There was also evidence that some students would communicate with the partners in the physical world during periods of time when they were only meant to be collaborating in the virtual world. The teacher and researcher recognised that this challenge encouraged students to learn new skills, both technical and relating to teamwork. However, the level of challenge should also be considered in terms of the cognitive load exerted on the students becoming too heavy as they learn multiple complex and new skills as once, for example developing their online communication skills whilst also learning to programme.

Recommendation:

- **This innovative form of collaboration should remain as only being used in the final workshop to help optimise the students' cognitive load.**
- **The age of the students should be considered – would this workshop be more effective with older students who have more experience in online communication?**
- **Teachers should monitor students' behaviour and ability and provide more support if they are collaborating in the physical world when they are not meant to.**
- **The teacher should explain to the students before the activity that there will be set times collaborating in the virtual world and set times in the physical world – activities around identifying what skills will be needed during these periods, or getting students to set their own rules could even be included to support students.**

23.4.1.2 COLLABORATION, COMMUNICATION AND PLANNING

Evidence was provided to suggest that students who developed an effective plan together were more likely to work in a successful collaboration and would be less on the cooperative end of the spectrum of teamwork. In order to develop a successful plan, the students needed to communicate with each other, which was best done in the physical world, as the online chat feature in the virtual world was found to be less effective for planning. During the planning period, students had to compromise to share their ideas and create a shared vision or plan of their creation. Overall, it is emphasised that the planning stage in the physical world is important and should be monitored to ensure students are working effectively during it. Therefore, if this activity were to be implemented with collaboration between different classes or different schools, as mentioned in 23.1.3, a number of considerations would need to be made. Students would have to meet up physically at least once to plan, be given more support in how to communicate and negotiate in an online written medium, or the activity would have to be aimed at older pupils who would be more skilled in online written communication.

Recommendations:

- **Students should be monitored during the planning stage to ensure they are working effectively and collaborating to form a shared vision. This could also be encouraged by asking teams to share their plan with another team – encouraging them to clarify their ideas in order to communicate them to others and giving them the opportunity to learn or gain inspiration from others.**

- **Students should be given more support in how to communicate effectively using the online chat feature in the virtual world.**
- **The activity should be aimed at older, more able students if the collaboration is to be made harder by taking away planning in the physical world.**

23.4.1.3 THE VALUE OF SUPPORT FROM OUTSIDE OF THE COLLABORATION

There was significant evidence showing that students found support from those sitting next to them, with whom they were not partnered with. Whilst this was sometimes social, students also often provided technical support to each other. This enabled the student who was helping to develop their teaching and communication skills, and enabled the other student to learn more about virtual robotics. It was found that this support happened in the physical world, with students pointing at each other's screens, talking and listening if the teacher was helping another pupil. By partnering students in a physically-distributed collaboration, the students had a second support network from their friends, but were still challenged and learnt new skills from being partnered with someone they knew less well, located in another part of the classroom. Furthermore, students shared their creations in the virtual world with their friends, therefore showing their ideas between collaborative groups. Whilst this sometimes occurred in the physical world, with students looking at each other's screens, it also happened in the virtual world, where students were actively encouraged by the teacher to look at other students' 40m x 40m area to see what they had created.

Recommendations:

- **Allow talking between students sitting next to each other and encourage them to help each other.**
- **Continue to encourage students to explore other students' areas of the virtual world, to enable sharing of ideas and gaining inspiration between groups.**
- **Foster this inter-group learning more through set activities between different groups, such as the shared planning recommendation made in 23.4.1.2.**

23.4.2 What did students learn through this collaboration?

While students were found to have a positive opinion towards teamwork before the workshops, they were evidenced as having learnt new 21st century skills through the challenge of this innovative form of collaboration. Evidenced both in the questionnaires and in interviews, students built their intrarelatinal and interpersonal skills such as patience, perseverance, communication in both the virtual and physical world, and compromise. As the students built a relationship with their partner over the course of the workshop and developed these skills, they stated that they began to find the collaboration easier and started to recognise each other's skills and strengths. Furthermore, the students learnt through helping each other and were inspired by each other's creations in the virtual world.

Recommendations:

- **Integrate activities during the workshop where students identify their own skills and weaknesses, and their partner's skills and weaknesses.**
- **Incorporate evidence of learning 21st century skills – see the Mary Immaculate Sways report from Year 3 for an example.**

23.4.3 Overview of Physically-Distributed Collaboration Strengths and Weaknesses

This final section summarises the overall positive and negative aspects that were found of this form of collaboration in the virtual robotics workshops.

23.4.3.1 STRENGTHS

- Students are challenged in their collaboration, encouraging them to develop intrarelatinal and interpersonal skills to succeed, such as communication, compromise, patience and perseverance.
- This challenge is added as another factor in the final workshop to maintain engagement in the virtual world.
- Students develop skills in online communication
- Students help each other, constructing together and building upon what each other has learnt
- Students can support those outside of their group, both socially and technically, and can share their ideas and constructions.
- Overall the students reported that the teamwork was fun and interesting

23.4.3.2 WEAKNESSES

- There was a decrease in the students agreeing that the physically-distributed collaboration was fun compared to when asked the same question about 'normal' pair work.
- The ability of the students has to be monitored and the activity adapted as the physically-distributed collaboration has the ability to create cognitive overload.
- An understanding is needed from the teacher about the importance of ensuring the students effectively plan their work in the physical world and that students refrain from communicating to their partner in the physical world at other points during the workshop.

24 APPENDIX P: YEAR 3 QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS

24.1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the approach followed to generate documents for each partner. This document includes an explanation on how the data was prepared, ER4STEM's objectives and a description of how an index for each objective was generated. It is important to notice that objectives five and seven cannot be calculated because there is not questions in the pre-questionnaire that could be used as base line. This report does not include a deep analysis on the data collection and questionnaires used to collect it. More information about this could be found in D6.4 and D2.3.

24.1.1 Data Preparation

Some modifications were necessary to do in data collected. The modification done are:

1. Clean the data and correct any discrepancies found it such us repeated student numbers, missing age or gender, among others.
2. Yes/No questions that were answered with other options are considered as NA.
3. Establish the correct meaning of 1 to 5. In Austria they tend to use 1 as strongly agree and 5 as strongly disagree.
4. Add information that could be useful to analyse the data:
 - Add type of questionnaire use. This would make easier to understand the questions that are present in each one of the questionnaires:
 - 0 = Y1
 - 1 = Y2 – questionnaire for ages between 11-18
 - 2 = Y2 – questionnaire for ages between 7-11
 - 4= Y3 – questionnaire for ages between 11-18
 - 5 = Y3 – questionnaire for ages between 7-11
5. Delete participants who did not answer pre and post questionnaires. This is due some questions from the prequestionnaire are used to quantify the disposition of the participants.

24.1.2 ER4STEM's Objectives

The objectives consider in this analysis are the following:

OB1. Do the activities encourage interest in STEM education and careers?

OB2. Do the activities appeal to girls?

OB3. Are girls interested in STEM topics?

OB4. Did they participate in collaborative work?

OB5. Do they learn about scientific topics?

OB6. Do the activities allow learners to connect robots to their personal interest?

OB7. Do children share their ideas with/through tangible artefacts?

OB8. Did children identify and define problems that influence their lives?

OB9. Were they equipped with the necessary skills to solve these problems?

OB10. Do they develop soft-skills?

These objectives are link to the questions in the prequestionnaire and postquestionnaire.

24.2 PROTOCOL FOR COMPARISON: GENERAL INFORMATION

The data was collected before (Pre-questionnaire) and after (Post-questionnaire) each workshop. The pre-questionnaire provided information about participants' attitudes and the post-questionnaire how the activity have change their perception of STEM, among other things. Considering information from both questionnaires let us to have a better understanding of the real impact of robotics. Also it help us to verify if the quality of the workshops has improved. Therefore, the following is our hypothesis:

Hypothesis: There is an improvement a difference between pre and post-questionnaire.

This hypothesis is going to be tested for each one of the objectives of ER4STEM separately, including differences in gender and age group. The subsequent subsections present how the analysis for each objective is done.

24.2.1 OB1 – Interest in STEM

Two indexes are calculated for this objective $STEMF_{pre}$ and $STEMF_{post}$. Each index is calculated:

$$STEMF_X = \frac{1}{|W|} \sum_{i=1}^W \left(\frac{1}{|n_i|} \sum_{j=1}^{|l_i|} \left(\frac{1}{|n_j|} \sum_{k=1}^{m_x} f(Question_{(l,j)}) \right) \right) \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where:

X = represents pre or post.

$|W|$ = is the number of workshops.

$|n_i|$ = number of participants who answered at least one question.

$|l_i|$ = number of participants in workshop i .

$|n_j|$ = number of questions answered by participant j .

m_x = questions used to calculate the index.

$$f(Question_{(l,j)}) \begin{cases} \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is likert} \rightarrow Value(Question_{(l,j)}) \\ \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is likert and inverted} \rightarrow 6 - Value(Question_{(l,j)}) \\ \text{if } Question_{(l,j)} \text{ is yes or no} \begin{cases} \text{if yes} \rightarrow 5 \\ \text{if no} \rightarrow 1 \\ \text{else} \rightarrow NA \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

The $STEMF_{pre}$ is calculated using the following questions:

- I like science
- I like maths
- I want to understand more about mechanical things

- I think it is important to learn about science
- I like learning about how things work
- What is your favourite subject in school? - This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes – this is just present in the second and third year
- Which subject do you like the least? - This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- In general I find maths easy
- Maths lessons are boring – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- We have fun in maths lessons
- Maths is important for the job I want to do
- Maths is important
- My teacher thinks I am good at maths
- I get good grades in maths
- I think maths is difficult – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$) – This question is just present in second and third year.
- Maths is the most interesting subject in school
- Maths is important to learn – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I am good at maths – This question is just present in second and third year.
- Most of my friends are good at maths
- Would you like to study maths when you are older? - This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- Science is the most interesting subject in school
- In general I find science easy
- Science lessons are boring – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- We have fun in science lessons
- Science is important for the job I want to do
- Science is important – This question is just present in second and third year.
- My teacher thinks I am good at science
- I am good at science – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I think science is difficult – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- Science is important to learn – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I get good grades in science
- Most of the students in my class are good at science
- My friends are good at science
- Would you like to study science when you are older? - This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes

The $STEMF_{post}$ is calculated using the following questions:

- I am now more interested in studying science – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I am now more interested in learning about how things work – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I like using computers – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I understand how important maths is – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes

- I understand how important science is – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to learn more about programming – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to learn maths in robotics workshops like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to learn about science in robotics workshops like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I think I am good at maths – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I think I am good at science – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I like maths – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I like science – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I like engineering – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes

24.2.2 OB2 – Activities are appealing to girls

The index here is calculated as it is presented in equation 1.

$AppealGirl_{pre}$ is calculated using the following questions:

- I like using computers
- I know a lot about robots

These two questions were selected because if participants like using computers and consider that they know a lot about robots, would mean that they are already attracted to this type of activities.

$AppealGirl_{post}$ is calculated using the following questions:

- The problems we had to solved were interesting
- The problems we had to solved were difficult – This question is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- The problems we had to solved were fun
- Working with robots was interesting
- Working with robots was difficult – This question is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- Working with robots was Fun
- I gave up too quickly – This question is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- I work hard
- I was bored – This question is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- I would like to do more activities like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes
- I like using computers – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no, and 5 if it was yes

24.2.3 OB3 – Girls interest in STEM Education

This is calculated in the same way that OB1 but just considering girls.

24.2.4 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The index is calculated as it was presented in equation 1.

The questions considered from the pre-questionnaire are:

- I learn best with other people
- I like working on my own – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- I like working in teams
- I like working with new people – This question is just present in second and third year.

The questions considered from the post-questionnaire are:

- Working in a team was interesting
- Working in a team was difficult – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- Working in a team was Fun
- I worked as a part of a team
- I worked on my own – This question is inverted
- I feel that other people did not listen to me – This questions is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- I did most of the work – This question is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- I was encouraged by my team
- I was good at listening –
- I think that I am good working in a team – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes

24.2.5 OB5 – Participants Learned about Scientific Topics

This index can be just calculated for the post-questionnaire. As a consequence, there is nothing to compare.

24.2.6 OB6 – The activities allowed Learners to Connect Robots to Their Personal Interest

The index is calculated as it was presented in equation 1.

The questions considered from the pre-questionnaire are:

- I want to solve problems that can help people

The questions considered from the post-questionnaire are:

- I worked on something that I was interested in
- I tried to solve an important problem
- I gave up to quickly – This questions is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- I worked hard
- I was bored – This questions is inverted ($6 - \text{answer}$)
- I would like to try to solve more challenges like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to build and programme robots to solve problems in the future– This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to use robots to learn new things in the future – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- I understand how robots can be used to solve important problems – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes

- I would like to learn about science in robotics workshops like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- I would like to do more activities like this one – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes

24.2.7 OB7 – Children Shared their Ideas with/through Tangible Artefacts

This index can be just calculated for the post-questionnaire. As a consequence, there is nothing to compare.

24.2.8 OB8 – Children Identified and Define Problems that Influence their Lives

The index is calculated as it was presented in equation 1.

The questions considered from the pre-questionnaire are:

- I want to solve problems that can help people

The questions considered from the post-questionnaire are:

- I worked on something that I was interested in
- I tried to solve an important problem
- I identified a problem to solve

24.3 OB9 – CHILDREN WERE EQUIPPED WITH THE NECESSARY SKILLS TO SOLVE THESE PROBLEMS

The index is calculated as it was presented in equation 1.

The questions considered from the prequestionnaire are:

- Have you created a robot before? – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- Have you ever done any programming before? – This question is converted to 1 if the answer was no and 5 if it was yes
- I like using computers
- I know a lot about robots

The questions considered from the postquestionnaire are:

- The problems we had to solve were difficult – This questions is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- I gave up too quickly – This questions is inverted ($6 - answer$)
- I worked hard
- I was bored – This questions is inverted ($6 - answer$)

24.3.1 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The index is calculated as it was presented in equation 1.

The questions considered from the prequestionnaire are:

- I like working on my own – This questions is inverted (6 – *answer*)
- I like working in teams
- I like trying to solve difficult problems
- I like problem solving – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I need help solving problems – This questions is inverted (6 – *answer*)
- I am good at solving problems
- I like working with new people – This question is just present in second and third year.

The questions considered from the postquestionnaire are:

- I identified a problem to solve
- I solved a problem – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I worked as a part of a team
- I worked on my own – This questions is inverted (6 – *answer*)
- I helped create a robot
- I built a robot – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I did most of the work – This questions is inverted (6 – *answer*)
- I was good at listening – This question is just present in second and third year.
- I helped someone

24.4 THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF AL

24.4.1 Introduction

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in **D6.3**. This report just take in consideration the data provided by AL, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 196 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. OB2 only has females because the objective is meant to check if there is an improvement in girls. OB3 is embedded in OB1 because OB3 just consider improvement in females. In **OB1**, there is difference in pre and post-indexes in the general ($t(361.12)=-6.02, p=0$) and female ($t(156)=-6.69, p=0$) levels. In addition, there is a difference between the scores in the pre and post-questionnaire ($t(361.12)=-6.02, p=0$). **OB2** shows that there is a significant difference between pre and post ($t(327.51)=-12.88, p=0$). Males have a lower average than females in **OB4** in the pre and post-questionnaire. The pre-questionnaire indexes are higher than in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test in at the general ($t(148.42)=1.5, p=0.13$), female ($t(172)=-6.08, p=0$) and male ($t(57)=-1.95, p=0.06$) levels shows that there is not differences between pre and post-indexes. There is not difference between males and females in pre ($t(68.08)=-0.23, p=0.82$) and post-questionnaire ($t(65.39)=-0.19, p=0.85$) in **OB6**. Neither, there is not difference between pre and post-questionnaire for female ($t(39)=1.27, p=0.21$) and males ($t(35)=1.1, p=0.28$). Pre-questionnaire indexes are higher in **OB8** than post-questionnaire indexes. There is a difference in females ($t(39)=2.71, p=0.01$) indexes between pre and post-questionnaire. However, there is not difference in males ($t(35)=1.45, p=0.16$) indexes. Post-questionnaire indexes are higher in **OB9** than in the pre-questionnaire. There is difference between them ($t(435.27)=-11.65, p=0$), as well as female ($t(174)=-14.51, p=0$) indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. However, there is not difference in males ($t(57)=-1.52, p=0.13$) indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. There is significant differences between indexes scores in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire ($t(452.51)=-6.37, p=0$) in **OB10**. With no difference between genders in the indexes in pre ($t(91.75)=0.73, p=0.47$) and post-questionnaire ($t(87.08)=1.57, p=0.12$). More information about each one of the indexes and objectives are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 196 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.4.2 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. Nevertheless, it is evident a difference between pre and post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done on the difference of index between pre-questionnaire ($M=4.06, SD=0.55$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.46, SD=0.73$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(361.12)=-6.02, p=0$), with a better result in the **post-questionnaire**. Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. In both figures, post-questionnaire indexes are higher. Two t test were done to check if there is statistical difference between genders in the pre and post-questionnaires. Females in the pre-questionnaire had ($M=4.04, SD=0.54$), while males in the pre-questionnaire had ($M=4.15, SD=0.58$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(53.45)=-1.06, p=0.29$). On the other hand, females in post-questionnaire had ($M=4.42, SD=0.73$) and males in post-questionnaire had ($M=4.61, SD=0.72$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(56.88)=-1.4, p=0.17$). This suggest that both genders are interested in STEM.

An additional paired t-test was done to verify if there is difference between female indexes in the pre ($M=4.04, SD=0.54$) and post-questionnaires ($M=4.42, SD=0.73$). The results suggest that there is a difference between pre and post ($t(156)=-6.69, p=0$), with better indexes in the post-questionnaire.

24.4.3 Workshop Level

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender offered in AL. There are not male participants in several workshops and in other workshops the number of participants is low, such as **AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1**, which only have one participant with a complete index. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. The workshop AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3 has more participants in the pre-questionnaire with an index between 4.5 and 5 than in the post-questionnaire. Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Three cases are interesting to observe due the big difference between indexes. In all three cases, the pre-questionnaire index were between 3.5 and 4.5. However, in the post-questionnaire index, all participants scored 5. This could be due different reasons but it would be recommendable to look in more detail these cases. These workshops are AL-2-13-StCat, AL-2-14-StCat and AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2. Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Male's indexes in pre-questionnaire for the workshops AL-2-13-StCat, AL-2-14-StCat, AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3 and AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2 are higher than females in the same workshops. Interestingly, male's post-questionnaire in workshop **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** did not score as high as females, which ones again makes this an interesting workshop to be analyzed in more detail. The workshop **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3** presents a decrement between pre and post-index for males, while females showed an increment between pre and post-questionnaire.

Table 35 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in AL.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14
AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	0	24
AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	0	23
AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	0	25
AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	1	0
AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	6	6
AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	24
AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	24
AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	7	4
AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	7	3

197 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 198 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 199 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 200 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 201 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 202 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.4.4 OB2 – Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=4.44, SD=0.52$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.63, SD=0.65$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(327.51)=-12.88, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.4.5 Workshop Level

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. This table reports one additional workshop than in Table 35 because participants from workshop **AL-2-11-VER3** did not answer the questions used to calculate the index. Workshops **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3**, **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** and **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** are not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. There is a positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire index. There is outstanding improvement in workshops **AL-2-12-VER4**, **AL-2-13-StCat**, **AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1**, **AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1**, **AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1** and **AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors**.

Table 36 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	7
AL-2-12-VER4	9
AL-2-13-StCat	10
AL-2-14-StCat	14
AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	24
AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	24
AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	25
AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	4
AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	24
AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	25
AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	4
AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	3

Figure 203 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 204 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

24.4.6 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a small positive difference between indexes from pre ($M=3.74, SD=0.73$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.11, SD=0.74$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(459.85)=-5.28, p=0$). Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females' indexes in pre ($M=3.84, SD=0.66$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.23, SD=0.69$). There is an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(172)=-6.08, p=0$), with a better indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males' indexes in pre ($M=3.48, SD=0.86$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.73, SD=0.77$). The suggest that there is a small difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is not difference between them** ($t(57)=-1.95, p=0.06$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The result suggests that there is a difference between the indexes in the pre-questionnaire for males and females ($t(80.56)=2.92, p=0$), with **females having more attitude to work in teams than males**. Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. The results suggest that **there is difference between indexes from males and females** ($t(89.28)=4.43, p=0$). This suggest that females considered more that they participated in collaborative work than males.

24.4.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshops **AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1**, **AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1**, **AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1**, **AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1**, **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** and **AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors** are not considered for the male analysis. On the other hand, workshops **AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1**, **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3**, **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** and **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** are not considered for the female analysis. Figure 208 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3**, **AL-2-14-StCat** and **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3** have a decrement in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaires. On the other hand, workshops **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** and **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** have a significant increment in the indexes, which would make them interesting to study more in detail. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3** and **AL-2-13-StCat** have a decrement in the indexes. On the other hand, workshop **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** has a significant increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire, reaching 3 participants with an index of 5. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-11-VER3** has a decrement in the index. On the other hand, workshop **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** has a significant increment.

Unfortunately, there is not a clear pattern in the results to identify workshops for further analysis, which could help to identify good and bad practices during a workshop to motivate the collaborative work.

Table 37 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	11	7

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-12-VER4	8	9
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14
AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	0	24
AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	0	24
AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	0	25
AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	1	0
AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	7	4
AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	24
AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	25
AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	7	4
AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	7	3

Figure 205 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 206 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 207 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 208 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 209 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 210 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.4.7 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. In addition, the number of participants who answered that question was 79. There is a reduction in the post-questionnaire index in comparison to the pre-questionnaire index. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=4.37, SD=0.73$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.2, SD=0.66$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(148.42)=1.5, p=0.13$). Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.35, SD=0.66$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.19, SD=0.57$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(39)=1.27, p=0.21$). Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.39, SD=0.8$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.22, SD=0.75$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(35)=1.1, p=0.28$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(68.08)=-0.23, p=0.82$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(65.39)=-0.19, p=0.85$). This suggest that both genders connected robots with their personal interest.

24.4.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3** and **AL-2-12-VER4** have slightly lower indexes in post than in the pre-questionnaire. The other two workshops tend to have close indexes in both questionnaires. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Similar situation that occurred in the previous graph happens in this one. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-12-VER4** has indexes from both questionnaires closer.

Table 38 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	11	7
AL-2-12-VER4	8	9
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14

Figure 211 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 213 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 214 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 215 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 216 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.4.8 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=4.37, SD=0.73$) to ($M=4.08, SD=0.73$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(150)=2.46, p=0.02$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.35, SD=0.66$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.01, SD=0.68$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(39)=2.71, p=0.01$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Similar situation occurs, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.39, SD=0.8$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.16, SD=0.77$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(35)=1.45, p=0.16$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(68.08)=-0.23, p=0.82$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(70.18)=-0.89, p=0.38$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.4.8.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **AL-2-14-StCat** has slightly better indexes in the post than in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-13-StCat** has slightly better indexes in post than pre-questionnaire. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is not a particular interesting workshop. It could be interesting to analyse workshops AL-2-14-StCat and AL-2-13-StCat to see what was done different there.

Table 39 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in AL.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	11	7
AL-2-12-VER4	8	9
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14

Figure 218 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 219 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 220 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 221 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 222 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.4.9 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=4.18, SD=0.72$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.28, SD=0.94$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(435.27)=-11.65, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. The difference between pre ($M=3.12, SD=0.9$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.25, SD=0.7$) indexes is bigger. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(174)=-14.51, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.97, SD=0.77$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.76, SD=0.89$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(57)=-1.52, p=0.13$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(99.21)=-4.74, p=0$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(89.97)=2.44, p=0.02$), with females having higher indexes. This suggests that females considered that the problems were not difficult and that they worked harder than males.

24.4.9.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1 is not considered in the following discussion because it only has one participant. Workshops AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1, AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1, AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1, AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors and AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors are not considered in the discussion about males because they do not have male participants. Workshops AL-3-7-QSI-Class1 and AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2 are not considered in the discussions about females because they have a low number of female participants. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1, AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1, AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1, AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors, AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** and **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** have a significant difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. There is not workshops with a decrement in the indexes between pre and post-questionnaires. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3, AL-2-12-VER4, AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1, AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1, AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1, AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3** and **AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors** have a significant difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-11-VER3** and **AL-2-12-VER4** have a decrement in the index values from pre to post-questionnaire. Workshops **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** and **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** have increment in the index in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the pre-questionnaire.

It would be interesting to analyse workshops AL-2-11-VER3 and AL-2-12-VER4 because they have a different effects in males and females. Also, the workshops AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1, AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1 and

AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1 would be interesting due the positive difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires.

Table 40 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	11	7
AL-2-12-VER4	8	9
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14
AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	0	24
AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	0	24
AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	0	25
AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	1	0
AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	7	5
AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	24
AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	26
AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	7	4
AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	7	3

223 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 224 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 225 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 226 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 227 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 228 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.4.10 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.89, SD=0.54$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.56, SD=0.57$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(452.51)=-6.37, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.57, SD=0.56$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.92, SD=0.52$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(170)=-6.69, p=0$). Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.78, SD=0.59$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.51, SD=0.59$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(56)=-2.8, p=0.01$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(91.75)=0.73, p=0.47$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(87.08)=1.57, p=0.12$).

24.4.10.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1 is not considered in the following discussion because it only has one participant. Workshops AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1, AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1, AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1, AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors and AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors are not considered in the discussion about males because they do not have male participants. Workshops AL-3-7-QSI-Class1 and AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2 are not considered in the discussions about females because they have a low number of female participants. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3** is the only workshop with lower post-questionnaire indexes than in the pre-questionnaire. The remaining workshops have higher post-questionnaire indexes than in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-12-VER4** has a negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes, with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. **AL-2-14-StCat** has a negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes, with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire.

There is not a clear pattern to suggest specific workshops.

Table 41 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-11-VER3	11	7
AL-2-12-VER4	8	9
AL-2-13-StCat	8	10

Workshop	Male	Female
AL-2-14-StCat	9	14
AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	0	24
AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	0	23
AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	0	25
AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	1	0
AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	7	4
AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	23
AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	0	25
AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	7	4
AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	6	3

229 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 230 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 231 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 232 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 233 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 234 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.5 THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF CU

24.5.1 Introduction

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in **D6.3**. This report just take in consideration the data provided by CU, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 235 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants. OB2 only has females because the objective is meant to check if there is an improvement in girls. OB3 is embedded in OB1 because OB3 just consider improvement in females. There is not difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(273.4)=-1.09, p=0.28$) in **OB1**. Nevertheless, there is a difference between male indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(90)=-3.56, p=0$). There is a difference between a pre and post-questionnaire ($t(183.82)=-4.29, p=0$). In **OB4**, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire indexes, with a significant difference ($t(337.12)=4.19, p=0$). Similarly, **OB6** has higher indexes in pre than in post-questionnaire ($t(365.94)=4.54, p=0$). Likewise, there is difference between pre and post-questionnaire for males ($t(92)=1.71, p=0.09$) and females ($t(90)=6.32, p=0$). Pre-questionnaire indexes have a higher score than post-questionnaire indexes in **OB8**, with significant difference ($t(346.1)=2.73, p=0.01$). Also there is a difference between female indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(90)=3.79, p=0$). However, there is not difference between males index in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(90)=0.76, p=0.45$). In **OB9**, there is a difference between pre and post-questionnaire at general ($t(348.67)=-3.47, p=0$) and female ($t(92)=-6.71, p=0$) level. However, there is not difference between pre and post-questionnaire for males ($t(93)=-0.73, p=0.47$). In **OB10**, there is not a difference between pre and post-questionnaire index for males ($t(92)=0.05, p=0.96$) and in general ($t(365.93)=-1.27, p=0.21$). There is difference between female indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(90)=-2.54, p=0.01$), with better indexes in post-questionnaire. More information about each one of the indexes and objectives are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 235 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.5.2 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 show a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. Nevertheless, it is evident a difference between pre and post-questionnaire. A t-test with paired data was done on the difference of index between pre-questionnaire ($M=3.32$, $SD=0.67$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.44$, $SD=1.23$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(273.4)=-1.09$, $p=0.28$, $\alpha=0.05$), with a better result in the **post-questionnaire**. Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Several females had a higher index score in pre than post-questionnaire. Although the figure would suggest a negative impact, a paired t-test was done comparing females' pre ($M=3.23$, $SD=0.65$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.12$, $SD=1.23$). The results suggest that there is not difference between pre and post-questionnaires ($t(86)=-1.04$, $p=0.3$, $\alpha=0.05$). Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done between pre ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.68$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.73$, $SD=1.16$). The results suggest that there is a difference between them ($t(90)=-3.56$, $p=0$).

Additionally two t-test were done to verify if there is difference between males and females in pre and post-questionnaire index. The results from pre-questionnaire index suggests that **there is not difference between gender's index** ($t(176)=-1.75$, $p=0.08$, $\alpha=0.05$). This suggests that both genders have the same predisposition towards STEM. The second test is on post-questionnaire index. The results suggest that **there is a difference between genders** ($t(174.27)=-3.42$, $p=0$), with males having a higher indexes.

24.5.2.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender offered in CU. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. The workshop **633_PYD_1** has an outstanding increment in post-questionnaire index. On the other hand, **632_MIHS_1** and **632_MIHS_1b** present a reduction on the index score in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the respective pre-questionnaire index.

Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Once again, the workshop **633_PYD_1** has a considerable increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire. The workshop **632_MIHS_1b** has a considerable reduction in the post-questionnaire indexes compared the pre-questionnaire indexes. Similar cases are the workshops **631_MIHS_1**, **631_MIHS_1b**, **631_MIHS_2b**, **631_MIHS_3** and **632_MIHS_3**. This means that more than 50% of the workshops had a negative on females.

Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Once again, the workshop **633_PYD_1** has a considerable increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire. Workshops **632_MIHS_1** and **632_MIHS_1b** present a reduction on the post-questionnaire index. Although, the number of participants is low, it would be beneficial to study these two workshops because females showed a similar behaviour.

Table 42 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in CU.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	6
631_MIHS_1b	12	4
631_MIHS_2b	10	10
631_MIHS_3	11	12
631_MIHS_3b	9	11
632_MIHS_1	4	5
632_MIHS_1b	5	7
632_MIHS_2b	7	8
632_MIHS_3	7	10
632_MIHS_3b	8	9
633_PYD_1	6	5

Figure 236 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 237 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 238 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 239 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 240 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 241 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.5.3 OB2- Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.41, SD=0.82$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=2.9, SD=0.79$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between ($t(183.82)=-4.29, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.5.3.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. Workshop **631_MIHS_1b** are not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. There is a positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire index. However the indexes tend towards neutral (3). Workshops **632_MIHS_2b**, **632_MIHS_3**, **632_MIHS_3b** and **633_PYD_1** have a considerable difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. It would be recommendable to analyze them a bit more.

Table 43 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
631_MIHS_1	8
631_MIHS_1b	4
631_MIHS_2b	10
631_MIHS_3	14
631_MIHS_3b	11
632_MIHS_1	7
632_MIHS_1b	7
632_MIHS_2b	8
632_MIHS_3	10
632_MIHS_3b	9
633_PYD_1	5

Figure 242 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 243 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

24.5.4 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a small negative difference between indexes from pre ($M=3.6, SD=0.85$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.28, SD=0.61$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(337.12)=4.19, p=0$). It is interesting to notice that participants consider that they have high attitudes towards collaborative works but they do not consider that they did a lot of collaborative work during the activity. Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females' indexes in pre ($M=3.56, SD=0.84$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.32, SD=0.61$). There is a reduction in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(92)=2.63, p=0.01$), with a worse indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males' indexes in pre ($M=3.64, SD=0.86$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.24, SD=0.61$). The figure suggest that there is a reduction in indexes from pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(184.98)=0.99, p=0.32$). This suggest that the gender does not influence the perception of collaborative works, because in both genders the same pattern is found.

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(184.96)=-0.66, p=0.51$). Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. **The results suggest that there is difference between them** ($t(167.74)=3, p=0$), with females having higher indexes than males.

24.5.4.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshop **631_MIHS_1b** is not considered for further discussions about females, due the low number of them. On the other hand, workshop **632_MIHS_1** is not considered for discussions about males. Figure 208 show a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. In all workshops, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. Workshops **631_MIHS_2b** and **633_PYD_1** are the only workshops with higher index in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshops **632_MIHS_2b** and **632_MIHS_3b** have a considerable negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. The only workshop with a slightly better index in the post-questionnaire is **631_MIHS_1**.

In general, all workshops showed a tendency to have a lower index in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. It could be interesting to study if all the workshops had the same activity plan and determine possible factors for the results obtained in this index.

Table 44 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	8
631_MIHS_1b	12	4

	Workshop	Male	Female
	631_MIHS_2b	11	10
	631_MIHS_3	12	14
	631_MIHS_3b	9	11
	632_MIHS_1	4	7
	632_MIHS_1b	5	7
	632_MIHS_2b	7	8
	632_MIHS_3	8	10
	632_MIHS_3b	8	9
	633_PYD_1	6	5

Figure 244 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 245 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 246 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 247 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 248 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 249 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.5.5 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the pre-questionnaire indexes. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=3.93, SD=1.09$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.41, SD=1.1$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(365.94)=4.54, p=0$). Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.02, SD=1.05$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.2, SD=1.1$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(90)=6.32, p=0$). Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=3.84, SD=1.12$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.62, SD=1.06$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(92)=1.71, p=0.09$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(181.77)=1.15, p=0.25$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(181.32)=-2.67, p=0.01$). The results suggest that females did not consider that the activities are connected with their personal interest as much as males.

24.5.5.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **632_MIHS_1**, **632_MIHS_1b** and **632_MIHS_2b** are interesting because they are the only ones with the pre-questionnaire index that does not tend to 5. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop 631_MIHS_2b is the one with the highest difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **633_PYD_1** has slightly higher post-questionnaire indexes than pre-questionnaire indexes.

Table 45 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	8
631_MIHS_1b	12	4
631_MIHS_2b	11	10
631_MIHS_3	12	13
631_MIHS_3b	9	11
632_MIHS_1	4	6

	Workshop	Male	Female
632_MIHS_1b	5	7	
632_MIHS_2b	7	8	
632_MIHS_3	7	10	
632_MIHS_3b	8	9	
633_PYD_1	6	5	

Figure 250 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 251 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 252 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 253 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 254 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 255 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.5.6 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=3.95, SD=1.08$) to ($M=3.66, SD=0.87$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(346.1)=2.73, p=0.01$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.02, SD=1.05$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.56, SD=0.83$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(90)=3.79, p=0$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Similar situation occurs, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=3.87, SD=1.11$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.77, SD=0.9$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(90)=0.76, p=0.45$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(179.56)=0.96, p=0.34$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(178.87)=-1.67, p=0.1$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.5.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **632_MIHS_1** and **632_MIHS_2b** have a significant reduction in the indexes in the comparison compared to the ones in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **631_MIHS_2b** has low post-questionnaire index. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **632_MIHS_2b** has significant lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. It is suggested to study the workshop 632_MIHS_2b to see why the low indexes in the post-questionnaires for males and females.

Table 46 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	8
631_MIHS_1b	12	4
631_MIHS_2b	11	10
631_MIHS_3	12	13

	Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_3b	8	11	
632_MIHS_1	4	6	
632_MIHS_1b	4	7	
632_MIHS_2b	7	8	
632_MIHS_3	7	10	
632_MIHS_3b	8	9	
633_PYD_1	6	5	

Figure 256 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 257 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 258 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 259 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 260 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 261 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.5.7 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.32, SD=0.91$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=2.79, SD=0.8$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(348.67)=-3.47, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. The difference between pre ($M=2.79, SD=0.8$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.29, SD=0.65$) indexes is bigger than in the previous figure. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(92)=-6.71, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Indexes from pre ($M=3.32, SD=0.91$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.4, SD=0.72$) are almost similar. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(93)=-0.73, p=0.47$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(182.6)=-4.29, p=0$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(183.19)=-1.08, p=0.28$), with females having higher indexes. This suggest that males considered that they have more experience with technology than females, who after the workshop does not show a statistical difference in index in comparison to males.

24.5.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop 631_MIHS_1b is not considered for discussion about females due the low number of female participants. Workshop 632_MIHS_1 is not considered for discussion about males due the low number of female participants. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **631_MIHS_1** is the only one with post-questionnaire indexes lower than pre-questionnaire indexes. Workshop **632_MIHS_1** and **632_MIHS_1b** are the workshops with significant different between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **632_MIHS_1**, **632_MIHS_1b**, **632_MIHS_3** and **633_PYD_1** are the workshops with significant different between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **631_MIHS_1**, **632_MIHS_2b** and **632_MIHS_3b** have lower indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. Workshop **632_MIHS_1b** is the workshop with significant different between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire.

It is recommendable to study in more detail workshop 632_MIHS_1b because it has a significant increment in indexes from pre to post-questionnaire.

Table 47 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	8

	Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1b	12	4	
631_MIHS_2b	11	10	
631_MIHS_3	12	14	
631_MIHS_3b	9	11	
632_MIHS_1	4	7	
632_MIHS_1b	5	7	
632_MIHS_2b	7	8	
632_MIHS_3	8	10	
632_MIHS_3b	8	9	
633_PYD_1	6	5	

Figure 262 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 263 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 264 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 265 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 266 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 267 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.5.8 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a slightly increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.37, SD=0.55$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.3, SD=0.56$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(365.93)=-1.27, p=0.21$). Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.2, SD=0.51$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.35, SD=0.49$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(90)=-2.54, p=0.01$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly lower indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.4, SD=0.61$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.4, SD=0.59$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(92)=0.05, p=0.96$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(179.56)=-2.5, p=0.01$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(175.31)=-0.58, p=0.56$).

24.5.8.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop 631_MIHS_1b is not considered for discussion about females due the low number of female participants. Workshop 632_MIHS_1 is not considered for discussion about males due the low number of female participants. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **631_MIHS_1**, **631_MIHS_1b**, **632_MIHS_1b** and **632_MIHS_2b** have higher pre-questionnaire than post-questionnaire indexes. There is not a workshop with a considerable increment from pre to post-questionnaire indexes. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **631_MIHS_1** and **632_MIHS_3b** have higher pre-questionnaire than post-questionnaire indexes. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **631_MIHS_3b** is the only workshop with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. The rest of workshops have lower indexes in post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire.

It could be interesting to analyse all workshops with especial focus on soft-skills, with particular interest on 631_MIHS_1.

Table 48 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_1	12	8
631_MIHS_1b	12	4
631_MIHS_2b	11	10
631_MIHS_3	12	13

	Workshop	Male	Female
631_MIHS_3b	9	11	
632_MIHS_1	4	6	
632_MIHS_1b	5	7	
632_MIHS_2b	7	8	
632_MIHS_3	7	10	
632_MIHS_3b	8	9	
633_PYD_1	6	5	

Figure 268 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 269 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 270 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 271 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 272 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 273 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF ESI

24.6 INTRODUCTION

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in **D6.3**. This report just take in consideration the data provided by AL, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 274 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants. OB2 only has females because the objective is meant to check if there is an improvement in girls. OB3 is embedded in OB1 because OB3 just consider improvement in females. In **OB1**, there is a significant increment from pre to post-questionnaire indexes in general ($t(564.26)=-7.68, p=0$), female ($t(151)=-5.39, p=0$) and male ($t(171)=-9.12, p=0$) levels. Post-questionnaire indexes are higher than pre-questionnaire in **OB2**, with significant difference ($t(284.97)=-12.7, p=0$). There is difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes for males ($t(171)=-8.7, p=0$), females ($t(151)=-13.56, p=0$) and general ($t(640.32)=-12.29, p=0$) in **OB4**. There is not difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes for females ($t(14)=-1.5, p=0.16$) and in general ($t(103.72)=-1.89, p=0.06$) in **OB6**. Pre-questionnaire indexes are higher than post-questionnaire indexes in **OB8**. Females do not have difference in the indexes between pre and post-questionnaire ($t(14)=2, p=0.07$). There is a difference between pre and post-questionnaire for males ($t(171)=-5.01, p=0$), females ($t(151)=-8.9, p=0$) and in general ($t(559.24)=-9.69, p=0$) in **OB9**. Similarly, there is difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes for males ($t(171)=-8.42, p=0$), females ($t(151)=-9.73, p=0$) and general ($t(587.8)=-12.38, p=0$) in **OB10**. More information about each one of the indexes and objectives are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 274 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.6.1 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 show a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. There is an increment in the index from pre ($M=4.03, SD=0.55$) to post-questionnaire ($M=4.45, SD=0.83$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaires ($t(564.26)=-7.68, p=0$), with a higher index in the post-questionnaire. Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Several females had a higher index score in pre than post-questionnaire. The figure suggest an increment of the index in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done comparing females' pre ($M=3.99, SD=0.6$) and post-questionnaires ($M=4.32, SD=0.93$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(151)=-5.39, p=0$). Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done between pre ($M=4.06, SD=0.51$) and post-questionnaires ($M=4.57, SD=0.7$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(171)=-9.12, p=0$).

Additionally two t-test were done to verify if there is difference between males and females in pre and post-questionnaire index. The results suggest that **there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire** ($t(299.6)=-1.24, p=0.21$). This suggests that both genders have the same predisposition towards STEM. The second test is on post-questionnaire index. **The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the post-questionnaire** ($t(277.8)=-2.76, p=0.01$), with males having a higher index.

24.6.1.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender offered in ESI. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. All the workshops show an increment in the post-questionnaire indexes respect the pre-questionnaire indexes. Nevertheless, there are 6 workshops that show a significant increment. These workshops are **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3v**, **PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm** and **PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm**. Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-4e** and **PRW2-3-125-4g** have a slightly reduction on the post-questionnaire indexes. On the other hand, workshops **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3v**, **PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm** and **PRW2-3-Kuystendil** show a significant increment in the post-questionnaire indexes. Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Males in all workshops present an increment in the index. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g**, **PRW2-3-125-3v**, **PRW2-3-125-4a**, **PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm** and **PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm** have a significant increment in post-questionnaire index.

Table 49 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in ESI.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-3a	8	18
PRW2-3-125-3b	15	6
PRW2-3-125-3d	7	13
PRW2-3-125-3e	10	12
PRW2-3-125-3g	8	11
PRW2-3-125-3v	11	14
PRW2-3-125-4a	9	11
PRW2-3-125-4b	9	10
PRW2-3-125-4d	9	14
PRW2-3-125-4e	12	9
PRW2-3-125-4g	15	12
PRW2-3-125-4v	14	7
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 275 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 276 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 277 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 278 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 279 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 280 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.6.2 OB2 – Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=4.53, SD=0.51$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.66, SD=0.66$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(284.97)=-12.7, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.6.2.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. Workshop **PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm** is not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. There is a positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire index in all workshops. There is a big difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes in most of the workshops. It would be interesting to analyze if the activity plan was the same for all and if it was the same, then implement in other schools and countries to measure the impact.

Table 50 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
PRW2-3-125-3a	18
PRW2-3-125-3b	6
PRW2-3-125-3d	13
PRW2-3-125-3e	12
PRW2-3-125-3g	11
PRW2-3-125-3v	14
PRW2-3-125-4a	11
PRW2-3-125-4b	10
PRW2-3-125-4d	14
PRW2-3-125-4e	9
PRW2-3-125-4g	12
PRW2-3-125-4v	7
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	3

Workshop	Female
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	6

Figure 281 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 282 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

24.6.3 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a positive difference between indexes from pre (M=3.72,SD=0.72) and post-questionnaire (M=4.38,SD=0.65). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them (t(640.32)=-12.29,p=0). Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females’ indexes in pre (M=3.7,SD=0.72) and post-questionnaire (M=4.49,SD=0.59). There is an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** (t(151)=-13.56,p=0), with a better indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males’ indexes in pre (M=3.73,SD=0.71) and post-questionnaires (M=4.28,SD=0.69). The figure suggest that there is a difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** (t(171)=-8.7,p=0).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The result suggests that there is not difference between the indexes in the pre-questionnaire for males and females (t(315.91)=-0.35,p=0.73). Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. The results suggest that **there is difference between indexes from males and females** (t(321.8)=2.98,p=0). This suggest that females considered more that they participated in collaborative work than males.

24.6.3.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshops **AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1**, **AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1**, **AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1**, **AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1**, **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** and **AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors** are not considered for the male analysis. On the other hand, workshops **AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1**, **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3**, **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** and **AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2** are not considered for the female analysis. Figure 208 show a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3**, **AL-2-14-StCat** and **AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3** have a decrement in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaires. On the other hand, workshops **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** and **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** have a significant increment in the indexes, which would make them interesting to study more in detail. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. Workshops **AL-2-11-VER3** and **AL-2-13-StCat** have a decrement in the indexes. On the other hand, workshop **AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors** has a significant increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire, reaching 3 participants with an index of 5. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **AL-2-11-VER3** has a decrement in the index. On the other hand, workshop **AL-3-7-QSI-Class1** has a significant increment.

Unfortunately, there is not a clear pattern in the results to identify workshops for further analysis, which could help to identify good and bad practices during a workshop to motivate the collaborative work.

Table 51 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
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Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-3a	8	18
PRW2-3-125-3b	15	6
PRW2-3-125-3d	7	13
PRW2-3-125-3e	10	12
PRW2-3-125-3g	8	11
PRW2-3-125-3v	11	14
PRW2-3-125-4a	9	11
PRW2-3-125-4b	9	10
PRW2-3-125-4d	9	14
PRW2-3-125-4e	12	9
PRW2-3-125-4g	15	12
PRW2-3-125-4v	14	7
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 283 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 284 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 285 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 286 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

Figure 287 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 288 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.6.4 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. A majority of post-questionnaire indexes have a value between 4 and 5, which lead to increase the median. Similarly, the majority of participants selected agree or strongly agree in the pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=4.33, SD=0.71$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.54, SD=0.48$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(103.72)=-1.89, p=0.06$). Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, the majority of female participants selected agree or strongly agree in the pre-questionnaire ($M=4.27, SD=0.7$) and the majority of indexes are between 4 and 5 ($M=4.51, SD=0.48$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(14)=-1.5, p=0.16$). Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Similar situation to the previous images, with a slightly more participants with a 5 post-questionnaire index. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.36, SD=0.7$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.55, SD=0.48$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(35)=1.1, p=0.28$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire.

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(24.29)=-0.42, p=0.68$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(23.96)=-0.28, p=0.78$).

24.6.4.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is not a particular difference between each workshop and the analysis done in the previous section.

Table 52 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 289 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 290 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 291 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 292 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

Figure 293 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 294 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.6.5 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=4.33, SD=0.71$) to ($M=3.81, SD=0.81$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(115.97)=3.82, p=0$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.27, SD=0.7$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.76, SD=0.88$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(14)=2, p=0.07$). Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Similar situation occurs, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.36, SD=0.71$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.82, SD=0.79$). The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(44)=3.42, p=0$), with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire.

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(24.29)=-0.42, p=0.68$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(22.08)=-0.26, p=0.8$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.6.5.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRW2-3-Kuystendil** has considerable lower indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **PRW2-3Kuystendil** has considerable lower indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is not a particular workshop of interest.

Table 53 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 295 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 296 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 298 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 299 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 300 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.6.6 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=4.3, SD=0.67$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.65, SD=1.01$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(559.24)=-9.69, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.38, SD=1.03$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.32, SD=0.72$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(151)=-8.9, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=4.29, SD=0.62$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.89, SD=0.93$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(171)=-5.01, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(305.95)=-4.63, p=0$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(299.6)=0.44, p=0.66$). This suggests that females considered that the problems were not difficult and that they worked harder than males. This suggest that males considered that they have more experience with technology than females, who after the workshop does not show a statistical difference in index in comparison to males.

24.6.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm is not considered in the discussion of females due the low number of females in the workshop. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-4b** and **PRW2-3-125-4e** have a decrement on the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the pre-questionnaire indexes. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g** and **PRW2-3-125-3v** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-4a** and **PRW2-3-125-4e** have a decrement on the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the pre-questionnaire indexes. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g**, **PRW2-3-125-3v** and **PRW2-3-Kuystendil** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g**, **PRW2-3-125-3v** and **PRW2-3-Kuystendil** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Workshops **PRW2-3-125-4b** and **PRW2-3-125-4v** have a decrement on the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the pre-questionnaire indexes.

It is recommended to study in more detail workshops **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g** and **PRW2-3-125-3v** because participants scored higher indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire.

Table 54 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-3a	8	18
PRW2-3-125-3b	15	6
PRW2-3-125-3d	7	13
PRW2-3-125-3e	10	12
PRW2-3-125-3g	8	11
PRW2-3-125-3v	11	14
PRW2-3-125-4a	9	11
PRW2-3-125-4b	9	10
PRW2-3-125-4d	9	14
PRW2-3-125-4e	12	9
PRW2-3-125-4g	15	12
PRW2-3-125-4v	14	7
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 301 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 302 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 303 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 304 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 305 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 306 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.6.7 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=4.01, SD=0.67$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.44, SD=0.48$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(587.8)=-12.38, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.4, SD=0.47$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.05, SD=0.68$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(151)=-9.73, p=0$). Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.98, SD=0.66$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.48, SD=0.4$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(171)=-8.42, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(320)=-1.54, p=0.12$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(314.33)=0.99, p=0.32$).

24.6.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm is not considered in the discussion of females due the low number of females in the workshop. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g** and **PRW2-3-125-3v** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g** and **PRW2-3-125-3v** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Workshop **PRW2-3-Kuystendil** has a decrement on post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **PRW2-3-125-3a**, **PRW2-3-125-3b**, **PRW2-3-125-3d**, **PRW2-3-125-3e**, **PRW2-3-125-3g**, **PRW2-3-125-3v** and **PRW2-3-125-4e** are the workshops with a high increment of indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes.

It is suggested to study deeper workshops PRW2-3-125-3a, PRW2-3-125-3b, PRW2-3-125-3d, PRW2-3-125-3e, PRW2-3-125-3g and PRW2-3-125-3v because they have a significant increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes.

Table 55 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-3a	8	18

Workshop	Male	Female
PRW2-3-125-3b	15	6
PRW2-3-125-3d	7	13
PRW2-3-125-3e	10	12
PRW2-3-125-3g	8	11
PRW2-3-125-3v	11	14
PRW2-3-125-4a	9	11
PRW2-3-125-4b	9	10
PRW2-3-125-4d	9	14
PRW2-3-125-4e	12	9
PRW2-3-125-4g	15	12
PRW2-3-125-4v	14	7
PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	16	3
PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	17	6
PRW2-3-Kuystendil	12	6

Figure 307 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 308 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 309 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 310 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 311 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 312 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.7 THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF PRIA

24.7.1 Introduction

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. This report also includes information about number of participants per each partner, if they have programmed or created a robot before, among other things. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in D6.3. This report just take in consideration the data provided by PRIA, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 313 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants. The post-questionnaires indexes are higher ($t(379.05)=-9.22, p=0$) than in the prequestionnaire in **OB1**. The difference is also significant for males ($t(127)=-8.91, p=0$) and females ($t(93)=-6.88, p=0$). **OB2** has significant increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire ($t(147.78)=-9.94, p=0$). Likewise, there is a significant difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes ($t(399.09)=-7.39, p=0$), in **OB4** with higher indexes in post-questionnaire. However there is only difference between females indexes ($t(93)=-5.64, p=0$). There is not difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes In **OB6** for males ($t(81)=0.46, p=0.65$), females ($t(50)=-0.28, p=0.78$) or in general ($t(244.15)=0.21, p=0.84$). Pre-questionnaire indexes are higher than post-questionnaire indexes ($t(256.97)=2.37, p=0.02$) in **OB8**. However, there is not difference between pre and post-questionnaire index for either females ($t(50)=1.7, p=0.1$) or males ($t(81)=1.75, p=0.08$). Although there is difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes at general level ($t(387.4)=-6.79, p=0$), there is not difference for males ($t(129)=-1.16, p=0.25$). In **OB10**, there is a difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(444.24)=-9.24, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. More information about each one of the indexes and objectives are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 313 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.7.2 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 show a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. There is an increment on the indexes from pre ($M=3.66, SD=0.55$) to post-questionnaire ($M=4.29, SD=0.85$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(379.05)=-9.22, p=0$). Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Several females had a higher index score in pre than post-questionnaire. There is an increment in the index from pre ($M=3.67, SD=0.58$) to post-questionnaire ($M=4.35, SD=0.94$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that **there is difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes** ($t(93)=-6.88, p=0$). Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done between pre ($M=3.66, SD=0.53$) and post-questionnaires ($M=4.24, SD=0.78$). The results suggest that **there is difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes** ($t(127)=-8.91, p=0$).

Additionally two t-test were done to verify if there is difference between males and females in pre and post-questionnaire index. The results from pre-questionnaire index suggests that **there is not difference between gender's indexes** ($t(191.07)=0.24, p=0.81$). This suggests that both genders have the same predisposition towards STEM. The second test is on post-questionnaire index. The results suggest that **there is not difference between genders** ($t(177.57)=0.93, p=0.36$).

24.7.2.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender offered in PRIA. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** have only four male participants, **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB** have two and one female participants, respectively. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. All workshops have a positive increment in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaire. Workshops **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB**, **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG**, **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** and **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** have an outstanding increment. Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Excluding the workshops mentioned before, there is a decrement in the index of post-questionnaire in comparison to the ones of pre-questionnaire in the workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG**. On the other hand, there is significant increment in the workshops **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG**, **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA**, **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** and **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS**. Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Excluding the workshop mentioned before, there is a decrement in the index in the workshop **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA**. On the other hand, workshops **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB**, **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** and **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** have a significant increment in the post-questionnaire index. As a consequence, it is recommended to analyse workshops **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** and **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** because they have a significant increment in both genders. In the case of extreme results in females, it is recommendable to analyse the workshops **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG**, **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG**, **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA**, **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** and **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS**.

Table 56 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in PRIA.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	8	6
PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	9	15
PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	10	2
PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	11	8
PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	8	12
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9
PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13
PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 314 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 315 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 316 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 317 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 318 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 319 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.7.3 OB2 – Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=4.19, SD=0.51$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.13, SD=0.89$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(147.78)=-9.94, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.7.3.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB** are not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** and **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS** have a negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. On the other hand, workshops **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA**, **PRIA-3-A1-05-KL**, **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** and **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** have a high positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes.

Table 57 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	6
PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	15
PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	2
PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	8
PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	12
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	9
PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	7
PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	13
PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	15
PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	6

Figure 320 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 321 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

24.7.4 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a small positive difference between indexes from pre ($M=3.55, SD=0.88$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.08, SD=0.61$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(399.09)=-7.39, p=0$). Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females' indexes in pre ($M=3.59, SD=0.86$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.15, SD=0.56$). There is an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that *there is difference between them* ($t(93)=-5.64, p=0$), with a better indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males' indexes in pre ($M=3.52, SD=0.89$) and post-questionnaires ($M=4.02, SD=0.65$). The figure suggest that there is a small difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is not difference between them** ($t(129)=-5.36, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The result suggests that **there is not difference between the indexes in the pre-questionnaire for males and females** ($t(205.27)=0.64, p=0.52$). Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. The results suggest that **there is not difference between indexes from males and females** ($t(215.22)=1.58, p=0.12$). This suggest that there is not difference of gender in this index.

24.7.4.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB** are not considered in the discussion of females because they have a low number of female participants. On the other hand, workshop **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** is not considered on the male discussion. Figure 208 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA** have a significant increment of post-questionnaire indexes. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** has a reduction of the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison indexes in pre-questionnaire. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. Workshop **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV** has a significant increment in the female indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB**, **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** and **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** have a reduction in the index in the post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** has the biggest negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes.

It is suggested to analyse the workshop **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV** because in both genders the positive change of the index between pre and post-questionnaire. In addition, it would be interesting to study in more detail the workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG**, in which males' index in the post-questionnaire decrease dramatically.

Table 58 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	9	6

	Workshop	Male	Female
	PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	9	15
	PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	10	2
	PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	11	8
	PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	9	12
	PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
	PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9
	PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
	PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13
	PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
	PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 322 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 323 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 324 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 325 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 326 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 327 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.7.5 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. Most of the post-questionnaire indexes are between 4 and 5. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=4.16, SD=0.85$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.14, SD=0.64$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(244.15)=0.21, p=0.84$). Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure. A paired t-test between indexes in the pre ($M=4.18, SD=0.82$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.21, SD=0.68$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(50)=-0.28, p=0.78$). Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.15, SD=0.88$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.09, SD=0.61$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(81)=0.46, p=0.65$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(111.8)=0.2, p=0.84$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(97.48)=1.02, p=0.31$). This suggest that both genders connected robots with their personal interest.

24.7.5.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** shows a considerable difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** presents a significant reduction in the indexes from pre and post-questionnaires in comparison to the rest of the workshops. This would suggest that in this particular workshop females did not manage to connect robots with their personal interest. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Once again, **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** presents an interest situation but in this case is the difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaire.

Table 59 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9
PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13
PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 328 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 329 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 330 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 331 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 332 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 333 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.7.6 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=4.16, SD=0.85$) to ($M=3.93, SD=0.72$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(256.97)=2.37, p=0.02$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.18, SD=0.82$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.92, SD=0.71$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(50)=1.7, p=0.1$). Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Similar situation occurs, post-questionnaire indexes are lower than pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.15, SD=0.88$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.93, SD=0.73$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(81)=1.75, p=0.08$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(111.8)=0.2, p=0.84$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(107.77)=-0.09, p=0.93$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.7.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** has particular low indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** and **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** have low indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG** has particular low indexes in the post-questionnaire. It is suggested to see in more detail workshop **PRIA-3-A2-02-MG**, which has low indexes in the pre-questionnaire for both genders.

Table 60 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9
PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13

	Workshop	Male	Female
	PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
	PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 334 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 335 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 336 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 337 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 338 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 339 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.7.7 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.82, SD=0.79$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.17, SD=1.2$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(387.4)=-6.79, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=2.56, SD=1.02$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.9, SD=0.75$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(93)=-9.15, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is not difference between indexes in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.6, SD=1.13$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.76, SD=0.82$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(129)=-1.16, p=0.25$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(211.41)=-7.19, p=0$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(210.69)=1.32, p=0.19$). This suggests that females considered that the problems were not difficult and that they worked harder than males. This suggest that males considered that they have more experience with technology than females, who after the workshop does not show a statistical difference in index in comparison to males.

24.7.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A2-01-AB** are not considered for the female discussion because they have a low number of participants. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA** and **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS** have a decrement in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaires. Workshop **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA**, **PRIA-3-A1-05-KL**, **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** and **PRIA-3-A2-05-MA** have a significant improvement in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS** has a decrement in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaires. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA**, **PRIA-3-A1-05-KL** and **PRIA-3-A2-04-MA** have a significant improvement in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-01-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-03-VA**, **PRIA-3-A2-03-MG** and **PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS** have a decrement in the indexes from pre to post-questionnaires. Workshops **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA** and **PRIA-3-A1-05-KL** have a significant improvement in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes.

It is recommended to study in more detail the workshop done during ECER because it has a negative difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Also, workshop **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV**, **PRIA-3-A1-04-VA** and **PRIA-3-A1-05-KL** are also recommended to analyse because they have a high positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes.

Table 61 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	9	6
PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	9	15
PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	10	2
PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	11	8
PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	9	12
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9
PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13
PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 340 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 341 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 342 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 343 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 344 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 345 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.7.8 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.9, SD=0.55$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.4, SD=0.59$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(444.24)=-9.24, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.38, SD=0.57$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.98, SD=0.48$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(93)=-8.9, p=0$). Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.84, SD=0.6$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.41, SD=0.6$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(129)=-5.63, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(207.4)=-0.37, p=0.71$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(219.64)=1.96, p=0.05$).

24.7.8.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops PRIA-3-A1-03-VA and PRIA-3-A2-01-AB are not considered for the female discussion because they have a low number of participants. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. All workshops have an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. Workshop **PRIA-3-A1-01-VV** and **PRIA-3-A1-02-VV** are particular interesting because they have higher post-questionnaire index for both genders.

Table 62 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	9	6
PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	9	15
PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	10	2
PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	11	8
PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	9	12
PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	16	1
PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	10	9

	Workshop	Male	Female
	PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	8	7
	PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	6	13
	PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	4	15
	PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	38	6

Figure 346 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 347 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 348 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 349 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 350 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 351 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.8 THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF TU WIEN

24.8.1 Introduction

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. This report also includes information about number of participants per each partner, if they have programmed or created a robot before, among other things. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in **D6.3**. This report just take in consideration the data provided by TU Wien, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 352 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants. There is not difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(184.48)=-0.46, p=0.65$) in **OB1**. However, there is a difference in the indexes for males ($t(94)=-3.78, p=0$) and females ($t(91)=-2.2, p=0.03$) in pre and post-questionnaires. **OB2** has a significant difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes ($t(175.01)=-3.55, p=0$). There is difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire ($t(365.49)=-7.38, p=0$) in **OB4**. In **OB6** and **OB8** the pre-questionnaire indexes are higher than the post-questionnaire indexes. There is different between them in **OB6** ($t(118.02)=2.06, p=0.04$) but there is not in **OB8** ($t(115.36)=0.47, p=0.64$). In **OB9** and **OB10** the post-questionnaire indexes are higher than in the pre-questionnaire, with enough statistical evidence ($t(363.4)=-4.19, p=0$) and ($t(371.62)=-6.77, p=0$), respectively. More information about each one of the indexes and objectives are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 352 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.8.2 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 show a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. There is not a significant increment on the post-questionnaire index ($M=3.94, SD=1.01$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire index ($M=3.7, SD=0.71$). A paired t-test was done to verify if there is or not a difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(184.48)=-0.46, p=0.65$). Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a slightly increment in the post-questionnaire index ($M=3.86, SD=1.08$), respect the pre-questionnaire index ($M=3.68, SD=0.68$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(91)=-2.2, p=0.03$). Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is a slightly positive increment in the index from pre ($M=3.72, SD=0.74$) to post-questionnaire ($M=4.03, SD=0.93$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(94)=-3.78, p=0$).

Additionally two t-test were done to verify if there is difference between males and females in pre and post-questionnaire index. The results from pre-questionnaire index suggests that **there is not difference between gender's index** ($t(184.48)=-0.46, p=0.65$). This suggests that both genders have the same predisposition towards STEM. The second test is on post-questionnaire index. The results suggest that **there is not difference between genders** The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(179.22)=-1.13, p=0.26$).

24.8.2.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender offered in TU Wien. The **robotic club** includes a reduce number of participants, just two for each gender, as well the workshop **TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305** with only 4 male and 0 female participants. These workshops will be omitted in the following discussion. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. There is not workshops with significant difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. However, the **TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406** has a small negative effect on the post-questionnaire index. Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406** and **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410** have a negative impact on the post-questionnaire indexes. On the other hand, workshop **TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425** has a significant positive impact on the post-questionnaire index. Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. There is not a workshop with a significant difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes. However, the workshop **TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214** has a negative effect on the post-questionnaire index. As a consequence, it is recommended to analyse the following workshops **TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214**, **TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406** and **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410**.

Table 63 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in TU Wien.

Workshop	Male	Female
TU_RoboticClub_2018	2	2
TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	8	9
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7
TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	9	12
TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	11	12
TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	11	7
TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	9	15
TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	9	10
TUWien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 353 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 354 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 355 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 356 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 357 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 358 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.8.3 OB2 – Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.88, SD=0.69$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.48, SD=0.84$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(175.01)=-3.55, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.8.3.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. Workshop **TU_RoboticClub_2018** is not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. There is a positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire index in nine workshops. Workshop **TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406** has similar indexes in pre and post-questionnaires.

Table 64 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
TU_RoboticClub_2018	2
TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	9
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	7
TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	12
TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	12
TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	7
TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	15
TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	10
TUWien-ITA-2017	11

Figure 359 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 360 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

24.8.4 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a positive difference between indexes from pre (M=3.4,SD=0.75) and post-questionnaire (M=3.93,SD=0.64). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(365.49)=-7.38, p=0$). Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females' indexes in pre (M=3.47,SD=0.68) and post-questionnaire (M=4.02,SD=0.58). There is an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(91)=-7.36, p=0$), with a better indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males' indexes in pre (M=3.34,SD=0.81) and post-questionnaires (M=3.85,SD=0.69). The figure suggest that there is a small difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(95)=-5.39, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The result suggests that **there is not difference between the indexes in the pre-questionnaire for males and females** ($t(182.36)=1.17, p=0.24$). Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. The results suggest that **there is not difference between indexes from males and females** ($t(183.17)=1.86, p=0.07$).

24.8.4.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshops **TU_RoboticClub_2018** and **TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305** are not considered because they have a low number of participants from both genders. Figure 208 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. All workshops have a positive difference between pre to post-questionnaire. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. Workshops **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410**, **TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411**, **TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222** and **TUWien-ITA-2017** have a big difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425** has a big difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaire.

There is not a clear patter between all workshops. Nevertheless, it could be important to analyse new ways to involve more males in collaborative work.

Table 65 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
TU_RoboticClub_2018	2	2
TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	8	9

Workshop	Male	Female
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7
TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	10	12
TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	11	12
TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	11	7
TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	9	15
TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	9	10
TUWien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 361 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 362 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 363 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 364 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 365 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 366 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.8.5 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction in the post-questionnaire index in comparison to the pre-questionnaire index. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=3.92, SD=0.92$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.55, SD=1.05$). The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(118.02)=2.06, p=0.04$), with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=3.88, SD=1.09$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.48, SD=1.16$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(24)=2.23, p=0.04$), with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=3.94, SD=0.79$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.6, SD=0.97$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(35)=2.15, p=0.04$), with higher indexes in the pre-questionnaire.

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(40.93)=-0.25, p=0.8$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(45.79)=-0.44, p=0.66$). Although there is not difference between genders, the post-questionnaire indexes show that a significant number of participants did not find a connection but either a disconnection.

24.8.5.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **TUWien-ITA-2017** has higher indexes than the rest of the workshop. However, this workshop is especial because it was done in a different country, activity and in a rural school. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshop **TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411** has a big difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411** has a big difference between indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. It would be interesting to analyse deeper workshop **TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411** because both genders had a low index in the post-questionnaire in comparison to the pre-questionnaire.

Table 66 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7

Workshop	Male	Female
TUWien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 367 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 368 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 369 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 370 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

Figure 371 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 372 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.8.6 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=3.92, SD=0.92$) to ($M=3.85, SD=0.75$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(115.36)=0.47, p=0.64$). Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=3.88, SD=1.09$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.8, SD=0.84$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(24)=0.45, p=0.66$). Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Males have a similar indexes in pre and post-questionnaires. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=3.94, SD=0.79$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.88, SD=0.69$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(35)=0.41, p=0.69$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(40.93)=-0.25, p=0.8$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(44.62)=-0.39, p=0.7$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.8.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410** has higher indexes in post-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. There is nothing particular on it. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410** has higher indexes in post-questionnaire.

Table 67 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7
TUWien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 376 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 377 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 378 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.8.7 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.61, SD=0.8$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.23, SD=0.95$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(363.4)=-4.19, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.12, SD=0.97$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.51, SD=0.79$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(91)=-3.27, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.71, SD=0.79$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.34, SD=0.92$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(95)=-3.32, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(184.23)=-1.58, p=0.12$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(185.73)=-1.74, p=0.08$). This suggests that perception of both genders is the same.

24.8.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops TU_RoboticClub_2018 and TUV_050318_Workshop_20180305 are not considered in the discussion because they have a low number of participants. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **TUV_060418_Workshop_20180406** and **TUV_100418_Workshop_20180410** have a significant reduction in the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire. Workshops **TUV_140318_Workshop_20180314**, **TUV_250418_Workshop_20180425** and **TUVien-ITA-2017** have significant increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the ones in the pre-questionnaire. It is important to remember that workshop TUVien-ITA-2017 has a different activity plan and it was done in a rural school. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **TUV_060418_Workshop_20180406**, **TUV_110418_Workshop_20180411** and **TUV_220218_Workshop_20180222** have a significant reduction in the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire. Workshops **TUV_140318_Workshop_20180314**, **TUV_190318_Workshop_20180319**, **TUV_250418_Workshop_20180425** and **TUVien-ITA-2017** have significant increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the ones in the pre-questionnaire. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshops **TUV_060418_Workshop_20180406** and **TUV_100418_Workshop_20180410** have a significant reduction in the indexes in the post-questionnaire in comparison to pre-questionnaire. Workshops **TUV_140318_Workshop_20180314**, **TUV_250418_Workshop_20180425** and **TUVien-ITA-2017** have significant increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the ones in the pre-questionnaire.

It is suggested to analyse deeper workshops TUV_060418_Workshop_20180406, TUV_100418_Workshop_20180410, TUV_140318_Workshop_20180314 and TUV_250418_Workshop_20180425. The two workshops have a negative difference between pre and post-questionnaire indexes in both genders, so it would be interesting to get a better understanding on why was this. On the other hand, the last two workshop have a positive impact in both genders.

Table 68 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
TU_RoboticClub_2018	2	2
TUV_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUV_060418_Workshop_20180406	8	9
TUV_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUV_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7
TUV_140218_Workshop_20180214	10	12
TUV_140318_Workshop_20180314	11	12
TUV_190318_Workshop_20180319	11	7
TUV_220218_Workshop_20180222	9	15
TUV_250418_Workshop_20180425	9	10
TUVien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 379 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 381 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 382 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 383 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 384 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.8.8 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.72, SD=0.51$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.35, SD=0.53$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(371.62)=-6.77, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.32, SD=0.51$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.75, SD=0.53$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(90)=-6.57, p=0$). Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.69, SD=0.5$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.39, SD=0.55$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(95)=-4.17, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(184.85)=-0.89, p=0.37$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(182.36)=0.77, p=0.45$).

24.8.8.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops TU_RoboticClub_2018 and T UW_050318_Workshop_20180305 are not considered in the discussion because they have a low number of participants. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. All workshops have a higher indexes in the post-questionnaire than in the pre-questionnaire. Workshop **TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406** and **TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410** are particularly interesting due the huge increment. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222** has a negative difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires.

Table 69 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
TU_RoboticClub_2018	2	2
TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	4	0
TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	8	8
TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	8	7
TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	12	7
TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	10	12

Workshop	Male	Female
TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	11	12
TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	11	7
TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	9	15
TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	9	10
TUWien-ITA-2017	12	11

Figure 385 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 386 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 387 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 388 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 389 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 390 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.9 THIRD YEAR ANALYSIS OF UOA

24.9.1 Introduction

General information is presented in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, which describes how the data was prepared and how the index were calculated. Additionally, information about the frequency of answers for each question could be found in **Report-Y3.docx**. In addition, this report not provide analysis about the rationale behind the questions used during the third year, this information is reported in **D6.3**. This report just take in consideration the data provided by UoA, other partners' data is not considered. As a consequence, this report provides information as good as the data provided.

Figure 391 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants. More information about each one of the indexes per objective is provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 391 Indexes' score per objective in the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the average of all indexes and the lines the standard deviation. The general type is the average of all participants.

24.9.2 OB1 and OB3- Interest in STEM and Girl interest in STEM

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 197 show a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **post-questionnaire** is because all questions considered were **yes or no**. There is a considerable difference between pre ($M=3.78, SD=0.58$) and post-questionnaire

($M=4.22, SD=0.86$) indexes. A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(180.82)=-4.32, p=0$). Figure 198 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.74, SD=0.59$) and post-questionnaire index ($M=4.14, SD=0.93$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(40)=-4.3, p=0$), which suggest that there is not increment in the index. Figure 199 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There is a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done between pre ($M=3.41, SD=0.68$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.73, SD=1.16$). The results suggest that there is a difference between them ($t(90)=-3.56, p=0$).

Additionally two t-test were done to verify if there is difference between males and females in pre and post-questionnaire index. The results from pre-questionnaire index suggests that **there is not difference between gender's index** ($t(176)=-1.75, p=0.08, \alpha=0.05$). This suggests that both genders have the same predisposition towards STEM. The second test is on post-questionnaire index. The results suggest that **there is not difference between genders** ($t(77.75)=-0.78, p=0.44$).

24.9.2.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 35 presents the number of participants per gender in the each workshop. Workshops **UoA 431** and **UoA 436** are not considered in the discussion of males because they have a low number of male participants. Similarly, **workshpos UoA 434b, UoA 435, UoA 436** and **UoA 437** are not considered in the discussion of females because they have a low number of female participants. Figure 200 shows a boxplot with the index for the pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index score for each participants. All workshops have an increment of index from pre to post-questionnaire. Figure 201 shows a boxplot with female's index for pre and post-questionnaire. All the workshops have a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. Figure 202 shows a boxplot with male's index for pre and post-questionnaire. All the workshops have a positive increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire

Table 70 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in UoA.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 431	1	7
UoA 432	6	8
UoA 433	7	5
UoA 434a	7	7
UoA 434b	11	2
UoA 435	8	1
UoA 436	2	2
UoA 437	10	0
UoA 438	11	9

Figure 392 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 393 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 394 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 395 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 396 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 397 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.*

24.9.3 OB2 – Activities are appealing to Girls

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 203 shows a boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire. The clear levels in the pre-questionnaire is due the use of **yes or no** questions. The indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=4.44, SD=0.52$) are higher than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.63, SD=0.65$). A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(327.51)=-12.88, p=0$), which suggest that the activities were appealing despite their attitude towards computers and knowledge about robots.

24.9.3.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 36 reports the number of female participants per workshop. This table reports one less workshop than in Table 35 because participants from workshop **UoA 437** did not answer the questions used to calculate the index. Workshops **UoA 434b**, **UoA 435** and **UoA 436** are not considered in the remaining discussion due their low number of female participants.

Figure 204 shows a boxplot with females' index for pre and post-questionnaire per workshop. There is a positive difference between pre and post-questionnaire index in all workshops. There is outstanding improvement in workshops **UoA 431**, **UoA 433** and **UoA 438**.

Table 71 Number of female participants per workshop.

Workshop	Female
UoA 431	7
UoA 432	8
UoA 433	5
UoA 434a	7
UoA 434b	2
UoA 435	1
UoA 436	2
UoA 438	9

Figure 398 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..* The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 399 Boxplot of the females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

24.9.4 OB4 – Participants participated in Collaborative Work

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 205 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is a small positive difference between indexes from pre ($M=3.61, SD=0.8$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.88, SD=0.71$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(205.03)=-2.53, p=0.01$). Figure 206 shows a boxplot for females' indexes in pre ($M=3.87, SD=0.78$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.1, SD=0.58$). There is an increment in the index from pre to post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify this. The results suggest **that there is difference between them** ($t(40)=-2.59, p=0.01$), with a better indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 207 shows a boxplot for males' indexes in pre ($M=3.45, SD=0.78$) and post-questionnaires ($M=3.73, SD=0.75$). The figure suggest that there is a small difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaires. To check this, a paired t-test was done. The results suggest that **there is difference between them** ($t(63)=-2.43, p=0.02$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The result suggests that there is a difference between the indexes in the pre-questionnaire for males and females ($t(85.73)=2.7, p=0.01$), with **females having more attitude to work in teams than males**. Similarly, a t-test was done on the post-questionnaire. The results suggest that **there is difference between indexes from males and females** ($t(99.36)=2.86, p=0.01$). This suggest that females considered more that they participated in collaborative work than males.

24.9.4.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 37 reports the number of female and male participants per workshop. Workshops **UoA 431** and **UoA 436** will not be included in the discussion about males because those workshops have a low number of male participants. On the other hand, Workshop **UoA 434b**, **UoA 435**, **UoA 436** and **UoA 437** are not considered in the discussion about females. Figure 208 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop UoA 433 is the only one with a negative difference between indexes in the pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 209 shows boxplots for indexes of females in each workshops. There is not workshops with negative difference but either workshops with significant difference between pre and post-indexes. Figure 210 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is not workshops with negative difference but either workshops with significant difference between pre and post-indexes.

There are not workshops with particular situations that would be interesting to have a further analysis.

Table 72 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 431	1	7
UoA 432	6	8

	Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 433	8	5	
UoA 434a	7	7	
UoA 434b	11	2	
UoA 435	8	1	
UoA 436	2	2	
UoA 437	10	0	
UoA 438	11	9	

Figure 400 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 401 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 402 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 403 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 404 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 405 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.9.5 OB6 – The activities allowed learners to connect robots to their personal interest

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. Figure 211 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the pre-questionnaire indexes. A paired t-test was done to verify the difference between indexes in the pre ($M=4.27, SD=0.83$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.27, SD=0.69$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(133.36)=-0.02, p=0.98$). Figure 212 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.39, SD=0.72$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.32, SD=0.55$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(22)=0.5, p=0.62$). Figure 213 presents a boxplot with the index of males. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.21, SD=0.88$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.25, SD=0.75$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(46)=-0.27, p=0.79$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(52.52)=0.9, p=0.37$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(57.51)=0.43, p=0.67$). This suggest that both genders connected robots with their personal interest.

24.9.5.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 38 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **UoA 433**, **UoA 435** and **UoA 436** are not considered in the discussion. Figure 214 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 215 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Figure 216 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is nothing particular interesting in any workshop.

Table 73 Number of participants per gender in the workshops.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 433	4	2
UoA 434a	7	7
UoA 434b	11	2
UoA 435	2	1
UoA 436	2	2
UoA 437	10	0
UoA 438	11	9

Figure 406 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 408 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 409 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 410 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 411 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for *Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.* per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.9.6 OB8 – Children identified and defined problems that influence their lives

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 217 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. The clear levels in the **pre-questionnaire** is because it was used only one question. There is a reduction of the indexes from pre ($M=4.27, SD=0.83$) to ($M=4.15, SD=0.58$). A paired t-test was done to check if there is a difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(123.27)=0.98, p=0.33$). Figure 218 presents a boxplot with the index of females. Similar to the previous figure, there is a decrement on the index values between pre ($M=4.39, SD=0.72$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4, SD=0.55$). A paired t-test was done to verify this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(22)=2.15, p=0.04$), with lower indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 219 presents a boxplot with the index of males. Post-questionnaire indexes are slightly lower than pre-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes in pre ($M=4.21, SD=0.88$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.23, SD=0.59$). The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(46)=-0.11, p=0.91$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(52.52)=0.9, p=0.37$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(46.36)=-1.59, p=0.12$). This suggest that both genders identified problems that could influence their lives.

24.9.6.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 39 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshops **UoA 433**, **UoA 435** and **UoA 436** are not considered due the low number of participants. Figure 220 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 221 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Figure 222 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. There is not any particular case to mention.

Table 74 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered in AL.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 433	4	2
UoA 434a	7	7
UoA 434b	11	2
UoA 435	2	1
UoA 436	2	2
UoA 437	10	0

	Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 438	11	9	

Figure 412 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 413 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 415 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 416 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 417 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.9.7 OB9 – Children were equipped with the necessary skills to solve the problems

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 223 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.77, SD=0.64$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.59, SD=0.94$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(559.24)=-9.69, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 224 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.21, SD=0.94$) and post-questionnaire ($M=3.88, SD=0.59$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(40)=-4.18, p=0$). Figure 225 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are slightly lower indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.83, SD=0.87$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.69, SD=0.67$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is not difference between them ($t(63)=0.97, p=0.33$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(80.53)=-3.35, p=0$), with males having higher indexes. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(93.61)=1.5, p=0.14$). This suggests that females considered that the problems were not difficult and that they worked harder than males. This suggest that males considered that they have more experience with technology than females, who after the workshop does not show a statistical difference in index in comparison to males.

24.9.7.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 40 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop UoA 436 is not considered on the discussion because it has a low number of participants. Workshop UoA 431 is not considered in the male discussion for the reason mentioned previously. Workshops UoA 434b, UoA 435 and UoA 437 are not considered in the female discussion for the same reason. Figure 226 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop **UoA 434b** and **UoA 435** have a reduction on post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the ones in the pre-questionnaire. Workshops **UoA 431** and **UoA 438** have an increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 227 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Workshops **UoA 431** and **UoA 433** have an increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes. Figure 228 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop **UoA 434b**, **UoA 435** and **UoA 437** have a reduction on post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to the ones in the pre-questionnaire. Workshop **UoA 435** has an increment in the post-questionnaire indexes in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes.

There is not a clear pattern to suggest a specific workshop to analyse. It is advice to verify if all the workshops had the same activity plan or not.

Table 75 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 431	1	7
UoA 432	6	8
UoA 433	8	5
UoA 434a	7	7
UoA 434b	11	2
UoA 435	8	1
UoA 436	2	2
UoA 437	10	0
UoA 438	11	9

Figure 418 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 419 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 420 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

*Figure 421 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants*

Figure 422 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 423 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

24.9.8 OB10 – Participants Developed Soft-Skills

The calculation of the index is explained in the file **GeneralInformation.docx**, for further information please refer to it. 229 shows a boxplot of the index for pre and post-questionnaire. The points represent the index for each one of the participants. There is increment in the post-questionnaire indexes ($M=4.02, SD=0.5$) in comparison to pre-questionnaire indexes ($M=3.58, SD=0.49$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(205.85)=-6.25, p=0$), with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. Figure 230 presents a boxplot with the index of females. There is a difference between pre ($M=3.67, SD=0.47$) and post-questionnaire ($M=4.12, SD=0.48$) indexes, with higher indexes in the post-questionnaire. A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(39)=-4.69, p=0$). Figure 231 presents a boxplot with the index of males. There are higher indexes in the post-questionnaire ($M=3.95, SD=0.51$) than in the pre-questionnaire ($M=3.53, SD=0.5$). A paired t-test was done to check this difference. The results suggest that there is difference between them ($t(63)=-5.22, p=0$).

Additionally, a t-test was done to verify if there is any difference between indexes of males and females in the pre and post-questionnaires. The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the pre-questionnaire ($t(86.27)=1.53, p=0.13$). The results suggest that there is not difference between genders in the post-questionnaire ($t(87.09)=1.64, p=0.1$).

24.9.8.1 WORKSHOP LEVEL

This subsection is done to inform further studies on the data collected from this partner. As a consequence, the index is presented for each workshop. Table 41 presents the workshops and number of participants per workshop who answered questions in pre and post-questionnaire. Workshop UoA 436 is not considered on the discussion because it has a low number of participants. Workshop UoA 431 is not considered in the male discussion for the reason mentioned previously. Workshops UoA 434b, UoA 435 and UoA 437 are not considered in the female discussion for the same reason. Figure 232 shows a boxplot for each workshop and indexes in pre and post-questionnaire. Figure 233 shows boxplots for indexes of females each workshop. Figure 234 shows boxplots for indexes of males each workshop. Workshop UoA 433 is the only one with a decrement of the indexes between pre and post-questionnaire. The rest of the workshops have increments.

Table 76 Number of participants per gender in the workshops offered.

Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 431	1	7
UoA 432	6	7
UoA 433	8	5
UoA 434a	7	7
UoA 434b	11	2
UoA 435	8	1

	Workshop	Male	Female
UoA 436	2	2	
UoA 437	10	0	
UoA 438	11	9	

Figure 424 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 426 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here..** The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 427 Boxplot of the index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants

Figure 428 Boxplot of females' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for **Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here.** per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participants.

Figure 429 Boxplot of males' index in the pre and post-questionnaire for Error! Use the Home tab to apply Überschrift 1 to the text that you want to appear here. per workshop. The points represent the index for each one of the participant

25 APPENDIX Q: ECER 3 YEARS QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS

25.1 ECER OVERVIEW

This report presents the results of the pre-competition and post-competition questionnaires completed by the Austrian participants at each of the three ECER's organised in the ER4STEM project.

Although ECER saw participants from a number of countries, only Austrian participants filled in the computerised questionnaire. In Year 1, 64 students completed the pre-ECER questionnaire and 49 complete the post-ECER questionnaire. In Year 2, 57 students completed the pre-ECER questionnaire and 27 complete the post-ECER questionnaire. In Year 3, 62 students completed the pre-ECER questionnaire and 61 complete the post-ECER questionnaire. These numbers are also presented in Table 77. In each year, fewer students completed the post-ECER questionnaire, most notably in Year 2, in which less than half of the participants completed the questionnaire, meaning that any findings from the post-ECER questionnaire in Year 2 should be interpreted with the knowledge that the data may not be accurate. Students did not necessarily answer all questions and so any calculations are based on the total number of respondents for that individual question.

Table 77. Number of ECER participants and questionnaire respondents

ECER	Total Number of Participants	Number of Austrian Participants completing Pre-ECER Questionnaire	Number of Austrian Participants completing Post-ECER Questionnaire
2016	180	64	49
2017	200	57	27
2018	130	62	61

Overall, it is found that the results of the pre-ECER questionnaire largely follow expected trends for the type of students who attend robotics competition. The post-ECER questionnaire results mostly show the ECER in positive light, with self-reported development of skills, overall enjoyment and plenty of constructive feedback. A comparison of girls' responses and boys' responses showed no notable difference between the genders.

25.1.1 Demographic of Participants

This section presents the demographics of the Austrian ECER participants across the three years. This includes the participant's ages and the split of genders in the participants, as well as finally presenting the number of returning participants in the second and third year who completed the questionnaires.

25.1.1.1 AGE

The ages of the participants are shown in Figure 430 and ranged between 13 and 19, with the largest range of ages seen in the third year. The most common ages in the first year is 16 and 17, in the second year is 16 and in the third year is 17. Overall, each year saw a bell-shaped distribution of ages, with the youngest and oldest participants being in the minority.

Figure 430. Ages of ECER participants shown as a percentage of students

25.1.1.2 GENDER

The proportion of male and female students at each of the three competitions is shown in Figure 431. It can be seen that in each year, males predominantly attend the competition, with less than one in five students being female. It can also be seen that the percentage of female students has reduced each year, although accuracy of this statement may be affected by how many students overall completed the questionnaires.

Figure 431. Proportion of male and female participants

25.1.1.3 RETURNING PARTICIPANTS

A number of Austrian students returned to the conference for a second or third time, with; 22 students attending in Year 1 and returning in Year 2; 6 of these students also attending in Year 3; and 12 further students attending in Year 3 after having first attended in the second year. Finally, 5 students returned in Year 2 who hadn't filled in a questionnaire in the first year (so either attended a different ER4STEM workshop or attended ECER but didn't complete the questionnaire) and 3 of these returned again in the third year. These returning students are represented visually in Figure 432.

Figure 432. Visual representation of returning Austrian students to ECER from questionnaire data

25.1.2 Pre-ECER Questionnaire

This section explores the questions from the pre-questionnaires in each year of the competition, which consisted of an open question regarding participants' future job aspirations, and a set of Likert-scale questions concerning participant's attitudes and opinions. Generally, the results are unsurprising considering the cohort of respondents.

25.1.2.1 WHEN YOU FINISH SCHOOL, WHAT JOB WOULD YOU LIKE TO DO?

Students were asked in both the pre-ECER and post-ECER questionnaire what job they would like to do when they finished school. In this section, the pre-ECER answers are presented. The total number of codes will not equal N, as some students listed more than one job.

As is shown in Table 78, a large number of the students in each year wanted to work in programming, software development, IT and computer science. Furthermore, almost all students stated STEM-related jobs, and most of these were in the technology or engineering sectors. This is not a surprising result when considering that these students have chosen to take part in a five-day robotics competition and so are likely to have a strong interest in these areas. Perhaps more interestingly though, very few students referred to specifically robotics. The majority instead referred to jobs that can relate to aspects of robotics (programming, engineering, robotics applications). Those who didn't generally referred to business, biosciences or research.

Table 78. Coding of what jobs ECER participants wanted to do in the future for each year (pre-ECER questionnaire data)

Year 1 (N=64)		Year 2 (N=57)		Year 3 (N=62)	
Job	No. of Students	Job	No. of Students	Job	No. of Students
Software Developer	13	Programmer	11	Programmer	16
Programmer	12	Software Developer	7	IT	10
IT	6	IT	3	Software Developer	8
Computer Science	4	AI	2	Computer Science	3
Automation Technician	2	Biotechnology	2	Game Design/Development	3
Bioinformatics	2	Computer Science	2	Robotics	2
Game Design/Development	2	Game Design/Development	2	Automation Technician	1
Web Developer	2	Research	2	Biochemist	1
Aerospace Engineer	1	Bioinformatics	1	CEO	1
App Developer	1	CEO	1	Doctor	1
AI	1	Engineer	1	Electronics Engineer	1
Electronics	1	Entrepreneur	1	Mechatronics Engineering	1

Founding a company	1	Pilot	1	Pilot	1
Physicist	1	Robotics	1	Security Manager	1
Project Manager	1	Web Developer	1	Teacher	1
Research and Development	1			Web Developer	1
Statistician	1				
Surgeon	1				
Don't know	10	Don't know	12	Don't know	2
No Answer	5	No Answer	7	No Answer	8

25.1.2.2 LIKERT-SCALE QUESTIONS

The pre-ECER questionnaires asked a number of questions that were presented as a Likert scale, where students stated how much they disagreed (1=strongly disagree) or agreed (5=strongly agreed) with each statement. The answers of these questions are presented firstly in Table 79, which presents the mean average, the mode and the range for each year. Figure 433, Figure 434 and Figure 435 present a breakdown of the proportion of answers for each question, for Years 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

Unsurprisingly, as they are attending a robotics competition, the participants reported to mostly enjoy using computers, working in teams and solving difficult problems. Whilst the question 'I need help solving problems' has an average of between 2 and 3, looking at the graphs, it can be seen that the majority of students disagreed with this statement, showing that they are self-confident. This self-confidence is further evidenced through their agreement with the statement 'I know a lot about robots'. The mode of each year to the question 'I prefer tasks that only have one correct answer' was 3, or 'Neither Agree nor Disagree'. This mode could be interpreted in a number of ways, as it may mean that students are uncertain as to their answer, or that their answer depends on the problem in hand. Finally, although it may be a stereotype for students who are interested in robotics to enjoy all STEM subjects, the ranges of questions 4) and 5) show that this was not the case for all participants.

Table 79. Results of pre-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions for each year (Agree, Neither, Disagree)

Question	Mean			Mode			Range		
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3
1) I like using computers	4.88	4.75	4.92	5	5	5	4-5	3-5	1-5
2) I know a lot about robots	3.97	3.91	4.19	4	4	4	2-5	3-5	3-5
3) I learn best with other people	3.29	3.41	3.63	3	4	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
4) I like science	3.71	3.73	4.08	4	5	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
5) I like maths	3.80	4.00	4.15	4	4	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
6) I like working on my own	3.43	3.28	3.65	3	4	4	2-5	2-5	2-5

7) I like working in teams	3.92	3.82	3.95	4	4	4	2-5	2-5	2-5
8) I like trying to solve difficult problems	4.23	4.05	4.37	4	5	5	2-5	2-5	3-5
9) I need help solving problems	2.78	2.64	2.85	3	3	3	1-5	1-5	1-5
10) I am good at solving problems	4.08	3.98	4.19	4	4	4	3-5	2-5	3-5
11) I want to understand more about mechanical things	3.69	3.75	4.05	4	4	5	1-5	1-5	2-5
12) I want to solve problems that can help people	4.06	3.91	4.15	4	4	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
13) I prefer tasks that only have one correct answer	2.94	2.84	3.08	3	3	3	1-5	1-5	1-5
14) I like to keep working on a project until it is perfect	4.14	3.91	4.18	4	4	4	2-5	2-5	2-5
15) I like it when I can solve problems quickly	4.15	4.11	3.98	4	4	4	1-5	2-5	1-5
16) I like learning about how things work	4.52	4.43	4.52	5	5	5	3-5	3-5	3-5
17) I enjoy participating in competitions	4.08	4.04	4.04	4	5	4	1-5	2-5	2-5

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Figure 433. Breakdown of answers for each of the pre-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year 1

Figure 434. Breakdown of answers for each of the pre-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year 2

Figure 435. Breakdown of answers for each of the pre-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year 3

25.1.3 Post-ECER Questionnaire

This section explores the questions from the post-questionnaires in each year of the competition. The section follows the structure of the questionnaire, which consisted of; a set of Likert-scale questions regarding participants' experience of the competition; questions concerning the student presentations and what participants learnt from them; open questions regarding what students learnt overall from the competition; and finally an out-of-5 star rating for the competition and participants reasoning for their rating. Overall, there is little variation between the ECER year's, with generally positive feedback and some constructive comments.

25.1.3.1 LIKERT-SCALE QUESTIONS

The post-ECER questionnaires asked a number of questions that were presented as a Likert scale, where students stated how much they disagreed (1=strongly disagree) or agreed (5=strongly agreed) with each statement. The answers of these questions are presented firstly in Table 80, which presents the mean average, the mode and the range for each year. Figure 436, Figure 437 and Figure 438 present a breakdown of the proportion of answers for each question, for Years 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

It can be seen that generally participants had a positive experience of the problems, the robots and teamwork. The concept of the problems being both difficult and fun relates back to the concept of 'hard-fun' and relates to the pre-questionnaire answers in 25.1.2.2 of the students enjoying difficult problems. Also shown in that section was the students' self-confidence, which is again portrayed in the breakdown of question 5), where a number of students state that they did not find working with robots difficult. Regarding teamwork, a range of answers were given for how difficult students found it, which may relate to the amount of experience the participants had with working in a team, especially when considering their range of ages. A range of answers was also given to the question 'I worked on my own'. This range makes sense when considering that in a functional team, some members will spend a portion of their time working individually on delegated tasks – an approach that was also noted in the observational data. The participants appear to have a respect for their team, mostly disagreeing to the statement 'I did most of the work'. The participants disagreed with the statement 'I gave up too quickly', implying that students developed resilience and perseverance. Finally, ECER appears to develop a good community spirit between the teams, with participants agreeing that they like sharing their ideas, and that they watched and learnt from other teams. It can be noted that the decrease in the number of participants that agreed that they had watched and learnt from other teams in the second ECER year correlates to having fewer test tables in that competition (although there is no firm evidence to prove causation).

Table 80. Results of post-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions for each year (Agree, Neither, Disagree)

Questions	Mean			Mode			Range		
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3
1) The problems we had to solve were: - Interesting	4.06	4.28	4.05	4	4	4	2-5	3-5	2-5
2) The problems we had to solve were: - Difficult	3.66	3.84	3.87	4	4	4	2-5	2-5	2-5
3) The problems we had to solve were: - Fun	3.62	3.76	3.59	4	3	4	1-5	2-5	1-5
4) Working with robots was: - Interesting	4.44	4.54	4.37	5	5	5	1-5	3-5	2-5
5) Working with robots was: - Difficult	3.42	3.50	3.55	3	4	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
6) Working with robots was: - Fun	3.96	4.12	4.15	4	4	4	1-5	3-5	1-5
7) Working in a team was: - Interesting	4.06	4.12	4.03	4	4	4	3-5	2-5	1-5
8) Working in a team was: - Difficult	3.31	3.15	3.62	3	2	4	1-5	1-5	1-5
9) Working in a team was: - Fun	4.10	4.35	3.98	5	5	5	1-5	1-5	1-5
10) I identified a problem to solve	4.38	4.31	4.19	5	4	5	3-5	3-5	2-5
11) I worked on something that I was interested in	4.31	4.31	4.19	4	4	5	3-5	3-5	2-5
12) I tried to solve an important problem	4.25	4.11	4.08	5	5	5	2-5	1-5	1-5
13) I worked as part of a team	4.34	4.31	4.12	5	4	5	1-5	3-5	1-5
14) I worked on my own	2.91	2.69	2.97	3	2	3	1-5	1-5	1-5
15) I helped design a robot	3.85	3.85	3.64	5	5	4	1-5	1-5	1-5

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Questions	Mean			Mode			Range		
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3
16) I helped create a robot	4.02	3.65	3.75	5	4	5	1-5	1-5	1-5
17) I helped programme a robot	4.25	3.81	4.05	5	5	5	2-5	1-5	1-5
18) I was able to choose what I wanted to do	4.17	4.08	4.00	5	4	4	2-5	3-5	1-5
19) I feel that other people did not listen to me	2.71	2.35	2.78	3	2	2	1-5	1-5	1-5
20) I did most of the work	2.83	2.77	2.78	3	2	3	1-5	1-5	1-5
21) I was encouraged by my team	3.67	3.60	3.54	3	4	4	2-5	1-5	1-5
22) I gave up too quickly	1.98	2.27	2.24	2	2	1	1-5	1-5	1-5
23) I worked hard	3.94	4.15	3.95	4	5	5	2-5	2-5	1-5
24) I was bored	2.48	2.46	2.71	3	2	2	1-5	1-5	1-5
25) I helped someone	4.17	4.00	4.22	4	4	4	3-5	1-5	1-5
26) I liked sharing what I had done with other people	4.15	4.15	3.88	4	4	4	2-5	3-5	1-5
27) I enjoyed watching other teams	4.29	4.08	4.21	5	4	5	3-5	3-5	1-5
28) I learned from other teams	4.13	3.73	4.05	4	4	5	1-5	1-5	1-5

Figure 436. Breakdown of answers for each of the post-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year 1

Figure 437. Breakdown of answers for each of the post-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year 2

Figure 438. Breakdown of answers for each of the post-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions in Year

25.1.3.2 STUDENT PRESENTATIONS

The post-ECER questionnaire had a section dedicated to questions regarding the student presentations. In the first year, 8 students who answered the questionnaire had presented at the conference, in the second year 4 students and in the third year 11 students. The majority of students stated that they had watched a presentation (94%, 96% and 98% of respondents in respective years).

Students were also asked 'What did you learn from the presentations?' which was answered by both those who presented and those who watched presentations. These answers are presented in Table 81, where it can be seen that most respondents referred to the content of the presentations – through the codes 'Relating to Hardware or Software' or 'Real-life Problems'. However, a number of skills and greater self-belief, such as 'Presenting Skills' and 'Confidence', were also mentioned by both those who had presented and those who had watched. It should also be noted that a large number of respondents did not answer the question.

Table 81. Coding of respondents answers to the question 'What did you learn from the presentations?'

Year 1 (N=49)		Year 2 (N=27)		Year 3 (N=61)	
Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students
Relating to Hardware or Software	11	Lots	6	Relating to Hardware or Software	10
Experience	3	Real Life Problems	5	Real life problem	9
Lots	3	Relating to Hardware or Software	4	Presenting skills	4
Real Life Problem	3	Presenting skills	4	Community Spirit	2
Differences in ability between teams	2	Interesting	2	Lots	2
English Language	2	Negative	2	Own Ability	1
Nerves	2	Boring	1	Boring	1
Perseverance	2	Perseverance	1	English Language	1
Presenting skills	2			Interesting	1
Own Abilities	2			Negative	1
Community Spirit	1				
Confidence	1				
Interesting	1				
Other Perspectives	1				

Nothing	2	Nothing	1	Nothing	2
No Answer	12	No Answer	8	No Answer	33

25.1.3.3 WHAT DID PARTICIPANTS LEARN?

This section explores the responses to three open questions about what the students had learnt; ‘What have you learned about yourself’; ‘What have you learned about working with other people’ and; ‘What have you learned about working with robots’. Answers to these questions were coded and are presented by each year.

25.1.3.3.1 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT YOURSELF?

Answers to the question ‘What have you learned about yourself?’ are presented in Table 82. It can be seen that the first year saw a common theme of answers relating to teamwork, where as the third year saw a wider range of answers. Although the question asks about the students themselves, many of the answers relate to interpersonal skills as well as intrarelational skills. Many respondents gave no answer, perhaps due to the open nature of the question making it seem more time consuming (a theme continued in the other open questions), and in the third year, 8 respondents claimed to have learnt nothing about themselves.

Table 82. Coding of respondents answers to the question ‘What have you learned about yourself?’

Year 1 (N=49)		Year 2 (N=27)		Year 3 (N=61)	
Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students
Teamwork	11	Perseverance	3	Lack of sleep/Tiring	5
Perseverance	3	Sleep	3	Control emotions	4
Robotics	3	Teamwork	3	Time management	3
Ambitious	2	Calm	1	Working under pressure	3
Hard work	2	Communication	1	Language	2
Leadership	2	Easily annoyed	1	Sense of community	2
Problem Solving	2	Help others	1	Skilled	2
Calm	1	Lots	1	Communication	1
Compulsion isn’t good	1	Reach goal	1	Easily annoyed	1
Programming	1	Skilled	1	Hard work	1
Understanding others	1	Working under pressure	1	Perseverance	1
Working under	1			Robots	1

pressure					
				Teamwork	1
				Trust no one	1
				Winning isn't important	1
Nothing	4	Nothing	1	Nothing	8
No Answer	15	No answer	9	No Answer	22

25.1.3.3.2 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT WORKING WITH OTHER PEOPLE?

Answers to the question ‘What have you learned about working with other people?’ are presented in Table 83. The majority of answers either relate to specific intrarelational or interpersonal skills, or refer to teamwork and working with other as being positive. However, some respondents did mention more negative experiences (selfishness, do not trust, arguments and annoyance) – it may be that they have treated the questionnaire as an opportunity to anonymously explain their frustrations from particular events. However, some answers have explained how their more negative experiences have resulted in the development of skills such as patience. Finally, ‘Sense of Community’ appeared as a code in each year, with some respondents talking about their positive experience with other teams rather than just the members of their own team.

Table 83. Coding of respondents answers to the question 'What have you learned about working with other people?'

Year 1 (N=49)		Year 2 (N=27)		Year 3 (N=61)	
Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students	Code	No. of Students
Help each other	9	Communication	4	Fun	4
Sense of Community	5	Helpful	4	Good	4
Hard	3	Sense of Community	3	Helpful	3
Inspiration	3	Fun	2	Languages	3
Teamwork	3	Hard	2	Team too big	3
Communication	2	Inspiration	2	Coordinate and Lead	2
Learning	2	Languages	2	Hard	2
Networking	2	Coordination	1	Help each other	2
Be strict	1	Don't trust everyone	1	Sense of Community	2
Don't listen	1	Help each other	1	Teamwork	2
Fun	1	Opinions	1	Annoying	1
Misunderstanding	1	Patience	1	Arguments	1
Motivation	1	Selfish	1	Communication	1
New Friends	1			Competitive	1
Patience	1			Consider different opinions	1

Robots	1			Doesn't work	1
Useful	1			Don't trust everyone	1
				Motivation	1
				Patience	1
				Share	1
				Uncooperative	1
Nothing	3	Nothing	5	Nothing	5
No Answer	16	No answer	2	No Answer	23

25.1.3.3.3 WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT WORKING WITH ROBOTS?

Answers to the question 'What have you learned about working with robots?' are presented in Table 84. It can be seen that the most commonly given answers related to the programming of the robots either itself, or the difficulty of working with robots. With regards to the latter, students commonly used the phrase 'Robots do what they want', placing the blame on the robots rather than their own ability where their plans have not worked out in the competition. However, again students have referred to a range of intrarelatational skills, such as resilience and patience.

Table 84. Coding of respondents answers to the question 'What have you learned about working with robots?'

Year 1 (N=49)		Year 2 (N=27)		Year 3 (N=61)	
Code	No. of Students	Code	Code	No. of Students	Code
Won't work (or don't do as wanted)	10	Programming (Language)	5	Won't work as they wish	6
Robots do what they want	7	Won't work as they wish	2	Robots do what they want	4
Inaccurate	5	Robots do what they want	2	Cool	2
Programming (Language)	3	Patience	2	Network security	2
Interesting	3	Elements of Computer Science	2	Programming (Language)	2
Not hard	2	Lego Unstable	1	Sensors	2
New kits	2	Testing	1	Spirit of botball	2
Testing	2	Backup	1	Application	1

Exciting	1	Dedicate Time	1	Check everything	1
Dedicate Time	1	Documentation	1	Dedicate time	1
Elements of Computer Science	1	Don't rebuild late	1	Difficult	1
Be Calm	1	Not hard	1	Don't break things	1
Be prepared	1	Resilience	1	Fun	1
Difficult	1	Surprised that it worked	1	Hardcoding better	1
Frustrating	1			Inaccurate	1
Fun	1			Interesting	1
Hard work	1			Last minute	1
Hardcoding is better	1			Lots	1
Had to be exact	1			Reliability	1
Sensors	1			Resilience	1
Simple is better	1			Simple is better	1
Stable hardware	1			Elements of Computer Science	1
				Stressful	1
				Tidy	1
				Time management	1
				Tiring	1
				Unexpected occurrences	1
				Weird	1
				Wifi	1
Nothing	1			Nothing	2
No Answer	12	No answer	6	No Answer	22

25.1.3.4 PARTICIPANT SATISFACTION WITH THE CONFERENCE

This section presents the students 'out-of-5' star rating for the ECER conference each year (Table 85 and Figure 439), alongside their explanations for their rating (

Table 86). It can be seen that overall, most students have high satisfaction with the ECER event, giving four or five stars. A small decrease is seen in the third year, with the lower end of the range dropping to one star, however the average rating was still four stars. Looking at students' reasoning behind their rating it can be seen that those who gave higher star ratings gave a broad range of reasons for having enjoyed ECER, but often still gave constructive feedback about the competition. Looking at the minority of students who gave ratings of three stars or lower, it can be seen that again, a range of reasons were given, from the location to the use of the gong. However, a trend is seen in the third year of students referencing conditions that related to the robotics itself, such as the hardware, the kits, the testing tables and the sensors. This could be interpreted that these students gave the ECER an overall lower rating as their performance in their tournament affected their overall enjoyment. A considerable number of students did not give a reason for their star rating.

Table 85. Results of students' star-ratings of ECER for each year

Question	Mean			Mode			Range		
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y1	Y2	Y3
Overall I would give this conference.... - How many stars?	4.14	4.44	3.96	4	5	4	2-5	3-5	1-5

Figure 439. Breakdown of Student Satisfaction of ECER

Table 86. Coding of respondents explanations for their star-rating of ECER

Star Rating	Year 1 (N=49)		Year 2 (N=27)		Year 3 (N=61)	
	Code	No. of Students	Code	Code	No. of Students	Code
1-3 Stars	Badly Organised	3			Bad for sensors	2
	Gong (bad)	2			More testing tables needed	2
	Could have been better	1			Bad Hardware	1
	First time	1			Badly organised	1
	Loud Music	1			Change of rules	1
	Not bad	1			Good	1
					Judges	1
					Location expensive	1
	No Answer	2	No Answer	1	No Answer	3
4-5 Stars	Good	9	Good	8	Fun	6
	Fun	8	Badly Organised	4	Good	5
	Learnt a lot	7	Fun	4	Interesting	4
	New friends	7	Interesting	3	Bad pizza	3
	Poor time management	5	Presentations	3	Bad spirit from some teams	3
	Interesting	4	Good location	2	Well organised	3
	Well organised	3	Good spirit between teams	2	Bad for sensors	2
	More testing tables needed	2	More testing tables needed	2	Badly organised	2
	Bad spirit from other teams	1	Poor time management	2	Good spirit between teams	2
	Badly organised	1	Well organised	2	Motivating	2
	Depressing	1	Could have been better	1	Time management poor	2
	Don't know	1	Gong (bad)	1	Being kind	1
	Experienced teams	1	New friends	1	Could have been	1

dominated				better	
Good support	1	Ok	1	Good game tables	1
Met expectations	1	PRIA organisers helpful	1	Good open practice distribution	1
Ok	1	Robots cool	1	Learnt a lot	1
Old friends	1	Tiring	1	Loud music	1
Poor robotics kit	1			More testing tables needed	1
				Not enough space	1
				Presentations	1
				Tiring	1
No answer	11	No answer	6	No Answer	23

25.1.4 Comparison of Girls to Boys

An analysis of the girls' responses to both questionnaires with the boys' responses was undertaken. Due to the small number of girls in the population, the genders were compared for the three years as a collective, rather than for the years individually. Across the three years, 183 Austrian participants completed the pre-ECER questionnaire, 27 of whom were female and 156 male, and 137 Austrian participants completed the post-ECER questionnaire, 21 of whom were female and 116 male.

Overall, it was found that there were no notable differences between the genders, as is shown in Table 87 and Table 88. This could be for a number of reasons. Firstly, only a portion of all participants completed the questionnaires, with 183 pre-ECER and 137 post-ECER respondents compared to 510 total participants over the three years. Therefore, results may not be accurate for the whole ECER participant population. Secondly, as in this report the three years are being analysed collectively, it should be noted that a number of the participants returned each year, which may particularly affect the results of the female population (with three female participants attending in years 1 and 2, two participants attending all three years and two participants attending in years 2 and 3). Only Austrian students completed the questionnaires, many of whom attend 'Technical High Schools' and therefore the females were self-selecting themselves into environments both at the ECER's and in their schools that were STEM-based, boy-dominated, involved teamwork and competitive, meaning their responses (noted in the sections above) were unsurprising.

Table 87. Results of pre-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions for girls and boys (Agree, Neither, Disagree)

Question	Mean		Mode		Range	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
1) I like using computers	4.67	4.92	5	5	1-5	4-5
2) I know a lot about robots	3.81	4.12	3	4	2-5	2-5
3) I learn best with other people	3.15	3.52	3	4	1-5	1-5
4) I like science	3.81	3.87	5	4	1-5	1-5
5) I like maths	4.19	3.97	5	4	1-5	1-5
6) I like working on my own	3.52	3.50	3	4	2-5	1-5
7) I like working in teams	3.85	3.94	4	4	2-5	2-5
8) I like trying to solve difficult problems	4.07	4.28	5	5	2-5	2-5
9) I need help solving problems	2.70	2.79	2	3	1-5	1-5
10) I am good at solving problems	4.00	4.13	4	4	3-5	2-5
11) I want to understand more about mechanical things	4.04	3.82	5	4	1-5	1-5
12) I want to solve problems that can help people	3.93	4.09	4	4	1-5	1-5
13) I prefer tasks that only have one correct answer	3.22	2.93	3	3	1-5	1-5
14) I like to keep working on a project until it is perfect	4.11	4.10	5	4	2-5	2-5
15) I like it when I can solve problems quickly	3.93	4.14	5	4	1-5	1-5
16) I like learning about how things work	4.37	4.54	5	5	3-5	3-5
17) I enjoy participating in competitions	4.33	4.06	5	4	2-5	1-5

Table 88. Results of post-ECER questionnaire Likert scale questions for girls and boys (Agree, Neither, Disagree)

Questions	Mean		Mode		Range	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
1) The problems we had to solve were: - Interesting	3.95	4.13	4	4	2-5	2-5
2) The problems we had to solve were: - Difficult	3.76	3.79	4	4	3-5	2-5
3) The problems we had to solve were: - Fun	3.48	3.66	5	4	1-5	1-5
4) Working with robots was: - Interesting	4.48	4.42	5	5	3-5	2-5
5) Working with robots was: - Difficult	3.71	3.45	4	4	2-5	1-5
6) Working with robots was: - Fun	4.33	4.03	5	4	1-5	1-5
7) Working in a team was: - Interesting	4.10	4.05	4	4	1-5	1-5
8) Working in a team was: - Difficult	3.57	3.40	5	4	2-5	1-5
9) Working in a team was: - Fun	4.19	4.08	5	5	1-5	1-5
10) I identified a problem to solve	4.05	4.32	5	5	2-5	2-5
11) I worked on something that I was interested in	4.24	4.26	5	4	3-5	2-5
12) I tried to solve an important problem	4.19	4.14	5	5	1-5	1-5
13) I worked as part of a team	4.10	4.26	5	5	1-5	1-5
14) I worked on my own	2.65	2.94	2	3	1-5	1-5
15) I helped design a robot	3.71	3.77	4	5	1-5	1-5
16) I helped create a robot	4.10	3.78	5	5	1-5	1-5
17) I helped programme a robot	4.14	4.06	5	5	1-5	1-5
18) I was able to choose what I wanted to do	3.86	4.12	5	5	1-5	2-5
19) I feel that other people did not listen to me	2.90	2.63	1	2	1-5	1-5
20) I did most of the work	2.76	2.83	3	3	1-5	1-5
21) I was encouraged by my team	3.57	3.57	3	4	2-5	1-5
22) I gave up too quickly	2.19	2.14	1	2	1-5	1-5
23) I worked hard	3.71	4.04	3	4	1-5	1-5
24) I was bored	2.38	2.62	3	2	1-5	1-5
25) I helped someone	4.24	4.14	5	4	3-5	1-5
26) I liked sharing what I had done with other people	4.00	4.04	5	4	2-5	1-5

Questions	Mean		Mode		Range	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
27) I enjoyed watching other teams	4.24	4.21	5	5	1-5	1-5
28) I learned from other teams	4.00	4.02	5	4	1-5	1-5

One notable difference can be seen in pre-ECER questionnaire question 3): “I learn best with other people”, in which the average score of the girls was ~0.4 less than the boys. This is perhaps an unexpected as it has been found that girls (in general) are generally more naturally suited to nurturing and social jobs than boys (generally) are.

Finally, no notable results were found in the analysis of the open questions, due to both the wide range of results and the small proportion of girls to boys.

26 APPENDIX R: DRAW-A-SCIENTIST

In project year 1 of ER4STEM, with more than 300 student drawings produced only in Bulgaria, less than 20 depicted a female scientist. Moreover, none of those that did depict a female scientist, was painted by a boy.

A possible contributing factor for this tendency was that languages such as Bulgarian and German, use gendered nouns. Following the onset of year two, ESI CEE, as well as other project partners, conducting educational robotics workshops in languages where the term “scientist” is not gender neutral, presented both the female and the male form of the word “scientist” within the “Draw-A-Scientist” task. More precisely, all Bulgarian students, who completed the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity during year 2 were asked to “Draw a Female or a Male Scientist at Work”. In year 3 this was reversed, resulting in all students being asked to “Draw a Male or a Female Scientist at Work”.

The following analysis will present a quantitative review of the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity sheets, collected by ESI CEE in Bulgaria from 17 workshops, conducted within the 2nd and the 3rd ER4STEM project years, implementing the above mentioned changes in the wording of the task. Furthermore, we compare the results from the 2nd and the 3rd project years.

It is worthy to mention that during the 2nd project year, ESI CEE conducted 14 workshops in total, out of which 8 workshops implemented the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity. The reason for this is that the remaining 6 workshops were conducted with recurring participants, who have already completed this activity within the 1st project year. Similarly, within the 3rd project year, out of the 15 workshops carried out by ESI CEE in Bulgaria, 9 implemented the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity. Last but not least, data, including through the “Draw-A-Scientist” activity, was obtained only from students, whose parents provided a written consent form. Not all students with written consent forms, however, completed the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity for various reasons, such as being late for the start of the activity, etc.

Thus, the total number of “Draw-A-Scientist” records obtained by ESI CEE within ER4STEM project years 2 and 3 is **387**, out of which **176 belong to female participants** and **211 to male participants**, the average age of participants being 10 years old. More specifically, the chart below (Figure 1) presents the male-to-female distribution of participants for the two project years:

Figure 440 Participant's Gender per Project Year (ESI CEE, Bulgaria)

In general, more students completed the “Draw-A-Scientist” activity during the 3rd project year. One workshop from year 2 and one workshop from year 3 were carried out as an out-of-school activity outside Sofia, Bulgaria (in the town of Kuystendil). For those workshops, students signed up based on pre-existing interest in STEM, or were signed up by their teachers. Students were between grades 4 and 7 with mixed abilities and prior knowledge in STEM, robotics or programming. One workshop in year 2 was carried out with a class with strong profile in mathematics (6th grade students), whereas in year 3, two workshops were carried out with classes profiled in mathematics (5th grade students). Those classes did have more male students in them, compared to other workshops, carried out with younger students (3rd grade students).

The results obtained from the 2nd and the 3rd project years, depict a more balanced representation of male and female scientists, compared to year 1. During the second project year, we received in total 161 records, where the gender of the scientist depicted could be recognized. Out of those 161 records, 88 are drawings of male scientists, and 73 are of female scientists.

Figure 441 Total Number of Male and Female Participants for Project Year 2 Drawing Female or Male Scientists

As seen from the Figure 2, both girls and boys drew female scientists more often during project year 2 (12 out of the 73 drawings of female scientists were made by boys), though children usually drew their own gender, resulting in girls overall drawing female scientists much more often than boys. Likewise, boys drew more male scientists.

Figure 442 Students' Drawings, Project Year 2

Another interesting shift from year 1 could be observed when analysing the drawings from the 2nd project year. Three students (2 girls and 1 boy) drew both a male and a female figure, most likely both figures being

scientists. Two of the participants (1 boy and 1 girl) who drew both a female and a male scientist participated together in the same workshop (PRW2-2-125-3g), however sitting in different student groups.

Those drawings remind of a conventional family portrait, where in two of the pictures, both drawn by girls, we see a robot of a humanoid shape, smaller than the two scientists, which stands in-between them, reminding of a child (see Figure 4).

In the third picture, we see two figures, a of a male and a female person. The male figure is making calculations, while the female one says “I’m more and more convinced that scientists are crazy”.

Figure 443 Depictions of Both Male and Female Scientists

In the second project year, again there were students who drew objects they referred to science and scientists. Most often, those objects were robots or laboratory equipment, in a few instances in all three years – test subjects. Last but not least, there were instances of students obviously drawing a person, whose gender it was hard to identify or assign. More about this distribution in Figure 5.

Figure 444 Student Drawings Per Gender, Project Year 2

During the third project year, we received in total 174 records, where the gender of the scientist depicted could be recognized. Out of those 174 records, 108 are drawings of male scientists, and 66 are of female scientists. As during the third project year, the participation of male students is more prominent than during

the second project year, and having into account the tendency for students to draw predominantly scientists of their own gender, we consider the number of male scientist drawn quite balanced.

During the third year, the “Draw-A-Scientist” activity began with “Draw a Male or Female Scientist at Work”, which could also act as a factor on why we see more girls drawing male scientists in year 3, compared to year 2.

Figure 445 Total Number of Male and Female Participants for Project Year 3 Drawing Female or Male Scientists

While during years 1 and 2, children’s artwork almost exclusively depicted men (and women in year 2) working inside with laboratory equipment, often with lab coats, glasses and facial hair, during year 3 we observed more students drawing “regular people”, explaining that scientists are regular people who happen to love science.

“I think scientists are smart people that engage with science. I respect them a lot.”
PRW2-3-125-3d, 23187

“Scientists are fun. They love working with science. When I grow up, I want to go to MATHS lessons, as well as to many other subjects.”
PRW2-3-125-3e, 23178

“Scientists are very smart people. They love science. According to me, the things they do are fun.”
PRW2-3-125-3e, 23158

Figure 446 Drawings of Scientists

Compared to the second year, there were more records from female participants of drawings of people, the gender of which was hard to identify (see Figure 8). Despite this difference, other quantitative results from the “Draw-A-Scientist” evaluation activity from year 3 remain similar to those from year 2. However, the difference between the last 2 project years and year 1 is significant.

Figure 447 Total Number of Male and Female Participants for Project Years 2 and 3 Drawing Female or Male Scientists

In conclusion, the three-year span of the ER4STEM project is a rather short one for gender stereotypes regarding women in STEM in Bulgaria to change. However, by simply introducing the non-neutral nouns for scientists, children, especially girls draw exponentially more female scientists.

By reversing the order of the nouns, i.e. putting the male scientist noun in front of the female scientist noun, we observed a slight increase of girls drawing male scientists, as compared to year 2.

We again see a tendency of depicting scientists as predominantly chemists. A certain diversity could be observed regarding what scientists do, potentially due to students being influenced by the workshop tutors and drew scientists as people who build or work with robots, or are engineers.

If we regard “Draw-A-Scientist” as an indicator of children’s beliefs related to science and potentially a STEM career, we see an increase of the number of students compared to year 1, who have a more “down-to-earth” view of what a scientist is and what they do, and potentially, what would they like to work on if they were a scientist.

PRW2-3-Kuystendil, 23228

PRW2-3-125-3a, 23075

PRW2-2-125-6e, 22180

